

Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 10000 Using Triangular Numbers

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Abstract

*This work brings natural numbers from 0 to 10000 written in two different forms. Increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. This is done using **Triangular numbers** along with basic operations. Previously, the author worked with same numbers using only basic operations. For the numbers some extra operations are used, such as, **square-root, factorial**, etc. The previous work is up to number 300.000. For more details refer author's work [7]-[27]. This kind of work using **Triangular numbers** is never seen before. The results are up to number 10000.*

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1 Introduction

First we shall give some different ways of representing natural numbers using the digits 0 to 9 or 1 to 9. See the subsections below

1.1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section natural numbers are* represented in three different types.

1.1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2014, author [7] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{100} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{101} &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{102} &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{103} &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\ \mathbf{104} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{105} &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{106} &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{107} &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\ \mathbf{108} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1. \end{aligned}$$

See more examples,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{786} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{999} &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\ \mathbf{2535} &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{2607} &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\ \mathbf{10483} &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 = (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{10549} &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\ \mathbf{10550} &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\ \mathbf{10553} &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\ \mathbf{10554} &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\ \mathbf{11807} &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1. \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer [7]-[27]. These works brings the representations of natural numbers from 1 to 300.000. Soon, we shall extend it to half-milion, i.e., 500.000.

2 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics [?]. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

The letter "C" represents as "**binomial coefficient**" as seen in subsection ??.

In this paper our aim is to bring **selfie numbers** by used of **triangle numbers**. This we have done in subsequent sections
 Due to high quantity of numbers, we restricted our work up to four digits, i

e
 from 1 to 9999. There are different ways of calling these numbers, such as, **tri-gonal**, **triangular** or **triangle selfie numbers**. For simplicity,
 we shall call them as **triangular selfie numbers**.

2.0.1 Natural Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Values

Below are few examples of natural numbers written in terms of **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular number** values.

1 := $F(2)$	1 := $T(1)$	22 := $F(2) + F(8)$	22 := $T(1) + T(6)$
2 := $F(3)$		23 := $F(3) + F(8)$	
3 := $F(4)$	3 := $T(2)$	24 := $F(4) + F(8)$	24 := $T(2) + T(6)$
4 := $F(2) + F(4)$	4 := $T(1) + T(2)$	25 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(8)$	25 := $T(4) + T(5)$
5 := $F(5)$		26 := $F(5) + F(8)$	26 := $T(1) + T(4) + T(5)$
6 := $F(2) + F(5)$	6 := $T(3)$	27 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(8)$	27 := $T(3) + T(6)$
7 := $F(3) + F(5)$	7 := $T(1) + T(3)$	28 := $F(3) + F(5) + F(8)$	28 := $T(7)$
8 := $F(6)$		29 := $F(6) + F(8)$	29 := $T(1) + T(7)$
9 := $F(2) + F(6)$	9 := $T(2) + T(3)$	30 := $F(2) + F(6) + F(8)$	30 := $T(2) + T(3) + T(6)$
10 := $F(3) + F(6)$	10 := $T(4)$	31 := $F(3) + F(6) + F(8)$	31 := $T(2) + T(7)$
11 := $F(4) + F(6)$	11 := $T(1) + T(4)$	32 := $F(4) + F(6) + F(8)$	32 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(7)$
12 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(6)$		33 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(6) + F(8)$	
13 := $F(7)$	13 := $T(2) + T(4)$	34 := $F(9)$	34 := $T(3) + T(7)$
14 := $F(2) + F(7)$	14 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(4)$	35 := $F(2) + F(9)$	35 := $T(1) + T(3) + T(7)$
15 := $F(3) + F(7)$	15 := $T(5)$	36 := $F(3) + F(9)$	36 := $T(8)$
16 := $F(4) + F(7)$	16 := $T(1) + T(5)$	37 := $F(4) + F(9)$	37 := $T(1) + T(8)$
17 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(7)$	17 := $T(1) + T(3) + T(4)$	38 := $F(2) + F(4) + F(9)$	38 := $T(4) + T(7)$
18 := $F(5) + F(7)$	18 := $T(2) + T(5)$	39 := $F(5) + F(9)$	39 := $T(2) + T(8)$
19 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(7)$	19 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(5)$	40 := $F(2) + F(5) + F(9)$	40 := $T(1) + T(2) + T(8)$
20 := $F(3) + F(5) + F(7)$			
21 := $F(8)$	21 := $T(6)$		

For more details refer author's work [35].

2.1 Selfie Numbers: Palindromic-Type

This section brings *selfie palindromic numbers* by use of triangular numbers. The idea of starting the work with palindromic numbers is as they are symmetric in itself, i.e., remains the same by changing the order of digits. Below are *selfie palindromic numbers*:

$$\begin{aligned}
66 &:= T(T(T(6))/T(6)) & 2662 &:= 2 \times (T(T(6))/T(6))^{T(2)} \\
171 &:= T(17+1) & 2772 &:= -T(2) + T(77 - T(2)) \\
222 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} + T(T(2)) & 3003 &:= T(T(T(T(3)))/003) \\
232 &:= -2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(2) & 3333 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(3) + T(3))) \\
242 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) + T(T(T(2))) & 3773 &:= T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
252 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 2 & 3993 &:= -T(3 \times 9) + T(93) \\
525 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5 & 4224 &:= T(42) + T(T(2)^4) \\
666 &:= T(-6 + T(6) + T(6)) & 4334 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)) \\
696 &:= T(T(6)) + T(9 + T(6)) & 4884 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4 \\
777 &:= T(7) \times T(7) - 7 & 5445 &:= T(54) \times T(T(4))/T(5) \\
969 &:= T(T(9)) - T(6) - T(9) & 5665 &:= T(5) \times T(T(6) + 6) - 5 \\
2222 &:= (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2))) & 5775 &:= T(5) \times 77 \times 5 \\
2332 &:= T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2))) & 5995 &:= 5 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(9) - 5) \\
2442 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4) \times 4)) \times T(2) & 6336 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 6 \\
2552 &:= (T(T(2))^5 - T(T(5)))/T(2) & 9339 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(T(3)) - T(T(9))
\end{aligned}$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

2.2 Selfie Numbers: Symmetric Representations

In this section, we shall give **selfie numbers** in terms of **triangular numbers** along with basic operations. These representations are in symmetric way, i.e., all is same except the digits 0 to 9. This happens in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits. In some cases numbers can written in both the ways. Below are examples of numbers written in digit's order and its reverse:

$$\begin{aligned}
120 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 0 = 0 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) & 216 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 6 = 6 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
121 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 1 = 1 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) & 217 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 7 = 7 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
122 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 2 = 2 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) & 218 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 8 = 8 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
123 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 3 = 3 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) & 219 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 9 = 9 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
124 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 4 = 4 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) \\
125 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 5 = 5 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) \\
126 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 6 = 6 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) \\
127 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 7 = 7 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) \\
128 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 8 = 8 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) \\
129 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 9 = 9 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) \\
210 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 0 = 0 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
211 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 1 = 1 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
212 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 2 = 2 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
213 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 3 = 3 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
214 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 4 = 4 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
215 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 5 = 5 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \\
990 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 0 = 0 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
991 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 1 = 1 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
992 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 2 = 2 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
993 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 3 = 3 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
994 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 4 = 4 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
995 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 5 = 5 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
996 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 6 = 6 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
997 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 7 = 7 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
998 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 8 = 8 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
999 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 9 = 9 + T(T(9)) - T(9)
\end{aligned}$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

2.3 Selfie Numbers: General Representations

$$\begin{aligned} 15 &:= T(1 \times 5) \\ &:= T(5) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21 &:= T(T(1+2)) \\ &:= T(T(2+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= 2 + T(T(3)) \\ &:= T(T(3)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24 &:= T(T(2)) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36 &:= T(3) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39 &:= -T(3) + T(9) \\ &:= T(9) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45 &:= T(4+5) \\ &:= T(5+4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49 &:= 4 + T(9) \\ &:= T(9) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55 &:= T(5+5) \\ &:= T(5+5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63 &:= T(6) \times 3 \\ &:= 3 \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 105 &:= T(-1 + T(05)) \\ &:= T(T(5) - 01) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 132 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 135 &:= T(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5)) + T((T(3) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 136 &:= T(T(1+3)) + 6 \\ &:= T(6 + T(3+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 147 &:= T(T(-1+4)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times T(T(4-1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 152 &:= -1 + T(T(5) + 2) \\ &:= T(2 + T(5)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 154 &:= T(T(T(-1+5)))/T(4) \\ &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(5-1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 167 &:= -1 + 6 \times T(7) \\ &:= T(7) \times 6 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 168 &:= 1 \times T(6) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times T(6 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 176 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) \\ &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 185 &:= (1 + T(8)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(8) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 186 &:= -T(1+8) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - T(8+1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 221 &:= -T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$223 := -2^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) - 2^{T(2)}$$

$$:= T(7) + T(54 \times 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 224 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2) - 4 \\ &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1462 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(6) - 2 \\ &:= -T(2 \times 6) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 225 &:= T(2 + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ &:= (5 \times T(2))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1463 &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(6 + T(3)) \\ &:= -T(T(3) + 6) + T(T(T(4))) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 226 &:= -2 - T(2) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - 2 - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1464 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - T(6) - T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(6) - T(T(4 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1446 &:= T(-1 + 4) \times (T(4) + T(T(6))) \\ &:= (T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(4 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1472 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - T(T(2)) \\ &:= -T(T(2)) - 7 + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1447 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(7) \\ &:= -T(7) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1474 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - 4 \\ &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(4) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1448 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8) \\ &:= -T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1479 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(-7 + 9)) \\ &:= -T(T(9 - 7)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1449 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(4) \times 9 \\ &:= -T(9 + 4) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1482 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(8 - T(T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(2)) + T(8) \times 41 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1455 &:= T(14) \times T(5) - T(T(5)) \\ &:= -T(5) - T(5) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1483 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 8 + T(3) \\ &:= -T(T(3)) - T(8) + T(T(T(4 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1456 &:= (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + T(5 \times T(4) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1484 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$1457 := T(-T(1 + T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(7)$$

For more examples of similar type refer author's work [?].

3 Crazy Representations from 0 to 10000 Using Triangular Numbers

In this work we have written natural numbers from 0 to 10000 in terms of increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1 by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. The same numbers are also written before by author [7] without use of **Fibonacci sequence**. Moreover, without use of any extra operations just with basic operations. Here we have done it by using **Fibonacci sequence values** just to have more possibilities. Still there are few numbers written without use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. Moreover, we have removed $F(5)$, because $F(5) = 5$.

$$0 := T(-1 - 2 + 3) \times (456789)$$

$$0 := T(T(T(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$1 := (-1 - 2 + 3) \times 456 + T(7) - T(8) + 9$$

$$1 := 9 - T(8) + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{2} &:= -1 - T(2 + T(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{2} &:= 9 + 8 \times T(7) - T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{3} &:= 1 \times 2 \times T(T(3)) - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & \mathbf{3} &:= -9 + 7 \times T(8) / (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{4} &:= -1 - 2 - T(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{4} &:= -9 - (T(8) - T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{5} &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 \times T(4) + 5 + (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{5} &:= (-9 - 8 - T(7)) / (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
\mathbf{6} &:= T(-T(1 \times 2 + T(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{6} &:= -9 + 8 + T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{7} &:= -1 - 2 - T(T(3)) + 1 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{7} &:= (9 - 8) \times (T(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
\mathbf{8} &:= -1 + 2 - T(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{8} &:= 9 - 8 + T(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{9} &:= -6 + T(2 + 3 + 4) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{9} &:= -9 - T(8) / (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
\mathbf{10} &:= T(-1 - 2 - T(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{10} &:= T(-9 - T(8) + T(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{11} &:= -T(-1 + 2 + T(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{11} &:= 9 + T(8) - T(7) - T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{12} &:= -1 + 2 - 4 \times T(3) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{12} &:= 9 + T(8 + 7 - 6) / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{13} &:= -1 - 2 \times (T(3 + 4) - 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{13} &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + T(4) + 3 - 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{14} &:= -T(T(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{14} &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + T(4) + 3 - 2 \\
\mathbf{15} &:= -1 - 2 - T(T(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{15} &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + T(4) + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{16} &:= T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & \mathbf{16} &:= 9 - 8 \times T(7) + T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{17} &:= -1 - T(2 \times 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{17} &:= -9 - 8 + T(7) + T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{18} &:= -T(1 \times 2 \times 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{18} &:= -9 + 8 + T(7) + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{19} &:= -1 + 2 - T(T(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{19} &:= -9 + T(8 - (7 - 6)^{54321}) \\
\mathbf{20} &:= -1 + T(T(2 \times T(T(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & \mathbf{20} &:= -9 + T(8) - T(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{21} &:= (-1 - 2) \times T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{21} &:= T(-9 + 8 + T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{22} &:= 1 + T(T(2 \times T(T(3)) - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)) & \mathbf{22} &:= T(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{23} &:= -1 - T(2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{23} &:= 9 \times 8 - T(7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{24} &:= -T(1 \times 2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{24} &:= -10 + (T(8) - T(7)) \times 6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1) \\
\mathbf{25} &:= 1 - T(2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{25} &:= -9 + T(8) + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{26} &:= -1 - 2 \times T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{26} &:= 9 + T(8) - T(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{27} &:= -1 \times 2 \times T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{27} &:= 9 - T(8) / (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 \times 2 \times 1) \\
\mathbf{28} &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{28} &:= T(-9 - 8 \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
\mathbf{29} &:= -T(-1 + 2 + 3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{29} &:= -9 + T(8) - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{30} &:= 1 + 23 + 45 + 6 - T(7) - (8 + 9) & \mathbf{30} &:= -9 + T(8) - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{31} &:= -1 \times 2 - T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{31} &:= -9 - T(8) + T(7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{32} &:= 1 - 2 - T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{32} &:= -9 - 8 + T(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{33} &:= (1 - 2) \times T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{33} &:= -9 + 8 + T(7) + T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{34} &:= -1 + 2 - T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{34} &:= -9 + T(8) + T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{35} &:= -1 - 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{35} &:= -9 + T(8) - (T(7) - T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
\mathbf{36} &:= (-1 \times 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{36} &:= 9 + 8 + T(7) + 1 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{37} &:= 1 - 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & \mathbf{37} &:= (-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{38} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 - T(7) + T(8) + 9 & \mathbf{38} &:= 9 + T(8) - T(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
\mathbf{39} &:= 12 + 3 + 45 + (6 - T(7) - 8 + 9) & \mathbf{39} &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 - T(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
\mathbf{40} &:= 12 - T(3) - T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{40} &:= (9 \times 8 + T(7)) \times 6 / (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
\mathbf{41} &:= T(-1 + 2 + 3) + 1 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & \mathbf{41} &:= -16 + T(8) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$42 := 1 - 2 + T(3 \times 4) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$43 := T(T(T(2+3))/T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$44 := (1+2-3 - (1/5) \times T(4)) \times (67-89)$$

$$45 := (-1+2) \times T(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$46 := -1+2+T(3)+4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$47 := 1 \times 2 + T(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$48 := 1+2+T(3)+4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$49 := T(-1+2+3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$50 := -1+2 \times T(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$51 := 1 \times 2 \times T(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$52 := 1+2 \times T(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$53 := -1+T(2+3)+4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$54 := (-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$55 := 1+T(2+3)+4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$56 := 1+T(T(2+3+4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$57 := (1+2) \times T(3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$58 := -1 \times 2 + T(T(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$59 := -1+T(2 \times 3) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$60 := (-1+2) \times T(T(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$61 := -1+2+T(T(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$62 := 1 \times 2 + T(T(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$63 := T((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$64 := -1+2+T(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$65 := -1 - 2 \times (T(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$66 := (-1 \times 2) \times (T(3) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$67 := T(-1+2+T(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$68 := -1 - T(2 \times 3) + T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$69 := (1-2) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$70 := T(1 \times 2 \times (3+4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$71 := 1 + T(2 \times (3+4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$72 := 1+2 - T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) + 5 + (6+7+8+9)$$

$$73 := T(-1+2+T(3)) + T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$74 := -1 + T(2+T(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$75 := (-1+2+3) \times T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$76 := -1+2-3 \times (T(4) - 5 - (6+7+8+9))$$

$$77 := -1 + T(2 - T(T(3))) + 1+6+7+8+9$$

$$78 := T(-1+2-4 \times T(3) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$79 := -1 + (T(2+3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$80 := -1+2 \times T(T(3)) + 4+5+6+7+8+9$$

$$81 := (-1-2) \times 3 + T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9$$

$$42 := T(-9+8+7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1$$

$$43 := -9 + T(8) + 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$44 := -9 - T(8)/(7+6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$45 := T(-9-8+T(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$46 := -9 + T(8-7-6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$47 := -9+8 \times (T(7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$48 := -9+8+T(7)+6+5+4+3+2+1$$

$$49 := -9+T(8)+T(7)-T(6)+5+4+3+2+1$$

$$50 := -9+8+7-6-5+T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$51 := 9 \times (T(8) - T(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$52 := -9 - T(8) + 7 + 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$53 := -9+8 \times 7 + T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$54 := 9 \times (T(8) - T(7)) - 6 - 5 - 4 - T(3) + 2 + 1$$

$$55 := -9 + T(8) + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$56 := 9 - 8 + T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$57 := T(-9+8+7) + T(6) + 5+4+3+2+1$$

$$58 := -9+8-7+6+5+T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$59 := -9-8+T(7+6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$60 := (9+T(8)) \times T(7)/(6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$61 := -9 - T(8) + T(7+6) + 5+4+3+2+1$$

$$62 := 9 - T(8)/(7+6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$63 := T(-9+8+7+6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$64 := -9 + T(8) + T(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$65 := T(-9+8+7) - 6 - 5 + T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$66 := T(-9-8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$67 := T(-9-8+T(7)) + 6+5-4-3-2-1$$

$$68 := 9+8+7-6-5+T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$69 := -9 \times (8+7 - T(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1$$

$$70 := -9 + T(8) + 7 + T(6) + 5+4+3+2+1$$

$$71 := -9+8+T(7) - 6 - 5 + T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$72 := 9 \times (T(8) - 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$73 := -9 - T(8) + T(7) + 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$74 := -9 - 8 + T(7+T(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$75 := -9+8+T(7+6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$76 := -9 + T(8) + T(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1$$

$$77 := 9 - 8 + T(7+6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$78 := T(-9+(8-7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$79 := (-9+T(8-7+6+5)) + 4+3+2+1$$

$$80 := 9 - T(8) - 7 - 6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$81 := -9 + (8+7) \times (T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
82 &:= (-1 \times 2) - T(3) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 82 &:= 9 + T(8) + T(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
83 &:= 1 - 2 - T(3) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 83 &:= 7 \times (9 - 8) + T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
84 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(3) + T(T(4)) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 84 &:= -9 + T(8) + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
85 &:= -(1 \times 2 + 3) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 85 &:= -9 + 8 + T(7 + 6) + 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
86 &:= T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 86 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + 6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
87 &:= -1 - 2 + T(T(3) + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 87 &:= T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
88 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 88 &:= T(-9 + T(8 + 7 + 6 - T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
89 &:= -1 + 2 \times (T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 89 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
90 &:= T(T(-1 - 2 + 3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 90 &:= (-9 - T(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
91 &:= T(-1 - 2 \times (T(3 + 4) - 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 91 &:= T(-9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
92 &:= -1 - 2 + T(3) \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 92 &:= 9 - 8 + T(2 + T(6) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
93 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 93 &:= T(-9 + 8 + 7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
94 &:= T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 94 &:= -9 + T(8) + 7 \times (6 + 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
95 &:= (-1 + 2) \times T(3) \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 95 &:= -9 + 8 + T(7 + 6) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
96 &:= (-1 + 2) \times T(3) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 96 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7) + T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
97 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 97 &:= T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
98 &:= 1 + 2 + T(3) \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 98 &:= -9 + 8 + T(7) + T(6) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
99 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 99 &:= -9 \times (8 - T(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
100 &:= T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 100 &:= -9 + T(8 + 7) - 6 + 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
101 &:= T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) - 5 - (6 + (7 + 8 + 9)) & 101 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
102 &:= -1 + 2^{T(3)} + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 102 &:= -T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) / T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
103 &:= 123 + 4 - 5 - T(6 + 7) + 8 \times 9 & 103 &:= 9 + 87 + 6 \times 5 + T(4) - 32 - 1 \\
104 &:= T(12) + 3 + 45 + 67 - 89 & 104 &:= (9 + 8) \times (T(7) - T(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
105 &:= (1 \times 2 \times 3 + 4 \times T(T(5))) / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 105 &:= -T(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
106 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(3 + 4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 106 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
107 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 107 &:= T(9) + 8 - 7 + T(6) - 5 + 43 + 2 \times 1 \\
108 &:= T(12) - T(3) - (45 + 6) + 78 + 9 & 108 &:= 9 + T(8 + 7) - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
109 &:= -1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 109 &:= -9 - T(8) + T(7) + 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
110 &:= -1 - 2 + T(3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 110 &:= 98 - 76 + T(5 + T(4)) - 32 \times 1 \\
111 &:= T(T(3 \times (-1 + 2))) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 111 &:= 98 - 76 + T(5 + T(4)) - 32 + 1 \\
112 &:= -1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) / T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 112 &:= 98 / 7 - 6 + 5 + T(4 \times 3) + 21 \\
113 &:= T(12) - 3 - 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 89 & 113 &:= 98 + T(7) - 65 \times 4 / (T(3 \times 2) - 1) \\
114 &:= 1 + T(T(T(2 + 3))) / T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 114 &:= (9 + T(8)) \times (7 - 6)^{54} \times 3 - 21 \\
115 &:= 1 - T(T(2 + T(3))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 115 &:= 9 + T(8) + 76 - 54 / 3^2 \times 1 \\
116 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 116 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
117 &:= T(12) - 3 \times 4 + 5 - 6 + 7 + T(8) + 9 & 117 &:= 98 - T(7) - 6 + 54 - 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
118 &:= 12 + 34 / (56 / T(7)) + 89 & 118 &:= (9 - 8) \times (76 + 54) - T(3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
119 &:= T(12) + 3 - 4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 89 & 119 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) - T(7) - T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
120 &:= T(-1 - 2 - T(T(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 120 &:= T(-9 + T(8) - 7 - 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
121 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 121 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7)/6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
122 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(T(3))) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 122 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7) + T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
123 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 123 &:= 98 + T(7) - 6 \times 54 + 321 \\
124 &:= -1 - T(2 + 3) + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 124 &:= T(9 + 8) + T(7) - 65 + 4 + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
125 &:= -1 + 2 \times (T(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 125 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7) - 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
126 &:= T(-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 126 &:= T(9 + 8) + T(7) - 65 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
127 &:= 1 \times 2^{T(3)-4+5} + (6 - 7)^{89} & 127 &:= 9 + T(8) + 76 + 54/3^2 \times 1 \\
128 &:= 1 + 2^{T(3)-4+5} + (6 - 7)^{89} & 128 &:= 9 + T(8) + 76 - 5 + 4 \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
129 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 129 &:= T(-9 + T(8))/(7 \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
130 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 \times 4)^{T(5)-6-7} - 8 - 9 & 130 &:= 9 + (8 - 7)^6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
131 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 131 &:= 9 + T(8 + 7) \times (6 - 5) - 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
132 &:= T(-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 132 &:= -9 + T(8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
133 &:= 1 - 2 - T(3) + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 133 &:= -9 + T(8) + T(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
134 &:= (1 - 2) \times T(3) + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 134 &:= 98 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4 - T(3) + 21 \\
135 &:= T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 135 &:= 98 + 76 - 5 - T(4) - 3 - 21 \\
136 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 136 &:= 9 + 6 \times (8 + 7) - 5 + T(4) + 32 \times 1 \\
137 &:= 1 \times 23 \times 4 - ((5 - 6 - 7)/8) \times T(9) & 137 &:= 9 + T(8) - 7 - 6 \times 5 + 4 \times 32 + 1 \\
138 &:= T(12) + 3 - 45 + 6 + 7 + 89 & 138 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + T(6 + 5) - 432 \times 1 \\
139 &:= -1 + T(2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 139 &:= -9 \times 8 + T(7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
140 &:= (1 + 2)/3 \times 4 \times (T(56/7) + 8 - 9) & 140 &:= T(9) + 87 + 6 \times 5 + T(4) - 32 \times 1 \\
141 &:= -22 + T(4) + T(5 + 6) + 78 + 9 & 141 &:= 98 - ((12 - T(6)) \times 4 - 3 \times 2 - 1) \\
142 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 142 &:= 9 - 87 - T(6) \times 5 + 4 + 321 \\
143 &:= 1 + 2 - (T(3) - T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 143 &:= 9 + T(8) + 7 \times (6 - 5) \times (T(4) - 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
144 &:= T(-1 + T(2 + 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 144 &:= 98 + T(7 + 6 - 5) + T(4) - 3 + 2 + 1 \\
145 &:= 1 \times 23 \times 4 - T(56/7) + 89 & 145 &:= T(9) + T(8) + 7 + 6 + 54 - 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
146 &:= (1 + 2) \times T(3 \times 4) + 5 - 6 - 78 - 9 & 146 &:= T(9 + 8 - 7) + 6 + 54 + 32 - 1 \\
147 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 147 &:= T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
148 &:= T(12) + 3 + 45 - 67 + 89 & 148 &:= T(98/7) + 65 - 43 + 21 \\
149 &:= -1 - 4 \times T(T(2 + 3)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 149 &:= -9 + 8 \times T(7) - 6 - 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
150 &:= T(-1 + 2 + 3) + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 150 &:= -9 - T(8) + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
151 &:= 1 \times T(23)/4 + (5 - 6) \times (7 - 89) & 151 &:= T(9) + T(8) - 58 + 4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
152 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + T(56/7) + 89 & 152 &:= 9 - 8 \times (7 - 65) - T(4 \times T(3)) - 21 \\
153 &:= 123 \times 4 - 56 \times 7 + 8 + T(9) & 153 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times T(6) + 5 \times 4 + T(3) - 21 \\
154 &:= 1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times 56 - T(7 \times 8 - T(9)) & 154 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + 7 - T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
155 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 + 4 \times 56 - T(7 \times 8 - T(9)) & 155 &:= 98 - T(7 + 6 - 5) + (T(4) + T(T(3))) \times (2 + 1) \\
156 &:= 123 - 4 + 56 - T(7) - T(8) + T(9) & 156 &:= (98 - 7 - 65) \times (4 - 3) \times T(2 + 1) \\
157 &:= -1 - 2 \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 157 &:= 9 + 8 + T(7 + 6) + 5 + 43 + 2 - 1 \\
158 &:= -1 + T(T(2 + 3)) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 158 &:= -9 - 8 + T(T(7)) - T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
159 &:= T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) + 4 + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 159 &:= T(9) + 87 + 6 + 54 - 32 - 1 \\
160 &:= -1 + T(2 \times 3) + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 160 &:= -9 + T(8) + 7 + 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
201 &:= 1 \times T(23 - 4 - 5 + 6) + (7 - 8) \times 9 & 201 &:= 98 + T(7 + 6 - 5) + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
202 &:= T(12) \times 3 + (45 - 6 - 7) \times (8 - 9) & 202 &:= 9 + 87 + 65 + T(4) + 32 - 1 \\
203 &:= 1 + 234 - 5 + 6 - 78 + T(9) & 203 &:= T(9) - T(8) - 76 + 54 \times (3 + 2 \times 1) \\
204 &:= T(12 + 3 - 4) + 56 - 7 + 89 & 204 &:= T(-9 + T(8))/7 \times 6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
205 &:= 1^{23} \times 4 + 5 \times T(6) + 7 + 89 & 205 &:= 9 \times 8 + T(7) + 6 \times 54/3 - 2 - 1 \\
206 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 - 45 + T(6 \times 7) - T(T(8)) + 9 & 206 &:= T(9) + 87 + 6 \times 5 + 43 + 2 - 1 \\
207 &:= 123 + 4 + 5 - T(6) + 7 + 89 & 207 &:= 9 + 8 + T(76 - 54) - 3 \times 21 \\
208 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + T(T(T(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 208 &:= T(9) - 87 + T(65 - 43) - 2 - 1 \\
209 &:= -1 + T(2 - T(T(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 209 &:= 98 - 7 + 65 - T(4) + 3 \times 21 \\
210 &:= T(-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 210 &:= T(9) - 8 + 76 + 5^4 - T(32) \times 1 \\
211 &:= 1 \times 2^{T(3)}/4 - T(5 + 6) - (7 - T(8)) \times 9 & 211 &:= 98 + 7 + T(T(6)) - T(T(5)) - 4 - 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
212 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 212 &:= -9 + T(T(8 + 7 + 6 - T(5))) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
213 &:= 123 - 45 + T(T(6)) - 7 - 89 & 213 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 - T(6)) - 54 + 321 \\
214 &:= 1^2 \times 3 \times T(4) + 5 \times (6 - 7 + T(8)) + 9 & 214 &:= -9 - T(8) + T(7) + T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
215 &:= (1^{23} \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 & 215 &:= 9 + 8 + (76 + 5) \times 4 - T(3) \times 21 \\
216 &:= (-1 + 2) \times T(3) + T(T(T(4))) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 216 &:= 98 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4 \times T(3) - 2 + 1 \\
217 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 5 \times 6 + 7 + T(8 + 9) & 217 &:= T(9) + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) + 43 \times 2 + 1 \\
218 &:= T(-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) + 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 218 &:= 98 + 7 \times (T(6) - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
219 &:= 12 \times 34 + 9 \times (5 - 6 - T(7) + 8) & 219 &:= T(98/7 + 6) - 54 + 3 \times 21 \\
220 &:= 12 + 34 \times 5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + T(9) & 220 &:= -9 \times 8 + T(T(7)) + 6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
221 &:= -1 - 2 - T(T(3 + 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 221 &:= 9 - T(8) - T(T(7)) + 654/3 \times (2 + 1) \\
222 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 - 4 - 5 - T(6) + T(T(7)) - T(8 + 9) & 222 &:= T(9 + 8) - 7 + T(6) + T(5) + 43 - 2 - 1 \\
223 &:= T(1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4 - 5) \times 6 - T(7) + 8 - 9 & 223 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
224 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 224 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 65 + T(4) \times 3 - T(2 + 1) \\
225 &:= -1 + 2 - T(T(3 + 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 225 &:= T(-9 + T(8) - 7 - 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
226 &:= (1 + 23) \times T(4 + 5 - 6) - 7 + 89 & 226 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times (65 - 43) + T(2 + 1) \\
227 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times T(4) - 5 + 6 - 7 + T(8 + 9) & 227 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7) + T(T(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
228 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 + T(4)) \times (5 + 6) - 7 + 89 & 228 &:= -9 - T(T(8)) + T(7 \times (T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
229 &:= 123 + 45 - T(6) - 7 + 89 & 229 &:= (9 - 8) \times T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - 54) \times 3/(2 + 1) \\
230 &:= (1^{2345} - 6) \times (7 - 8 - T(9)) & 230 &:= (9 + 87)/6 \times T(5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
231 &:= 1 + 2 - T(3) - 45 \times 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 & 231 &:= 9 - T(8) - 7 + 65 \times 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
232 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 232 &:= 9 - T(8) - T(7) + 65 \times 4 + T(3) + 21 \\
233 &:= (1^{23} \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 & 233 &:= T(9) + 8 \times 7 + T(6) - 5 - T(4) + T(3) \times 21 \\
234 &:= (-1 + 2) \times T(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 234 &:= -9 + T(8) \times 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
235 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 235 &:= -9 - 8 - T(7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
236 &:= -1 + T(2 + T(T(3))) - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 236 &:= 98 - (7 + 65) + (4 + T(3)) \times 21 \\
237 &:= 1^{23} - T(4) + 5 \times 67 - 89 & 237 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - T(6 + T(5)) - 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
238 &:= (12/3 \times 4 + T(5)) \times 6 + 7 + T(8) + 9 & 238 &:= T(9 + 8) + 76 - 54 + 3 \times 21 \\
239 &:= 3 \times T(12) - 45 + 6 + 7 - 8 + T(9) & 239 &:= (9 - 8)^{765} + 4 + 3 + T(21) \\
240 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3) \times T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 240 &:= T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$281 := 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times (T(4)/5 + 6 \times 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$282 := (-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$283 := T((-2) - T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$284 := 1 \times 2^3 - T(4) - 5 + 8 \times 6 \times 7 - T(9)$$

$$285 := (1 + 2) \times (T(3) \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$286 := (-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$287 := (-1 - 2) \times T(T(3)) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$288 := (12 - 3) \times 45 + 6 - 78 - T(9)$$

$$289 := -1 + T(T(2 + 3) + T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$290 := 123 \times 4 - 49 - T(8 + 9)$$

$$291 := 1 + T(T(2 + 3) + T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$292 := 123 - 4 + 56 + T(7) + 89$$

$$293 := -1 + T(T(2 \times 3)) \times 4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$294 := (-1 + 2) \times T(T(T(3))) \times 4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$295 := (1 + 2 + 3) \times (45 + 6) - T(7) + 8 + 9$$

$$296 := (12/3 \times 4 - 5) \times T(6) + 7 \times 8 + 9$$

$$297 := 12 \times 3 \times 4 + (5 + 6 - T(7)) \times (T(8) - T(9))$$

$$298 := 1 - 23 - 45 - 6 - 7 + T(T(8) - 9)$$

$$299 := -1 + T(2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$300 := 1^2 + T(34) + T(5) + 6 + 7 - T(8) \times 9$$

$$301 := T(12) + (3 + 45) \times 6 - 7 \times 8 - 9$$

$$302 := 1 - T(23) + T(4) \times 56 + (7 + T(T(8)/9))$$

$$303 := -1 \times 2 - T(T(T(3)) + 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$304 := 12/3 - (45 + 6) \times 7 + T(T(8)) - 9$$

$$305 := 1^2 \times 3 + 4 + 5 \times 67 + 8 - T(9)$$

$$306 := 1^2 \times 345 - 6 - 78 + T(9)$$

$$307 := (1 - 2 + 3) \times T(4) - 5 \times 6 - 7 + T(8) \times 9$$

$$308 := -1 \times 2 \times T(T(3)) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$309 := 12 - 3 + 45 \times 6 - 7 - 8 + T(9)$$

$$310 := T(1 + 23) + T(4)/5 - (6 - 78)/9$$

$$311 := -1 + (2 + T(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$312 := (-1 - 2) \times (T(3) + T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$313 := -1 - T(2 + T(3)) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$314 := -1 + T(2 + T(T(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$315 := ((1 + 2)^3 - 4 + (5 + T(T(6)) - 7 \times T(8))) \times T(9)$$

$$316 := 12 \times T(3) + 4 \times 56 - 7 + T(8) - 9$$

$$317 := (1 + 2 + 3) \times (45 + 6) + T(7) - 8 - 9$$

$$318 := 1 + 2 \times (34 \times 5) + T(6) - 7 + 8 - T(9)$$

$$319 := 12 + 345 + 6 + T(7) - 8 \times 9$$

$$320 := 1 \times 234 + 56 - 15 + T(9)$$

$$281 := (98 + 7 + 6) \times 5 - 43 - T(21)$$

$$282 := 9 + (87 + 6 - 5 - 4) \times 3 + T(T(2 + 1))$$

$$283 := T(9) + 8 - 7 + T(6) \times 5 + 4 \times (32 + 1)$$

$$284 := -9 + T(T(8)) - T(T(7) - 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$285 := T(-9 + T(8))/7 + T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$286 := 98 - T(7 + T(6)) + 5^4 - 32 + 1$$

$$287 := -9 + 8 + 6 \times T(7) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$288 := T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$289 := -9 \times (8 - T(7) - 6 - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$290 := 98 - 7 + T(T(6)) - (T(5) - 4) \times 3 + 2 - 1$$

$$291 := T(9) + 8 + 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4) + T(3) + T(21)$$

$$292 := T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7) + 6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$293 := -9 + 8 \times 7 + T(T(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$294 := -9 + 8 + T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$295 := 98 + 7 + T(T(6) - 6 + T(4)) - 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$296 := T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7) - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$297 := 9 \times 8 + T(7 + 6) + 5 + 4 \times 32 + 1$$

$$298 := -9 \times 8 + T(T(7)) - T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$299 := -9 - 8 + T(T(7)) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$300 := -9 \times (8 - 7 - T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$301 := -9 \times 8 + T(T(7) - 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$302 := 9 \times T(8) + 7 - 65 + 4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$303 := (-9 + T(8)) \times 7 - 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$304 := T(-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6))/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$305 := -9 - 8 + 7 + T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$306 := 9 \times (T(8) + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$307 := 9 \times T(8) - 7 + 6 + 5 + T(4) - 32 + 1$$

$$308 := 9 \times T(8) + 7 - 6 - 54/3 + 2 - 1$$

$$309 := 98 - T(7) + 654/3 + 21$$

$$310 := ((9 + 87)/6 + T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$311 := 9 + 87 + T(6) + 5 \times 43 - 21$$

$$312 := 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 - 5 + 43 \times T(2 + 1)$$

$$313 := 9 - T(8) \times 7 - 6 + 5^4 - 3 \times 21$$

$$314 := 9 + T(8) \times 7 + T(6) - 5 + 4 + 32 + 1$$

$$315 := 9 - (8 + T(7)) \times 6 + 543 - 21$$

$$316 := T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$317 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 65 + 4 - T(3) \times 21$$

$$318 := -9 \times 8 + (T(7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$319 := (T(T(9) - 8) - (7 + 65 - 4 - 3))/2 \times 1$$

$$320 := (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
321 &:= (-1 + 2) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 321 &:= T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
322 &:= (1 + 2) \times T(3 \times 4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 322 &:= T(9 \times (8 - 7)) + T(T(6)) + 5 + T(4) + 32 - 1 \\
323 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(T(3) \times T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 323 &:= (98 - 76 - 5) \times (4 - T(3) + 21) \\
324 &:= -1 + T(2^{T(3)} - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) & 324 &:= -9 - T(T(8))/(7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
325 &:= T((1 \times (2 - (3 - 45)/6) - 7) \times 8 + 9) & 325 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times T(65 - 43 + 2 + 1) \\
326 &:= T(T(1 + 2)) + T(3) - 4 \times 5 - 6 + T(T(7)) - T(8) - T(9) & 326 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7) + T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
327 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times (T(4) + 56) - 78 + 9 & 327 &:= 9 - 87 - T(6) - 5 + 432 - 1 \\
328 &:= 12/3 \times (T(4) - 5 - 6) \times (7 - 89) & 328 &:= -9 \times 8 + T(T(7)) - T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
329 &:= 123 + 4 + 56 - 7 + T(8 + 9) & 329 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) - T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
330 &:= -1 + 2 - T(T(3)) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 330 &:= T(9) - 87 - 6 + 54/3 \times 21 \\
331 &:= 1^2 + 34 - T(5) - 6 - 7 + T(8) \times 9 & 331 &:= 98 - T(7) - 6 - 54 + 321 \\
332 &:= (1 + 2) \times T(T(3)) - 4 \times (56 \times (7 - 8)) + T(9) & 332 &:= 9 + T(T(8)) - 76 - T(5) - 4 \times 3 \times 21 \\
333 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(4 \times T(3)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 333 &:= -9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
334 &:= 1 \times 234 + 56 + 7 - 8 + T(9) & 334 &:= 98 \times 7 - 6 - T(5) - T(4) - 321 \\
335 &:= -1 \times T(2 + 3) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 335 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 54 \times T(3) - 2 - 1 \\
336 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 336 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 54 \times T(3) - 2 \times 1 \\
337 &:= (1 + 23) \times T(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 89 & 337 &:= 98 - 7 - T(6) - 54 + 321 \\
338 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3 - T(4) + (5 + 6 \times 7 - 8) \times 9 & 338 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
339 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 - 56)/7 + 8 \times T(9) & 339 &:= (98 + 7 \times 6)/5 - T(4) + 321 \\
340 &:= -1 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 340 &:= T(9) - 8 \times 7 + T(6) \times T(5) + 4 + 32 \times 1 \\
341 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 341 &:= (9 + T(8)) \times (7 - 6) - T(5) - T(4) + 321 \\
342 &:= 12/3 + 45 - 67 + 8 \times T(9) & 342 &:= T(98/7 - 6 - 5) \times (T(4 \times 3) - 21) \\
343 &:= 12/3 \times 4 + T(5) + 6 \times (7 + T(8) + 9) & 343 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
344 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 344 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
345 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 - 4 \times 5 + 6 \times 7 + T(8) \times 9 & 345 &:= T(98 - 7 - 65) \times (4 - 3) - T(2 + 1) \\
346 &:= 123 + 4 + T(5) \times T(6) - 7 - 89 & 346 &:= -9 - T(8) + T(7 + T(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
347 &:= T(12) - 34 + 56 \times 7 - 89 & 347 &:= T(9) + T(8) - 7 - 6 \times (T(5) - 4^3) - 21 \\
348 &:= T(12) + 345 - 6 - 78 + 9 & 348 &:= 987/T(6) - 5 \times 4 + 321 \\
349 &:= T(23) - (4 - 5)^6 - 7 + T(8) + T(9) & 349 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + T(4) \times (32 + 1) \\
350 &:= 1 + T(23) - (4 - 5)^6 - 7 + T(8) + T(9) & 350 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
351 &:= T(-1 - 2 \times T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 351 &:= T(-9 + 8 \times 7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
352 &:= 1 + 234 + T(5) + 6 + 7 + 89 & 352 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (65 - (T(4) + 3) \times 2 + 1) \\
353 &:= T(12 + 3 \times 4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + T(8) + 9 & 353 &:= 9 + 87 + T(6) + 5 \times 43 + 21 \\
354 &:= 12 + 345 + 6 + T(7) + 8 - T(9) & 354 &:= 9 \times T(8) + 7 + 6 + 54/3 - 2 + 1 \\
355 &:= (1 \times 23 - T(4)) \times (T(5) + 6) - 7 + 89 & 355 &:= -9 \times 8 + T(T(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
356 &:= 12/3 + 4 \times (T(5) + T(6) + 7 + T(8) + 9) & 356 &:= -9 - 8 + T(T(7) - 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
357 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 357 &:= T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
358 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 345 + T(6) + 7 - 8 \times T(9) & 358 &:= 4 + T(8) + 7 - 6 - 4 + 321 \\
359 &:= 12 \times 34 - 5 \times 6 - T(7) - T(8) + T(9) & 359 &:= (98 + 7 \times 6)/5 + T(4) + 321 \\
360 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3 - 4 + 5) \times (6 - 7 - 8 + T(9)) & 360 &:= 98 + 76 - (5 + T(4)) \times 3 + T(21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
361 &:= T(1+2+T(3)+T(4))+T(5)+67+89 & 361 &:= -9-T(8)+T(7+6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
362 &:= -1-2+T(3)\times T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9 & 362 &:= T(-9+T(8))-7+6-(5+4+3+2+1) \\
363 &:= -1\times 2+T(3)\times T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9 & 363 &:= T(9)\times 8+T(7)+6+T(5)-43-2-1 \\
364 &:= 1+2\times 34\times 5-T(6)+7-8+T(9) & 364 &:= T(-9+T(8))+7-(6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
365 &:= (-1+2)\times T(3)\times T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9 & 365 &:= -9+T(T(8))-T(T(7))-6+T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
366 &:= 1\times 2-3-T(4)+(5-6)^7+T(T(8)-9) & 366 &:= (-9+T(8))\times(7+6)+5+4+3+2+1 \\
367 &:= 1+2+T(3\times 4)+5\times(67-8)-9 & 367 &:= -9-T(8)+T(T(7))+T(6)+5+4+3+2+1 \\
368 &:= -1-2+T(T(3+4))-5-6-7-8-9 & 368 &:= (9+8)\times T(7)-T(6+5)-43+2-1 \\
369 &:= -7+T(T(3+4))-6-7-8-9 & 369 &:= T(9)+T(8-7+65-43+2)-1 \\
370 &:= -1+T(T(2\times 3))+4\times(5+6+7+8+9) & 370 &:= (T(9)-8)\times(7+6\times 54-321) \\
371 &:= 1-T(T(2\times 3))-T(4)\times(5\times 6-T(7))+T(T(8))-T(9) & 371 &:= T(9)+T(8-7+65-43+2)+1 \\
372 &:= -1+2+T(T(3+4))-5-6-7-8-9 & 372 &:= T((98-7-65)\times(4-3))+T(T(2+1)) \\
373 &:= 12+(-3+4)^{567}+8\times T(9) & 373 &:= -9-8+(T(7)+6+5)\times(4+3+2+1) \\
374 &:= 1+2+3+45+6-7+9\times T(8) & 374 &:= -9-8+T(7+T(6))-5-4-3-2-1 \\
375 &:= (1+2-T(3))\times 45+6+7\times 8\times 9 & 375 &:= 9-T(8)+76\times 5+4-3+21 \\
376 &:= -1-T(2\times T(3)+T(4))+T(5+6+7+8+9) & 376 &:= T(-9+T(8))+7+6-5-4-3-2-1 \\
377 &:= T(12)-3^4-5\times(6+7-89) & 377 &:= 98-7+65-4-T(3)+T(21) \\
378 &:= (1+2^3+4-5+6)\times(T(7)+8-9) & 378 &:= T(9)+T(T(8)+7)-6\times(54-3)\times 2-1 \\
379 &:= 1^2\times 3-4+5\times 67+T(9) & 379 &:= 98/7-6+5\times T(4)+321 \\
380 &:= T(1+2^3)-T(T(4))+5\times T(6+7+8-9) & 380 &:= T(9)-8\times(76-5)+43\times 21 \\
381 &:= (1+2)\times(3+T(4))\times(5+T(6)-7)-8\times T(9) & 381 &:= T(-9-8+T(7))+T(6)\times(5+4+3+2+1) \\
382 &:= -1-2+(T(T(3))-T(4))\times(5+6+7+8+9) & 382 &:= T(9)+87+T(65-43)-2-1 \\
383 &:= -1+2\times(T(T(T(3))))-4-5-6-7-8-9 & 383 &:= T(9)+8\times(T(7)+65)-T(4+3+21) \\
384 &:= 1+23+(4+5+67-T(8))\times 9 & 384 &:= 98-7+T(T(6))+T(T(5)-4)-3-2+1 \\
385 &:= 12+(5\times(3+4)+6)-T(7)+8\times T(9) & 385 &:= 9\times(8+7)+T(6)\times(5+4+3)-2\times 1 \\
386 &:= 1\times 2-T(3)+45+6\times 7\times 8+9 & 386 &:= (9+8)\times T(7)+(T(6)-54+3)\times(2+1) \\
387 &:= (-1-2)\times 3^4+T(5+6+7+8+9) & 387 &:= -9+T(T(8)-7-6)+T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
388 &:= (T(12)-3-4-5)\times 6-7+8-9 & 388 &:= 98-T(7)+6\times(54-3+2\times 1) \\
389 &:= -T(T(1\times 2\times 3))-T(4)+T(5+6+7+8+9) & 389 &:= -9-8+T(7+6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
390 &:= 12\times 34+5+6-T(7)+8-9 & 390 &:= -9+8+T(7+T(6))-5-4-3-2-1 \\
391 &:= 1\times 2\times 34\times 5+T(6)-7-8+T(9) & 391 &:= 9\times(87+6)-5\times 43-T(21) \\
392 &:= -1-2-T(T(T(3)))-4+T(5+6+7+8+9) & 392 &:= T(-9+T(8))-7+6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
393 &:= T(-1+2+T(T(3)))+4\times(5+6+7+8+9) & 393 &:= (9-8)\times T(7)\times(6+5+4-3+2)+1 \\
394 &:= 12+3\times 4-(5-6\times 7)\times T(T(8)/9) & 394 &:= T(9)-8+7\times(6+54)-3\times 21 \\
395 &:= 12+345-6-T(7)+8\times 9 & 395 &:= 98+7\times 6-T(T(5)-4)+321 \\
396 &:= 1+2\times 3+4-T(5)-6+T(7\times T(8)/9) & 396 &:= 9\times 8+7-65+4+T(T(3)+21) \\
397 &:= T((123-4+56)/7)+8\times 9 & 397 &:= 9\times T(8)+T(7)-6+T(5+4)+3\times 2\times 1 \\
398 &:= 1-2\times 3+45+6+T(7)+T(8)\times 9 & 398 &:= 9+8-T(7)\times 6+5\times 4+T(32)+1 \\
399 &:= -1+2\times(T(T(T(3))))+4-5-6-7-8-9 & 399 &:= T(9)-8-7-6+54+321 \\
400 &:= T(12)+34+(5+6-7)\times 8\times 9 & 400 &:= -9+T(8)+T(T(7)-6)+T(5+4+3+2+1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
401 &:= T(1+2^3) - (4-56/7) \times 89 & 401 &:= -9 - (T(8) - 7 \times (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
402 &:= (1+23)/4 \times (567 + T(8))/9 & 402 &:= (-9+8 \times 7) \times 6 + T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
403 &:= (-1-2 \times T(3)) \times (4-5-6-7-8-9) & 403 &:= T(9) \times 8+7+6 \times (5+(4-3)^{21}) \\
404 &:= T((1+2)^3) + (T(4) \times T(5) + 6+78)/9 & 404 &:= T(9) + (87-6) \times 5 - 43 - 2 - 1 \\
405 &:= 123 - 45 + T(T(6)) + 7 + 89 & 405 &:= -9+8 + T(7+6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
406 &:= (12-34) \times 5 + T(6) \times T(7) - 8 \times 9 & 406 &:= T(-9+T(8)) + 7+6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
407 &:= -1+2 + T(3-T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 407 &:= 9 \times (T(8) + T(7)) - 65 - T(2 \times (4+3)) + 1 \\
408 &:= -1 - T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) & 408 &:= T(9) - 8 + (7 \times 6 + T(5) - 4) \times (3 \times 2 + 1) \\
409 &:= 1+2 - T(T(3)) + 456 - T(7) + 8 - 9 & 409 &:= 9+8+76+5 - T(4) + 321 \\
410 &:= -1+2 - T(T(T(3))) + T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) & 410 &:= -9-8 + T(T(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
411 &:= 12+3+456-7-8-T(9) & 411 &:= 98 \times 7 - 65 - (4+T(3)) \times 21 \\
412 &:= -1 + T(2+T(T(3))+4) + 5+6+7+8+9 & 412 &:= -9 + T(8) + T(T(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
413 &:= ((1-2)^{345} - 6 - T(T(7))) \times (8-9) & 413 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - T(7) - T(T(6)) + 5+4+3+2+1 \\
414 &:= T(1+2) - T(T(3)) + 456 - T(7) - 8+9 & 414 &:= -9+8 + T(T(7)) - 6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
415 &:= (1+2) \times (3 \times 4)^{T(5)-6-7} - 8-9 & 415 &:= T(-9+T(8)) + T(7) - 6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
416 &:= (1 \times 2 + T(3)) \times (4+56-7+8-9) & 416 &:= 9 \times T(8) + 7+65-4+3+21 \\
417 &:= 1 + T(2+T(T(3))) + 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9) & 417 &:= -9 + T(T(8)-7) + 6 - (5+4+3+2+1) \\
418 &:= 12+3-4 + T(5) \times 6-7 + T(8) \times 9 & 418 &:= 98-7-T(6) + (T(5)+43) \times T(2+1) \\
419 &:= 1+2 - (3-4) \times 5+6 + T(T(7)) + 8-9 & 419 &:= (9+8) \times T(7) + 6-54-3-T(2+1) \\
420 &:= -T((1 \times 2+3) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) & 420 &:= (-9+T(8)) \times 7 + T(6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
421 &:= T(1+2) \times T(3) \times T(4) - 5+67+8-9 & 421 &:= 9 - T(8) - T(7) + 43 \times (6+5) + 2+1 \\
422 &:= -1+2 \times T(T(T(3))) - 4-5-6-7-8-9 & 422 &:= T(-9+8+T(7)) - 6-5 + T(4+3+2+1) \\
423 &:= 1+2+34+5+6 \times 7 \times 8 + T(9) & 423 &:= -9 \times (T(8)+7-6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
424 &:= -1+2+3 - T(4+5) + T(6+7+8+9) & 424 &:= 987 - T(6) - 543 + 2 - 1 \\
425 &:= -1+2 \times (3 + T(T(T(4)) - 5-6-7-8-9)) & 425 &:= 9 \times 8 - T(7) + 6+54+321 \\
426 &:= T(12 \times 3) - 45 - 6 \times 7 - T(8+9) & 426 &:= -9+8 + T(T(7)) + 6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
427 &:= 12 \times 34 - (5-6-7) \times 8 - T(9) & 427 &:= T(-9+T(8)) + T(7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
428 &:= 1+23+456-7-T(8)-9 & 428 &:= -9-8+5 \times T(7+6) - 4-3-2-1 \\
429 &:= (-1+2 \times T(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9) & 429 &:= T(-9+T(8)) + 7-6-5 + T(4+3+2+1) \\
430 &:= (-1+2) \times T(3 \times T(4)) - 5-6-7-8-9 & 430 &:= 9 \times T(8) - 7 \times (6+T(5)) + T(43-21) \\
431 &:= 12 - (3-4) \times (56 \times 7 + T(8)) - 9 & 431 &:= 9+87 \times 6+5 - T(T(4)+3+2-1) \\
432 &:= (1 \times 2^3 + 4 \times 5 + T(6)) \times 7 + 89 & 432 &:= (-9+T(8)) \times (7-6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
433 &:= -1 \times 2 - T(T(3)) - 4-5 + T(6+7+8+9) & 433 &:= 9-8+7 \times 65 + T(4) - 32 - 1 \\
434 &:= 1 - 2^{T(3)} - 4 + T(T(5)) + 6 \times 7 \times 8 + T(9) & 434 &:= T(9+8) + 7 \times T(6) + 5+4 \times 32+1 \\
435 &:= T(-1+2-3-4+5+6+7+8+9) & 435 &:= T(9) \times 8+7+6-5+4+3 \times 21 \\
436 &:= -1+2 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(4) - 5-6-7-8-9 & 436 &:= (9 \times 8 + T(7) \times T(T(6)))/(5+4+3+2+1) \\
437 &:= T(T(-1+2+T(3))) - 4+5+6+7+8+9 & 437 &:= T(-9+T(8)) - 7+6+5 + T(4+3+2+1) \\
438 &:= 12 - 3^4 + T(5) - 6 \times (7-89) & 438 &:= -9 \times 8 + (T(7)+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
439 &:= 12 \times 34 + 5 \times 6 + T(7) - T(8) + 9 & 439 &:= T(9) - T(8) + 76+54 + T(3+21) \\
440 &:= -T(T(1 \times 2+3)+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) & 440 &:= 9 + T(8) - 7-6 \times 5 + 432 \times 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$441 := T(T((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$442 := (1+2) \times (3-4) + 56 \times 7 + 8 + T(9)$$

$$443 := T(1+2) + 3 - 4 \times 5 + T(6) + T(T(7)) + T(8) - 9$$

$$444 := -1 + T(T(2+3)) \times 4 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$445 := T(T(-1+2+T(3))) + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$446 := 1 + 23 + 456 - 7 - T(8) + 9$$

$$447 := -1 - 2 \times (T(T(3+4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$448 := -1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3+4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$449 := (1+2) \times (3 \times 4)^{T(5)-6-7} + 8 + 9$$

$$450 := T(-1+2+3) \times (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$451 := 1 - 23 \times 4 + T(5) + 67 \times 8 - 9$$

$$452 := 1 - 2 - 3 \times 4 \times T(5) + 678 - T(9)$$

$$453 := -1 - T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$454 := (1^2 + 3 + 45 - 6) \times 7 + T(8+9)$$

$$455 := T(T(T(1+2))) + 345 - T(6) - T(7) - 8 \times 9$$

$$456 := -1 + 2 + (3 + T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$457 := T(12) \times T(3) - 4 - 5 + 6 - 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$458 := 1^{23} \times (T(4) - 56 + 9 \times (7 \times 8))$$

$$459 := 1^{23} + T(4) - 56 + 7 \times 8 \times 9$$

$$460 := -1 + T(T(2 \times 3) + T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$461 := T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$462 := 1 \times 2 \times (T(3) \times 45 + 6 + (7-8) \times T(9))$$

$$463 := T(-1+2+T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$464 := 1 \times 23 - 4 + T(5+6) + T(T(7)) - T(8) + 9$$

$$465 := T(12 \times 3) - 45 - 67 - 89$$

$$466 := 1 - 23 + T(4) + 567 - 89$$

$$467 := 1 + 2 - T(T(3)) + 456 + T(7) - 8 + 9$$

$$468 := T(1+2) - T(T(3)) + 456 + T(7) + 8 - 9$$

$$469 := 1 \times 2 \times T(3) + 4 \times 56 + 8 \times T(7) + 9$$

$$470 := T(-1+2+T(3+4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$471 := (1-2) \times 3 + 45 + 6 + T(T(7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$472 := -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 5 + T(6+7+8+9)$$

$$473 := -1 - 2 \times T(3 \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$474 := 12 + 345 + T(6) + 7 + 89$$

$$475 := 1^2 + 345 + 6 + 78 + T(9)$$

$$476 := 12/3 + 45 + 67 + 8 \times T(9)$$

$$477 := 1 \times 2 + 3 + 456 + 7 - T(8) + T(9)$$

$$478 := T(T(1+2)) + 345 + 67 + T(8) + 9$$

$$479 := T(12) \times T(3) + 4 + 5 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 9$$

$$480 := 12 + T(3) + 456 + 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$441 := 9 + (T(8) + 76) - 5 + 4 + 321$$

$$442 := (9-8) \times T(T(7)) + (65+43)/(2+1)$$

$$443 := (98+T(7)) \times (6-5) - 4 + 321$$

$$444 := 98 + (7+65+43) + T(21)$$

$$445 := (9-T(8)) \times 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4 \times 32 \times 1$$

$$446 := 987 + 6 - 5 \times 4 - T(32) + 1$$

$$447 := 9 - 87 - T(6) + 543 + 2 + 1$$

$$448 := 98 + T(7) + (6-5)^4 + 321$$

$$449 := T(-9+T(8)) - T(7) - T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$450 := -9 \times (T(8) + T(7) + 6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))$$

$$451 := (T(9) + T(8) + 76 \times 5 - 4 - T(3)) \times (2-1)$$

$$452 := (9+8) \times T(7) - T(6+5) + 43 - 2 + 1$$

$$453 := T(9) \times 8 + 76 - 5 + 43 - 21$$

$$454 := 98 + 76 \times 5 - T(T(4)) + 32 - 1$$

$$455 := 98 + 76 \times 5 - T(T(4)) + 32 \times 1$$

$$456 := 98 + 76 \times 5 - T(T(4)) + 32 + 1$$

$$457 := T(-9+T(8)) + T(7+6) - T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)$$

$$458 := -9 - 8 + T(T(7)+6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$459 := -9 \times T(8) + T(7 \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$460 := -9 \times 8 + T(T(7)) + 6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$461 := (9+T(8)) \times 7 + 6 - 5 + (4 \times 3)^2 + 1$$

$$462 := T(T(-9+8+7)) + T(6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$463 := T(9) + 8 + T(7) + 65 - 4 + 321$$

$$464 := 9 \times 8 + T(7 \times (6-5)) \times (T(4)-3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$465 := 9 \times T(8) + 76 + 5 + T(4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$466 := -9 \times T(8) + T(T(7)+6+5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$467 := 9 + T(8) - T(7) - 6 - T(5) + T(T(4) \times 3) + T(2+1)$$

$$468 := T(-9+8+T(7)) + 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$469 := T(-9+T(8)+7) - 6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$470 := 9 \times 8 + T(7) \times 6 + 5 \times (43+2+1)$$

$$471 := (-9+T(8)) \times (7+6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$472 := 9 + T(T(8)) + T(7) - T(6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$473 := 98 + T(7+T(6)) + 5 - 4 - 32 \times 1$$

$$474 := -9 + T(8) \times 7 + T(6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$475 := T(-9+T(8)) + 7 + 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$476 := 9 \times 8 + 7 - 65 - (4-T(3)) \times T(21)$$

$$477 := T(9-8+7+T(6)) + 5 + 4 + 32 + 1$$

$$478 := T(9+T(8)-7) + 6 + 5 - 43 - T(21)$$

$$479 := T(9) - (8-76+54) \times (32-1)$$

$$480 := -9 \times (T(8) - T(7+6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$521 := T(-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$522 := 1^{234} \times 567 - T(8) - 9$$

$$523 := -1 + 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$524 := -1 - T(2 \times (3 + 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$525 := 1 - 2^3 + 4 + T(47 - 7 - 8)$$

$$526 := 1^2 - 3 + T(T(4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$527 := (1 - 2)^3 + T(T(4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$528 := (1 + 23)/4 + 567 - T(8) - 9$$

$$529 := 1 + 2 + T(34) + (5 - 6) \times (78 - 9)$$

$$530 := -1 + T(T(2 \times 3) + T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$531 := (-1 + 2) \times T(T(T(3)) + T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$532 := 1 \times 2^3 - 4 + T(56 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$533 := (1 + 23 + T(4) - 567) \times (8 - 9)$$

$$534 := (-1 - 2 - T(T(3))) \times 4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$535 := 1 + 2 - 3 + 45 \times T(6) - T(T(7)) - T(8)/9$$

$$536 := (-1) - 2 - T(3 + T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$537 := (1 \times 2 - 3 + 4) \times (56 + 78 + T(9))$$

$$538 := 1 + (2 - 3 + 4) \times (56 + 78 + T(9))$$

$$539 := 12 \times T(T(3)) - T(T(4)) + T(5) + T(T(6)) - 7 + 89$$

$$540 := T(3 \times (-1 + 2)) \times (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$541 := 123 - 4 - 5 + 67 + 8 \times T(9)$$

$$542 := 1^{23} \times T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 \times (7 - 89)$$

$$543 := 12 \times 34 + T(5) \times 6 + T(7) + 8 + 9$$

$$544 := -1 \times 2 - T(T(3)) \times 4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$545 := (1^{234} + 5) \times T(6 + 7) + 8 - 9$$

$$546 := (1 + 2) \times T(3) + T(T(4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$547 := (1^{234} + 5) \times T(6 + 7) - (8 - 9)$$

$$548 := 12 \times 34 + T(5 + 6) - 7 + T(8) + T(9)$$

$$549 := 1 - 2 - T(3 \times 4) - 5 + 678 - T(9)$$

$$550 := -1 + 2 - T(T(T(3))) + T(4 + (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$551 := -1 - T(T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$552 := (1 - 2) \times 3^{T(4)-5} + 6 + 789$$

$$553 := T(T(T(1 + 2))) + 3 - 4 + 5 + T(T(6)) + 78 + 9$$

$$554 := 1 \times 2 + 3 + 45 + T(6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$555 := T(T(T(1 + 2))) - 3 + 4 + 5 + T(T(6)) + 78 + 9$$

$$556 := 12 + T(3) + 456 - 7 + 89$$

$$557 := 1 \times 2 + T(34) + 56 - 7 - 89$$

$$558 := 1^{234} \times 567 + T(8) - T(9)$$

$$559 := T(1 \times 2 + 34) - 5 - T(6) - 7 - T(T(8))/9$$

$$521 := 9 \times (8 \times 7) + 6 - 5 + T(4) + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$522 := 9 + 87 + 654 + 3 - T(21)$$

$$523 := -9 + T(8) + T(T(7)) + 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$524 := -9 + T(T(8)) - (7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$525 := 9 - (8 + T(7))/6 + 543 - 21$$

$$526 := 9 \times (T(8) + T(7)) - 65 + (4 + 3) \times 2 + 1$$

$$527 := 9 \times T(8) - T(7) + T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$528 := T(-9 - 8 + T(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$529 := 9 - 8 + 7 - T(6) + 5 + T(4) + T(32) - 1$$

$$530 := T(T(9) - 8) - 76 - 5^4 + T(32) \times 1$$

$$531 := 98/7 \times 6 + T(5) + 432 \times 1$$

$$532 := (9 - 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 + T(32) \times 1$$

$$533 := 98 \times 7 - T(T(6)) + T(5) + 4^3 - 2 + 1$$

$$534 := 9 \times (87 + T(6)) - 5 - 432 - 1$$

$$535 := 9 \times (87 + T(6)) - 5 - 432 \times 1$$

$$536 := 9 \times (87 + T(6)) - 5 - 432 + 1$$

$$537 := 98 + T(7 + T(6)) + 5 - 4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$538 := 9 + 87 \times 6 - 2 + T(4) - 2 + 1$$

$$539 := 9 + (8 - T(7) + T(6))^{5+4} + T(32) + 1$$

$$540 := 9 \times (T(8 + 7 - 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$541 := 9 + 87 \times 6 - 5 + T(4) + 3 + 2 \times 1$$

$$542 := 9 - 8 + 76 - T(5) + 4 \times T(T(3 + 2 \times 1))$$

$$543 := -9 - T(8) + T(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$544 := -9 + T(T(8)) + T(7) - T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$545 := -9 - T(8) - (7 - T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$546 := T(9) - 8 - 7 - 6 + 543 - 21$$

$$547 := 9 - 87 + (6 + 5^4 - T(3)) \times (2 - 1)$$

$$548 := 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5 - 4 + T(32 \times 1)$$

$$549 := 9 + (8 + 7) \times (T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$550 := T(T(7 \times (9 - 8))) + (6 + 5 + 4 - 3)^2 \times 1$$

$$551 := -9 + T(T(8)) - T(7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$552 := 98 + 765 + T(4) - 321$$

$$553 := T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7)) - T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$554 := -9 + T(T(8)) + 7 - (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$555 := (T(9) + 87 + 6 + 54) \times 3 - 21$$

$$556 := -9 - 8 + T(7) \times T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$557 := 98 \times 7 + (6 - T(5)) \times 4 \times 3 - 21$$

$$558 := 9 + (T(8) + 76) + 5 + 432 \times 1$$

$$559 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 - T(4)) + T(3^2 + 1)$$

$$560 := (1+2)/3 + (4-5 + T(6)) \times T(7) + 8 - 9$$

$$561 := (12+3+4) \times (5+6) + T(7) + T(8) \times 9$$

$$562 := (1+2)/3 + (4-5 + T(6)) \times T(7) - 8 + 9$$

$$563 := 1^{234} \times 567 - T(8)/9$$

$$564 := -1 - (T(T(2+3)) - T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$565 := 12 - 3 - T(4) + 567 + 8 - 9$$

$$566 := 1 - 23 - 4 \times 5 - 67 + T(T(8)) + 9$$

$$567 := -1 - 2 - T(3) \times T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$568 := 1 - T(23) + T(4) + (56-7) \times (8+9)$$

$$569 := 1 - 2 - T(3) + T(4) + 567 + 8 - 9$$

$$570 := 1 \times 2 \times 345 - 67 - 8 - T(9)$$

$$571 := 1 + 2 \times 345 - 67 - 8 - T(9)$$

$$572 := -1 - 2 - T(T(3)+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$573 := -1 - 2 \times T(3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$574 := 1 + T(2+34) - 5 - 6 + 7 - 89$$

$$575 := 12/T(3) + 456 + T(7) + 89$$

$$576 := (-1+2)^3 - T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$577 := (-1-2) \times T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$578 := (-1+2) \times 3 - T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$579 := -1 + 2 + 3 - T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$580 := 1^{23} + 456 + 78 + T(9)$$

$$581 := 1 \times 2 + (T(3) - 45 \times (6+7)) \times (8-9)$$

$$582 := 12 - 3 + 456 + T(7) + 89$$

$$583 := 1 \times T(2+34) + 5 - 6 + 7 - 89$$

$$584 := -1 + T(2+3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$585 := T(-1+2 \times 3) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$586 := 12 + (T(3) + 45) \times (6+7) - 89$$

$$587 := -1 + 2 \times (T(T(T(3)))) \times 4 - T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$588 := 1 - 23 - (4 + T(5) - 6) + 7 \times 89$$

$$589 := 123 - T(T(4))/5 + 6 \times 78 + 9$$

$$590 := 1 \times 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 - 67 + T(T(8)) - 9$$

$$591 := T(-1 + T(2 + T(3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$592 := 12 + 34 + T(5) + (67-8) \times 9$$

$$593 := (1-2) \times 34 + (56 + T(7)) \times 8 - T(9)$$

$$594 := 1^{234} \times 567 + T(8) - 9$$

$$595 := 1^{234} + 567 + T(8) - 9$$

$$596 := (1 - T(23)/4) - 5 + 678 - 9$$

$$597 := 12 \times 34 - (5 - 6 - T(7) + 8) \times 9$$

$$598 := T(1 \times 23) + 4 + 5 \times 67 - 8 - 9$$

$$599 := -1 - 2 - T(3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$560 := -9 + T(T(8)) - 7 - 6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$561 := T(T(-9 + T(8)))/7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$562 := T(-9 + T(8)) - T(7+6) + 5 \times T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$563 := -9 - 8 + T(T(7)+6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$564 := -9 \times T(8) + T(7 \times 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$565 := 98/7 \times T(6) + 54 \times (3+2) + 1$$

$$566 := (9+8) \times T(7) - (T(6) - 54+3) \times (2+1)$$

$$567 := (98+7-65-T(4)-3) \times 21$$

$$568 := 9 \times (87+6) + 5 - 43 - T(21)$$

$$569 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 65 + 4 + T(3) \times 21$$

$$570 := T(9) + 8 + T(T(7)) + 65 + 43 + 2 + 1$$

$$571 := -9 - 8 + T(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$572 := 9 - 87 - T(6) \times (5-4-32) - 1$$

$$573 := 9 + 8 + 7 - T(6) + 5 + 4 + T(32+1)$$

$$574 := 98 \times 7 - 6 \times T(5) - 4 + 3 - 21$$

$$575 := -9 + 8 \times (7+6+5 + T(4+3+2+1))$$

$$576 := T(-9+8 + T(7)+6) + 5+4+3+2+1$$

$$577 := 98/7 + T(6) + 543 - 2 + 1$$

$$578 := 9 \times T(8) - 76 + 5 + 4 + 321$$

$$579 := 7 \times (9+8) \times 6 + (5+4) \times (T(3)-21)$$

$$580 := 9 \times 87 + 6 + 5 - 4 + T(T(3)) - T(21)$$

$$581 := T(9) - 87 + 654 - 32 + 1$$

$$582 := 9 \times (T(8) + 7 \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$583 := T(98/7 - 6 - 5) + (4 \times T(3))^2 + 1$$

$$584 := (9+8) \times T(7) + T(6+5) + 43 - 2 + 1$$

$$585 := 9 - 8 - T(7) - 6 + 5^4 - 3 \times 2 - 1$$

$$586 := -9 + T(T(8) + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$587 := 9 - T(8+7)/6 + 5^4 - 3^{2+1}$$

$$588 := 98 \times (7 - 6 + 5 \times 4 + T(3) - 21)$$

$$589 := 987/T(6) + 543 - 2 + 1$$

$$590 := 98 \times 7 - 65 - 4 - T(3) - 21$$

$$591 := -9 - (8 - 7 - 6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$592 := 9 + T(T(8)) - 76 + 5 - 4 \times 3 \times (2-1)$$

$$593 := 987/T(6) + 543 + 2 + 1$$

$$594 := 9 \times 87 - T(6) - T(T(5)) - (4+3)^2 + 1$$

$$595 := T(9) + 8 \times (7+6) + T(5) + 432 - 1$$

$$596 := 9 - 8 + T(T(7) + T(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$597 := -9 + 8 - 7 + (6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$598 := (-9+8) \times 7 + (6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)$$

$$599 := -9 + 8 \times T(7+6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$600 := -1 \times 2 - T(3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$601 := -1 + 2 - 3 \times T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$602 := -1 - 2 - T(T(3)) - 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$603 := -1 + 2 - T(3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$604 := T(1 \times 23) + 4 \times (5 - 6) \times (7 - 89)$$

$$605 := -T(1 \times 2 + 3) - T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$606 := T(12 \times 3) - T(4+5) + 6 - T(7+8-9)$$

$$607 := (1+2)^{T(3)} - 4 \times 5 - 6 - 7 - 89$$

$$608 := T(12) \times 3 + 456 + 7 - 89$$

$$609 := (-1 - 2) \times (3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$610 := (1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 + 5 + 6 \times 7) \times T(T(8)/9)$$

$$611 := 12 + (T(34) + T(5) + 6 \times 7 - 8 - T(9))$$

$$612 := 1^{234} \times 567 + T(8) + 9$$

$$613 := 1^{234} + 567 + T(8) + 9$$

$$614 := 1 - 23 + 4 + T(5) - 6 + 7 \times 89$$

$$615 := 12 + 3 \times 4 - 56 - T(7) + T(T(8)) + 9$$

$$616 := -1 \times 2 \times (3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$617 := (1 \times 2 - 3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5) - 678 - 9)$$

$$618 := -1 - (T(2+3) - 4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$619 := 1 - 2 + 3 - T(T(4)) - T(5) + 678 + 9$$

$$620 := (1 - 2)^{34} \times (567 + 8 + T(9))$$

$$621 := 1 + 2 + T(34) - 56 + 7 + 8 \times 9$$

$$622 := (-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$623 := 1 \times 2 - T(T(3)) - 45 + 678 + 9$$

$$624 := T(12) + 3 \times 4 + (5 - 6 + 7) \times 89$$

$$625 := 1 \times 2 + T(34) + 5 - T(6) + 7 - 8 + T(9)$$

$$626 := -1 + T(T(2 + T(3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$627 := (1+2)/3 - 4 + T(T(56/7) + 8 - 9)$$

$$628 := -1 - 2 - 3 + 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$629 := (1 \times 2 \times (3 + T(4) + 5) - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$630 := T(-1 - 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$631 := 1 + 23 + 4 - 5 - 67 + T(T(8)) + 9$$

$$632 := 1 + 23 - 4 + 567 + T(8) + 9$$

$$633 := -1 + 2 + T(3) - 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$634 := -1 - 2 + 3 + 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$635 := 1 \times T(23)/4 + 567 + 8 - 9$$

$$636 := T(1 \times 23) + 456 - 7 - 89$$

$$637 := 1 \times 2 - 3 - T(4) + T(5) + 678 - T(9)$$

$$638 := -1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)$$

$$639 := -1 - (2 - 3) \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$$

$$600 := -9 + (T(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$601 := (-9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$602 := T(-9 + T(8)) - 7 + T(6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$603 := 9 + 876 - 51 - T(21)$$

$$604 := 98 \times 7 - T(6) - 54 - 3 \times 2 - 1$$

$$605 := -9 - 8 + T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$606 := -9 + T(T(8) - 7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$607 := T(9) + 8 + 7 + (6 \times 5 - 4) \times T(T(3)) + 2 - 1$$

$$608 := -9 + T(T(8)) - T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$609 := 987 - T(6 + 54 - 32 - 1)$$

$$610 := 98 \times 7 - 6 \times T(5) - 4 - 3 + 21$$

$$611 := -9 + 8 + 7 + (6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$612 := 9 \times (-8 + T(7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$613 := 9 + T(T(8)) + T(7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$614 := 9 - 87 + T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4)/3 - 2 + 1$$

$$615 := -9 + T(8) + T(7) \times (6 + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$616 := 9 + T(T(8)) - 76 + 54/3 - 2 + 1$$

$$617 := 9 + T(T(8)) - 76 + 54/3 \times (2 - 1)$$

$$618 := T(9) - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5^4 - 32 + 1$$

$$619 := 987 \times 5 \times 4 / T(6) - 321$$

$$620 := -9 - 8 + T(T(7)) + T(6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$621 := -9 + T(8 \times 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)$$

$$622 := 9 \times 87 - T(6) + 5 - (4 \times 3)^2 - 1$$

$$623 := 98 \times 7 + 6 - 54 + T(3) - 21$$

$$624 := T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + T(T(6)) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$625 := -9 + T(8) - 7 + (6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$626 := 9 + T(8) + 7 \times (6 + T(5) + 4^3 - 2 \times 1)$$

$$627 := 4 \times (9 \times 8 + 76 + 5) + T(3 \times 2 - 1)$$

$$628 := T(9) + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5^4 - 3 \times 21$$

$$629 := 9 - T(8) + 7 + 654 - 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$630 := T(9) - 87 + 654 - 3 + 21$$

$$631 := (9 + 8) \times 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 + T(32) - 1$$

$$632 := T(9) \times (8 + 7 - (6 - 5)^{43}) + 2 \times 1$$

$$633 := T(9) \times (8 + 7 - (6 - 5)^{43}) + 2 + 1$$

$$634 := 9 - 8 \times T(7) - 6 - 5 + T(43 - 2) - 1$$

$$635 := T(9) + 8 - T(7) - 6 + T(5) \times (43 - 2) + 1$$

$$636 := 98 \times 7 - 6 - T(5) + 4 - 32 - 1$$

$$637 := T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7) + T(6+5+4+3+2+1)$$

$$638 := (-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$639 := 9 \times (-T(8) - 7 - 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
640 &:= T(1-2+34) - 56 + (7+8) \times 9 \\
641 &:= T(12 \times 3) + 4 - 56 + T(7) + 8 - 9 \\
642 &:= (-1+2) \times (3 \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
643 &:= -1+2 \times (3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
644 &:= T(-1+2+3) + 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
645 &:= 1+2+3^{T(4)-5} - 6 + (T(T(7))+8) - 9 \\
646 &:= (-1+2+3) \times 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
647 &:= T(T(1^2+3+4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 + 8 - 9 \\
648 &:= 1^{234} \times 567 + T(8) + T(9) \\
649 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4 + 5 \times 67 + T(8) \times 9 \\
650 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 - T(T(4))) \times (56 - 78 + 9) \\
651 &:= T(T(-1+2+3) - 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
652 &:= 1+2 \times 345 + 6 + (7-8) \times T(9) \\
653 &:= 1+23 - T(4) + 567 + 8 \times 9 \\
654 &:= -1 + T(2+3) + T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
655 &:= (1^2+3+4) \times (T(5)+67) + 8 - 9 \\
656 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(3+4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
657 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
658 &:= 1^2 + 3^4 + 567 - T(8) + T(9) \\
659 &:= 1 - (2-3)^{4567} + T(T(8)) - 9 \\
660 &:= (1+2 \times 3^4 + T(5) - (6+7)) \times T(8)/9 \\
661 &:= T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
662 &:= T(-1+2+T(3)) + 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
663 &:= 1+2+3^{T(4)-5} - 6 + (T(T(7))+8) + 9 \\
664 &:= -1 + (T(2+3)+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
665 &:= -1 + T(2+3-4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
666 &:= T(-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
667 &:= 1+2+T(34) - (5-6) \times (78-9) \\
668 &:= T(-1+2+T(3)) + T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
669 &:= 1+2+T(34) - 5 - 6 - 7 + 89 \\
670 &:= T(12) + 34 + 567 + T(8) - T(9) \\
671 &:= 1^2 \times (4 \times T(T(3)) \times 56/7 + 8 - 9) \\
672 &:= 1 \times 2^3 + 4 \times 5 + T(6) + 7 \times 89 \\
673 &:= 1+2 \times (3-4+T(5)) + T(6) + 7 \times 89 \\
674 &:= 1^2 \times T(34) - 5 + 67 + 8 + 9 \\
675 &:= T(T(-1+2+3)) - T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
676 &:= (-1-2) \times 3 + T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
677 &:= 1+2 \times 345 - 67 + 8 + T(9) \\
678 &:= (1+2) \times (3+4 \times 5) + T(6) \times (T(7) - 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
640 &:= 98/7 + 654 - T(T(3) + 2 - 1) \\
641 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
642 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + T(T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
643 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + 7 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
644 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - 7 - T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
645 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + 7 \times T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
646 &:= (9-8) \times (7+654+T(3)) - 21 \\
647 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 654 + T(3) - 21 \\
648 &:= -9 \times T(8) \times (7+6-5-4-3-2-1) \\
649 &:= (9-8) \times T(7) + 6 + T(5) \times (43-2 \times 1) \\
650 &:= (9+T(8+7)+6-5) \times (4+3/(2+1)) \\
651 &:= 7 \times (9-8) \times (T(6)+5+4^3) + 21 \\
652 &:= 9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4 + T(32+1) \\
653 &:= 98 \times 7 + 6 - 54 - T(3) + 21 \\
654 &:= -9 + 8 \times T(7+6) - T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1) \\
655 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + 7 + 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
656 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - (7-6)^{54321} \\
657 &:= -9 + T(8+7+6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
658 &:= T(9) - 8 + 76 + 543 + 2 \times 1 \\
659 &:= 98/7 + 654 - T(3) - 2 - 1 \\
660 &:= 9 + T(T(8) \times (7-6)) - 54/3 + 2 + 1 \\
661 &:= (9+8+T(7) \times (T(6+5) - 43)) \times (2-1) \\
662 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times (6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1) \\
663 &:= 9 \times T(8) + 76 \times 5 - 43 + 2 \times 1 \\
664 &:= -9 + T(8) + T(T(7)) + T(6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
665 &:= -9 + T(8) - T(7) + T(T(6)+5+4+3+2+1) \\
666 &:= 9 + T(8) + 76 + 543 + 2 \times 1 \\
667 &:= 9 \times T(8) + 76 - 54 + 321 \\
668 &:= 9 \times 8 - T(7) + 6 \times (5+T(4 \times 3) + 21) \\
669 &:= T(9+8+7) - 6 + 54 + 321 \\
670 &:= 9+8-7+T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
671 &:= 98 \times 7 - T(6) - 5 - 4 + T(T(3) - 2 + 1) \\
672 &:= -9+8+7+T(T(6)+5+4+3+2+1) \\
673 &:= -9+T(T(8))+7-6+5+4+3+2+1 \\
674 &:= 9+8 \times 7 - T(T(6) - T(5)) \times (4-32-1) \\
675 &:= (9+T(8) \times (7-6)) \times (54/3 - 2 - 1) \\
676 &:= 9+8 \times (76+5) + T(4) + 3^2 \times 1 \\
677 &:= 98/7 + 654 + T(3) + 2 + 1 \\
678 &:= T(9) + 87 + 6 + 543 - 2 - 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
679 &:= (1-2) \times (3+T(4)) + 5 + 678 + 9 & 679 &:= -9 + T(T(8) + 7 - 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
680 &:= (1 \times 2 + T(3)) \times (4 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 89) & 680 &:= -9 + T(T(8) + 7 - 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
681 &:= 1 + (2 + T(3)) \times (4 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 89) & 681 &:= T((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
682 &:= 1 - 2 - ((34 - 5) \times (6 - T(7)) - T(8) - 9) & 682 &:= -9 - T(8) + 7 + 6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
683 &:= (1 - 2) \times ((34 - 5) \times (6 - T(7)) - T(8) - 9) & 683 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + T(7 + 6 - 5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
684 &:= 1 + 2 \times 345 + 67 - T(T(8))/9 & 684 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + 7 \times 6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
685 &:= 1^2 \times (3^4 + 567 - 8 + T(9)) & 685 &:= T(9 - 8 + T(7) + 6) + T(5) + 43 - 2 - 1 \\
686 &:= 1^2 + 3^4 + 567 - 8 + T(9) & 686 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - T(7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
687 &:= -1 - 2 + T(3) \times T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 687 &:= T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
688 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 5 \times T(6) \times 7 - 8 \times 9 & 688 &:= -9 + 8 \times (T(7) + T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
689 &:= T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + 4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 689 &:= T(9) - 8 + 7 + 6 \times 54 + 321 \\
690 &:= T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 690 &:= 9 + T(T(8) \times (7 - 6)) + 54/3 - 2 - 1 \\
691 &:= 1 \times 23 - 4 \times 5 + (6 + 7 + T(T(8)) + 9) & 691 &:= 9 - 8 + (7 + 65 + 43) \times T(2 + 1) \\
692 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) + T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 692 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - 6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
693 &:= (12 - 3) \times (4 - T(5) + (6 - 7 + 89)) & 693 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
694 &:= 123 \times 4 + 56 - 7 + T(8 + 9) & 694 &:= 98/7 \times T(6 + 5) + 4 - 3 - T(21) \\
695 &:= 1 + 23 \times 4 - T(5) - 6 + 7 \times 89 & 695 &:= 98 \times 7 + 6 + 5 - T(4)/(T(3) - 2 + 1) \\
696 &:= (1 + 23) \times (4 + T(5) + 6) + 7 + 89 & 696 &:= 9 + 8 + 765 - T(T(4)) - 32 + 1 \\
697 &:= 1 + 2 \times T(3) + (T(4) + 5 + 678 - 9) & 697 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - (7 - 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
698 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 698 &:= 9 \times 87 + 65 + T(4) \times (T(3) - 21) \\
699 &:= 1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 699 &:= 9 + T(8 + 7) + 6 + 543 + 21 \\
700 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 700 &:= T(9) + 876 - 5 \times 43 - T(2 + 1) \\
701 &:= 123 + (T(4) + 567 - 8 + 9) & 701 &:= T(9) - 8 + 76 + 4 \times T(5) + T(32) \times 1 \\
702 &:= ((-1) - 2 + T(T(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 702 &:= -9 + 8 + T(T(7) - 5 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1) \\
703 &:= T(123 + 45 - 6 \times 7 - 89) & 703 &:= T(9) + 876 - 5 \times 43 - 2 - 1 \\
704 &:= 1 + (2 + 3 \times 4) \times 5 + 678 - T(9) & 704 &:= -10 + 8 \times T(7 + 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
705 &:= 1 + 2 \times 345 + 59 - T(9) & 705 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
706 &:= 1 \times 2 - 34 + 5 - 6 + T(7) + T(T(8)) + T(9) & 706 &:= -9 + T(T(8) + 7) - T(6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
707 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 34) - 5 - T(6) - 7 + T(T(8))/9 & 707 &:= -9 + 8 + T(7) \times T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
708 &:= T(12 + 3) - 45 + 678 - T(9) & 708 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
709 &:= 1 + 2 + T(3) + 45 + 6 + T(7) + T(T(8)) - T(9) & 709 &:= -9 + (T(T(8) + 7 - 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
710 &:= 1 - 2 - 3 \times 4 + T(5) + 6 + 78 \times 9 & 710 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times T(6) + 5 + T(4) + T(32) - 1 \\
711 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 711 &:= 98 \times (7 + 6 - 5) - T(T(4)) + 3 - 21 \\
712 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(4)) \times (5 - 6 \times 7) - 8 - 9 & 712 &:= T(9) + 876 - 5 \times 43 + T(2 + 1) \\
713 &:= T(-1 + 2 + T(3)) + T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 713 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
714 &:= T(T(12 - 3 + 4 - 5)) + T(6)/7 + T(8) + 9 & 714 &:= (-9 + T(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
715 &:= T(1 \times 2 \times T(3)) - T(4) \times 5 + 678 + 9 & 715 &:= T(-9 + T(8) + T(7) - T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
716 &:= 1 \times 2 - (3 - T(4)) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 & 716 &:= -9 + T(8 + 7) + (6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
717 &:= (1 \times 2^{T(3)} + 4) \times 5 + 6 - 7 + T(T(8) - 9) & 717 &:= T(9) + 8 \times (T(7) - 6 - 54/3) \times 21 \\
718 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 718 &:= -9 - 8 + (T(7) + T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$719 := 12 + 3 \times T(4) + 56 + T(T(7) + 8) - T(9)$$

$$720 := (1 + 2^3 + T(4) + 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$721 := T(-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$722 := -1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$723 := (-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) \times (4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$724 := -1 + (2 + 3) \times T(T(4)) - T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$725 := T(-1 + T(2 + 3)) - T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$726 := (12 - 34) \times (78 \times (5 - 6) + T(9))$$

$$727 := -1 - 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$728 := -1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$729 := -1 + 2 \times (T(3) \times T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$730 := (1 + 2)^{T(3)} + (4 \times (T(T(5)) + 6)) / (7 \times 8 \times 9)$$

$$731 := 12 - 34 - T(5) - T(6) + 789$$

$$732 := (-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$733 := -1 - 2 \times (3 - T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$734 := 1 + T(23)/4 - 5 + 678 - 9$$

$$735 := T(1 + 2) - T(3) \times 4 - T(5) - T(6) + 789$$

$$736 := -1 + 2 + T(3) \times T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$737 := -1 - 2 \times T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$738 := -1 \times 2 \times T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$739 := 1 - 2 \times T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$740 := 123 + 4 - 56/7 + T(T(8)) - T(9)$$

$$741 := 1 \times 2 \times T(3)/4 + T(T(56/7)) + 8 \times 9$$

$$742 := 12 \times T(3) - 4 + 5 + 678 - 9$$

$$743 := -1 - T(2 + T(3)) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$744 := 1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (T(4 + 5 + 6) + T(7)) - 8 \times 9)$$

$$745 := 1 + 2 - T(3) - 4 \times 5 - T(6) + 789$$

$$746 := 12 - 34 - T(5) - 6 + 789$$

$$747 := (-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$748 := 123 - 4 + 56/7 + T(T(8)) - T(9)$$

$$749 := T(1 \times 2 + 34) - 5 + 6 - 7 + 89$$

$$750 := T(T(-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$751 := T(12 \times 3) + 4 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 89$$

$$752 := -1 + 2 + T(T(3 + 4)) - T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$753 := -1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + 4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$754 := T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) + 4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$755 := (12 \times 3)/4 \times (56 + T(7)) + 8 - 9$$

$$756 := T(1 + 2) + 3^4 - 5 + 6 - 7 + T(T(8)) + 9$$

$$757 := 12 \times 3/4 \times (56 + T(7)) - 8 + 9$$

$$758 := -1 - T(2 \times 3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$719 := 9 \times (8 + 7 + T(6 + 5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$720 := (98 + 7 - T(6) - 54) \times (3 + 21)$$

$$721 := T(-9 + T(8) + 7) + 6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$722 := 9 - 8 + T(T(7)) + T(6 - 5 + 4) \times T(T(3)) \times (2 - 1)$$

$$723 := -9 + T(8 + T(7)) + 6 + 5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$724 := 98 \times 7 - 6 + T(5) - 4 + 32 + 1$$

$$725 := 9 + T(8) - 7 + 654 + 32 + 1$$

$$726 := -9 + (T(8) + 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$727 := -9 - 8 \times (7 + T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$728 := 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$729 := 9 - (8 + 7 - T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$730 := -9 + T(8) + T(T(7) - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$731 := 98 \times 7 + 6 + 54 + T(3) - 21$$

$$732 := -9 + T(T(8) - 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$733 := (9 + T(T(8)) + 76 - 54/3) \times (2 - 1)$$

$$734 := 9 + T(T(8)) + 76 - 54/3 + 2 - 1$$

$$735 := 9 \times 87 + 6 - (5 + T(4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$736 := 9 - 8 + (T(7) + T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$737 := -9 + T(T(8)) + (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$738 := -9 \times (T(8) - T(7) - 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$739 := -9 + T(T(8)) - T(7) + (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$740 := 9 \times (8 + 7) + (6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$741 := 9 - T(8) + 7 \times (5 \times T(6) + 4) + 3 \times 2 - 1$$

$$742 := 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5^4 + 3 - T(21)$$

$$743 := 9 \times 87 - 6 - 54 + T(3 \times 2) - 1$$

$$744 := 9 \times 87 - 6 - 54 + T(3 \times 2) \times 1$$

$$745 := 9 \times 87 - 6 - 54 + T(3 \times 2) + 1$$

$$746 := (-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6 + T(5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$747 := -9 + (8 + T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$748 := 98 \times 7 + T(6) + 5 + 4 + 32 \times 1$$

$$749 := T(9) \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5 + 43 \times 2 - 1$$

$$750 := 98 + 7 + 6 - 54 + 3 \times T(21)$$

$$751 := 9 \times T(8) + T(T(7)) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$752 := T(9) - 8 + 765 - T(4) \times (3 \times 2 - 1)$$

$$753 := -9 - T(8) - 7 \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$754 := 98 \times 7 + T(6) + 53 - 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$755 := T(9) \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5 \times 4 + T(T(3)) - T(21)$$

$$756 := 9 \times 87 - 6 + 5 - 4 \times T(3) - 2 \times 1$$

$$757 := T(9) + 87 + 6 + 5^4 - 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$758 := 9 + 8 + 765 - T(T(4)) + 32 - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
759 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 + T(4)) - 56 + 789 & 759 &:= -9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6) - T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
760 &:= T(12)/3 \times (45 - 6 - 7) - 8 \times 9 & 760 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
761 &:= -1 + 2 \times T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 761 &:= 98 \times 7 + 6 + 54 - T(3) + 21 \\
762 &:= T(12) + T(34) + 56 + 78 - T(9) & 762 &:= T(9) + 87 + 6 + 5^4 - 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
763 &:= 12 - T(3) + 4 - T(5) - T(6) + 789 & 763 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
764 &:= -1 - T(2 + 3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 764 &:= 98 \times 7 - 6 \times (T(5) - 4 - 3 - 21) \\
765 &:= 123 + 4 + 5 + 678 - T(9) & 765 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 - 54 + 3 + T(2 + 1) \\
766 &:= T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 766 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7 \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
767 &:= 1 \times 2 + 34 + 56 + T(T(7) + 8) + 9 & 767 &:= 98/7 - T(6) + 543 + T(21) \\
768 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 34 + 5) - 6 - 78 - 9 & 768 &:= (9 + 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 + T(4) + 32 + 1) \\
769 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4) \times 56/7 + T(T(8)) - 9 & 769 &:= 98 + T(7) - 6 + 5^4 + 3 + 21 \\
770 &:= (-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 770 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - T(7) + T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
771 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 771 &:= (9 + 8) \times T(7) + T(T(6)) + 54 + T(T(3) - 2 \times 1) \\
772 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times 4 \times 56 + 7 \times 8 + T(9) & 772 &:= -9 \times (8 - T(7 + 6)) + T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
773 &:= 1^2 \times (3 \times 4 \times 56 + 7 \times 8 + T(9)) & 773 &:= 9 + T(8) + 765 - T(4) - T(3) - 21 \\
774 &:= 1^2 + 3 \times 4 \times 56 + 7 \times 8 + T(9) & 774 &:= (9 + T(8 + 7)) \times (T(6) - 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
775 &:= 1 \times 23 + 456 - T(7) + T(8) \times 9 & 775 &:= (98 - 7 + (T(6) - 5) \times 4) \times (3 + 2 \times 1) \\
776 &:= 1 - 2 \times (3 - 456 + 7 + T(8)) - T(9) & 776 &:= (9 + 8) \times T(7) + T(T(6 + 5) - 43 + 2 - 1) \\
777 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 777 &:= (-9 + T(8)) \times T(7) + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
778 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 778 &:= (T(9) + 8 - 7 - 6 - T(5)) \times T(4) + T(32 \times 1) \\
779 &:= -1 - (2 - 3) \times T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 779 &:= 987 + 6 + 5 + 4 \times 3 - T(21) \\
780 &:= T((1 + 2)/3 \times 4 + T(56/7) + 8 - 9) & 780 &:= T(9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 + 43)/2 + 1) \\
781 &:= 1 - (2 \times (3 - T(4)) - T(T(5))) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 781 &:= T(9) + T(T(8)) + 7 - 65 + 4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
782 &:= -1 + T(T(2 \times 3) - 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 782 &:= 98 \times 7 + 65 + (4 + T(3)) + 21 \\
783 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 783 &:= T(T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
784 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 784 &:= 9 + (T(8 + 7)/6 + 5) \times (T(T(4) - 3) + 2 + 1) \\
785 &:= 1^2 - T(3) + T(4) + 5 \times (67 + 89) & 785 &:= 98 + (7 + 65) \times T(4) - 32 - 1 \\
786 &:= T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 786 &:= T(9) + T(8 + 7 + 6 - 5 + 43 - 21) \\
787 &:= 1 - 2^3 - 4 + T(5) - 6 + 789 & 787 &:= T(9) - 8 + 765 - T(4) - 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
788 &:= T(T(1 \times 2 \times 3)) \times 4 - 5 - 6 + T(7) - T(8 + 9) & 788 &:= -9 \times 8 + (T(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
789 &:= -1 + T(2 + 3) \times T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & 789 &:= 9 + 87 + (6 + 5 + T(4)) \times (32 + 1) \\
790 &:= T(-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 790 &:= 9 - T(8) + 765 + T(4) + T(T(3)) + 21 \\
791 &:= -1 + 2 \times T(3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 791 &:= (9 + 8) \times T(7) + T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
792 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 792 &:= (9 \times 87 - 654 + 3) \times T(2 + 1) \\
793 &:= T(1 + 2 \times T(3)) + T(4) + 5 + 678 + 9 & 793 &:= T(98 - 76) + 5 \times 4 \times (T(3) + 21) \\
794 &:= -1 + T(2 + 3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 794 &:= 98 + 7 \times (6 - 5) - 4 + 3 \times T(21) \\
795 &:= T(-1 + 2 \times 3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 795 &:= T(9) \times (8 + 7) + T(T(6)) + 5 \times 4 \times T(3) - T(21) \\
796 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 796 &:= 98 \times 7 + 65 + 4 \times T(3) + 21 \\
797 &:= 1 - 23 + 4 + 5 + T(6) + 789 & 797 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
798 &:= T(12 + 3) - 45 + 678 + T(9) & 798 &:= 98 \times (7 + 6 - 5) - T(4) + 3 + 21
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 799 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(T(3)) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
 800 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 + 45 + (T(6) + 7) \times (T(8) - 9) \\
 801 &:= T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
 802 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + T(5 \times 6 + 7) + 89 \\
 803 &:= 1 - 2^3 - T(4) \times (56/7 - 89) \\
 804 &:= -1 + T(T(2+3)) + T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
 805 &:= (-1 + T(2+3)) \times T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9 \\
 806 &:= 12 \times 3 + T(45-6) + 7-8-9 \\
 807 &:= 1 \times 2^{T(3)} + 4 + T(5) + 67 + T(T(8)) - 9 \\
 808 &:= T(12) + 3 - 4 + (T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times (8+9) \\
 809 &:= -1 + (T(2+T(3)) - 4-5) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
 810 &:= (-1-2 + T(T(3))) \times T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
 811 &:= (1+2)/3 \times T(4 \times (5+6-7)) + T(T(8)) + 9 \\
 812 &:= (1+2 \times 3) \times (T(4+5) + 67 + T(8)/9) \\
 813 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) - 4 + T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
 814 &:= -1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) \times T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
 815 &:= -1 + T(2+T(3)) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
 816 &:= (T(T(1+2)) + 3 \times 4 - 5+6) \times (7+8+9) \\
 817 &:= 1 \times 23 - 4 + T(5) - 6 + 789 \\
 818 &:= T(12) + 3 + 4 - 56 + 789 \\
 819 &:= T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
 820 &:= T(-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 821 &:= (12+3) \times T(4+5) + 7 \times T(6) + 8-9 \\
 822 &:= (T(12) + 3 + 45) \times 6 + T(7 \times 8 - T(9)) \\
 823 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - T(T(4)) \times (T(5) - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 824 &:= T(T(1+2)) + T(T(3)) + (45 - 6 + 7) \times (8+9) \\
 825 &:= T(T(-1+2+3)) \times (T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 826 &:= T(T(-1+2+T(3))) - T(4+5) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
 827 &:= -1 - 2 \times (T(3) + T(4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 828 &:= T(-1+2+T(T(3))) - T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
 829 &:= 1 - (2 \times (3 - T(4)) - T(T(5))) \times 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 830 &:= T(-1+2 \times T(T(3))) + 4-5-6-7-8-9 \\
 831 &:= 1 + T(2 \times 3 \times 4) + 5 + T(6) + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\
 832 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times 5 \times (6+7+8+9) \\
 833 &:= 1 + 23 + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) + 6 \times 7 - 8 - T(9) \\
 834 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + T(4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 835 &:= 12 \times (3 \times 4 + 5 \times 6) + 7 + T(8) \times 9 \\
 836 &:= T(-1 + T(2 \times 3)) - 4 + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
 837 &:= -1 - 2 + T(3) \times 4 \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
 838 &:= (1^2 - 3 + 45) \times T(6) - 7 \times 8 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 799 &:= 98 - 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4 \times T(3) - 2 \times 1) \\
 800 &:= T(9) \times 8 + 765 - 4 - 321 \\
 801 &:= T(9) + 8 + 765 - T(4) - 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 802 &:= T(9) + 8 + 765 - T(4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 803 &:= (-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - 6 - T(5) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 804 &:= T(9) + 876 - 54 - 3 \times 21 \\
 805 &:= 9 + T(8) + 765 - 4 - 3/(2+1) \\
 806 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + T(7) + T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1) \\
 807 &:= 9 + T(8) + 765 - 4 + 3/(2+1) \\
 808 &:= -9 + (T(T(8)) + T(7+6) + 5 + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 809 &:= T(-9 + 8 + T(7+6))/5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 810 &:= -9 \times (8+7 - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
 811 &:= 9 - T(8) + T(7) - 6 \times 5 \times (4-32+1) \\
 812 &:= (-9 + T(8)) \times T(7) + T(6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 813 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 + T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
 814 &:= 987 - T(6) - 5 - (4+3) \times 21 \\
 815 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 \times (-6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 816 &:= -9 - (T(8) - T(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1) \\
 817 &:= T(9) - 8 + 765 + T(4) + 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 818 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + T(7+6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 819 &:= 9 \times T(T(8-7+6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 820 &:= T(-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 821 &:= 9 \times 8 - 76 + 5 + T(43 - 2 - 1) \\
 822 &:= (-9 + T(8)) \times T(7) + 6 + 5 + T(4+3+2+1) \\
 823 &:= 9 \times (8 + 76 + 5) - T(4) + 32 \times 1 \\
 824 &:= 9 \times (8 + 76 + 5) - T(4) + 32 + 1 \\
 825 &:= (9 + T(8) + 7 - 6 + 5 + 4) \times T(3 \times 2 - 1) \\
 826 &:= T(T(9) - 8) + 7 + (65 - 4 - 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
 827 &:= 9 + T(8) + 765 - T(4) + T(3) + 21 \\
 828 &:= -9 \times (T(8 - 7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 829 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + (T(6) + 54/3) \times 21 \\
 830 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 831 &:= -9 + T(8+7) + 6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
 832 &:= 9 + T(T(8) + 7 - 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
 833 &:= 5 \times (98 + 76) - T(4) - T(3) - 21 \\
 834 &:= 9 + 8 + 765 + T(T(4)) - 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
 835 &:= T(-9 + T(8) + 7 + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 836 &:= T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 837 &:= 987 + 6 - T(5 + 4 + 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
 838 &:= T(9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times 5) + T(4) + T(32 \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}839 &:= (12/T(3))^{4+5} + T(T(6)) + 7 + 89 & 839 &:= (9-8) \times (7 + T(T(6))) + 5^4 - 3 - 21 \\840 &:= (1^{23} + 4) \times 56 \times (7 - T(8)/9) & 840 &:= -9 + (T(T(8)) + T(7) \times 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\841 &:= 1 \times 234 + 5 - T(6) + 7 \times 89 & 841 &:= (T(9) + 8 \times 7 - 65 - 4 - 3)^2 \times 1 \\842 &:= -1 + T(T(2 + T(3))) - 4 - 5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 842 &:= T(9) - (8 - 7)^6 - (5 - 43) \times 21 \\843 &:= -1 + 2^{T(3)} + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 843 &:= 9 \times 87 + 6 + (5 + T(4) + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\844 &:= T(12) + 3 \times 45 \times 6 - 7 + 8 - T(9) & 844 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\845 &:= T(12) + 34 - 56 + 789 & 845 &:= 9 + 87 + T(6) + (5 + 4)^3 - 2 + 1 \\846 &:= (1 + 2) \times (T(3) + 4 \times 5) - T(6) + 789 & 846 &:= 9 \times 8 + T(T(7)) - 65 + 432 + 1 \\847 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 847 &:= (9 - 8) \times T(7) - 8 - T(T(5)) + T(43) + 1 \\848 &:= T(12)/T(3) - T(4) + 56 + 789 & 848 &:= T(-9 - 8 - 7 + T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\849 &:= 1 + 234 + 5 + T(6) \times (T(7) - 8 + 9) & 849 &:= (-9 + T(8)) \times 7 + T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\850 &:= 12 + 3 - T(4) + 56 + 789 & 850 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7)) + 6 + 5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\851 &:= T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 851 &:= 9 - 8 + 76 + 543 + T(21) \\852 &:= 1 + T(2 + 3) + (4 - T(5)) \times (6 + 7 - 89) & 852 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + (7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\853 &:= T(1 + 2) - 29 + T(6 \times 7) - T(8) + 9 & 853 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 + T(4) - T(3) - 21 \\854 &:= T(T(1 - 2 + T(3))) - T(4) + T(5) \times (6 + 7 + T(8)) + 9 & 854 &:= 9 + 876 + T(5) - 43 - 2 - 1 \\855 &:= T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 855 &:= T(9) - 87 + T(6 \times 5) + 432 \times 1 \\856 &:= 1^2 \times T(3) + T(4) \times (5 + 6 - 7 + T(8) + T(9)) & 856 &:= 9 - 8 \times T(T(7)) + T(6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\857 &:= 12 \times 34 + T(5 \times 6) - 7 + T(8) - T(9) & 857 &:= -9 \times (8 - T(7 + 6)) + T(T(5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\858 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 858 &:= -9 - T(8) + T(7 \times (T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\859 &:= -1 + (T(2 + 3) \times T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 859 &:= 98 - 7 - 6 + 543 + T(21) \\860 &:= (1 - 2)^3 + T(T(4) - 56 + 78 + 9) & 860 &:= 9 + T(8) + (7 + 5 \times T(6)) + T(4 + 32 + 1) \\861 &:= T(1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(4) + 5 + 6 - 7 + T(8) - 9) & 861 &:= 9 - 87 + T(6) + T(5) + 43 \times 21 \\862 &:= T(12) - (3 - 4)^5 - 6 + 789 & 862 &:= 9 \times 8 + T(T(7) + 6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\863 &:= 1 - 2 - 3^4 + T(5) \times (6 - 7 + 8) \times 9 & 863 &:= -9 \times 8 + (T(7) - 6 - 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\864 &:= (1^2 + 3 + T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7) \times (T(8) - 9) & 864 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) \times (T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\865 &:= (1 - (2 - 3) \times 4) \times (56 + T(7) + 89) & 865 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\866 &:= T(T(1 + 2 + 3)) - T(4) \times (5 + 6 - 7) + T(T(8)) + 9 & 866 &:= (9 + 8) \times (T(7) + T(6 + 5) - 43) - 2 + 1 \\867 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(3 + 4)) - 5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 867 &:= (9 + 8) \times (T(7) + T(6 + 5) - 43) \times (2 - 1) \\868 &:= -1 - 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 868 &:= (9 + 8) \times (T(7) + T(6 + 5) - 43) + 2 - 1 \\869 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 869 &:= -9 + 8 \times T(7 + 6) + T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\870 &:= 12 + 3 + T(4) + 56 + 789 & 870 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - T(6 + 5) + 432 \times 1 \\871 &:= T(12) \times 3 \times 4 - 56 + (T(7) + 8 - T(9)) & 871 &:= 98 - 7 + 6 + 543 + T(21) \\872 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 872 &:= T(9) - T(8) - 7 \times 6 + 5 - 4 \times (T(3) - T(21)) \\873 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 456) - T(7) - 8 - 9 & 873 &:= -9 \times (T(8) - 7 - 6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\874 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 34) + T(T(5)) + 6 - 7 + 89 & 874 &:= 987 - 65 - 4 - T(3^2) + 1 \\875 &:= 1 - 2 - 3 + T(4 \times 5) + 678 - 9 & 875 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times T(5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\876 &:= (1^2 - 3 + 45) \times T(6) - T(7) - 8 + 9 & 876 &:= T(T(9) - 8) + 76 + 5^4 - T(32 \times 1) \\877 &:= 12 \times 3^4 - 5 - T(6) - 78 + 9 & 877 &:= 9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
878 &:= T(-1+2+T(3)) + T(T(T(4)) - T(5)) + 6+7+8+9 \\
879 &:= T(1+2) \times (3+T(4) - T(5)) + (T(6)+78) \times 9 \\
880 &:= (T(1 \times 2^3) + 4) \times (T(5-6+7) - 8+9) \\
881 &:= T((1-2) \times 3 + 45) + 67 - 89 \\
882 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(3) + T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
883 &:= 1^2 + 3 + T(4 \times 5) + 678 - 9 \\
884 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 + T(4 \times 5) + 678 - 9 \\
885 &:= 1 \times 2 + 4 \times T(3) + 5 + T(T(6)) + 7 \times 89 \\
886 &:= (-1+2+3)^4 + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
887 &:= 12 + T(34)/5 + (6+78) \times 9 \\
888 &:= (12+34 - T(5)+6) \times (7+8+9) \\
889 &:= T(1+2) + T(34) + (5+67) \times T(8)/9 \\
890 &:= -1+2+4 \times T(T(T(3))) - 5-6-7-8-9 \\
891 &:= T(T(-1+2+3+4) + 5) + 6+7+8+9 \\
892 &:= 5 \times (123+4) + 6 \times T(7) + 89 \\
893 &:= T(12) - 34 + 78 \times (5+6) - 9 \\
894 &:= 1 - 2 \times T(3) + 4 + T(5) + T(6 \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\
895 &:= 12 \times (3+4+5+67) - 8 - T(9) \\
896 &:= -1 + (2 + T(T(3))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
897 &:= T(1+2) \times T(3) \times 4 - T(5) - T(6) + 789 \\
898 &:= T(T(1 \times 2 \times 3)) - 4 - 5 - 6 + 7 + T(T(8)) + 9 \\
899 &:= T(1+2) - 3 - T(4) + T(5) + (T(6)+78) \times 9 \\
900 &:= 1^{23} \times T(T(4)) + 56 + 789 \\
901 &:= 1^2 \times (34+5) \times T(6) - 7 + 89 \\
902 &:= 1 + (2-3+4-5) \times (T(T(6)) + 7 - T(T(8))) + T(9) \\
903 &:= 1 \times 2 \times T(3) \times T(4) / T(T(5)) + T(6 \times 7) + 8 - 9 \\
904 &:= 1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) - 4 + 5 + 678 - 9 \\
905 &:= (1 \times 2 - 3) \times (4 \times (5 - T(T(6))) - 7) + T(8) - 9 \\
906 &:= T(-1+2 \times 3 \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
907 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3+456) - T(7) + 8+9 \\
908 &:= -1+2-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
909 &:= 12 - 3 + 45 \times (6+7+8) - T(9) \\
910 &:= 12 + (34 + (T(5) - 6) \times (7+89)) \\
911 &:= 123 + T(T(4)) \times 5 + 6 \times 78 + T(9) \\
912 &:= 1 \times 2^{T(3)} + 4 + T(T(5)) + 67 + T(T(8)) - 9 \\
913 &:= 1 \times 23 + T(4) \times (T(5+6-7) \times 8+9) \\
914 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
915 &:= (1-2) \times 3 + T(4)/5 \times (6 \times 78 - 9) \\
916 &:= T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
917 &:= 12 \times 3 + T(4) - T(5) + T(6 \times 7) - 8 - 9
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
878 &:= T(98 - 5 \times (7+6)) - 4 + 321 \\
879 &:= T(9) + (8+76 - 5 + T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(2+1) \\
880 &:= 9 + 876 + T(5) + 4 - 3 - 21 \\
881 &:= T(T(9-8+7) + 6) + 5 - 4 - T(T(3)) - 2 \times 1 \\
882 &:= -9 \times (8 - T(7+6)) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
883 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
884 &:= (-9-8) \times (7+6 - T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
885 &:= -9 - T(T(8)) + (7+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
886 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7 \times (T(6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1)) \\
887 &:= (98+76) \times 5 - T(4) + T(3) + 21 \\
888 &:= (T(9) - T(8)) \times 7 + (65 - T(4)) \times T(3+2 \times 1) \\
889 &:= 9 \times (8+76 - T(5) + 4) + T(T(T(3))) + 2 - 1 \\
890 &:= 9 + 876 - T(5) - 4 + 3 + 21 \\
891 &:= 9 + (8+7 + T(6) - T(5)) \times (T(4) + 32 \times 1) \\
892 &:= (-9 \times T(8) + T(T(7))) \times (6+5) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
893 &:= T(-9-8-7 + T(6+5)) - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
894 &:= -9 + (T(8) + 7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
895 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + 7 + T(6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
896 &:= 9 + 876 - 5 + T(4) \times 3/2 + 1 \\
897 &:= 9 \times 87 + 6 \times (5 + T(4) + 3) + T(2+1) \\
898 &:= (9+87) \times 6 + 54 \times T(3) - 2 \times 1 \\
899 &:= T(9) + T(T(8)) - 7 \times 6 - 5 + T(4) - T(3) + T(21) \\
900 &:= 9 \times (-T(8+7)/6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
901 &:= -9 - 8 + T(7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
902 &:= (9+87) \times 6 + 54 \times T(3) + 2 \times 1 \\
903 &:= T(T(-9+8+7) + 6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
904 &:= 98/7 \times T(6+5) + 4 - 3 - 21 \\
905 &:= 9 + 8 + T(7 \times 6) - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
906 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times T(5) \times (4+3+2+1) \\
907 &:= (98+76) \times 5 + T(4) + T(3) + 21 \\
908 &:= T(T(-9+8+7) + T(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
909 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - T(7) \times (6-5-4-3-2-1) \\
910 &:= (98-7) \times T(6+5-4 - T(3) + 2+1) \\
911 &:= 9 + T(T(8) + 7) + 6 + 5 - T(4+3+2+1) \\
912 &:= 98 + 765 + 43 + T(2+1) \\
913 &:= T(9+8) + 765 - T(4)/(3-2+1) \\
914 &:= (9+8 \times T(7) + 6 - T(5)) \times 4 - 3 + 21 \\
915 &:= T(9) + 876 + 5 + 4 - T(3 \times 2 - 1) \\
916 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + T(7) + T(6+5+4+3+2+1) \\
917 &:= -9 + 8 + T(7 \times 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 918 &:= T(T(12) - 34) - 5 + 67 \times (8 - 9) \\ 919 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 34) + (T(5) - 6) \times T(7) - 8 + 9 \\ 920 &:= (1 - 23 + 45) \times (67 - T(8) + 9) \\ 921 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (T(3) + 4 + 5 + 6 \times 78) - T(9) \\ 922 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 923 &:= 1 \times 2 \times T(3) - 4 - 5 + T(6 \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 924 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 34 + 5) - 6 + 78 - 9 \\ 925 &:= T((1 - 2) \times 3 + 45) - 67 + 89 \\ 926 &:= T(T(12)/T(3)) - T(4) + 56 + 789 \\ 927 &:= T(1 \times 2 \times T(3) + 4 + 5) - 6 + 78 \times 9 \\ 928 &:= 1 - 2 \times T(3) + (4 - 5 + T(6 \times 7) - 8 + T(9)) \\ 929 &:= 1 + T(2 \times T(3)) - T(T(4)) - (T(5) - T(6 \times 7) - 8) + 9 \\ 930 &:= (1^2 - 3 + 45) \times T(6) + T(7) + 8 - 9 \\ 931 &:= (1^2 - 3 + 45) \times T(6) - T(7) \times (8 - 9) \\ 932 &:= (1 \times 23 + 4) \times T(5) + 67 \times 8 - 9 \\ 933 &:= T(1 + 2) \times 3 \times T(T(4)) - 6 \times T(5) + 78 - T(9) \\ 934 &:= T(1 \times 23 + 4 - 5) - T(6) + 78 \times 9 \\ 935 &:= 1^{23} \times (4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + T(T(8)) + 9) \\ 936 &:= 1^{23} + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) + T(T(8)) + 9 \\ 937 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 - 45 + T(6 \times 7) + T(T(8))/9 \\ 938 &:= T(-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 939 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 3) + 45 - T(6) + (T(7) - 8) \times T(9) \\ 940 &:= 12 - T(3) - 4 + T(5) \times T(6) + 7 \times 89 \\ 941 &:= (1 - 2 \times 3 + 45) \times T(6) + 7 \times 8 + T(9) \\ 942 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 34 + 5) - 6 + 78 + 9 \\ 943 &:= 1^2 - 3 - (4 + 5 + 6 - T(7 + 8)) \times 9 \\ 944 &:= 12 + 3 + (T(4) \times (56 + (T(7) + 8)) + 9) \\ 945 &:= -1 + T(T(T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)) - 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 946 &:= 12 \times T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) + 5 + (T(T(6)) + 7) - 89 \\ 947 &:= (1 - T(2^3)) \times (4 - 5 - 6) + 78 \times 9 \\ 948 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 + 4 \times T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 949 &:= 1 + 2 + (T(34) + 5) - T(6) + 7 + 8 \times T(9) \\ 950 &:= (1^2 - 3 + 45) \times T(6) + 7 \times 8 - 9 \\ 951 &:= 123 + 4 + 5 \times T(6) \times 7 + 89 \\ 952 &:= 1^{234} - T(5) - T(6) \times (7 - 8 - T(9)) \\ 953 &:= T(12 + 3 - 4) - (5 - T(6)) \times 7 \times 8 - 9 \\ 954 &:= T(1 \times 2 + 34 + 5) + 6 + 78 + 9 \\ 955 &:= 1 \times 2 + (T(3^4 - 5 \times 6 - 7) + 8 - T(9)) \\ 956 &:= (1 \times 2 \times 3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(T(6)) - 7 + T(T(8)) - 9 \\ 957 &:= 1 + 2 + T(3) \times (4 + 5 - 6 \times T(7)) \times (8 - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 918 &:= 987 - 65 - 4 + T(T(3)) - 21 \\ 919 &:= -9 + 8 \times (T(7 + 6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 920 &:= 9 + 876 + T(5) - 4 + 3 + 21 \\ 921 &:= 9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(7) - 6) - 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 922 &:= (9 - 87)/6 - 5 + T(43) - T(2 + 1) \\ 923 &:= -9 - 8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 924 &:= (9 \times 8 - T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 925 &:= (9 - 87)/6 - 5 + T(43) - 2 - 1 \\ 926 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + T(T(6) - T(5)) \times (43 - 2 \times 1) \\ 927 &:= 9 + T(T(8)) - T(7) \times (6 - 5 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 928 &:= (T(9 + 8) + T(7) - 65) \times (4 + 3 + 2 - 1) \\ 929 &:= T(9) \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4 \times 3 + T(21) \\ 930 &:= T(9) + 876 - 54 + 3 \times 21 \\ 931 &:= (9 - 87)/6 - 5 + T(43) + 2 + 1 \\ 932 &:= 9 \times 8 + (T(7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 933 &:= (-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + 6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 934 &:= (9 - 87)/6 - 5 + T(43) + T(2 + 1) \\ 935 &:= T(9) + 876 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 - 1 \\ 936 &:= 987 + 6 - T(5) - 43 + 2 - 1 \\ 937 &:= -9 + T(T(8) + T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 938 &:= (9 - T(8) + T(7))^6 - T(5) + T(43) + T(2 + 1) \\ 939 &:= T(9) - 8 + T(7 \times 6) + T(5) - T(4) \times 3/2 - 1 \\ 940 &:= T(-9 + T(8) + 7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 941 &:= -9 + (T(8) - 7 + T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 942 &:= -9 - T(8) + 7 \times (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 943 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 944 &:= (T(9) + 8 \times 7) \times (6 + 5 - 4) + T(3) + T(21) \\ 945 &:= 9 \times T(8) + 76 + 543 + 2 \times 1 \\ 946 &:= 98/7 \times T(6 + 5) + 4 - 3 + 21 \\ 947 &:= T(9) - 8 + 7 - (6 + T(5) - 4^3) \times 21 \\ 948 &:= -9 + T(T(8) + 7) + T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 949 &:= 9 + T(T(8) + 7) - T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 950 &:= (-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 951 &:= T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + 6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 952 &:= 9 + 8 + (T(7) - 6 - 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 953 &:= T(9) - 8 + 76 + (5 + 4 \times T(3))^2 - 1 \\ 954 &:= 9 \times T(8) + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 955 &:= 987 + 6 + 5 - 4^3 + T(T(2 + 1)) \\ 956 &:= T(T(-9 + T(8))/7 - (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 957 &:= 9 + (87 + T(6) + 5) \times 4 + T(32 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 997 &:= 1^{23} + T(T(4)) + 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9) & 997 &:= 9 \times T(8) + 7 + T(T(6) + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 998 &:= (12 + 3) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6)) + 7 - 8 + 9 & 998 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6 - T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 999 &:= 12 - 3 + 45 \times (6 + 7 + 8) + T(9) & 999 &:= 9 \times (T(8) + 7 + 65 - 4) + 3 \times 21 \\
 1000 &:= 1 + (2 - 34 - 5) \times (6 - 78 + T(9)) & 1000 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 7 + 6) \times 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 \\ \\
 1001 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1001 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 - (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1002 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1002 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1003 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + T(T(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1003 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1004 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1004 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 1005 &:= (T(-1 + 2 \times 3) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1005 &:= ((-9 + (T(8 \times 7)/T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1006 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1006 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1007 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(T(3)) + 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1007 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) \times (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1008 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1008 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1009 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1009 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T((7 + 6 - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1010 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1010 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)/T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1011 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1011 &:= ((-9 + T(T(((8 + 7) - 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1012 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1012 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1013 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1013 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(T(7) - 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1014 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1014 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1015 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1015 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1016 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1016 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1017 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1017 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1018 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1018 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1019 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1019 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1020 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1020 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1021 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1021 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1022 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T((T(3) + 4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1022 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1023 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1023 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1024 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1024 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)))^{4+3+2+1}) \\
 1025 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 + (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1025 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7 + 6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1026 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1026 &:= (-9 + T(T((T(8 + 7) - (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1027 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1027 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T((T(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1028 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1028 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - ((7 + T(T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1029 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1029 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1030 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1030 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7) - 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1031 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1031 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1032 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1032 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1033 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1033 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((T(7) + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1034 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times 3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1034 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T((7 + 6 - 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1035 &:= T((T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1035 &:= T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1036 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1037 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1038 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1039 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1040 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1041 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1042 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1043 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1044 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1045 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1046 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1047 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1048 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1049 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1050 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1051 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1052 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1053 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1054 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1055 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3)))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1056 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1057 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1058 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)+4}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1059 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1060 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1061 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1062 &:= ((T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))))/5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1063 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1064 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1065 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1066 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - ((4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1067 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1068 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1069 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 + (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1070 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1071 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1072 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1073 &:= (-1 - (T((2 + T(T(3)))) - (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1074 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1075 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1036 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/(T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1037 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1038 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1039 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7 + 6) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1040 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1041 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1042 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1043 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) - (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1044 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1045 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7 + 6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1046 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/(T(6) - T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
1047 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1048 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1049 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1050 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1051 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1052 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1053 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7 \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1054 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1055 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1056 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1057 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) - T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1058 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1059 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1060 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1061 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 \times T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1062 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) + (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1063 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1064 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1065 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1066 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1067 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1068 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1069 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1070 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1071 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1072 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1073 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1074 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1075 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1076 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1076 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1077 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3 + T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1077 &:= ((-9 \times (T((8 + T(7))) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1078 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((3 + T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1078 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1079 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((3 + T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1079 &:= (-9 + (8 \times T((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1080 &:= (-1 + T((T(2 + 3) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1080 &:= ((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1081 &:= T((-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1081 &:= T((-9 + T((8 - ((7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1082 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((3 + T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1082 &:= (-9 + (T((8 - (T(7) - T(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1083 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1083 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1084 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 \times 3) + T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1084 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1085 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 1085 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8) - 7) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1086 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1086 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1087 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1087 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1088 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1088 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1089 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{T(3)})) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1089 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1090 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1090 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7 + 6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1091 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1091 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1092 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1092 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1093 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((3 \times T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1093 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7) + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1094 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T(3 + 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1094 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 + 6))) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1095 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1095 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7) + 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1096 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1096 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (7 + 6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1097 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1097 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1098 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1098 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1099 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1099 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(T(7))) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1100 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1100 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1101 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1101 &:= (-9 + ((T((8 + (7 + 6))) - T(T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1102 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1102 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1103 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T((3 \times 4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1103 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1104 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T((3 \times 4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1104 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1105 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - T((4 - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1105 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1106 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1106 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1107 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1107 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1108 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 1108 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + 6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1109 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + 3)) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1109 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1110 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1110 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1111 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1111 &:= (-9 - ((8 - T(7)) \times (T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1112 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1112 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1113 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 1113 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) - (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1114 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3 + 4) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1114 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 + 6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1115 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 1115 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times (7 - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1116 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+T(3)) \times (4-(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1117 &:= ((-1-2+(T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1118 &:= ((-1 \times 2+(T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1119 &:= (-1+((2+T(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1120 &:= ((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1121 &:= ((-1+2+(T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1122 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T((T(3+4)-T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1123 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(T(3))+T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1124 &:= (-1 \times 2+(T((T(T(3))+T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1125 &:= (-1-2+T(((3 \times 4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1126 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1127 &:= (-1+T((2+(T(3)+(4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1128 &:= T(((T((-1+T(2+3))) + T(T(T(4))))/(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1129 &:= (-1+2+T(((3 \times 4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1130 &:= (-1+(T(T((2-(3-(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1131 &:= (T((-1+2+3) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1132 &:= (-1 \times 2-(T(T(3+4)) - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1133 &:= (-1-(2 \times (3-(T(T(4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1134 &:= ((T((-1+(2^{T(3)}))) / 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1135 &:= (((-1+T(2 \times 3)) \times T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
1136 &:= (T(T((-1+(2+(3+4)))) + (5+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1137 &:= (-1-(2 \times (T(3)+(T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1138 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1139 &:= (-1 \times 2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1140 &:= (T((-1+2+3)+T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1141 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1142 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1143 &:= (-1-(2 \times ((3+T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1144 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3+T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1145 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((3+T(T(4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1146 &:= (-1+((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1147 &:= ((-1-T(2+T(3))) \times (4-(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1148 &:= ((-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5)) / (6+7+8+9))) \\
1149 &:= (-1-(2 \times (T((T(3)+4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1150 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1151 &:= (-1+(2 \times (T(3)+(T(T(4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1152 &:= ((-1+2+(T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) / (6+7+8+9))) \\
1153 &:= (T((-1+(2^{3+4}))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1154 &:= (-1+(T(T(2+3)) + T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1155 &:= ((T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) / 4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1116 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1117 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) - (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1118 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1119 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1120 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7)) + T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1121 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1122 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) - (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1123 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) + (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1124 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8) + T(7))) - T(T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
1125 &:= (-9 \times ((8-7-6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1126 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1127 &:= (-9+(8 \times (T(7) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1128 &:= T((-9+(8 \times (T(7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1129 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1130 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7)) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1131 &:= (-9+((T(8 \times 7) / T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1132 &:= (-9+(T(8) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1133 &:= (((-9+(T(8) \times 7)) \times (6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1134 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) / 7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1135 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1136 &:= (T((-9+T(T((8+7) - (6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
1137 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1138 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((T(7) + T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1139 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7 \times (6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1140 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1141 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
1142 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8)+7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1143 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1144 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1145 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1146 &:= (-9+(T(T((8+7)-6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1147 &:= (((-9+8)-7) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1148 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (7 \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1149 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1150 &:= ((-9+T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1151 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (((7+6) \times 5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1152 &:= (-9 \times (8 - T((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1153 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1154 &:= (-9+8+(T((7 - (6 - 5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1155 &:= ((-9+(T(8)+T(7))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

- 1156** := $(-1 \times 2 \times ((3+4) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))$
1157 := $(-1 + (T((2 + (3 \times T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1158 := $(T((-1+2+(T(T(3)) + T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1159 := $((-1 + ((2+3) \times T((T(4) + T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))$
1160 := $((T((-1-2+T(3+4))) \times 5) - T(6+7+8+9))$
1161 := $(T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))))$
1162 := $(-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))))$
1163 := $(T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1164 := $((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) \times T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
1165 := $((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) \times T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
1166 := $(-1 + ((T(2 \times T(3)) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
1167 := $((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))))$
1168 := $(T((T((-1+2+T(3))) + 4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))$
1169 := $((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1170 := $(((-1-2-3) + T(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))$
1171 := $(-1+2 - ((T(3) - T(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
1172 := $(-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))))$
1173 := $(-1-2 + T((3 + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))))$
1174 := $(-1 \times 2 + T((3 + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))))$
1175 := $(((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
1176 := $T((-1 + ((2 \times (3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$
1177 := $(-1+2 + T((3 + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))))$
1178 := $(-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$
1179 := $(-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))))$
1180 := $((T(-1+2+3) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1181 := $(-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9))))$
1182 := $((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9))))$
1183 := $(-1 + (2 \times ((3+4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))$
1184 := $((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1185 := $((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))))$
1186 := $(T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9))$
1187 := $((-1-2) - ((T(T(3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1188 := $(-1 \times 2 - ((T(T(3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1189 := $(-1 + (2 \times T((3 - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))))$
1190 := $(T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1191 := $(-1+2 - ((T(T(3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1192 := $(-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + ((T(4) \times T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))))$
1193 := $((-1+2-3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))))$
1194 := $((-1-2-3) + ((T(T(4)) - T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
1195 := $(T(((-1+2+3) + T(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9))$
- 1156** := $((T((-9 + T(8+7)))/6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))$
1157 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
1158 := $(((-9 - (T(8) \times T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1159 := $(-9 - 8 + T(((T(7) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1160 := $((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7+6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1))$
1161 := $((-9 - T(8+7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))$
1162 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))$
1163 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))))$
1164 := $(T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))$
1165 := $(-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1166 := $(((-9 + T(8+7)) \times (6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))$
1167 := $(-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))))$
1168 := $(-9 + (T((T(8)+7)) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1))))$
1169 := $((-9 \times (T((T(8) + T(7))) - T(T(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$
1170 := $(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))$
1171 := $((-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))$
1172 := $(T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))$
1173 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1174 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))$
1175 := $((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(7+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1176 := $T((-9+8+(T(7)+(6+5+4+3+2+1))))$
1177 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))$
1178 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
1179 := $(-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1180 := $(-9 - (T(8) - T((T(7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))))$
1181 := $(-9 + (((8 \times (7+6)) + T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$
1182 := $(-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))$
1183 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7+T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1184 := $(T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))$
1185 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))))$
1186 := $((-9 + (T(T(8+7)))/6) - (5+4+3+2+1))$
1187 := $(-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) \times (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))))$
1188 := $(-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (7 \times (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))$
1189 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))$
1190 := $((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))))$
1191 := $(T((-9+8+(T(7)+T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1))$
1192 := $(T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))))$
1193 := $((-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1))$
1194 := $(-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1195 := $(-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
1196 &:= (-1+2)^{T(T(T(3)))} + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9) & 1196 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) - T(6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1197 &:= ((-1-2+T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1197 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + 7)) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1198 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1198 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7+6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1199 &:= ((-1+T((2+3+T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1199 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1200 &:= (T((T(((-1+2) \times 3)) \times T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1200 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + T(6)))) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1201 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1201 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1202 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times T(T(T(4))))/5) - (6+7+8+9) & 1202 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1203 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3+4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1203 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1204 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3+4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1204 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1205 &:= (T((-1+T(2+T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1205 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7+6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1206 &:= (T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) + T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 1206 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1207 &:= (-1+2+(T((3+T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) & 1207 &:= ((-9-8) \times (T(7) + (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1208 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 1208 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1209 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (4+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1209 &:= ((-9+8+T((T(7) + T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1210 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) + (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1210 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) - 6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1211 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 1211 &:= (((-9+T(8+7)) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1212 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((T(3) \times 4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1212 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1213 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 1213 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7)) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1214 &:= (((-1+(2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1214 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times 7) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1215 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times 3))) + (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) & 1215 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1216 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 1216 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8+7))/6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1217 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times 4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1217 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1218 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1218 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1219 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1219 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1220 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1220 &:= ((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
1221 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1221 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1222 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1222 &:= (-9 + (T(((T(8+7) \times 6)/T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1223 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1223 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1224 &:= (-1 + T(((2 \times (3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 1224 &:= (-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1225 &:= T((T(-1+2+3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 1225 &:= T(((-9 \times 8 + (7 - 6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1226 &:= (-1+2+T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1226 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) - (T(7) - T(6+5)))))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1227 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1227 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1228 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) + (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1228 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1229 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3) \times 4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1229 &:= (((T((-9 + T(8+7))) - T(6))/5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
1230 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1230 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1231 &:= (-1+2+(T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 1231 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7+6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1232 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1232 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1233 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3+T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1233 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1234 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 1234 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1235 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times 4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1235 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + T(6+5)))))) + 4+3+2+1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1236 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1237 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1238 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1239 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 + 3) \times T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1240 &:= (T((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 1241 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1242 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) + (T(4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1243 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1244 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + 3 + T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1245 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1246 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1247 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((4 + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1248 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T((T(4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 1249 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + T((T(4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1250 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + T(3)))) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1251 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\ 1252 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1253 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T((4 + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1254 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1255 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3)^4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1256 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1257 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 - 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1258 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 1259 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - 4)) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1260 &:= (T((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1261 &:= (T((T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1262 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 1263 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1264 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1265 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1266 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1267 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1268 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1269 &:= (-1 + (((2^{T(3)}) \times T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 1270 &:= ((T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 1271 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1272 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1273 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1274 &:= (-1 + T((2 + 3 + (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 1275 &:= T((-1 + (2 \times T(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1236 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1237 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1238 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - ((7 + T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1239 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1240 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) - 6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 1241 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 - (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 1242 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1243 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T((7 + 6 - 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1244 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 1245 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1246 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + 7)) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1247 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1248 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (T(7) - T(6))))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 1249 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1250 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) - (6 + 5))))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 1251 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1252 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 1253 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1254 &:= (T((T(-9 + T(8))/7)) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1255 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1256 &:= ((-9 + (T(8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 1257 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (7 - 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1258 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) + T(T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1259 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 1260 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7) - (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1261 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1262 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1263 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1264 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 1265 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1266 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) - (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 1267 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + ((7 - 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1268 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7)) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1269 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1270 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 + 6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 1271 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(6))))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 1272 &:= ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1273 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 1274 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 1275 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - 7 + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1316 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1317 &:= (T((-1+(2\times T(T(3))))) - ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1318 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 1319 &:= (-1+(2\times((3\times T(4))+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1320 &:= (T((-1+2\times T(3)))\times(T(T(4))-(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1321 &:= (-1+(2\times(T(T(3))+T(4)+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1322 &:= ((-1+T((2+(T(3)\times T(4))))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1323 &:= (T((-1+2+(T(3)+T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1324 &:= (-1\times 2+T((T(3)+(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1325 &:= (-1+T((2\times T(3)+(4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1326 &:= T(((T(-1+2+3)\times 4)+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1327 &:= (-1+2+T((T(3)+(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1328 &:= (-1-2+(T(3)^4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1329 &:= (-1\times 2+(T(3)^4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1330 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - T((T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1331 &:= ((T(((T(-1+2)\times 3)^4)+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1332 &:= (-1+2+(T(3)^4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1333 &:= ((-1-(2\times T(T(3))))\times(4-(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1334 &:= (-1-(T(2+3)-(T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1335 &:= (-1\times(T(2+3)-(T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1336 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3))-4)+T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1337 &:= (-1-((2\times T(3))-(T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1338 &:= ((-1\times 2\times T(3))+T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9)) \\
 1339 &:= (-1+(((2+3)\times(T(T(4))+T(T(5))))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1340 &:= (-1+(T((2+T(T(3))))+(T(T(4+5))+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1341 &:= ((-1-2)-(T(T(T(3))))-(T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1342 &:= (-1\times 2-(T(T(T(3))))-(T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1343 &:= (T((-1-2+T((T(3)+4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1344 &:= ((T((-1+T(T(2+3))))/T(4))+T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1345 &:= (-1+2-(T(T(T(3))))-(T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1346 &:= (-1+2+(((T(T(T(3))))-T(T(4)))\times 5)+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 1347 &:= (T(T((-1+2)\times 3))+T((T(T(4))-(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1348 &:= ((-1+2-3)+(T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1349 &:= (-1+(T(2+3)\times(T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1350 &:= (T(-1+2\times 3)\times(T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1351 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(T(3)))})+(T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1352 &:= ((-1+2+3)\times((T(T(T(4)))/5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1353 &:= (((-1+2)\times 3)+(T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1354 &:= ((-1+2+3)+(T(4+5)\times(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1355 &:= (-1+((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(4))+T(5+6+7+8+9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1316 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-(7-T((T(6)+(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1317 &:= (-9+T(((8+7)+(T(6)+(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1318 &:= (-9-((8\times T(7))-((6+5)+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1319 &:= (-9+8+((T(7)-6)\times(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1320 &:= (-9-(T(8)-(T(7+6)\times(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1321 &:= (-9+((T(T(8+7))/6)+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1322 &:= ((-9\times T(8))+(T(7+6)+(T(5)+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1323 &:= ((-9+T(8))\times(T(7)+(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1324 &:= (T(-9+T(8))+T((7+(T(6)+(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1325 &:= (-9+8+T(((7-(6+5))+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1326 &:= T(((T(-9+8+7)\times 6)+(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1327 &:= (-9-(T(T(8))-((7\times T(6+5))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1328 &:= (-9-8+(T((T(7)+T(6)))+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1329 &:= ((-9\times T(8))+T(((7\times 6)+(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1330 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(7+T((T(6)+(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1331 &:= ((T(-9+8+7)\times T(6+5))-T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 1332 &:= (-9\times(((T(8)-T(T(7)))\times 6)/(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1333 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+T(T((7+6-5))+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1334 &:= (((-9-8)\times(7+6))+T(5)+T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1335 &:= (-9+((T(8)+T(7))\times(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1336 &:= (-9+(T((T(8)+(7+6)))+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1337 &:= (-9-(T(T(8))-(T(T(7)))+(T(6+5)+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1338 &:= (((-9+(T(8)\times 7))\times 6)-T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 1339 &:= ((-9\times(8+7))-(T(6+5)-T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1340 &:= ((-9+(T(8)\times(T(7)+6+5)))-T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 1341 &:= (-9+((8+7)\times(6\times(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1342 &:= (-9-(T(8)+(T((T(7)-(6+5)))-T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1343 &:= (-9+(8\times(T(7)+(T(6)+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1344 &:= (-9+8+(T((T(7)+T(6)))+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1345 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+(T(7)-6))))+T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 1346 &:= (((-9\times(8+(7+6)))-5)+T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1347 &:= ((-9\times T(T(8)))+(T(7+6)+(T(T(T(5)))-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1348 &:= (-9-8+(T(7+6)\times(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1349 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-(T(7)-(6\times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1350 &:= ((-9+8+T(7+6))\times(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 1351 &:= ((-9+T((T(8)+T(7))))-(6\times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1352 &:= (-9-8-(T(7+6+5)-T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1353 &:= (-9+(T(8)+T(((7-(6+5))+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1354 &:= ((-9+8+(T(7+6)\times T(5)))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
 1355 &:= (((-9-8)\times 7)-(T(6+5)-T(T(4+3+2+1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1396 &:= (T((-1+2-3) + T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\1397 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\1398 &:= ((T((-1+T((2+3+T(4)))))/5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\1399 &:= (-1 - ((T(2+3) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\1400 &:= (T(-1+2+3) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\1401 &:= (T((-1+(2 \times (3 \times (4+5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\1402 &:= (-1+2 - ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\1403 &:= (-1+(T(2+T(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\1404 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3) - ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\1405 &:= (-1+(2 \times T((T(3) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))))) \\1406 &:= (T((-1+2-3) + T(T(4)))) + (5-(6+7+8+9)) \\1407 &:= (-1-2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\1408 &:= (T((-1+2+(T(3)+T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\1409 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 \times T(3)) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\1410 &:= (T((-1+T(2+T(3)))) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\1411 &:= (-1+(2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\1412 &:= (-1+(T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\1413 &:= (T((-1-2+T((T(3)+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\1414 &:= (-1+(((2+3) \times T((4+T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\1415 &:= (-1+(2 \times (T((3 \times 4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\1416 &:= (T((-1+2 \times T(3))) + (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\1417 &:= ((-1+(2^{T(T(3))-T(4)})) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\1418 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\1419 &:= (-1-2+(3 \times ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\1420 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\1421 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((3^4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\1422 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\1423 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\1424 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (T(T(3)) \times T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\1425 &:= ((T((-1+T(2 \times 3))) \times (4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\1426 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\1427 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\1428 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\1429 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(3+4) - (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\1430 &:= (-1+T((2+(T(3)+(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\1431 &:= T((-1+(T(2+3)+(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\1432 &:= (-1+2+T((T(3+4) - (5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\1433 &:= (T((-1-2+T((T(3)+4)))) + T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\1434 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times (3+4))) - T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))) \\1435 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1396 &:= ((-9+T(8)) - (T(7+6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1397 &:= ((T(T(T(-9+8+7) - 6))/5) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\1398 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 \times (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\1399 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7)))) - (T(6)+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\1400 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) + (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1401 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times T(T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\1402 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7))) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1403 &:= (-9-8+((T(7+6) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\1404 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6-5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\1405 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + (T(7) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\1406 &:= (-9+((8 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\1407 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7+6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1408 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7+6)) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1409 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1410 &:= (((-9+(8 \times T(7))) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\1411 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\1412 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7+6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\1413 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + ((7 \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\1414 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7)))) - (6+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\1415 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(7) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1416 &:= (T((-9+((8 \times 7) + 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\1417 &:= ((-9+T(T(8))) - (T((T(7)+6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1418 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 \times (6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1419 &:= (T((T(-9+T(8))/7)) - ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\1420 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+(7+T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\1421 &:= (-9+((8+7+6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\1422 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7)) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\1423 &:= ((((-9-T(8)) \times (7+6))/5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\1424 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\1425 &:= ((-9+(8 \times (7+6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\1426 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7)))) + (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\1427 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + (7 \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\1428 &:= ((-9-8) \times (T(7+6) - (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1429 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\1430 &:= (((-9-(8-7)) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\1431 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - ((7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\1432 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\1433 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7+6) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\1434 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\1435 &:= (((-9+(8 \times (7+6))) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1436 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1437 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1438 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + T(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1439 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) - (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1440 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1441 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3 + 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1442 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1443 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1444 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (T((T(T(4))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1445 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + T(3))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1446 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1447 &:= (((T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - T(T(4)))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1448 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1449 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 - 3) + T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1450 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1451 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1452 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1453 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1454 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) \times T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1455 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1456 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1457 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1458 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1459 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1460 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(3) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1461 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
1462 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1463 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1464 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + T(3)) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1465 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1466 &:= (T((-1 + 2 - 3) + T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1467 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1468 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1469 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1470 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1471 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1472 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1473 &:= ((-1 - T(2 + 3)) + ((4^5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1474 &:= ((-1 \times T(2 + 3)) + ((4^5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1475 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4)))/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1436 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
1437 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((T(7) + (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1438 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1439 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1440 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1441 &:= -9 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1442 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1443 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1444 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1445 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) + (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1446 &:= (T((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1447 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1448 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - T(6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1449 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1450 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1451 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1452 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 \times T(T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1453 &:= (-9 - (T((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1454 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7 + 6) - (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1455 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1456 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1457 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7 + 6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1458 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times 7)) \times (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1459 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T((7 + 6 - 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1460 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6 - 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1461 &:= ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1462 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1463 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1464 &:= (T((T(-9 + T(8))/7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1465 &:= (-9 - (T(((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1466 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + 7 + 6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1467 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (T(7) - T(6)))))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1468 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1469 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
1470 &:= (T((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1471 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1472 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1473 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1474 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1475 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

1476 := $((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1477 := $(((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1478 := $(-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1479 := $(-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1480 := $(-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1481 := $((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1482 := $((-1 - 2) \times (T((T(3) + T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1483 := $(-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1484 := $(-1 + T((T(2 + 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1485 := $T(((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1486 := $(-1 + 2 + T(((3 - 4) + T(T((T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
1487 := $(((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1488 := $((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1489 := $(-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1490 := $(-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1491 := $(((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1492 := $(-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1493 := $((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1494 := $((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1495 := $(T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1496 := $(T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (T(T(T(4))) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1497 := $(-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1498 := $(((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1499 := $(((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1500 := $(((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1501 := $(T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1502 := $((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1503 := $(((-1 + 2 - 3) + T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1504 := $(-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1505 := $(T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1506 := $(((-1 + 2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1507 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1508 := $(((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1509 := $(T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1510 := $(((-1 + 2 \times 3) + T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1511 := $(T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1512 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1513 := $(-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1514 := $((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1515 := $(T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$

1476 := $(-9 + ((8 + T(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1477 := $(-9 - (T(8) + ((7 + 6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1478 := $(-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1479 := $(T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1480 := $((-9 - 8 + (7 \times T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1481 := $((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1482 := $((-9 \times 8 + T(7 + 6)) \times T((T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1483 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1484 := $(T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7)) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1485 := $T((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1486 := $((-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1487 := $(((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1488 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1489 := $-9 - T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1490 := $((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (7 - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1491 := $(T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1492 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + 6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1493 := $((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7 + 6) - T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1494 := $(T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1495 := $(-9 - 8 + (7 \times (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1496 := $((-9 + 8 + (7 \times T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1497 := $((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1498 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1499 := $((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1500 := $(T((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1501 := $((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1502 := $((-9 + T(8)) - (((7 + 6) \times 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1503 := $(-9 \times (T(8) + (T(7) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1504 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1505 := $((-9 - (8 + 7 + 6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1506 := $(T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7)) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1507 := $(-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1508 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1509 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1510 := $(-9 - (T(((8 + (7 + 6)) - T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1511 := $(-9 + 8 + (7 \times (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1512 := $((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7))) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1513 := $(-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1514 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1515 := $(-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$

1516 := $(-1 + (2 \times T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1517 := $(-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1518 := $(-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1519 := $(-1 + (T(2 + 3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1520 := $(T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1521 := $(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1522 := $((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1523 := $(-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1524 := $(-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1525 := $(-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1526 := $(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1527 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1528 := $((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1529 := $(-1 + ((2 \times 3 + T(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1530 := $(((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1531 := $(-1 + (2 \times (T((T(3) + T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1532 := $(-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1533 := $(T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1534 := $((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) + T(T(T((T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
1535 := $(-1 + (T(2 + T(3)) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1536 := $(-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1537 := $(-1 - 2 + T(T(T((T(T(3) + 4 + 5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
1538 := $(-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1539 := $(-1 + T(T(T((2 + (3 + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1540 := $((-1 + T((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1541 := $(-1 + 2 + T(T(T((T(T(3) + 4 + 5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
1542 := $(((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1543 := $((T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) / 4) - (T(T(T(5))) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1544 := $(-1 + ((T(T(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1545 := $(-1 - (((2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1546 := $(((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1547 := $(-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1548 := $(-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1549 := $(-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))$
1550 := $(((-1 + T(T(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
1551 := $(-1 - 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1552 := $(-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1553 := $(-1 - (2 \times (3 - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
1554 := $(-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
1555 := $(-1 + 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$

1516 := $(((-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 \times 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1517 := $(((-9 \times 8) - 7) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1518 := $(T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1519 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1520 := $((-9 + 8 + T((T(7) - (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1521 := $(T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7)) + (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1522 := $(((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1523 := $(-9 - 8 + T((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1524 := $((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7))) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1525 := $((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1526 := $(-9 - (T((8 + T(7))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1527 := $((-9 - ((8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1528 := $((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
1529 := $(-9 - ((T(8) / (7 + 6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1530 := $((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1531 := $(-9 + T(T((8 - ((7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
1532 := $((-9 + T(T((8 - (7 - (6 + 5))))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1533 := $(-9 + ((T(8) / (7 + 6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1534 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1535 := $(((-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1536 := $((-9 + ((T(T(8)) - T(T(7))) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
1537 := $((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1538 := $(((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) / T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1539 := $(-9 + 8 + T((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
1540 := $T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
1541 := $((-9 - (8 - (7 + 6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1542 := $((-9 + ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1543 := $(-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1544 := $(((-9 + 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1545 := $(-9 \times 8 + (7 \times T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1546 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1547 := $(((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) - 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1548 := $(-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1549 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
1550 := $(T(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1551 := $(-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1552 := $(-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))$
1553 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) - (7 + (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1554 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + T(((T(7) \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
1555 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{1556} & := (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
\mathbf{1557} & := (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1558} & := (((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1559} & := (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1560} & := ((-1 + T((2 \times T(3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1561} & := (T(((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1562} & := (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1563} & := ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1564} & := (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + (T(4) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))))) \\
\mathbf{1565} & := (-1 + (2 \times (3 + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
\mathbf{1566} & := (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1567} & := (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1568} & := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1569} & := ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1570} & := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1571} & := (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
\mathbf{1572} & := (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1573} & := ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1574} & := (-1 + (T((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1575} & := (T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
\mathbf{1576} & := (((-1 + 2)^{T(T(3))}) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1577} & := (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) - (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1578} & := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1579} & := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1580} & := ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3) - 4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1581} & := (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1582} & := ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3) - T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1583} & := (-1 + (T(2 + T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
\mathbf{1584} & := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1585} & := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1586} & := (-1 + (2 \times T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1587} & := (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
\mathbf{1588} & := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1589} & := (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1590} & := (T(-1 + 2 \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\mathbf{1591} & := (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1592} & := (-1 - ((2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
\mathbf{1593} & := (-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3 + T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
\mathbf{1594} & := (-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3 + T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
\mathbf{1595} & := (-1 + T(T(T(T(2 - (3 - 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{1556} & := ((-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1557} & := (-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1558} & := (((-9 \times 8)/(7 - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1559} & := (-9 + 8 + ((7 + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1560} & := ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{1561} & := (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{1562} & := (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1563} & := ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1564} & := ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1565} & := (-9 - (T((T(8) + 7)) - (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1566} & := ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{1567} & := (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1568} & := (-9 + ((T(T(8)))/(7 + 6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1569} & := ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1570} & := ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1571} & := ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7 - (6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1572} & := (-9 - (T(8) - (7 \times T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1573} & := (((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))/T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1574} & := (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1575} & := (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1576} & := (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1577} & := ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) - (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1578} & := (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1579} & := ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1580} & := ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1581} & := (-9 \times 8 + T(((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1582} & := ((-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) - 6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{1583} & := (-9 - (8 \times (T(T(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1584} & := (T((T(-9 + T(8))/7) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1585} & := ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\mathbf{1586} & := (-9 + (T(T(((8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1587} & := (-9 + T((8 \times (T(7) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1588} & := (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1589} & := (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1590} & := ((-9 \times T((T(8) - 7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1591} & := (-9 - (T((8 + T(7))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1592} & := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) - (6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1593} & := (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
\mathbf{1594} & := ((-9 + 8) - ((T(7 + 6) - T(T(5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
\mathbf{1595} & := (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1596 &:= T((-1 \times (2 \times ((3+4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1597 &:= (-1+2+T((T(3+T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1598 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - T(T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1599 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1600 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{T(3)}) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1601 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1602 &:= (-1+2+(T(3)+(T(T(4))+T(T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1603 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3)))+(T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1604 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times (3+4))) \times T(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
1605 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)))+(T(T(4+5))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1606 &:= (T((-1+(T(T(2+3))/T(4))))+T(T(T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1607 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1608 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1609 &:= (-1 + ((T(2+T(3)) + T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1610 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)))+(T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1611 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1612 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1613 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) \times (4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1614 &:= ((T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) \times (4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1615 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3))+4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1616 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1617 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3+T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1618 &:= (T((-1-2+(T(3) \times T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1619 &:= (-1 + (T(2+T(3)) \times (T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1620 &:= (T((-1+T((2+(3+4))))+T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1621 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1622 &:= ((-1 + T((2 \times T(3) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
1623 &:= (((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) \times (4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1624 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1625 &:= (T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1626 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(3) + T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
1627 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1628 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(3+4))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
1629 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1630 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3+4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1631 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
1632 &:= (-1+2+(T(3+T(4))+T(T(T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1633 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
1634 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((4+T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
1635 &:= (T((-1+T(2+T(3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1596 &:= T(((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7+6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1597 &:= (-9 + (T(((8-7) \times (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1598 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1599 &:= (T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7)) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1600 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1601 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1602 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1603 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T((T(7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1604 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1605 &:= (T((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1606 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1607 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
1608 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1609 &:= (-9 + (T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1610 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) \times (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1611 &:= (T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7) + (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1612 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1613 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1614 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times T(7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1615 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (T(7) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
1616 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1617 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1618 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1619 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) - T(7)) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1620 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1621 &:= (-9 - ((8 - T(7+6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1622 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(((7+6) + T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1623 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7 \times 6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1624 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(7+6) + T(T(5))))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
1625 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1626 &:= (T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7) + (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1627 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1628 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7+6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
1629 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1630 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1631 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1632 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
1633 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
1634 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T((7 - (6 - 5)))))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1635 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 - T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

- 1636** := $(T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1637 := $(-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))))$
1638 := $((-1-2) \times ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1639 := $(-1 \times 2 + (T((3+T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
1640 := $(-1 + (T((2 \times T(3+4))) + (T(5)+6+7+8+9)))$
1641 := $(T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9))$
1642 := $((T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1643 := $(T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$
1644 := $(-1 - (((2+T(3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1645 := $((-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - T(T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))$
1646 := $((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))$
1647 := $((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4+5+6+7+8+9)))$
1648 := $(T((-1+2+T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1649 := $(-1 \times (T((2+T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$
1650 := $(((-1-2+T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1651 := $(-1 \times 2 + T(((3 \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$
1652 := $(-1 + T((2 \times T(3)) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))$
1653 := $T((-1-2 + (T(T(3)) + (4+5+6+7+8+9))))$
1654 := $(-1+2 + T(((3 \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$
1655 := $(-1 + (T(T(2+T(3))) + T((T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))))$
1656 := $((-1-2) \times (T((3 \times 4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1657 := $((-1+2+T((3+T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$
1658 := $(T((-1+2+T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$
1659 := $((T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)$
1660 := $(((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1661 := $(-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$
1662 := $((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))))$
1663 := $(-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (4 + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))))$
1664 := $(-1 + (T(T((2+(3+4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
1665 := $(T((T(T(-1+2+3)) - T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1666 := $(T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
1667 := $(-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$
1668 := $(-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)))$
1669 := $((-1+2+3) + ((T(4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
1670 := $(((-1+T(T(2 \times 3))) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))$
1671 := $(T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
1672 := $((-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))/5)) - (6+7+8+9))$
1673 := $((-1-2+T((3+T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
1674 := $((-1 \times 2 + T((3+T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
1675 := $((T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
- 1636** := $(-9 - 8 + T(((7 \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1637 := $(-9 - (T(8+7) - (T(T(6)) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
1638 := $(-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))$
1639 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1640 := $((-9 + T(8+7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1641 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1642 := $((-9 + T((8+(7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1643 := $(T((-9 + T(((8-7) \times (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1))$
1644 := $(-9 + (T(8) + (7 \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1))))$
1645 := $(T((-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T(6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))$
1646 := $(((-9+8) - 7 - 6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1647 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7+6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))))$
1648 := $(-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7) - (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1649 := $((-9 - 8) \times ((7+6) - (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))))$
1650 := $(-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1651 := $((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1652 := $(-9 + 8 + T(((7 \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1653 := $T((T(-9+8+7) + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1654 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1655 := $(((-9 - T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1))$
1656 := $(-9 + ((8+7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1657 := $(-9 + (T((T(8)+7)) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1658 := $(((-9+8) - 7 + 6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1659 := $(-9 + (T(8) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))))$
1660 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))$
1661 := $(((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))$
1662 := $(-9 + (T(8+7) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
1663 := $(-9 - 8 - ((7 - T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1664 := $(-9 + (((T(T(8)) - 7 + 6)/5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1665 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1666 := $((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1667 := $(-9 + ((8 \times (T(7) - (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1668 := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))))$
1669 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7+6) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$
1670 := $(-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
1671 := $(-9 - ((8 - (T(7) - 6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
1672 := $((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T((7+T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
1673 := $(((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))$
1674 := $(-9 \times (T((T(8) + T(7))) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))))$
1675 := $((-9 + (8 \times (7+6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1676 &:= (T(((−1+2) \times 3) + T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1677 &:= ((−1 + 2 + T((3 + T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1678 &:= ((−1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1679 &:= (−1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 1680 &:= (T(T(T(−1 + 2 + 3))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1681 &:= ((−1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1682 &:= (−1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1683 &:= (T((T(−1 + 2 \times T(3))) - (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 1684 &:= (−1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1685 &:= (−1 + (2 \times (T((3 \times (4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1686 &:= (T(T(T(−1 + 2 + 3))) - (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1687 &:= (−1 + (T((2 + T((T(3) + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1688 &:= (T((−1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 1689 &:= (−1 + ((T(2 + 3) \times T(4)) + T(T(T((T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1690 &:= (((−1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1691 &:= ((−1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1692 &:= ((−1 - 2) \times (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1693 &:= (−1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1694 &:= (−1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1695 &:= (−1 + 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1696 &:= (T(((−1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1697 &:= (((−1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4))))/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 1698 &:= (T((−1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1699 &:= ((−1 + ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1700 &:= (−1 + (T(T(2 + T(3))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1701 &:= (−1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1702 &:= ((−1 + 2 + T((3 + T(T(4)))))) - T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1703 &:= (T((−1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1704 &:= (−1 + (T(2 + 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 1705 &:= ((T(−1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1706 &:= (((−1 + T(2 + 3)) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1707 &:= ((−1 - 2) \times (T(3) + (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1708 &:= ((−1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1709 &:= (−1 - ((2 - T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1710 &:= ((−1 - 2) \times ((T(3) \times T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1711 &:= T(((−1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1712 &:= ((−1 - 2) - ((T(3) - T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1713 &:= (−1 \times 2 - ((T(3) - T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1714 &:= (−1 - (((2 \times 3) - T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1715 &:= (((−1 - 2 - 3) + T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1676 &:= (T(((−9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1677 &:= (−9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1678 &:= ((−9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 1679 &:= (−9 + (8 \times (T(7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1680 &:= (((−9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1681 &:= (T((−9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1682 &:= ((−9 + 8 + 7) + (T((T(6) - 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1683 &:= (−9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1684 &:= (T(((−9 + T(8)) - 7)) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1685 &:= (((−9 \times T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1686 &:= ((−9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1687 &:= ((−9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) - 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1688 &:= ((−9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1689 &:= ((−9 + (8 \times T(7))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1690 &:= ((−9 \times (T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1691 &:= ((−9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1692 &:= (−9 \times (T(8) + (7 - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1693 &:= ((−9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 1694 &:= (−9 - 8 + (T(7 + 6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1695 &:= ((−9 \times ((8 \times 7) - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1696 &:= ((−9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1697 &:= (−9 + (T(8 \times 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1698 &:= (−9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1699 &:= (−9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1700 &:= ((−9 + 8 + T(7 + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1701 &:= (−9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1702 &:= (−9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) - (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 1703 &:= (−9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T((T(6) - 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 1704 &:= (T(−9 + T(8)) + T(((7 - (6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1705 &:= (−9 - 8 + (7 \times (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1706 &:= (−9 - (T(8) - (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 1707 &:= ((−9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1708 &:= (T((−9 + T(((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1709 &:= (−9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1710 &:= (T((T(−9 - 8 + T(7)) - 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1711 &:= T(((−9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7)))/(T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1712 &:= (−9 - (T(T(8) - 7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1713 &:= (−9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1714 &:= ((−9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1715 &:= (T((((−9 + 8) \times 7) + T(6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 1716** := $(-1+2 - ((T(3) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))$
- 1717** := $-1+2+T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$
- 1718** := $(T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(T(T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$
- 1719** := $(-1 - (T(T(2+3)) + (4 \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))))$
- 1720** := $(T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)))$
- 1721** := $(-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))))$
- 1722** := $((-1-2) - (3 \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1723** := $(-1 \times 2 - (3 \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1724** := $(-1 + ((2+T(T(3))) \times (T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))$
- 1725** := $((-1-2) \times (T((T(3)+4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))$
- 1726** := $(-1+2 - (3 \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1727** := $(T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$
- 1728** := $(-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))$
- 1729** := $(-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)))))$
- 1730** := $(((-1+T(2 \times 3)) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$
- 1731** := $(T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
- 1732** := $(-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))$
- 1733** := $(-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1734** := $(-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1735** := $(T(((-1+2+3) + T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
- 1736** := $(T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))$
- 1737** := $(-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1738** := $((-1+2-3) + (T((T(4) \times 5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
- 1739** := $(-1 + (T((2+3+T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
- 1740** := $(T((-1 + (T(2+3) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9))$
- 1741** := $(-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))))$
- 1742** := $((-1+2 + T((T(3) + T(T(4))))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))$
- 1743** := $(-1-2 + (T((3+T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$
- 1744** := $(-1 \times 2 + (T((3+T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$
- 1745** := $((T((-1-2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)$
- 1746** := $(T(((-1+2) \times 3) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)$
- 1747** := $(-1+2 + (T((3+T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$
- 1748** := $(T((-1+2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))$
- 1749** := $(-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1750** := $(T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))))$
- 1751** := $(-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3+4)) + (5+T(6+7+8+9)))))$
- 1752** := $(T(((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T((T(T(4)))/5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))$
- 1753** := $(T((-1+2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
- 1754** := $(-1 + (T(((2+3) \times T(4)) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))))$
- 1755** := $(T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)))$
- 1716** := $(T((T(-9+T(8))/7)) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1717** := $(-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) - 6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1718** := $(((-9+T(8)) \times 7) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1719** := $(-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
- 1720** := $(-9 - 8 + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1721** := $(-9+8 + (7 \times (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))))$
- 1722** := $(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))$
- 1723** := $(T(-9+T(8)) + (T((T(7)+T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1724** := $((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1725** := $(((-9-8) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))$
- 1726** := $(T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1727** := $(((-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))$
- 1728** := $(-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
- 1729** := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))$
- 1730** := $(T((-9-8+T((7+6-5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))$
- 1731** := $(T((T(-9+T(8))/7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1732** := $(-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7+6)) + (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
- 1733** := $(-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1734** := $(-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
- 1735** := $(-9 - ((8 \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1736** := $(-9+8 + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1737** := $((((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))$
- 1738** := $(-9 + (T(8) + (T(7+6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
- 1739** := $(T(((-9+T(8)) - 7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1740** := $((-9 \times ((8+T(7)) - T(T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1))$
- 1741** := $((T(T(-9-8+T(7)))/(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))$
- 1742** := $(-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7+6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
- 1743** := $(T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$
- 1744** := $((-9 + (8 \times T(7))) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1745** := $(((-9-8) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))$
- 1746** := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1))))$
- 1747** := $(T(-9+T(8)) - (T(7+6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1748** := $(-9 - (T(8) - ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))$
- 1749** := $((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
- 1750** := $((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1751** := $(-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6+5))) \times T(4+3+2+1)))$
- 1752** := $(-9 + (T(T(((8+7) - 6))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1))))$
- 1753** := $(T(-9+T(8)) + ((T(7+6) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))$
- 1754** := $((-9 \times ((8+7) - (T(T(6)) - T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1))$
- 1755** := $(-9 \times ((8+T(7)) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1756 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 1756 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T((T(7) + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1757 &:= ((-1+2+(T(3)^4)) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) & 1757 &:= (-9 + (T(((T(T(8)) - T(7))/(6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1758 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 1758 &:= ((((-9+8) - 7) + T(T(6))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1759 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (4 \times (5+T(6+7+8+9)))) & 1759 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7+6) + (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1760 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T((4+T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 1760 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1761 &:= (T(T((-1+(T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 1761 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1762 &:= (-1+2+(T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 1762 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1763 &:= (-1-2+(T(3)^4 + (5+T(6+7+8+9)))) & 1763 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (T(7+6) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1764 &:= ((-1-2-3) + T((4+T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 1764 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1765 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 1765 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1766 &:= (T(((T(-1+2+3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 1766 &:= (T(((((-9+8) - 7) + T(6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1767 &:= (-1-2+T(((T(3) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 1767 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8) - 7) - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1768 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((T(3) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 1768 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1769 &:= (-1 + T((T(2+3) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1769 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1770 &:= T((-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1770 &:= T(((((-9-8) + T(7+6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1771 &:= (((-1+2+T(3))^4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 1771 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1772 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 1772 &:= ((-9 + T(((8+7) + T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1773 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) + T((4+T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 1773 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7+6) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 1774 &:= ((-1+2+3) + T((4+T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 1774 &:= (((-9-8) \times (T(T(7)) + 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1775 &:= (-1 + (T((2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 1775 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1776 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) - 4) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 1776 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1777 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 1777 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1778 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1778 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1779 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1779 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1780 &:= ((T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))/4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1780 &:= (T(((((-9+8) \times 7) + T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 1781 &:= ((T((-1+T(T(2+3)))/4) - (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)) & 1781 &:= (-9 + ((8 + T(7+6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 1782 &:= (-1-2+((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1782 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (7 \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1783 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1783 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1784 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 \times 3) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1784 &:= (-9+8+(((T(7) + T(6)) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1785 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1785 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) + T(T(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 1786 &:= (-1+2+((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 1786 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1787 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 1787 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + 6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1788 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(3) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 1788 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1789 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 1789 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - ((6-5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1790 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times 3 + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 1790 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1791 &:= (T((T(((T(-1+2) \times 3) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 1791 &:= (-9 - (T((8 \times (7+6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1792 &:= ((-1-2+T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1792 &:= ((-9+8+(T(7) \times T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 1793 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1793 &:= (T((-9-8+(T(7)+6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1794 &:= ((-1+T((2+3+T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1794 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1795 &:= (T((T(((T(-1+2) \times 3) \times T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 1795 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1796 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1797 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) + (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1798 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - (4 \times (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1799 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 1800 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 \times T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1801 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1802 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1803 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1804 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1805 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 1806 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3 + 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1807 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1808 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1809 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1810 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1811 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1812 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1813 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 1814 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1815 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) + (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1816 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1817 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1818 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((T(3) \times 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1819 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(3) + 4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1820 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1821 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1822 &:= (((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - 4)))/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1823 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1824 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(((T(4)/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1825 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + T(T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1826 &:= (((-1 - T(2 + 3)) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 1827 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1828 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1829 &:= (-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1830 &:= T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 1831 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1832 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) + (4 \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 1833 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + 3 + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1834 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(((T(4)/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 1835 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1796 &:= (T((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1797 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1798 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1799 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7 + 6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1800 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1801 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1802 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1803 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1804 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1805 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1806 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1807 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1808 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1809 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1810 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + T(7)) - T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1811 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1812 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1813 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(7) \times T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1814 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1815 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) - 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1816 &:= (T((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1817 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1818 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1819 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1820 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1821 &:= (-9 + T((T((8 + 7) - 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1822 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) - 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1823 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - 7 - 6) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1824 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1825 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1826 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1827 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1828 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1829 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 1830 &:= T(((9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 1831 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1832 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
 1833 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 1834 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 1835 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1876 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1877 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1878 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1879 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1880 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + (T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1881 &:= (T(((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) - (4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1882 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1883 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1884 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1885 &:= (T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1886 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((3 + T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1887 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1888 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1889 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1890 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1891 &:= T((-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1892 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1893 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1894 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1895 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1896 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1897 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T((T((4 \times T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1898 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T((T((4 \times T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1899 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1900 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
1901 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1902 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1903 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1904 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 + 3) \times T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1905 &:= (T((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
1906 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1907 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1908 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (4 \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1909 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1910 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1911 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1912 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1913 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
1914 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (4 \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
1915 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (T((4 \times T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1876 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1877 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1878 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1879 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1880 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1881 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1882 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((T(7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1883 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) + 7) \times (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1884 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1885 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1886 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1887 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) + T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1888 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - ((6 \times 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1889 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) \times (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1890 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1891 &:= T(((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1892 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(6) + (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1893 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1894 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1895 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1896 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + T(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1897 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1898 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) + ((7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1899 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times ((7 + 6) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1900 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 + 6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1901 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1902 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1903 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1904 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times (T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1905 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - 7) \times ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1906 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
1907 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1908 &:= (-9 \times (8 + ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1909 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1910 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + T(T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1911 &:= ((T(T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)))/T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
1912 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1913 &:= (T(((-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1914 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 - (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
1915 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1916 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1917 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1918 &:= (T((-1+2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - (5+6+7+8+9) \\
1919 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1920 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1921 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1922 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(3)+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1923 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1924 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1925 &:= (T(T((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))))) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
1926 &:= ((T(((-1+2) \times 3))^4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
1927 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3)^4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1928 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1929 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1930 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1931 &:= (T(((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1932 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1933 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(3) - T(4)))))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1934 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) \times (4 \times 5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
1935 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1936 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1937 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1938 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1939 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1940 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1941 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
1942 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + (4 \times (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
1943 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1944 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1945 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1946 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
1947 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1948 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3) \times (4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1949 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1950 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1951 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) \times (4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
1952 &:= (-1 + T((2 + (T(T(3)) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1953 &:= T(((-1+2-3) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
1954 &:= (-1+2 + T(((3+4) + T(T((T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
1955 &:= (-1 + (T((2 - (T(3) - T(T(4)))))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1916 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
1917 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7+6) + (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1918 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1919 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7+6)) - T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1920 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7+6) + T(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1921 &:= ((-9-8) \times (T(7) - (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1922 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 - (6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1923 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1924 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1925 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
1926 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1927 &:= (-9 + (((8 + T(7)) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1928 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (((7+6) \times T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1929 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1930 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1931 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + T(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
1932 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1933 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7+6) \times (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
1934 &:= ((-9+8 + T(T(7))) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1935 &:= (-9 \times ((8-7) - (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1936 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7+6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1937 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - (7+6-5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1938 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1939 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1940 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1941 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1942 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1943 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1944 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1945 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
1946 &:= (T((-9 + (T(T(8))/(7+6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
1947 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7+6) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1948 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7+6) + T(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1949 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
1950 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) - T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1951 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (7+T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
1952 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
1953 &:= T((-9 - (T(8) + ((7+6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
1954 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T(((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
1955 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1956 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) - 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1957 &:= (T((-1+2+(T(3)+T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1958 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + T((T(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1959 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3+4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1960 &:= ((-1 + T(2+3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1961 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(3)^4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1962 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(4 \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1963 &:= (((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T((T(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1964 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3+4)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 1965 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1966 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1967 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 1968 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 1969 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1970 &:= (((T(-1+2+3)^4)/5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 1971 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1972 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1973 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 1974 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 1975 &:= ((-1 - T(2 \times T(3))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1976 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 1977 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1978 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3)) + T(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 1979 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(T((T(3)+4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 1980 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1981 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1982 &:= -1 + T(T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
 1983 &:= (-1 - ((2^{T(3)}) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1984 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{T(3)}) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1985 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1986 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3)) \times (4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 1987 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1988 &:= (T((-1+2+(T(3)+T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
 1989 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 1990 &:= (T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 1991 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1992 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 1993 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 1994 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T((T(3)+4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 1995 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1956 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7)) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1957 &:= (-9+(T((T(8)+T(7))) + (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1958 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T((7+T(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1959 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 1960 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8)+T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1961 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8)+T(7)))) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 1962 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7+6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1963 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7))/(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1964 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T((7+T(6)))) - T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1965 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) - (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1966 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7+6)) - (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1967 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1968 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times (7 - T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1969 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7+6))) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1970 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1971 &:= (-9 + ((8 - T(7)) \times (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1972 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8)+T(7))) + (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1973 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(((7+6) + T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1974 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1975 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1976 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1977 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1978 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1979 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) - (T(7) - T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1980 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1981 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8)+T(7)))) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1982 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7+6) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1983 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(((7 - (6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1984 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1985 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1986 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1987 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1988 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 1989 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 1990 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
 1991 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (7 + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 1992 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 1993 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (((7+6) \times T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 1994 &:= (-9+8+((T(7+6) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 1995 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (7 \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2035 &:= ((-1 + T(2^{T(3)})) - (T(T(T(4)))) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2036 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2037 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2038 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2039 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2040 &:= ((-1 + T(2^{T(3)})) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2041 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2042 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2043 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T(4))))) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2044 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2045 &:= (T(((T(-1 + T(2 + 3))) - T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2046 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2047 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2048 &:= (-1 + (T(2^{T(3)})) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2049 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2050 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2051 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2052 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2053 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2054 &:= (-1 + (T(2^{T(3)})) + (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2055 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2056 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2057 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2058 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2059 &:= ((-1 + T(2^{T(3)})) - (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2060 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (T(T(T(4)))) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2061 &:= (T(((T(-1 + 2 - 3)) + T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2062 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2063 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2064 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2065 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2066 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2067 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2068 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + T(((T(4)/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2069 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2070 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2071 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3 + 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2072 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2073 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2074 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2035 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(7) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2036 &:= (T(((T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2037 &:= (((T(-9 - 8) \times 7) + T(T(6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2038 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7 + 6) + T(T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2039 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2040 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + 6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2041 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2042 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2043 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times ((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2044 &:= (((T(-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2045 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((T(7) - T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2046 &:= (((T(-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2047 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8 + 7)) - T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
2048 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2049 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(T(5))) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2050 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2051 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2052 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2053 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2054 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7 + 6) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2055 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2056 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (7 + T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2057 &:= (((T(-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2058 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 - T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2059 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2060 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2061 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2062 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2063 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2064 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2065 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2066 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + T(T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2067 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2068 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2069 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2070 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2071 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) + (7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2072 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2073 &:= (T(((T(-9 + T(8))) - T(T(7) + 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2074 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2115 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2116 &:= (((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))/5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2117 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2118 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2119 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) - T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2120 &:= (((-1 + T((2 + T(T(3)))))) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
2121 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2122 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + T((T((4 \times T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2123 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2124 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2125 &:= (T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2126 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2127 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2128 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2129 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2130 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + T(3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2131 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2132 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2133 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2134 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2135 &:= (T(((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2136 &:= (-1+2 + ((T(3) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2137 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2138 &:= (T((-1+2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2139 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((T(4) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2140 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2141 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2142 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(((3 \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2143 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((3 \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2144 &:= (-1 + T((2 + (T(3+4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2145 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2146 &:= (-1+2 + T(((3 \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2147 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2148 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2149 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2150 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2151 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (4 \times (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2152 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2153 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2154 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2115 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2116 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2117 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((T(7) - T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2118 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7 \times 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2119 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2120 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 \times (6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2121 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2122 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + T(T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2123 &:= ((((-9+8) - T(T(7))) \times (6 - T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2124 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2125 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2126 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (7+6-5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2127 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2128 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2129 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2130 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6))) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2131 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2132 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) + T(T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2133 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2134 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T((T(7) - (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2135 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7) - 6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2136 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) - (T(7+6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2137 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2138 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2139 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2140 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + (7+6))) \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2141 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2142 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2143 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (T(7) - (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2144 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7) + 6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2145 &:= T((-9 - (T((8 + T(7)))/(6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2146 &:= (((-9 - (8-7)) + T(T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2147 &:= ((-9 + T(T(((8-7) \times (6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2148 &:= ((T(-9+8 + T(7)) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2149 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + T(T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2150 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7+6))) + T(T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2151 &:= (T((T(-9 + T(8))/7) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2152 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7+6) - T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2153 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + ((T(T(6)) - T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2154 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2155 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2156 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2157 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2158 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2159 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(3)) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2160 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2161 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2162 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2163 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2164 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2165 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2166 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2167 &:= (-1-2+(T(T((T(3)+4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2168 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2169 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2170 &:= (T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2171 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2172 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2173 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2174 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2175 &:= ((-1 + T(T((T(2+3) - 4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2176 &:= (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2177 &:= (-1+2+(T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2178 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2179 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) - T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2180 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2181 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2182 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(3)) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2183 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+T(3))) - T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2184 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2185 &:= (T(-1+2 \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2186 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2187 &:= (-1+2+(T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2188 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2189 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2190 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2191 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2192 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2193 &:= (((-1 \times T(T(T(2+3))))/T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2194 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) + (T(4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2155 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2156 &:= (T(((-9+8+7) \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2157 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2158 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2159 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2160 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7))/T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2161 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2162 &:= (((-9+8+7) + T(T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2163 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + T(T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2164 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2165 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2166 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2167 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2168 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2169 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(7 \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2170 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2171 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2172 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2173 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2174 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7+6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2175 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) - (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2176 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2177 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2178 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7+6) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2179 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7+6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2180 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2181 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2182 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2183 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(7) + T(T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2184 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2185 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2186 &:= (((-9-8) \times (T(7) - T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2187 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2188 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2189 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (7 - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2190 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2191 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 + T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2192 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2193 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + T(T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1) \\
2194 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + T(T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2195 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T((4+T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2196 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2197 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2198 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2199 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2200 &:= (-1 + (T((2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2201 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) + (4 - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2202 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2203 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) - ((T(T(4)) - T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2204 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2205 &:= ((-1-2+T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2206 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 + (3+4)))) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2207 &:= (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
2208 &:= (-1-2+T((T(T(3)) + (T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2209 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2210 &:= (-1 + T(T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2211 &:= T((T((-1+T(2+3))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2212 &:= (-1+2+T((T(T(3)) + (T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2213 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
2214 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (T(4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2215 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(4 \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2216 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
2217 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times ((T(T(4)) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2218 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2219 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2220 &:= (T((-1-2+T((3 \times 4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2221 &:= (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2222 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2223 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2224 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times ((4 \times 5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2225 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3+4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2226 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2227 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2228 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2229 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times ((4+T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2230 &:= (T((-1+2+3) + T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2231 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2232 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2233 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2234 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) \times T(4)) + T((T(5)+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2195 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - 7) \times (T(6+5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2196 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2197 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2198 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2199 &:= (-9+8 + (T(((7+6) \times 5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2200 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7)) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2201 &:= (T(((-9+8+7) \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2202 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2203 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2204 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2205 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2206 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2207 &:= (((-9+8+7) + T(T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2208 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7))) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2209 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7) + 6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2210 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2211 &:= T(T((-9 - (8 - (7 + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2212 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2213 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2214 &:= (((-9-8+T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2215 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7+6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2216 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2217 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2218 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2219 &:= (-9-8 + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2220 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2221 &:= (T(((-9+8+7) \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2222 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2223 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times (T(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2224 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2225 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2226 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2227 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2228 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2229 &:= ((-9+8+T(T(7))) - (6 - T(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2230 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7)) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2231 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2232 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2233 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T(((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2234 &:= (-9 + (T((T(T(8))/(7+6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2235 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2+3) + T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2236 &:= (T((-1 + 2 \times T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 2237 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2238 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\ 2239 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2240 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2+3))) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2241 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\ 2242 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 2243 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2244 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2245 &:= (-1 + (T(T((T(2+3) - 4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2246 &:= (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\ 2247 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2248 &:= (T((-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\ 2249 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) - T(4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\ 2250 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2251 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2252 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2253 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\ 2254 &:= ((T(T((-1+2 + T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2255 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(((3 \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2256 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2257 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\ 2258 &:= (-1 - (T((T(2+3) - 4)) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2259 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2260 &:= (T((-1-2-3) + T(T(4))) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\ 2261 &:= (((-1 - T(2+3)) \times 4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2262 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\ 2263 &:= (T((-1+2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2264 &:= ((-1-2-3) - (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2265 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 \times 3))) \times T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2266 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2+3))/T(4)) + T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2267 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3+4)) - T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\ 2268 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3+4)) - T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\ 2269 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3+4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2270 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times ((T(T(4))/5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\ 2271 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(3))}) - (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2272 &:= ((-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2273 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 2274 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2235 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2236 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\ 2237 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2238 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(T(7)))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2239 &:= ((-9+8) - ((7 - T((6+T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\ 2240 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7+6))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2241 &:= (((T(-9+T(8)) - 7) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2242 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\ 2243 &:= (T(((-9+8) - (T(7) - T(6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2244 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2245 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\ 2246 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - (7 \times (6+5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2247 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2248 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\ 2249 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2250 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T((7+T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2251 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((T(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2252 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7+6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2253 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2254 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\ 2255 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) - (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2256 &:= ((-9 - (8-7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2257 &:= (-9 + (T(T(((8-7) \times (6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2258 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2259 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2260 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2261 &:= (-9-8 + T(((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2262 &:= (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times 6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2263 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2264 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2265 &:= ((-9-8 + (T(7) \times 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2266 &:= (T((-9+8+7) \times (6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\ 2267 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2268 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 2269 &:= (-9 + T(((8 - (7 - (6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2270 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\ 2271 &:= (-9 + ((8 - T(7)) \times (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2272 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 2273 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((7 \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2274 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2275 &:= ((T(-1+2+3) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2275 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7)+6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 2276 &:= ((-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2276 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2277 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 2277 &:= (-9+8 + T(((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2278 &:= T((T((-1+2+T(3))) + (4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 2278 &:= T((-9 + (T(8 \times 7)/(6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2279 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T((3+4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 2279 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T((7+T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2280 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((3+4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 2280 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(7+6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 2281 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2281 &:= (T((-9+8) \times (T(7) - T(6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 2282 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T((T(3)+4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2282 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7+6))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2283 &:= (T((-1-2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2283 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 2284 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/4) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2284 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7+6))) - T(5 + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 2285 &:= (((-1+2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2285 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2286 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2286 &:= ((-9 + T(((8+T(T(7)))/6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 2287 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2287 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2288 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2288 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 2289 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2289 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2290 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2290 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(7+6)) \times T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
 2291 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((3+T(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2291 &:= (T((-9-8) \times (7 - (6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1) \\
 2292 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2292 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7+6))) + (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2293 &:= ((-1-2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2293 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 2294 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2294 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 2295 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) + T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2295 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + 6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 2296 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2296 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7+6))) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2297 &:= ((-1+2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2297 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7+6)) - T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2298 &:= (-1+2 - (T(3+4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2298 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8+7) \times 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2299 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2299 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 2300 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 2300 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2301 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 2301 &:= (-9 - (T((8+T(7+6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2302 &:= (((-1+2 - T(T(T(3))))/T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 2302 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2303 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) & 2303 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(7) + 6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2304 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 2304 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2305 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + (T((4 \times T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2305 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T(((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2306 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) + (4 - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2306 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((T(7+6) - T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2307 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2307 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2308 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2308 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 2309 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) - 4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2309 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T((7 - (6-5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 2310 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)))/T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2310 &:= (((-9+8+T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 2311 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2311 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7+6)) - T(5 + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2312 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 2312 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2313 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 2313 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 2314 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) - (4 + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2314 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + T(6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2315 &:= (((-1-2+T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2316 &:= (T(((-1+T(2 \times T(3))) - (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2317 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times 4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2318 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2319 &:= ((-1+2-(3+4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2320 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2321 &:= ((-1+(2 \times T((3+T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2322 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2323 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3) - 4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2324 &:= (-1 - (((2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2325 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2326 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(3+4))}) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2327 &:= ((-1+2-(3-4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2328 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - ((T(4) - T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2329 &:= ((-1-(2-(3+4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2330 &:= ((-1 \times (2-(3+4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2331 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2332 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2333 &:= ((-1+(2+(3+4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2334 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (4 \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2335 &:= (((-1+T(T(2 \times 3))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2336 &:= ((-1 - T(2+3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2337 &:= (-1-2+(3 \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2338 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2339 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((3+T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2340 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2341 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2342 &:= (-1+2+(T((3+T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2343 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2344 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2345 &:= ((T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2346 &:= (-1+2+((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2347 &:= (-1+2+T(((T((3 \times 4)) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2348 &:= (((-1-2+T((T(3)+T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2349 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2350 &:= ((-1 \times (2-(3+4))) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2351 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2352 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2353 &:= (T(((-1+2) \times (3+4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2354 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(3)) \times T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2315 &:= ((-9+8+(T(T(7)) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2316 &:= (((-9+T(8+7)) \times T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2317 &:= (-9+(T((T(8)+T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2318 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((7 \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2319 &:= (((-9-8+T(T(7))) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2320 &:= ((T(-9+T(8))/7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2321 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2322 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2323 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + T(6))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2324 &:= (-9+(T(((8-7)+T(6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2325 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2326 &:= (T(((-9+8+7) \times 6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2327 &:= (-9+(8 \times (T(T(7)) + (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2328 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((7 \times (T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2329 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((7+6) - (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2330 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + ((7+6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2331 &:= ((-9+T(8+7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2332 &:= (-9+(T(8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2333 &:= (((-9+T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2334 &:= ((-9-8+T(T(7))) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2335 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2336 &:= (T(((-9-8) \times (7 - (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2337 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7+6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2338 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((7 \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2339 &:= ((-9-8+T(T(7+6))) - T(5+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2340 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7) - 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2341 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times T(7)) + 6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2342 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2343 &:= (-9+(T(8) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2344 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2345 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2346 &:= T((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2347 &:= (-9+(T(8) + (T((T(7)+6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2348 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2349 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) - 7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2350 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) - (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2351 &:= (-9+(8 \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2352 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2353 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + ((T(T(6))+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2354 &:= (-9+(T((T(8) + (7-6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2355 &:= (((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2356 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3 + 4) + T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2357 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (4 + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2358 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2359 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2360 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2361 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2362 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2363 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2364 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2365 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2366 &:= (((-1 + 2 + T(3))^4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2367 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2368 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (4 \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2369 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2370 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((3 + 4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2371 &:= (T((T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2372 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2373 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2374 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2375 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2376 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) - (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2377 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2378 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2379 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((T(T(3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2380 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2381 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2382 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3)) - T(T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2383 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2384 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2385 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((3 + 4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2386 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2387 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2388 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2389 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2390 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (T(4) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2391 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2392 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2393 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (T((T(T(4))/5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2394 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (T((T(T(4))/5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2355 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + T(T(7))) \times 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2356 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) + 6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2357 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + T(7)) \times T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2358 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2359 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2360 &:= (T((-9 + T((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2361 &:= (T(((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2362 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2363 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times ((6 \times 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2364 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2365 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(7))) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2366 &:= (T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2367 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times T(7))) \times T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2368 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7 + 6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2369 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2370 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2371 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2372 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2373 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(7 + 6) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2374 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times 6) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2375 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((T(7) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2376 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2377 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T(((7 + 6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2378 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2379 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2380 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2381 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2382 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 + T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2383 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2384 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2385 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2386 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2387 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2388 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2389 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2390 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2391 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2392 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2393 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) \times (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2394 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2395 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) \times T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2395 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + ((T(6) \times T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2396 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2396 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7+6) - T(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2397 &:= (((-1+2+T(3))^4) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) & 2397 &:= (-9-8 - (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2398 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2398 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2399 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2399 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2400 &:= (T((-1+2+3) + T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2400 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 \times 6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2401 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2401 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2402 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2402 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 - (6-5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2403 &:= (T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 2403 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times ((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2404 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - (T(4) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2404 &:= ((-9-8 + (T(T(7)) \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2405 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2405 &:= (T((-9 + T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2406 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3)^4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)) & 2406 &:= (-9 + T((T(T(((8+7) - 6)))/(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2407 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2407 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2408 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2408 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7+6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2409 &:= ((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times 4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 2409 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2410 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 2410 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2411 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((3+T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 2411 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8)+7))) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2412 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 2412 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2413 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3+4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2413 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2414 &:= (-1 + ((T((2+T(T(3))))/4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2414 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2415 &:= T((-1 + T((2 \times (3+4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2415 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2416 &:= (-1+2 - ((3+4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2416 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2417 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2417 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2418 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2418 &:= ((T(-9+8 + T(7)) \times 6) + (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2419 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (4 + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2419 &:= (-9-8 + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2420 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2420 &:= ((-9+8 + (T(T(7)) \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2421 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2421 &:= ((-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(T(7)))) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2422 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2422 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2423 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2423 &:= ((-9+8 + (T(T(7)) \times 6)) - (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2424 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T(4) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2424 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7)+6) + T(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2425 &:= ((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 2425 &:= (T((-9 + T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2426 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3))) - (4 - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2426 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2427 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + (T(4) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2427 &:= (T(T(-9-8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2428 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2428 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + T(6))) - (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2429 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2429 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7+6)) - T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2430 &:= (T((-1+2+3) + T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 2430 &:= ((-9+8 + T(7)) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2431 &:= (-1+2 - (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2431 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times (6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2432 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2432 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2433 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 2433 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2434 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3))) + (4 + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2434 &:= (-9-8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2435 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2436 &:= (((-1+2+T(3))^4) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2437 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2438 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
2439 &:= ((T(((T(-1+2+3)) \times T(4)))/5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2440 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2441 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2442 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2443 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2444 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2445 &:= ((T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))/4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2446 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2447 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2448 &:= ((-1-2+T(T((3 \times 4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2449 &:= (-1 + ((T(2+3) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2450 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2451 &:= (T(T(((T(-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2452 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((3 \times 4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2453 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2454 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2455 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2456 &:= (-1 \times (2^{T(3)} - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2457 &:= ((-1 + (2^{T(3)})) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2458 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2459 &:= (-1 + (T((2+3+T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2460 &:= (T((T(((T(-1+2) \times 3)) \times T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2461 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(3) \times T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2462 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(3) + T(4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2463 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2464 &:= T(T(T(-1+2) \times 3)) \times 4 + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
2465 &:= (((T(-1+2+3)^4)/5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2466 &:= (T(((T(-1+2-3) + T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2467 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2468 &:= (((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2469 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2470 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((T(4)/5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2471 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2472 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2473 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2474 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2435 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2436 &:= (((-9+T(T(8)-7)) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2437 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2438 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) \times (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2439 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2440 &:= (-9-8+(7 \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2441 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2442 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2443 &:= (T(((T(-9-(8+7)) + T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2444 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2445 &:= (((-9+8+T(T(7))) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2446 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2447 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2448 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2449 &:= (-9+8+((T(7) + T(6)) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2450 &:= (-9+8+((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2451 &:= (((-9+T(8+7)) \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2452 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2453 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7+6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2454 &:= (((-9-8+T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2455 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2456 &:= (-9+8+(7 \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2457 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2458 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + T((T(7) + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2459 &:= ((-9-8+(T(T(7)) \times 6) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2460 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2461 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) + 6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2462 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2463 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2464 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2465 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2466 &:= (T(((T(-9+(8 \times 7)) + T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2467 &:= ((-9 - ((8+7) - 6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2468 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2469 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2470 &:= (T((-9+T((8-(7-(6+5)))))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2471 &:= (((-9+8) - 7 - 6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2472 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2473 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2474 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7+6) - T(5+T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2475 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) \times (T(4)+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2476 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2477 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2478 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2479 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2480 &:= (((-1 - 2 + T(T(3+4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2481 &:= (T(((T(-1+2+T(3)) \times (4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2482 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(((T(3) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2483 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((T(3) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2484 &:= (-1 + T(((T(2 \times (3+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2485 &:= T((T((-1+2+3) + T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2486 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(((T(3) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2487 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3 \times 4) + 5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2488 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2489 &:= ((-1+2+3) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2490 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2491 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2492 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2493 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2494 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2495 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2496 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2497 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2498 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2499 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2500 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2501 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4+5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2502 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2503 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(3)) \times (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2504 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2505 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2506 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2507 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2508 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2509 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2510 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2511 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2512 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2513 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2514 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2475 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2476 &:= (-9 + T(((8 - (T(7) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2477 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2478 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2479 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7) - 6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2480 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7+6)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2481 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2482 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2483 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2484 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2485 &:= T((T((-9 \times 8 + T(7+6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2486 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7)) \times (6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2487 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7+6) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2488 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2489 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2490 &:= (-9 - (T(8 \times 7) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2491 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2492 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2493 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2494 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8+7) - (T(T(6)) - 5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2495 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2496 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2497 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2498 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2499 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2500 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7+6))) - (5 \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2501 &:= (T(((T(-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2502 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2503 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2504 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7+6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2505 &:= ((-9+8 + (T(7) \times 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2506 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2507 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2508 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2509 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2510 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2511 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2512 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2513 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2514 &:= (((-9 - T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2515 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2515 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2516 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 2516 &:= (((-9+8+7) + (T(6) \times T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2517 &:= ((-1-2) - ((T(3) - T(4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2517 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) \times (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2518 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2518 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (6 + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2519 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 2519 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2520 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2520 &:= (T((-9+8 + T(7)) - T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2521 &:= (T((T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2521 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2522 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2522 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2523 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2523 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2524 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2524 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) - (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2525 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2525 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) - (T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2526 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2526 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2527 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2527 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (7 - (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2528 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 2528 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2529 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 2529 &:= (((-9 - T(T(8))) \times 7) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2530 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2530 &:= ((-9 + T(T(((8+7) - (6+5)))))) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2531 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2531 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2532 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2532 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2533 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2533 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
2534 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2534 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2535 &:= (T(-1+2 \times 3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2535 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 \times 6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2536 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2536 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2537 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2537 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2538 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2538 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2539 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2539 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2540 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2540 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (7 - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2541 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2541 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2542 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2542 &:= (-9 + (T((T(T(8)) - T(T(7)+6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2543 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2543 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2544 &:= ((T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 2544 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7+6))) - T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2545 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) + 4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 2545 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2546 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3) + T(T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2546 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2547 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2547 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2548 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2548 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times (T(7) + T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2549 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 2549 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2550 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) \times (T(4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2550 &:= (((-9+8+T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2551 &:= (((-1+2+T(3))^4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 2551 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7)) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2552 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2552 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) \times (6 - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2553 &:= (((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 2553 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2554 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))) & 2554 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2555 &:= (-1 + T((T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) / (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2556 &:= T((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2557 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2558 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2559 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2560 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2561 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2562 &:= ((-1+2+T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2563 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2564 &:= (-1 - (T(T((2+(3+4)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2565 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2566 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2567 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2568 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2569 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2570 &:= ((-1+T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2571 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (4 - T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2572 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2573 &:= (-1 - (T((2+T(T(3)))) - T((T(4+5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2574 &:= (T((-1+2 \times T(3))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2575 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2576 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2577 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2578 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2579 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(3+4) + T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2580 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
2581 &:= (((-1+2+3)^4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2582 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2583 &:= (T((-1+2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2584 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times T(((T(T(4))/5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2585 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 \times T(3+4) + T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2586 &:= (T((-1+2 \times T(3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2587 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) - (T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2588 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2589 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2590 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2591 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2592 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2593 &:= (T(((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2594 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((4^5) + 6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2555 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2556 &:= T(((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2557 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + ((T(6) \times T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2558 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7)) + 6) - (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2559 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7+6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2560 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2561 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2562 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2563 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2564 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 + T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2565 &:= (T((T(-9+8+T(7))/T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2566 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 \times 7) - (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2567 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2568 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7) - 6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2569 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7+6))) - (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2570 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + ((7 - T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2571 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2572 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2573 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2574 &:= ((T(-9+T(8))/7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2575 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2576 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (T(7) + 6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2577 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2578 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(((7+6) \times 5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2579 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2580 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2581 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7+6) \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2582 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (7 - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2583 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2584 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times (T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2585 &:= ((T(-9+8+7) + (T(6) + 5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2586 &:= (T(-9-8+T(7)) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2587 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2588 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7)) + 6) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2589 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (7 \times T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2590 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2591 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T((T(7) - (6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2592 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) \times (T(7) - (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2593 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + 6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2594 &:= (((-9-8) \times (T(7) - (6 \times T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2595 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2596 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2597 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2598 &:= (T((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2599 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2600 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2601 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2602 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2603 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - T((T(T(T(4))/5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2604 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) - T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2605 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2606 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2607 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4^5)) - T(6+7+8+9) \\
2608 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times (4^5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2609 &:= (-1 - (T(T(T(2+3))) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2610 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(T(2+3))) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2611 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) \times T((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2612 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2613 &:= ((-1-2 + T(T((3+4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2614 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T((3+4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2615 &:= ((-1 + T(T((T(2 \times 3) - (4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2616 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times (3+4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2617 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T((3+4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2618 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2619 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2620 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2621 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
2622 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2623 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2624 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2625 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2626 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3)^4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2627 &:= (-1 + T((2 + ((T(3) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2628 &:= T((-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2629 &:= (-1+2 + T((T(T(3)) - (4 - T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2630 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3+4))) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2631 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2632 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2633 &:= (T((-1+2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2634 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2595 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times 7) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2596 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7) + 6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2597 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2598 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2599 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2600 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times (7 - (6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2601 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - 7) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2602 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T((T(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2603 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(((7+6) + T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2604 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2605 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2606 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2607 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2608 &:= (-9-8 + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2609 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2610 &:= (((-9+8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2611 &:= (-9-8 + T((T(7) - (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2612 &:= (-9 + (T((8 - (T(7) - T(6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2613 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7)) + 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2614 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2615 &:= (-9-8 + ((7 \times T(6)) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2616 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2617 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2618 &:= (T((-9+8+7) + T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2619 &:= ((-9+T(8)) \times (7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2620 &:= (((-9+T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) - (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2621 &:= (T((-9+T(T(((8+7) - (6+5)))))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2622 &:= (T(-9-8+T(7)) + T((T(6) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2623 &:= (-9-8 + ((T(7) - 6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2624 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2625 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2626 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2627 &:= (-9+8 + T((T(7) - (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2628 &:= T(((((-9+8) - 7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2629 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T(((7+6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2630 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2631 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2632 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2633 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7)) + 6)) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
2634 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2635 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3)) \times T(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 2635 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) - (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2636 &:= (T((-1+(2^{T(3)}))) - (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2636 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2637 &:= ((-1-2+(3 \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 2637 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2638 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 2638 &:= (T((-9+8+7) + T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2639 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2639 &:= (-9+8+((T(7)-6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2640 &:= (T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2640 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) - (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2641 &:= ((-1+2+(3 \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 2641 &:= (-9+((T(8+7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2642 &:= (T((-1+(2^{T(3)}))) - (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2642 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) - (T(6) + (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2643 &:= (((-1+2+T(3))^4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 2643 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7))+6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2644 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3+T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2644 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2645 &:= (-1 + (T((2+(T(3)+T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2645 &:= ((-9+8+T((7+T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2646 &:= (T((-1-2+T((T(T(3))-T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2646 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) \times (T(7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2647 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(3+T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2647 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2648 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2648 &:= ((-9+((T(8)+T(T(7))) \times 6)) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
2649 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2649 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + T(((6 \times T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2650 &:= (T((-1+(2^{T(3)}))) + (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2650 &:= (((-9+T((8+(7+6)))) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2651 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2651 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2652 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2652 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2653 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 2653 &:= ((T(T((-9+T(8)) - 7 - 6))/5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2654 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2654 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2655 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + T(3+4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 2655 &:= (T((-9-8+T(7+6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2656 &:= (T((-1+(2^{T(3)}))) + (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2656 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T(((7+6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2657 &:= (-1-2+((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2657 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2658 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2658 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2659 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(T(3))) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2659 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 \times T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2660 &:= ((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2660 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7+6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2661 &:= (-1+2+((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 2661 &:= (((-9-8+T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2662 &:= ((-1+(T(T(2+3))/T(4))) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 2662 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2663 &:= (T((-1-2+T(T(3))) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 2663 &:= (((-9+(T(8) \times 7)) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2664 &:= (T(T((-1+(2+(3+4)))) \times (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 2664 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2665 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 2665 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times (7 - (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2666 &:= (T((-1-2+(T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2666 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((7+T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2667 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2667 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2668 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2668 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) - (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2669 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T((T(3+4) - T(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 2669 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2670 &:= ((-1 + T(((2^{T(3)} + 4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 2670 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
2671 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) + T(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 2671 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2672 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(3 \times 4) - 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 2672 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2673 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(T(3)) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2673 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((7+T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2674 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2674 &:= ((-9-8+T((7+T(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2675 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times 3) + T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2676 &:= (T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2677 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(T(3)) - T(4)}) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2678 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2679 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2680 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2681 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2682 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2683 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2684 &:= ((-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times T(4 \times 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2685 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2686 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2687 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2688 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(3^4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2689 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(3^4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2690 &:= (-1 + (T(T((T(2 + 3) - 4))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2691 &:= (T(((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2692 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3^4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2693 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2694 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2695 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2696 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) - 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2697 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2698 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + T(3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2699 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2700 &:= (-1 + T(((2 \times T(T(3))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2701 &:= T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2702 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(3 + 4) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2703 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (3 \times T(4)))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2704 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2705 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) - (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2706 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2707 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2708 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2709 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + T((T(4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2710 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2711 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2712 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2713 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2714 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) \times (T(4) \times T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2675 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + T(7)) \times T(6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2676 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2677 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6 - (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2678 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2679 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2680 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2681 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) - T(6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2682 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2683 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2684 &:= (-9 - 8 + T(((7 + 6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2685 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((7 + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2686 &:= (-9 + ((T((8 + (7 + 6))) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2687 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((T(T(6)) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2688 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2689 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2690 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((7 + T(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2691 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2692 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2693 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2694 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2695 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2696 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) - 7 - 6) \times T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2697 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) - T((T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2698 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T((T(7) + 6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2699 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2700 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2701 &:= T(((9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2702 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2703 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2704 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2705 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2706 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2707 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (7 + 6))) + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2708 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2709 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2710 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((7 + T(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2711 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2712 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2713 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2714 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) - T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2715 &:= (((-1 + T((2 + T(T(3)))))) \times T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2716 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2717 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2718 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2719 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2720 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (T(4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2721 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2722 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2723 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2724 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2725 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4))) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2726 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times (4 + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2727 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2728 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2729 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2730 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2731 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2732 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2733 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2734 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2735 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2736 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2737 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2738 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2739 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2740 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2741 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2742 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2743 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2744 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + T(3)))/(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2745 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2746 &:= (T((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2747 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 + T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2748 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2749 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2750 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2751 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2752 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2753 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4))/5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2754 &:= (((-1 - 2) - T(T(3))) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2715 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2716 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2717 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7 + 6) - T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2718 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2719 &:= ((-9 \times (T((T(8) + T(7))) - T(T(6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2720 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) + T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2721 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8) - 7) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2722 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2723 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2724 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2725 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2726 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) - T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2727 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2728 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T(((7 + 6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2729 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2730 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2731 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2732 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2733 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2734 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2735 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2736 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2737 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2738 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((7 + T(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2739 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2740 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2741 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - T(7 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2742 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2743 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2744 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7 + 6) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2745 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2746 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) - T(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2747 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((T(7) - T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2748 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2749 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2750 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2751 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - 7 - 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2752 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2753 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2754 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + T(T(7))) - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2755 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
2756 &:= T(-1 - 2 + T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2757 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((T(3 + 4) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2758 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((T(3 + 4) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2759 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(T(3))) \times T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2760 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2761 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(3 + 4) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2762 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + T((4 \times T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2763 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2764 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2765 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2766 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2767 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2768 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2769 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2770 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2771 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2772 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + 4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2773 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2774 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2775 &:= T((-1 + (T(2 + T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2776 &:= (T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2777 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2778 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times ((T(4)/5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2779 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3) \times ((T(4)/5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2780 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (T(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2781 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2782 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times ((4 - 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2783 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2784 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times ((4 - 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2785 &:= (((-1 + T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
2786 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2787 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2788 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2789 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) - (4 + 5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
2790 &:= (T((-1 - ((2 + 3) - (4 + 5)))) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2791 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((3 + T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2792 &:= -1 \times 2 - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2793 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - T((T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
2794 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
2755 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2756 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2757 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2758 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 - 6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2759 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + T(6)))) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2760 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2761 &:= (((-9 + T(8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2762 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2763 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2764 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T(6) \times (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2765 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2766 &:= (((-9 - T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2767 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2768 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) - T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2769 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2770 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2771 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2772 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2773 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2774 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times T(6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2775 &:= T((-9 - (T(8) + ((7 - 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2776 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - (T(7) - T(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2777 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2778 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2779 &:= (((T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - T(6))/5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2780 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
2781 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2782 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (T(7 + 6) - T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2783 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (7 - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2784 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2785 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2786 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) + 6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2787 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2788 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) - (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2789 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2790 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2791 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2792 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(((7 + 6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2793 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2794 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6) - T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2795 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2795 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6)) - T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2796 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2796 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) - T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2797 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3) \times ((4 - 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2797 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2798 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2798 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2799 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T((3 \times 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2799 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times ((7 \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2800 &:= ((-1 + T(2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2800 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2801 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times 4) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2801 &:= (-9 + ((T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2802 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((T(4)/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2802 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) + 6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2803 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times ((T(4)/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2803 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 - 6) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2804 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + T(3)))/(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2804 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7) - 6) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2805 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 2805 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T(T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2806 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2806 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2807 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2807 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2808 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2808 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2809 &:= (-1 + (T(((2^{T(3)}) + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2809 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2810 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 2810 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2811 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) - (4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2811 &:= (-9 - ((8 - T(7)) \times (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2812 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 - (T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2812 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2813 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2813 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2814 &:= ((T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2814 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2815 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2815 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2816 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((3 + T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2816 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2817 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2817 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - T(((6 \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2818 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2818 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2819 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2819 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2820 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2820 &:= ((T((-9 + (8 \times 7)))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2821 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(3 + 4) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2821 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - (T(7) - T(6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2822 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2822 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2823 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2823 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) - (6 - T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2824 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(4)) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 2824 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2825 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T((T(T(4)) - T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2825 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2826 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2826 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7) - (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2827 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2827 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T((7 + 6 - 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2828 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2828 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7) - 6) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
2829 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2829 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2830 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2830 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
2831 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2831 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2832 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2832 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7) - 6)) \times (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
2833 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 2833 &:= (-9 - 8 + T(((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
2834 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 2834 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((T(7) + T(T(6))) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2835 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3^4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2836 &:= (-1+2 + ((3^4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2837 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2838 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2839 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2840 &:= (-1 + (T(T((T(2+3) - 4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2841 &:= (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2842 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2843 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2844 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2845 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2846 &:= (T((-1-2 + T((3 \times 4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
2847 &:= (-1-2 + T(((3+4) \times T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2848 &:= ((-1+2-3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2849 &:= (-1 + T((T(2+T(3)) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2850 &:= T(((((-1+2+3) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2851 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2852 &:= ((-1+2 + T((3^4))) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2853 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2854 &:= ((-1+2+3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2855 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + (3^4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2856 &:= (T((T((-1+2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2857 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2858 &:= (-1-2 + (T((3^4)) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2859 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2860 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2861 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2862 &:= (-1+2 + (T((3^4)) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2863 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2864 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2865 &:= (T(-1+2 \times 3) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2866 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) - 4)) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2867 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2868 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2869 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 \times T(3)) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2870 &:= ((-1+2 + (3^4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2871 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
2872 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2873 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2874 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2835 &:= ((-9 - T(8)) \times (7 \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2836 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2837 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2838 &:= (T(-9+8 + T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) + T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2839 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + 7) \times T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2840 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2841 &:= (-9 + T(((8+7) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2842 &:= (-9 + ((T((T(8+7) - 6))/5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2843 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (T(T(6)) - T(T((T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2844 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times T((T(7) - (6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2845 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2846 &:= ((T(-9+8+7) \times T((T(6) - 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2847 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2848 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(T(7))) - T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2849 &:= (-9+8 + T(((7+6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2850 &:= T((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2851 &:= (-9 + ((T(8+7) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2852 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7+6) + T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2853 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + 7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2854 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2855 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2856 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) - T(7+6)) \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2857 &:= (((-9-8) \times (T(7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2858 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2859 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + T(((6 \times T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2860 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2861 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2862 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7+6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2863 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T((7+6-5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2864 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7+6) - T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2865 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2866 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) - T(7+6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2867 &:= (((-9-8) \times (T(7) + T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
2868 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) \times (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2869 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (T(6 \times 5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2870 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2871 &:= (((-9+8) - T(7)) \times (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2872 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7+6) + T(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2873 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (T((6+T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2874 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 \times 7) + T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2875 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2875 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2876 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3) + (T(4) \times T(T(5)))))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 2876 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((7 \times (6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2877 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 2877 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2878 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + T((T(4+5)+6+7+8+9))) & 2878 &:= (-9 + (T((8+T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2879 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) \times (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 2879 &:= (-9+8 + (((T(7) \times 6) + T(T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2880 &:= (T((-1-2+T((3+4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) & 2880 &:= ((((-9 \times T(8)) - T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2881 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3+4)) + T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) & 2881 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((T(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2882 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) - (T(5)+6+7+8+9)) & 2882 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2883 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2883 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2884 &:= (-1 + (T((T((2+T(T(3))))/4) + (5+T(6+7+8+9)))) & 2884 &:= (-9 + (((T(8)+7) \times T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2885 &:= (T((-1-2+T((3 \times 4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 2885 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2886 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3) - (4 \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2886 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2887 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(T(3))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2887 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2888 &:= ((-1-2+T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2888 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2889 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2889 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (7 \times (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2890 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) + T(T(4)))))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2890 &:= (((-9+8 + T(7+6)) \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2891 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2891 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (7 - (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2892 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2892 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2893 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3+4) \times T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 2893 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2894 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2+3)) \times T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2894 &:= ((-9-8 + T(T(7+6))) - T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2895 &:= ((T((-1+2) \times (3+4))) \times T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 2895 &:= (T((-9-8 + T(7+6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2896 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2896 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2897 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(3+T(4)) - T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 2897 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2898 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2898 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2899 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2+3)) - 4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2899 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7+6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2900 &:= (-1 \times ((T(T(2+3)) - 4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2900 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2901 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) & 2901 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2902 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2902 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2903 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(4)) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2903 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((7 \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2904 &:= (T((-1+2 \times T(3))) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))) & 2904 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7+6) \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2905 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 2905 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (7 + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2906 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + (T(T((T(T(4)))/5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 2906 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + (T(7) - (6+5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2907 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 2907 &:= (T((-9-8 + T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2908 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2908 &:= ((-9-8 + T((T(7) + T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2909 &:= (-1 + (((2^{T(3)}) \times T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 2909 &:= (-9-8 + T((T(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2910 &:= (((-1-2+T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2910 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times T(7))) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2911 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 2911 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2912 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 2912 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2913 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 2913 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(8) \times 7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2914 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 2914 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7+6))) - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2915 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
2916 &:= (T((-1+2 \times T(3))) + T((T(4+5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
2917 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(3))+T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
2918 &:= (T((-1+2+T((3 \times 4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
2919 &:= (-1 - (((2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2920 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2921 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T((T(T(4))+T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
2922 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
2923 &:= (T((-1+2+(3^4))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2924 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3+4)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2925 &:= (-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2926 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2927 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T((T(4+5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2928 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4+5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
2929 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2930 &:= (((-1+T(T(2 \times 3))) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2931 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2932 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
2933 &:= (T((-1+2+(3^4))) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2934 &:= ((-1+T((T(2+3)+T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2935 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2936 &:= T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
2937 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2938 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2939 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2940 &:= ((-1+T(2+3)) \times T((T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2941 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3)) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2942 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(3))+T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2943 &:= (T((-1+2+(3^4))) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2944 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (T((T(T(4))+T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2945 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (T((T(T(4))+T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2946 &:= (-1+2+((T((T(T(3))+T(4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2947 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(T(3)+4)) + T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
2948 &:= (-1 + ((T((2+T(T(3)))) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2949 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times ((3+4) \times 5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2950 &:= (((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
2951 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2952 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2953 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T((T(T(4))+T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2954 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T((T(T(4))+T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2915 &:= (((-9+8+T(T(7))) \times (6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2916 &:= (-9 \times ((8+T(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2917 &:= (-9 + T((T(8 \times 7)/(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2918 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + T((T(6+5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
2919 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + T((T(6+5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
2920 &:= ((-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(7+6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2921 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((7 \times (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
2922 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2923 &:= (-9 + (T((8+T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2924 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2925 &:= (-9+8+T((T(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2926 &:= T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2927 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2928 &:= ((-9 + T(((8-7) + T(6)))) \times (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
2929 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7+6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2930 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2931 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2932 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 \times 7)/T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2933 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2934 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2935 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(((7 \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2936 &:= (T((-9+8+(7 \times (6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2937 &:= (-9-8+(T(7) + T((T(6+5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
2938 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) - T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2939 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) \times (T(6) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2940 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2941 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2942 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8)))/(7+6) - T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2943 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times (T(7) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2944 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7+6)) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2945 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7+6) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2946 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2947 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + T((T(6+5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
2948 &:= (T((-9-8+(T(7) + T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
2949 &:= (T(T((-9+(8+(7+6)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2950 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (T(7) - T(6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
2951 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2952 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (7 \times 6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
2953 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2954 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7+6) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2955 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2956 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((3+4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2957 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2958 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2959 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2960 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times 3) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2961 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2962 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
2963 &:= (-1 - (T((2 + T(T(3)))) - T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
2964 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
2965 &:= (T(((-1 + 2 + T(3)) \times T(4))) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2966 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - ((4^5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2967 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2968 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2969 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
2970 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2971 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2972 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2973 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) - (4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
2974 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2975 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times 4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2976 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
2977 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3^4) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2978 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) - T(5+6+7+8+9) \\
2979 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (4^5))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
2980 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
2981 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2982 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
2983 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
2984 &:= (-1 + ((T(T((2 - (3 - 4)))) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2985 &:= ((T((T(-1+2+3) - 4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
2986 &:= (((-1 + 2 + T(3))^4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
2987 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2988 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2989 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
2990 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) \times T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9) \\
2991 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9) \\
2992 &:= ((-1 - T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2993 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
2994 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
2955 &:= (-9 - (T((8 + T(7))) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2956 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times (T(T(6)) + 5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2957 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2958 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((7 \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
2959 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(T(7) - 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2960 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
2961 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
2962 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2963 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7+6) - T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2964 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(7+6) - T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2965 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7+6))) \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2966 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7+6)))) - T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2967 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7)) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2968 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((7 \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2969 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7+6-5) - T(4+3+2+1) \\
2970 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
2971 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
2972 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(((7+6) + T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2973 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((T(7) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2974 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2975 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7) - 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2976 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T((7 \times (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1) \\
2977 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
2978 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1) \\
2979 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2980 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8))/7) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
2981 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1) \\
2982 &:= ((-9 - ((8+7) \times 6)) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2983 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2984 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7) + 6) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1) \\
2985 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
2986 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((7 \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2987 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
2988 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2989 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2990 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7+6) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
2991 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (T(7) \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
2992 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((7 \times (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1) \\
2993 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
2994 &:= (-9 + T(((8 \times 7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2995 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3))^{T(4)/5}) - (6+7+8+9)) \\ 2996 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\ 2997 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 2998 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 2999 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3000 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3001 &:= ((-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4)+5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\ 3002 &:= (-1 + T((2 - (3 \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\ 3003 &:= ((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 3004 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 3005 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3006 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + T((T(T(T(4))))/(5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 3007 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\ 3008 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\ 3009 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(3)+4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3010 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\ 3011 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3012 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3013 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3014 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3015 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3016 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3017 &:= (((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4))/5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\ 3018 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\ 3019 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\ 3020 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 \times T(3+4)) + T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\ 3021 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3022 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(3 \times 4)) + 5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\ 3023 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 3024 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\ 3025 &:= ((-1 - T(T(2+3))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 3026 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4))) - T(T((T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3027 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((3 \times 4)))) - T(T((T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\ 3028 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\ 3029 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 3030 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + T(4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\ 3031 &:= (((-1+2+T(3))^4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 3032 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\ 3033 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2995 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T(((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 2996 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((7 \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\ 2997 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8)))/(7+6) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 2998 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - T(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\ 2999 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\ 3000 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 3001 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 \times (T(6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\ 3002 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7+6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3003 &:= T(((((-9+8) - (7 \times 6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 3004 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3005 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + T(T(7))) \times (6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 3006 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3007 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7+6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 3008 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 3009 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 \times 7) + T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 3010 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\ 3011 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) - (7 - T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 3012 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((7 \times (6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\ 3013 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + T(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\ 3014 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\ 3015 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3016 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7+6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3017 &:= ((-9 + T(T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\ 3018 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(7) - 6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 3019 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3020 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((7 \times (6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3021 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 3022 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\ 3023 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3024 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3025 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) - (6+5))) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\ 3026 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(((8 + (7+6)) - T(5)))))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\ 3027 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - 7 - 6) \times (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3028 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((T(7) - T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\ 3029 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3030 &:= (((-9+8) - (T(7) - T(T(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\ 3031 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((T(7) - T(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\ 3032 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7+6) - 5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\ 3033 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7) - 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3034 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3035 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3036 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3037 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3038 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3039 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3040 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3041 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3042 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3043 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3044 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3045 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3046 &:= (T(T(((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3047 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3048 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3049 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3050 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + T(T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3051 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3052 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T((3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3053 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3054 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3055 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3056 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + T(T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3057 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3058 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3059 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3060 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3061 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3062 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3063 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3064 &:= -1 - (T(2 + 3) - T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3065 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3066 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - T(T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3067 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3068 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3069 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3070 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3071 &:= (T(T(((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3072 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3073 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3034 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6 - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3035 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3036 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3037 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 \times 7)/T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3038 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3039 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3040 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3041 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3042 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3043 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - T(6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3044 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((T(7) - T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3045 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((T(7) - T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3046 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3047 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3048 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3049 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + 6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3050 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3051 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3052 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3053 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3054 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3055 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (((7 + 6) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3056 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3057 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3058 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3059 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3060 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3061 &:= ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3062 &:= ((-9 + T(T((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3063 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3064 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T((T(7) + 6 + 5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3065 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - T((T(6) + (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3066 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3067 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7 - 6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3068 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3069 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7))) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3070 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3071 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3072 &:= (-9 + T((T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3073 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3074 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3075 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T(4+5))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
3076 &:= ((-1+2+(3 \times T(T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3077 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(T(3)))+T(T(4))))+(5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3078 &:= (-1-2+T((3+(T(4+5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
3079 &:= (-1+((T(2 \times T(3))+T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3080 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3081 &:= T((-1+(T(T(2 \times T(3)))/(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3082 &:= (-1+2+T((3+(T(4+5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
3083 &:= (-1+2) \times 3 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3084 &:= (-1+(T((2^{T(3)})))+(T(T(4+5))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
3085 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4))))+(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9) \\
3086 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (T(T(3))+T(T(T(4))))))-(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3087 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3)-T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3088 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3))-T(T(T(4)))-(5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3089 &:= (-1-((2-((3+4) \times T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3090 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
3091 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4))))+T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3092 &:= (-1+(T(((2+T(3)) \times (4+5))))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3093 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3))))+(T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3094 &:= -1+T(2+3)+T(T(T(4)))+T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3095 &:= (-1+(T(T(2 \times T(3))))+(T(4+5)-(6+7+8+9))) \\
3096 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3-T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3097 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((3 \times 4))))-(T(5)-(6+7+8+9))) \\
3098 &:= (-1-((2 \times (3-T(T(T(4)))))+(5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3099 &:= (-1-((2+3) \times (T(4)-T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3100 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (T(4)-T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3101 &:= ((-1+T(T(2 \times T(3))))-((4+5)-(6+7+8+9))) \\
3102 &:= (-1-2+(3 \times T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3103 &:= (-1 \times 2+(3 \times T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3104 &:= (-1-((2+(3+4)) \times (T(T(5))-T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3105 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3106 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3107 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4)+T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3108 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3))-T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3109 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3-T(T(T(4)))))+5+6+7+8+9) \\
3110 &:= ((-1+T((2+(T(T(3)) \times 4))))-T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3111 &:= ((-1+T(T(2 \times T(3))))-(4-(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3112 &:= (-1+2+(T(T((3+4+5))))+6+7+8+9) \\
3113 &:= (-1-2+(T(T((3 \times 4))))+5+6+7+8+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3074 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7+6))-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3075 &:= ((-9 \times T(((8+T(7))-6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3076 &:= (-9 - (T((8+T(7)))) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3077 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7+6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3078 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times T(7)) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3079 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + T(((7+6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3080 &:= (T(T((T(-9+8+7) - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3081 &:= T(T((-9 + ((8-7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3082 &:= (-9 + (T(T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
3083 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3084 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3085 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((7 \times (6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3086 &:= ((-9+T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3087 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 \times 6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3088 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3089 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T((7+T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3090 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + T(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3091 &:= (-9-8+(T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3092 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3093 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(T(6)))))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3094 &:= (((-9+8)-7) + (T(6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3095 &:= ((-9+T(8)) - ((7+6) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3096 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))))) + (5+4+3+2+1) \\
3097 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (T(7+6) - 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3098 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3099 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3100 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) - 7) \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3101 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7+6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3102 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3103 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3104 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3105 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3106 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3107 &:= (-9+8+(T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3108 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3109 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7-6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3110 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3111 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (T(7) + 6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3112 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
3113 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3114 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3115 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3116 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
3117 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3118 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (4 + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
3119 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3120 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3121 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3122 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3123 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3124 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3125 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((3 \times 4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3126 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3127 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3128 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
3129 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3130 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3131 &:= ((-1+2 + T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) - 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3132 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3133 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times T(T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
3134 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + T(3+4)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3135 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
3136 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times T(T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
3137 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3138 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3139 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T((3-4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3140 &:= ((-1+2 - T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3141 &:= (T((T((-1+2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3142 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (4 + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3143 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3144 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3145 &:= (T((-1+2+3) \times T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3146 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3147 &:= ((-1-2) - ((3+4) \times (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3148 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3+4) \times (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3149 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3+4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3150 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3+4))) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3151 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3152 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T(3+T(4)))) - T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3153 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3114 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 \times 7) + T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3115 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3116 &:= ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3117 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7+6))) - (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3118 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3119 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T((7+T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3120 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) - 7+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3121 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3122 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times 6)) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3123 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times ((7 \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3124 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3125 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3126 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3127 &:= (-9 + (T(T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3128 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3129 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3130 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7+6) \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3131 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3132 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7+6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3133 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3134 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (7 - (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3135 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3136 &:= (T((-9 - (8 - 7)) + T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3137 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7+6))) - (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3138 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3139 &:= ((-9+8) - ((T(T(7)) - (6 \times T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3140 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + 7)) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3141 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3142 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (T(7+6) - 5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3143 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7+6) - (T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3144 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3145 &:= (T((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3146 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3147 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7+6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3148 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3149 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3150 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7)) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3151 &:= (-9 + T((8 - (T(7) + (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3152 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3153 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(((7 \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3194 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((3 \times (4 \times 5)))))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3194 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3195 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((3 \times 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3195 &:= ((-9 - T(8)) \times (T(7) + (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3196 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3196 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3197 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 3197 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3198 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3198 &:= (-9 + (T(8 + 7) + (6 + T(T((T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
3199 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3199 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7 + 6) + T(T((T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
3200 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3200 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 - T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3201 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + T((T(T(T(4))) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3201 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3202 &:= -1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3202 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3203 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3203 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3204 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3204 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3205 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times 3)) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3205 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3206 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + T((T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3206 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) - 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3207 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3207 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3208 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3208 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 + T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3209 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T((3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3209 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3210 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 + T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3210 &:= (((-9 - T((8 + T(7)))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3211 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3211 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3212 &:= ((-1 - T(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3212 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) + T(7))) \times (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3213 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3213 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7 \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3214 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T((3 \times 4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3214 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3215 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (T(4) \times 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3215 &:= (T((-9 + ((T(8) - T(7)) \times (6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3216 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3216 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3217 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3217 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3218 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times T(3))) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3218 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3219 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(T(3))) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3219 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3220 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3220 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3221 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3)^4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3221 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3222 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3222 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7 + 6) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3223 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3223 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3224 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 3224 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T((7 + T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3225 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3225 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3226 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4)) + (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3226 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3227 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3227 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3228 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3228 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3229 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3229 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(((7 + 6) + T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3230 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3230 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3231 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3231 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3232 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3232 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3233 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3233 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3234 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3235 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3236 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3237 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3) + 4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3238 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3239 &:= (-1 + T((T((2 + (3 + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3240 &:= T(((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3241 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{T(T(3))}) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3242 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (4 \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3243 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3244 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3 + 4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3245 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (4 + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3246 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3247 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3248 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3249 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4)) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3250 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(3 + 4))) \times T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3251 &:= T((-1 + 2) \times 3 + T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3252 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 + T(T(4)))) + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3253 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3254 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(3 + T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3255 &:= ((-1 + 2 - (3 - (4 + 5))) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3256 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3257 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3258 &:= (T(((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3259 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3260 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + 4))) \times T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3261 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3262 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3263 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(3^4))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3264 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T(3 \times 4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3265 &:= (T(((-1 + T(2 \times 3)) \times 4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3266 &:= (T((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3267 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3268 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
3269 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T(3 + 4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3270 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 + T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3271 &:= (T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3272 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3273 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3234 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times T(T(6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3235 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3236 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) \times (6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3237 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 + 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3238 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3239 &:= (-9 + (8 \times T((7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3240 &:= T(((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3241 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3242 &:= (-9 + (T(((T(T(8)) - T(7))/(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3243 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3244 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3245 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3246 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3247 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3248 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3249 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3250 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3251 &:= (T((((-9 + 8) - 7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3252 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3253 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (T(6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3254 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T((7 + T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3255 &:= (-9 - ((T((8 + T(7))) \times 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3256 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))))) + (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3257 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 + 7) + T(6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3258 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3259 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3260 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3261 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3262 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3263 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + ((6 \times 5)/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3264 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3265 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3266 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8))/(7 - (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3267 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 - 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3268 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3269 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
3270 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3271 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(7 + 6))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3272 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3273 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3274 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T((3 \times 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3275 &:= (T(((-1 + T(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3276 &:= (T((-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3277 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3278 &:= T(-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3279 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (4 + T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3280 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T((T(4) \times 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3281 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3282 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3283 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((3^4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3284 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((3^4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3285 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3286 &:= (T((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3287 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((3^4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3288 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3289 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3290 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3291 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3292 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3293 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + T(3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3294 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - ((T(4) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3295 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3296 &:= ((-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3297 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3298 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - ((T(4) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3299 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times (3 + 4))) + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3300 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3301 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(3) + (4 - T(T(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3302 &:= -1 - (2 \times T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3303 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((T(4) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3304 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - ((T(4) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3305 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(((3 \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3306 &:= (T((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3307 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3^4)) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3308 &:= -1 - 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3309 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3310 &:= T(T(T((-1) + 2 + 3)) + T(4 + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3311 &:= -1 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3312 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3313 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3274 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3275 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3276 &:= (((-9 - T(T(8))) \times 7) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3277 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3278 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3279 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3280 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 + 6) \times (T(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3281 &:= ((-9 + T((8 + T(7 + 6)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3282 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3283 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3284 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3285 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7) - 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3286 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3287 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3288 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3289 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3290 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3291 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8) - 7) + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3292 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3293 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3294 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3295 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3296 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(T(6))) - (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3297 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - 7) \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3298 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3299 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (7 - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3300 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3301 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) - (T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3302 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3303 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(T(7)))) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3304 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T((T(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3305 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3306 &:= (T((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3307 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8) - 7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3308 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3309 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3310 &:= (T((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3311 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3312 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3313 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3314 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) - T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3315 &:= (T((-1-2+T((3+4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3316 &:= (-1+2+(T((3 \times (T(4)+T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3317 &:= (T(((((-1+2) \times 3)^4)) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3318 &:= ((-1+2+T(3)) \times ((4+5)+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3319 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + (T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
3320 &:= (-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3321 &:= T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) - (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3322 &:= (-1+2+T((T(3) + (T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
3323 &:= (T(T(((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3324 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3325 &:= ((T((-1+T(2+3))) - T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3326 &:= (-1+2+(T((3^4)) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3327 &:= ((-1-2+(T(3+4) \times T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3328 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3+4) \times T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3329 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) - (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3330 &:= ((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) - (4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
3331 &:= (T((-1-2+(T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3332 &:= ((-1+T(T(2+3))) \times T((T(4 \times 5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3333 &:= T(-1+2+T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3334 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((3^4))) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3335 &:= ((-1+T((2+(3^4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3336 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3337 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3338 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3339 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3340 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (4 \times (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3341 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + ((T(4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3342 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3343 &:= ((-1-2+T((3^4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3344 &:= (-1 + (((2^{T(3)}) \times T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3345 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3346 &:= (T(((((-1+2) \times 3)^4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3347 &:= ((-1+2+T((3^4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3348 &:= (T((-1+T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3349 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T((T(3) + T(4)))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3350 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3351 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((3+T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3352 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
3353 &:= (-1-2+(T((3^4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3314 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T((T(7+6) - T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3315 &:= (((-9 - (8-7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3316 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3317 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3318 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3319 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3320 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7) + T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3321 &:= T((T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3322 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3323 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3324 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8) - 7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3325 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(7+6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3326 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3328 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3329 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3330 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - T((7 + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3331 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3332 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3333 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(7))) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3334 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3335 &:= (((((-9+8) - 7) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3336 &:= (T((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3337 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3338 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3339 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3340 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((7 + T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3341 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3342 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + T((T(6) + (5 + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3343 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3344 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3345 &:= ((((-9+8) - 7) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3346 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3347 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3348 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 + T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3349 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3350 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3351 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3352 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3353 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7)))) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3354 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((3^4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3354 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3355 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (T((4 \times T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3355 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) - T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3356 &:= (T(((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3356 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))))) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3357 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3^4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3357 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(6) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3358 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3358 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(((7 + 6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3359 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3359 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3360 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3360 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3361 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3361 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3362 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3362 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) - 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3363 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + 4)))/5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3363 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - ((6 \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3364 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)))/5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3364 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3365 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) + (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3365 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3366 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3366 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3367 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3367 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3368 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3368 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 + T(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3369 &:= (((-1 \times T(T(T(2 + 3))))/T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3369 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3370 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3370 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3371 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4)) + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 3371 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3372 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times T(T(5)))))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3372 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3373 &:= (T((-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4)) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3373 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3374 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(4 \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3374 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3375 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3375 &:= ((T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3376 &:= (T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3376 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8))/(7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3377 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3377 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3378 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3378 &:= (((-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3379 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3) + 4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3379 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3380 &:= (((-1 + T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3380 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3381 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3381 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T((7 \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3382 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3382 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3383 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3383 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(T(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3384 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T((T(T(4)))/5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3384 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3385 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3385 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3386 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((3 + T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3386 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3387 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3387 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3388 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3388 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3389 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 + T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3389 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3390 &:= ((T(((1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3390 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) - T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3391 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((3 + 4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3391 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3392 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3 + T(4)) - T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3392 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3393 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3393 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3394 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3395 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3396 &:= (T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3397 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3398 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T((T(3) + T(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3399 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3400 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T((4 \times T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3401 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T((T(3) + T(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3402 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3403 &:= T((-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3404 &:= (-1 + (T(((2^{T(3)}) + T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3405 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3406 &:= (T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3407 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3408 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((3^4)) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3409 &:= ((T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3410 &:= (-1 \times (T((T(2 + 3) + 4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3411 &:= (T(((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3412 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3^4)) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3413 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3414 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3415 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) + (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3416 &:= T(-1 + 2 \times T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3417 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3418 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3419 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3420 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3421 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3422 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3423 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3424 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3425 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3426 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3427 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3428 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + T(3))) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3429 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + T(3))) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3430 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3431 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3432 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3433 &:= (T((-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4))) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3394 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3395 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3396 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3397 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3398 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + T(6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3399 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8) - 7) - 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3400 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3401 &:= ((-9 + (T((8 + (7 + 6))) \times T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3402 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3403 &:= T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3404 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3405 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7) + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3406 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3407 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3408 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (7 + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3409 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3410 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(7 + 6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3411 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3412 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3413 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (7 - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3414 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((7 + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3415 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3416 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3417 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T((T(7 + 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3418 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3419 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3420 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3421 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3422 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3423 &:= (-9 - (((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3424 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3425 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) - 7 + 6) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3426 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3427 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (7 + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3428 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3429 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3430 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3431 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + (T(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3432 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3433 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3434 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3) \times (4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3435 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3436 &:= (T(((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4)) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3437 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3438 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3439 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times (T(T(3)) - 4))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3440 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3441 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3442 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3443 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T((3 \times 4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3444 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(((T(T(4)))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3445 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3446 &:= (T(((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4)) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3447 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3448 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3449 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3450 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3451 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3452 &:= (((-1 - T(2 + T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3453 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3454 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3455 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4)) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3456 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((3 + T(T(4)))))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3457 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(3 \times 4)) + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3458 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3459 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3460 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (4 \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3461 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3462 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3463 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3464 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) \times (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3465 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3466 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3467 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3468 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) - (4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3469 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3470 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3471 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3472 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3473 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3434 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3435 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + T((6 + T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3436 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3437 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3438 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times T(T(7))) - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3439 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3440 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3441 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3442 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3443 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3444 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3445 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) - 7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3446 &:= ((-9 + (T((8 + (7 + 6))) \times T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3447 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T((7 + T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3448 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3449 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6) - T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3450 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T((7 + T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3451 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3452 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3453 &:= (T((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3454 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6)) + (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3455 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3456 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3457 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3458 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3459 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3460 &:= ((((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3461 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3462 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((7 + T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3463 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3464 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3465 &:= (T(T(((-9 + 8 + T(7)) - T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3466 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3467 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3468 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3469 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((7 + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3470 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3471 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3472 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3473 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3474 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3474 &:= (-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3475 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3475 &:= ((T(T((-9 + 8 + T(7)) - T(6))) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3476 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + 3)) + (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3476 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3477 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3477 &:= (-9 + T(((8 \times T(7)) - (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3478 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3478 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (((7 + 6) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3479 &:= ((T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3479 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3480 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((3 \times 4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3480 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (T(T(7)) + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3481 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3481 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3482 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3482 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3483 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(3 + 4) + T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 3483 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3484 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) \times T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3484 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3485 &:= (-1 + T(((2 \times (T(3) \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3485 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3486 &:= T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3486 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3487 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(3 + 4) + T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 3487 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3488 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3488 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3489 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) - (T(4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3489 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3490 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3490 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3491 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((3 + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3491 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 + 7)/6) \times (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3492 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3492 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3493 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3493 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3494 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3494 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3495 &:= (((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) \times T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3495 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3496 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3496 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3497 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3497 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3498 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3498 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3499 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3499 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3500 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3500 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3501 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3501 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3502 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 3502 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3503 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3503 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3504 &:= (((-1 - 2) - T(T(3))) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3504 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3505 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3505 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7 + 6) - T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3506 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3506 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3507 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3507 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3508 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3508 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - (T(6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3509 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3509 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8))/7) \times T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3510 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((T(3) - T(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3510 &:= ((-9 - T(8)) \times ((7 \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3511 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3511 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3512 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3512 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3513 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3513 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T(T(7)))) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3514 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3 \times 4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3515 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + T(3))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3516 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3517 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3 \times 4) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3518 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + T(3))) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3519 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + T(3))) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3520 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (3^4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3521 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3522 &:= (-1 \times (T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3523 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T((3 \times 4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3524 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3525 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - T(4))) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3526 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times T((4 + T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3527 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) - (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3528 &:= ((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times (T(4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3529 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) + (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3530 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3531 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + 4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3532 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3)) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3533 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3534 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3535 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3536 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3537 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4^5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3538 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3539 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(((T(3) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3540 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3541 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3542 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3543 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((3 + 4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3544 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((3 + 4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3545 &:= (-1 + (T(T((T(2 \times 3) - (4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3546 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3547 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((3 + 4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3548 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3549 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3550 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3551 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3552 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - T(T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3553 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3514 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3515 &:= ((-9 - (T(T(8)) + (7 + T(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3516 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3517 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3518 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3519 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3520 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3521 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3522 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) + T(T((T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3523 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3524 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3525 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3526 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3527 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3528 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T(T(7)))) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3529 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3530 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3531 &:= (T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3532 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((7 + T(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3533 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - 6))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3534 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T((7 + T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3535 &:= (((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + T(6)) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3536 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3537 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7 + 6) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3538 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3539 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((T(T(7)) - 6) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3540 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7) - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3541 &:= (T((T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3542 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3543 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(7) - 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3544 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3545 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3546 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) - T(7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3547 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3548 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7) + (T(6) + T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3549 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3550 &:= ((-9 + (T((8 \times (7 + 6)))/T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3551 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3552 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + T((T(6) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3553 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3554 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3554 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3555 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times 3) + T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3555 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3556 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3556 &:= (T((T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) - T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3557 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3557 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3558 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3558 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3559 &:= ((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3559 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 + T(T(6))) \times T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3560 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3560 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3561 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - T(T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3561 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3562 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3562 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7 + 6) \times T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3563 &:= (T(((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3563 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T((6 + T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3564 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3^4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3564 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 \times T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3565 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3565 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3566 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3566 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) - T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3567 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times T(T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3567 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((7 + T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3568 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times T(T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3568 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3569 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times (3 + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3569 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3570 &:= T(((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3570 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3571 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times T(T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3571 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3572 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) + (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3572 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3573 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3573 &:= (-9 + ((8 - T(T(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3574 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) + (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3574 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8))/7) \times T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3575 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (T(4) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3575 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T(6 + 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3576 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3576 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times T(T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3577 &:= (((-1 + 2 - T(T(T(3))))/T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3577 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((7 + T(6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3578 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3578 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3579 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3579 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3580 &:= ((-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3580 &:= (((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + 6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3581 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(3) + T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3581 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3582 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3582 &:= (-9 \times (8 - T((7 + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3583 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3583 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((T(7 + 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3584 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3584 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + ((T(6) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3585 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3585 &:= ((T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3586 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3586 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3587 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3587 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3588 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3588 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + T(T(7))) - 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3589 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(3) \times T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3589 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3590 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3590 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3591 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 3591 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3592 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 3592 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3593 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 3593 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3594 &:= ((-1+2-(3+4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3594 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3595 &:= ((T((-1+2 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 3595 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7+6) \times (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3596 &:= (((-1 - T(2+3))/4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3596 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (T(7) + T(6)))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3597 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(3)+4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3597 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + T(T(6)))))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3598 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3)+4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3598 &:= ((-9+8) - ((T(T(7)) \times (6 - T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3599 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times 3+4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3599 &:= (-9+8 + (((T(T(7)) + 6) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3600 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)) - (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 3600 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - T(7)))/6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3601 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3)+4+5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3601 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3602 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 3602 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3603 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 3603 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3604 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times 3) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 3604 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3605 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 3605 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3606 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 3606 &:= ((-9 \times T(T((8-7+6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3607 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3607 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3608 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3+4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3608 &:= ((((-9+8) - T(T(7))) \times (6 - T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3609 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3609 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3610 &:= (T((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3610 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) - (T(7) - (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3611 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3611 &:= (T((-9 + (T(T(8+7))/T(6+5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3612 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3612 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3613 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3613 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3614 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + (4 + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3614 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((T(7+6) - 5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3615 &:= (T((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3615 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3616 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3616 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3617 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) - (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3617 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3618 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + (4 + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3618 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3619 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times 4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3619 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7)) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3620 &:= (T((-1+2 + (T(T(3)) \times 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 3620 &:= ((-9 - (8-7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3621 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) - 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3621 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + 6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3622 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3)^4 + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 3622 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3623 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3623 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3624 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) \times T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 3624 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3625 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((3+4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 3625 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3626 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3+4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3626 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) - (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3627 &:= ((-1-2) - (((3-4) - T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3627 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) - (T(T(7+6)) - T(T(5))))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
3628 &:= (T((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3628 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7+6) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3629 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) - (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3629 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3630 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 3630 &:= ((-9-8 + (T(7) + T(T(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3631 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (4^5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 3631 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7+6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3632 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3632 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3633 &:= (T((-1+T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 3633 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - (T((6 \times T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3634 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3635 &:= ((T(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4))) \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3636 &:= (T((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3637 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3638 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3639 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3640 &:= ((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3641 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3642 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3^4) \times (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3643 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3644 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (3 + 4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3645 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3646 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times T(3))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3647 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 + T(3)) \times 4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3648 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3649 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3650 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3651 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - 4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3652 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(((T(3) \times T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3653 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3654 &:= (-1 + T((T((2 + 3 + T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3655 &:= T((T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3656 &:= (((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3657 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - T((4 + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3658 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3659 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3660 &:= ((-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3661 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3662 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3663 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3664 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3665 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3666 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) / T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3667 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3668 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3669 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3670 &:= (T(((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(4))) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3671 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + T((4 \times T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3672 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times T((4 + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3673 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3634 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3635 &:= ((T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) \times 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3636 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3637 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3638 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3639 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3640 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(7))) \times T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3641 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3642 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + 6))) + T(T((T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3643 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5)) / T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3644 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3645 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - 7) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3646 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3647 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7 + 6) - T(T((T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3648 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3649 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3650 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3651 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8) - 7) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3652 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T(6) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3653 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3654 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3655 &:= T(((-9 + 8) - (T(7) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3656 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3657 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3658 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3659 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((T(7 + 6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3660 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 - 7) + T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3661 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) + T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3662 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T((T(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3663 &:= (((-9 + 8) - T(T(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3664 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3665 &:= (T(((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6)) - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3666 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times T(7)) + T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3667 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3668 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(((7 + 6) \times 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3669 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(7 + 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3670 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3671 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + 6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3672 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times T((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3673 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - T(T(7))) \times (6 - T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3674 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3675 &:= (T(((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3676 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3677 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3678 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3679 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times 4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3680 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3681 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3682 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3683 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3684 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3685 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3 + 4) + T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3686 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3 + 4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3687 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3 + 4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3688 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3689 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3690 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3691 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3692 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3693 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3694 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3) \times T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3695 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3696 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) \times ((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3697 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3698 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3699 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((T(T(4)) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3700 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3701 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3702 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(((T(3) + T(4)) \times 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3703 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3704 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
3705 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + (T(T(3)) \times 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3706 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times T(3)))) - (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3707 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3708 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3709 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3710 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3711 &:= (T(T(((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3712 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3713 &:= (-1 - (T(T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3674 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3675 &:= (T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3676 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) + T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3677 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3678 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3679 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3680 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3681 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3682 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3683 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3684 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3685 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3686 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3687 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3688 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3689 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3690 &:= ((T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3691 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 + T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3692 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3693 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3694 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3695 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((7 + T(6)) \times (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3696 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3697 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3698 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))))) - (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3699 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3700 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 + 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3701 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3702 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3703 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3704 &:= ((-9 + T((8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3705 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3706 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3707 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3708 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3709 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3710 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3711 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((T(7 + 6) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3712 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3713 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3714 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3715 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + T(T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3716 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3717 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3) \times (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3718 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) \times (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3719 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3720 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3721 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3) \times (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3722 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3723 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3724 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3725 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3726 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3727 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3728 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3729 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3730 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3731 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3732 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3733 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) - ((4 - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3734 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + ((4 + T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3735 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3736 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3737 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3738 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + (T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3739 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + (T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3740 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times (T(3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3741 &:= T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3742 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + (T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3743 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3744 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3745 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3746 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3747 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3)) + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3748 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (3^4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3749 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3750 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) + T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
3751 &:= ((-1 - T(T(2 + 3))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3752 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3753 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3714 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T((T(7 + 6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3715 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3716 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3717 &:= (-9 - ((8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3718 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3719 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T((7 + T(6))) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3720 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3721 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) + T(7 + 6)) \times 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3722 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3723 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3724 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7 + 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3725 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 + 6) \times T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3726 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) \times 7) - T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3727 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3728 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3729 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3730 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7 + 6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3731 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3732 &:= (-9 + T(((8 - (7 \times 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3733 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3734 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
3735 &:= ((-9 - T(8)) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3736 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3737 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3738 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3739 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3740 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3741 &:= T(((9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3742 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3743 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3744 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3745 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7 + 6)) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
3746 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9 + 8 + 7))/T(6)))) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3747 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3748 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) - (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3749 &:= -9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) - T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3750 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3751 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3752 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7 + 6) + T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3753 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3754 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) \times (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3754 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3755 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3755 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + T(6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3756 &:= ((-1-2-3) \times (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3756 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7)+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3757 &:= (-1+2 - (T(3) \times (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3757 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3758 &:= (((-1+T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3758 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7+6) - 5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3759 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((T(3) - T(4)) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 3759 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1) \\
3760 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3+4))) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) & 3760 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7+6) - T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3761 &:= (T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3761 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3762 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 3762 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - 7)) \times (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3763 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((T(3) \times T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3763 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) \times T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))) \\
3764 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3764 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (7 - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3765 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 3765 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3766 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times 4) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 3766 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) + T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3767 &:= ((-1-2) - (T((T(T(3)) + 4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3767 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3768 &:= ((-1-2+T((3^4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 3768 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7+6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3769 &:= (-1 - (T((T(2+3) + T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 3769 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times 6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3770 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (T(3+4) + T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 3770 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3771 &:= (T((-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3)) + T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) & 3771 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3772 &:= ((-1+2+T((3^4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 3772 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3773 &:= ((-1-2+T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3773 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3774 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3774 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3775 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(T(3)) \times 4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 3775 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times T(6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3776 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3776 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) + T(7+6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3777 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3777 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3778 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T((T(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 3778 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3779 &:= (-1 + (T((2 - (3 - 4))) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 3779 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3780 &:= ((T(-1+2+3) - 4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 3780 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3781 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3+4)) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))))) & 3781 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3782 &:= ((-1+2+T((3^4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) & 3782 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3783 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 3783 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T(((7 \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3784 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 3784 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3785 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+T(3)) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 3785 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3786 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 3786 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3787 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 3787 &:= (-9 + (T((T(T(8) + 7)/(6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3788 &:= (-1-2 + (T((3^4)) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 3788 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3789 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 3789 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1) \\
3790 &:= (T((-1+2+T((3 \times 4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 3790 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((T(7) + ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3791 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)))))) - T(5+6+7+8+9) & 3791 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7) + 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3792 &:= (-1+2 + (T((3^4)) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 3792 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3793 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 3793 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3794 &:= (-1 - ((T(2+3) - 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3795 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times (T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3796 &:= (-1+2 - ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3797 &:= ((-1+T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3798 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3+4)))/5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3799 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4))/5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3800 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3801 &:= (-1-2 + (T(3) \times (4+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3802 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (4+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3803 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3804 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4+T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3805 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) \times (4+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3806 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3807 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3808 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3809 &:= (-1 + (T(((2+3) \times 4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3810 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9) \\
3811 &:= (-1+2 + (((3+4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3812 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3813 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3+4) - T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3814 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times 3))) + (4 + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3815 &:= (((-1+T(T(2+3))) - T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3816 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3817 &:= (-1 + (T(((2+T(T(3))) \times 4) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3818 &:= (-1 - (T((2+T(T(3)))) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3819 &:= (-1 \times (T((2+T(T(3)))) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3820 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3821 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) - (T(4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3822 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3823 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3+4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3824 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) \times (T(4 \times 5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3825 &:= ((T((-1+2) \times (3+4))) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
3826 &:= (-1+2 + ((T(3+4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3827 &:= (-1+T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3828 &:= T(((((-1-2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3829 &:= (-1+2+T((3 \times (4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3830 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T((2 - (3 - 4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3831 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2+3) - 4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3832 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T((T(4) + 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3833 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (4 + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3794 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3795 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3796 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + 6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3797 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3798 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3799 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3800 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((T(7) + T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3801 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3802 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3803 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3804 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(8) + T(7)) \times 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3805 &:= ((T(-9+T(8))/7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3806 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3807 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7+6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3808 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3809 &:= (-9 + (T(((8-7) + T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3810 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3811 &:= (-9-8 + T(((7 \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3812 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3813 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3814 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times 6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3815 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3816 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7+6) - T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3817 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3818 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3819 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3820 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) - (7 - (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3821 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7) + T(6)) \times T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3822 &:= (((-9+T((8+T(7)))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3823 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3824 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times T(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3825 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) - 7) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3826 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3827 &:= (-9+8 + T(((7 \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3828 &:= T((T(-9-8+T(7)) + (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3829 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7+6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3830 &:= ((-9 - (T(T(8)) + T(7+6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3831 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) + T(7+6)) \times 5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3832 &:= (((-9+T((8+T(7)))) \times 6) - (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3833 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3874 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3875 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3876 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3877 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3878 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3879 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3880 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3881 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3882 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
3883 &:= (T((-1+2+(3^4))) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3884 &:= (-1 - (T(((2+3) \times 4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3885 &:= (-1 \times (T(((2+3) \times 4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3886 &:= (T((-1-2+T((T(3+4) - T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
3887 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3888 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + ((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3889 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (3 + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
3890 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3891 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3892 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3893 &:= (-1 - (T(T((T(T(2+3))/T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3894 &:= ((-1-2-3) + ((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3895 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3896 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (4 \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3897 &:= (T((-1+2+(T(T(3)) \times 4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3898 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3899 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
3900 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3901 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3902 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3903 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3904 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3905 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T((T(3+4) - T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3906 &:= (T((-1+2-(T(3+4) - T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3907 &:= ((-1+2+T((T((3 \times 4) + T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3908 &:= (-1 - (T((2+T(T(3)))) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3909 &:= (-1 \times (T((2+T(T(3)))) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3910 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + ((T(4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3911 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3912 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times 4) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
3913 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3874 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3875 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7+6) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3876 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) \times (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3877 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3878 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3879 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3880 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3881 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3882 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (6 \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3883 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + T(6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3884 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3885 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1) \\
3886 &:= (T((-9-8) \times (7 - (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3887 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3888 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - ((T(7) \times T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3889 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times T(6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3890 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) + 6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
3891 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3892 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (T(T(7+6)) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3893 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) - 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3894 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1) \\
3895 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7) \times 6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3896 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7+6)))) - (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3897 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3898 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3899 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
3900 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3901 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3902 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 - T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3903 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) \times (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3904 &:= ((-9+8) - ((T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5)))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3905 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3906 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8) - 7) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3907 &:= (-9 + T((T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
3908 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + (6 \times 5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3909 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) + 7) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3910 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3911 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 \times (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3912 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(7) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3913 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (6 + T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3954 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3955 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(T(3))) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3956 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3957 &:= (-1-2 + (((3 \times 4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3958 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
3959 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3960 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3961 &:= (-1+2 + (((3 \times 4) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3962 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
3963 &:= (((-1 \times T(T(T(2+3))))/T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3964 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) + (T(4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3965 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) + (T(4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3966 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3967 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3968 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3969 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - T((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3970 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3971 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) + (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3972 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3973 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + ((4+T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3974 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3975 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
3976 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times ((4^5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
3977 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
3978 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3979 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - (4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
3980 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3981 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3982 &:= (-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
3983 &:= (-1 - (T((2 + (T(T(3)) \times 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3984 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
3985 &:= ((T(T(T(-1+2+3)))/4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
3986 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
3987 &:= ((-1-2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3988 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3989 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3990 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3991 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
3992 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) + ((5+6) - (7+8+9))) \\
3993 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3954 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 \times T(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3955 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + 6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3956 &:= ((-9 + T(((8+7) \times 6))) - (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3957 &:= (((-9 + T((8+T(7)))) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3958 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3959 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3960 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3961 &:= (T((-9 + T(8)) - 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3962 &:= (-9 + (T(((T(8) - T(7)) \times (6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3963 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) - (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3964 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3965 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) - (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
3966 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3967 &:= (-9-8 + (T(7 \times 6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3968 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7+6) \times 5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3969 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3970 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3971 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3972 &:= ((-9 + (T((8+T(7))) \times 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3973 &:= ((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (7 + (6 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
3974 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 \times T(6))) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
3975 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3976 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3977 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) - (6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
3978 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times T(7)) - T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3979 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
3980 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3981 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7)/6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3982 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3983 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7 \times 6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3984 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + 7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
3985 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) - (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
3986 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 \times (7+6)) - T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
3987 &:= (-9 + ((8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
3988 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) \times (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
3989 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
3990 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(7))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
3991 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3992 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
3993 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3994 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3995 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
3996 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times T(T((4 + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3997 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times T(T((4 + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
3998 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
3999 &:= ((-1 + T((2 - (T(3 + 4) - T(T(5)))))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4000 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4001 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) \times (T(T(4))/5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4002 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) - (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4003 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4004 &:= (-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4005 &:= T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4006 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4007 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4008 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4009 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3 - 4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4010 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4011 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3 + 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4012 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4013 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (T(T(T(4))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4014 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T((3 \times 4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4015 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4))) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4016 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4017 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4018 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T((3 \times 4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4019 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4020 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4021 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4022 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) - (T(4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4023 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) \times 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4024 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4025 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4026 &:= (T((-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4027 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3)) \times 4)) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4028 &:= (-1 - (T((T(2 + 3) - 4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4029 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3 + 4)) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4030 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4031 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(3 + 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4032 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3994 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
3995 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3996 &:= (-9 + T(((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3997 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
3998 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
3999 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + 7)) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4000 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4001 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4002 &:= (-9 + ((T((8 + T(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4003 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T((7 + T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4004 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4005 &:= T((-9 - 8 + (T(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4006 &:= (-9 - (((T(8) - T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4007 &:= ((-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) \times 6)) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4008 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7) + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4009 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(T(7))) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4010 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4011 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4012 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4013 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7 + 6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4014 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) + 7) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4015 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4016 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4017 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4018 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) \times (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4019 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4020 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4021 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4022 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4023 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7))) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4024 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(T(7))) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4025 &:= (T(T((-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T(6 + 5)))))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4026 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4027 &:= ((-9 + (T((8 + T(7))) \times 6)) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4028 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + T(T(7))) - 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4029 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) + 7) \times (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4030 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4031 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4032 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4033 &:= (T((-1+2+(3^4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4034 &:= ((-1-2-3) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4035 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4036 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4037 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(3+T(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4038 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) + T(T(4)+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4039 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3+4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4040 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(3+T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
4041 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4042 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4043 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4044 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4045 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) \times T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4046 &:= (T(((T(-1+2) \times 3)) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4047 &:= (-1-2+(3 \times (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4048 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4049 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) \times ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4050 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4051 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((3+T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4052 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4053 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4054 &:= ((-1 + T(2+3)) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4055 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4056 &:= ((T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) \times T(4)) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4057 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3+4)) \times T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4058 &:= (-1 - (T(2+T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4059 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4060 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4061 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3+4)) \times T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4062 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4063 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) + (T(4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4064 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4065 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4066 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (4^5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4067 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(3)) + (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4068 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4069 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) + (T(4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4070 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4071 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4072 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4033 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7+6) \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4034 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) + 7) \times 6)) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
4035 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(7)+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4036 &:= (T(((T(-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7))+6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4037 &:= ((-9-8+T(T(7+6))) - (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4038 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4039 &:= ((-9-8+T(T(7+6))) - (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4040 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - (7+6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4041 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)))) + T(5+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4042 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7+T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4043 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4044 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) + 7) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4045 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4046 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4047 &:= (T((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
4048 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4049 &:= ((-9-8+T(T(7+6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4050 &:= (-9-8 - (T(7) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4051 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4052 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + ((T(6) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4053 &:= ((-9+8+T(T(7+6))) - (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4054 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4055 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4056 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4057 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4058 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) + T(6 \times 5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4059 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4060 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4061 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - T(T(7))) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4062 &:= (((-9 + T((8+T(7)))) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4063 &:= (-9-8 + ((T(7)+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4064 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7+6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4065 &:= ((-9+8+T(T(7+6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4066 &:= (T(T(((T(-9+8) - 7) + T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4067 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4068 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - ((6-5) - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4069 &:= (T(((T(-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4070 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) - (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4071 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4072 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T((T(6) \times 5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4073 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4074 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4075 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4076 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - ((4^5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4077 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4078 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (T(4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4079 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4080 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4081 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4082 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4083 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4084 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - (4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
4085 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4086 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4087 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4088 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4089 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4090 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4091 &:= (((-1 - T(2 + 3))/4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4092 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3) + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4093 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4094 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times (T(3) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4095 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4096 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4097 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4098 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4099 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4100 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4101 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4102 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4103 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4104 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4105 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4106 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4107 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4108 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4109 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4110 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4111 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4112 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4073 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((T(7) + 6) \times T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4074 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4075 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4076 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T((T(7) - (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4077 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7 + 6) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4078 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4079 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7) + 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4080 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4081 &:= ((T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4082 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - T(((T(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4083 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4084 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + T(((T(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4085 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4086 &:= (-9 + T((T((T(8 + 7)/6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4087 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4088 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4089 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 \times T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4090 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4091 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4092 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4093 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4094 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4095 &:= T(((-9 + T(8 + 7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4096 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4097 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T((6 \times T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4098 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4099 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4100 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4101 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4102 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4103 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4104 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + 7)) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4105 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4106 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4107 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4108 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7 + 6) - T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4109 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4110 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4111 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (T((6 \times T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4112 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4113 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4114 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4115 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4116 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4117 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4118 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4119 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4120 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4121 &:= (-1 \times (2^{T(3)} - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4122 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4123 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4124 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3 + 4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4125 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4126 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4127 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4128 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4129 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4130 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4131 &:= (T((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4132 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - T(T((T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4133 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4134 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (4 \times T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4135 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4136 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4137 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 \times 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4138 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (4 \times T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4139 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4140 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4141 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4142 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4143 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4144 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (4 \times T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4145 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4146 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4147 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (4 \times T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4148 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4149 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4150 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4151 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4152 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4113 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4114 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T(T(((7 + T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4115 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4116 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4117 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4118 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((T(7) + 6) \times T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4119 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4120 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4121 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T(6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4122 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4123 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4124 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(T(7))) - T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4125 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4126 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4127 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7))) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4128 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) \times (6 \times (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4129 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4130 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7 + 6) + T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4131 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4132 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4133 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4134 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((T(7) + 6) \times T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4135 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4136 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4137 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4138 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4139 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4140 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4141 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T(T(((7 + T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4142 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4143 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((7 + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4144 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4145 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4146 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4147 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4148 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4149 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4150 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4151 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) - (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4152 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4153 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3+4) - T(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 4153 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) + 6 + 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4154 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T((T(3+4) - T(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 4154 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7+6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4155 &:= ((-1 + T(T((T(2+3) - (T(4)/5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 4155 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) + T(7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4156 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 + (3+4+5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 4156 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7+6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4157 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T((T(3+4) - T(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 4157 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
4158 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4158 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4159 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2+3))) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))) & 4159 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7 + T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4160 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 4160 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + 6 + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4161 &:= (T((-1 + 2 \times T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 4161 &:= (T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4162 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4162 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6)))) + T(T((T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4163 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4163 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((7 \times (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4164 &:= (-1 + (((2^{T(3)}) + T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 4164 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4165 &:= ((-1 + T((2+3+T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4165 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7+6))) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4166 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(3)) + T((4 \times T(5)))))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 4166 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4167 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4167 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7+6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4168 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (4 \times T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 4168 &:= (T(((-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4169 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4169 &:= (-9 - 8 + T(T(((7 + T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4170 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) & 4170 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7+6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4171 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 4171 &:= (T(T(((-9 + 8) - 7) + T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1) \\
4172 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4172 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6 \times 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4173 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4173 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4174 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))) & 4174 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7+6))) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
4175 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 4175 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4176 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4176 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4177 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4177 &:= (-9 + T(T((T((8-7+6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4178 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4178 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + T((T(6) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4179 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4179 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7+6) - T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4180 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4180 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (7 \times (6+5))) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4181 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))) & 4181 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4182 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)) & 4182 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4183 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4183 &:= (T(((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T(T(6)))) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4184 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4184 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4185 &:= (-1 + T(((2 \times T(3+4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 4185 &:= (-9 + 8 + T(T(((7 + T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4186 &:= T(T((-1 - (2 \times (T(3+4) - (5+6+7+8+9))))) & 4186 &:= T(T(((-9 + 8) - (7 - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4187 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4187 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4188 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4188 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
4189 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4189 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6 \times 5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4190 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 4190 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 \times (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4191 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3))) - (4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9) & 4191 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - 7+6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4192 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4192 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + T((T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4193 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4194 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times ((4 - 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4195 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4196 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(3) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4197 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4198 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4199 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + 3 + T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4200 &:= (T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4201 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4202 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4203 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4204 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4205 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4206 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4207 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4208 &:= (-1 - (T(T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4209 &:= (-1 \times (T(T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4210 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4211 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4212 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4213 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3)) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4214 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4215 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4216 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4217 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times (4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4218 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4219 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4220 &:= (-1 \times (T((2^{T(3)})) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4221 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4222 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4223 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4))) - T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4224 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3) + (T(4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4225 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) \times 4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4226 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4227 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T((T(4) \times 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4228 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4229 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4230 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4231 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4232 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4193 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - T(6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4194 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4195 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times (7 - (6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4196 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((7 + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4197 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4198 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4199 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T((7 + T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4200 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4201 &:= (T(T(((T(-9 + 8) - 7) + T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4202 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4203 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7) + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4204 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(7)) \times (6 - T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4205 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + T(7)) \times T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4206 &:= (-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4207 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4208 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4209 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4210 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4211 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4212 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) \times 7) - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4213 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T(T((7 + T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4214 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(T(7) - 6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4215 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4216 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4217 &:= (((-9 + T((8 + T(7)))) \times 6) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4218 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4219 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4220 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4221 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4222 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4223 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + ((7 + 6) \times 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4224 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((7 + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4225 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4226 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4227 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4228 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4229 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4230 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4231 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T(6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4232 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4233 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3+T(4)))) - (T(5)+6+7+8+9)) \\
4234 &:= -1+T(T(T(2+3))) - T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4235 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (T(3)+T(T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4236 &:= (-1+((2 \times (T((T(3)+T(T(4)))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4237 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times (5+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4238 &:= (((-1+T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4239 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - T((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4240 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4241 &:= (-1+((T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4242 &:= ((-1+T(((2+T(T(3))) \times 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4243 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3+T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4244 &:= (-1+((T(2+3) \times T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4245 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3))) + (4 \times T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4246 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4247 &:= (-1+T((T(2 \times 3) - 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4248 &:= (-1+((2^{T(3)}) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4249 &:= (-1+T((2^{T(3)}) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4250 &:= (-1+((2 \times T((3 \times 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4251 &:= (T((-1+2 \times T(3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4252 &:= (-1+T(((2+T(T(3))) \times 4) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4253 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3+T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4254 &:= ((-1+(T(2 \times T(3)) \times T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4255 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3))) + (T(T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4256 &:= (T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4257 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4258 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4259 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4+5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4260 &:= ((T((-1+2 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4261 &:= (T(((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times 4) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4262 &:= (-1+T(2 \times T(3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4263 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3+T(4)))) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4264 &:= (-1+((T(2 \times T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
4265 &:= ((((-1-2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9 \\
4266 &:= (T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4267 &:= T(T(-1+T(2+3))) - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9) \\
4268 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3+T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4269 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((T(3)+T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4270 &:= (((-1+T(2 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
4271 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4272 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4233 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) + (T(5)+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4234 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4235 &:= ((-9-8+(T(7)+T(6+5))) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4236 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4237 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4238 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - T(6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4239 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4240 &:= (-9+8+(T((7+T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4241 &:= (-9+((8+(T(T(7))+6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4242 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4243 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6 \times 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4244 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4245 &:= (((T(-9+T(8)) + 7) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4246 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4247 &:= (-9+(8 \times (T(T(7)) + (6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4248 &:= (-9 - (T(((8 \times 7) + T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4249 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4250 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4251 &:= (-9+((8 \times (T(T(7)) - T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4252 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4253 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4254 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times T(7)) - ((6 - T(T(5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4255 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7+6)) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4256 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4257 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7+6)) - T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
4258 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4259 &:= ((-9+T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4260 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times ((6 \times T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4261 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7+6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4262 &:= (-9+(T(8) + ((7 \times (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4263 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + ((T(7) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4264 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4265 &:= ((((-9+8+7) \times 6) \times T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4266 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - ((T(7)+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4267 &:= (-9+((T(8) \times (T(7+6) - T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4268 &:= (-9+(T(8) + (T((7+T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4269 &:= (-9+T(((8 \times 7) + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4270 &:= (-9+(((T(8) + T(7)) \times T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4271 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
4272 &:= (-9+(T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4273 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4274 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) \times T(T(4)))) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4275 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4276 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4277 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4278 &:= T(((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4279 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(3) - (4 - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4280 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4281 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - T((T(4) \times 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4282 &:= (((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times (T(T(T(4)))/5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4283 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4284 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 + 3) + 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4285 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4286 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4287 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((3 \times 4) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4288 &:= (T((((-1 + 2 - T(T(T(3))))/T(4)) + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4289 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3) \times T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4290 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4291 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times 4) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4292 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4293 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + 4)))/5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4294 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4295 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4296 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4 + (5 + 6)))))) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
4297 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4298 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4299 &:= -1 + T(2 + T(T(3))) \times T(4) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4300 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4301 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4302 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4303 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4304 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4305 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4306 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4307 &:= (((-1 - T(T(2 + T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4308 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(3 + 4) - T(5)))))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
4309 &:= (-1 - (T((T(2 + 3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4310 &:= (-1 \times (T((T(2 + 3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4311 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4312 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 + T(T(3))) \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4273 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4274 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) \times (6 - T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4275 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times ((7 - 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4276 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) - T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4277 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4278 &:= T((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4279 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4280 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 - (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4281 &:= (-9 + (T((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4282 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4283 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4284 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4285 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4286 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + T(T(6))) \times T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4287 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4288 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4289 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4290 &:= ((T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4291 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) - 7 - 6) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4292 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4293 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - (T(6 \times 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4294 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4295 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4296 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4297 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7 + 6) \times (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4298 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((T(7) - T(6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4299 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4300 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4301 &:= ((T((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4302 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - T(T(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4303 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4304 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) + 7) \times 6) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4305 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4306 &:= (T(T((((-9 + 8) - 7) + T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4307 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + ((7 \times 6) + T(5)))))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4308 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4309 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + 7) \times 6) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4310 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4311 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4312 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7 + 6)) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4313 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3+T(4))))+5+6+7+8+9) & 4313 &:= (((-9+T(T(8)))\times 7)-(T((6+T(5)))+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4314 &:= ((T((-1+T(T(2+3))))/T(4)+(T(T(5))\times(6+7+8+9))) & 4314 &:= (-9-(((8-T(T(7)))\times(6+5))+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4315 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3))\times(T(T(4))+T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9)) & 4315 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T(7)+(T(6+5)\times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4316 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2)\times 3)))-(T(4)-T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4316 &:= (T((-9+8+(T(7)+T(6+5))))-T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4317 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(T(3))))-(T(4)-T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4317 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7+6))+(T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4318 &:= (T((T((-1+T(2+3)))-T(4)))-(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 4318 &:= ((-9-8)\times(T(T(7))-(T(6+5)\times(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4319 &:= (-1+(T(2+T(3))\times T((T(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4319 &:= (-9-8+(T(T(7+6))+(T(5)\times(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4320 &:= ((-1+2+3)\times(T(T(T(4)))+(5-T(6+7+8+9))) & 4320 &:= (((-9+8+7)\times 6)\times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4321 &:= (-1+2+(((T(3)\times 4)+T(T(5)))\times(6+7+8+9))) & 4321 &:= (-9+(((8+7)+T(6))\times T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1) \\
4322 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2)\times 3)))-(4-T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4322 &:= ((-9\times T(8))+(T((T(7+6)+5))-(4+3+2+1))) \\
4323 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3)))+T((T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) & 4323 &:= (-9+(T(8)+(T(T(7+6))+(T(T(5))-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4324 &:= (-1\times 2+(T(T(T(3)))+T((T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) & 4324 &:= (-9+(T(((8\times 7)+(T(6)+T(5))))+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4325 &:= (-1+(T(T(2\times 3))+T((T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) & 4325 &:= (-9-(T((T(8\times 7)/T(6)))-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4326 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2)\times 3)))+T((T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) & 4326 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7))+T((6\times(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4327 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3)))+T((T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) & 4327 &:= ((-9+8)-(T(7)-(6\times(T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4328 &:= (-1\times 2\times(T(3)-(T(T(T(4)))+T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 4328 &:= (T(-9+T(8))+((T(T(7))-(6+5))\times(4+3+2+1))) \\
4329 &:= (-1+(T(T(2\times 3))+(4+T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4329 &:= (-9\times(T(8)-(T(T(7))+(T(T(6))-T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4330 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2)\times 3)))+(4+T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4330 &:= (T((-9-8+T(7+6)))+(T(5)+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4331 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3)))+(4+T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4331 &:= ((-9+((T(8)+(7+6))\times T(T(5))))-T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4332 &:= (((-1-2)\times(T(T(T(3)))-T((4\times T(5)))))-T(6+7+8+9) & 4332 &:= ((-9-(T(8)-7))\times(6-T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4333 &:= (-1-(2\times(3-(T(T(T(4)))+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4333 &:= (-9+(T(8)+(T(T(7+6)))+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4334 &:= (-1\times 2\times(3-(T(T(T(4)))+T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 4334 &:= (((-9-8+T(T(7)))\times(6+5))+T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4335 &:= ((-1+T((2+T(3+T(4)))))-(5+6+7+8+9) & 4335 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7+6))+(T(5)\times(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4336 &:= (T(T((-1+(2\times(3+4)))))+(5\times(6+7+8+9))) & 4336 &:= (-9-(T(T(8))-(T(T(7+6)))+(T(5)\times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4337 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3+T(4)))+(5\times(6+7+8+9))) & 4337 &:= (-9+(T((T(8)+T(7)))+(T(T(6+5))+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4338 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))))-(T(4)-T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4338 &:= (-9+((T(8)\times 7)+T((6\times(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4339 &:= (-1+((T(T(2+3))+4)\times(5+6+7+8+9))) & 4339 &:= ((-9\times 8+(T(T(7))\times(6+5)))-T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4340 &:= ((T(T(-1+2\times 3))+4)\times(5+6+7+8+9) & 4340 &:= ((-9+8+T((T(7)+(6-5))))\times(4+3+2+1)) \\
4341 &:= (T((-1+2-(T(3+4)-T(T(5)))))-(6+7+8+9) & 4341 &:= (-9+((T(8+7)\times T(6))+T(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4342 &:= (((-1+T(2+3))\times(T(T(T(4)))/5))+6+7+8+9 & 4342 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T(((7+6)\times 5))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4343 &:= (-1-(2\times(T((T(T(3))-4))-(5\times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4343 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T((T(7+6)-5))-T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4344 &:= (-1-(T(T(2+3))-T(((4+T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4344 &:= (-9-8+(T(T(7+6))+(T(T(5))+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4345 &:= (-1+(2\times(3+(T(T(T(4)))+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4345 &:= ((-9+((T(8)-T(7))\times(6+5))\times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4346 &:= (-1-(T((2\times T(T(3))))-(T(T(4))+T(T(5))\times(6+7+8+9))) & 4346 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-(T(T(7))-T((6\times(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4347 &:= (((-1-2)\times(T(T(T(3)))-T(T(T(4)))-T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9) & 4347 &:= (-9+(T(8)\times((7-6)+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4348 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))))+T((T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) & 4348 &:= (((-9+8)-7)+(6\times(T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
4349 &:= (-1-(T(2+3)\times(T(T(4))+(T(T(5))-T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4349 &:= (-9+8+(T((T(7)+(6-5))\times(4+3+2+1))) \\
4350 &:= ((T((-1\times 2+T(T(3))))-T(4+5))\times(6+7+8+9) & 4350 &:= (((T(-9+T(8))\times 7)-T(T(6+5)))\times(4+3+2+1)) \\
4351 &:= (-1+(2\times(T(3)+(T(T(T(4)))+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4351 &:= (-9-((T(8)-(T(T(7))+T(6+5))\times(4+3+2+1))) \\
4352 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))))+(4+T((T(T(5))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 4352 &:= ((-9+T((T(8)+((7\times 6)+T(5))))-(4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4353 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4353 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4354 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((3^4)) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4354 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((7 + (T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4355 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + T(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4355 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + T(6 \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4356 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4356 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(7)) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4357 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3^4)) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4357 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times ((7 - 6) + T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4358 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 4358 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) \times (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4359 &:= ((T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) \times (4 + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4359 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4360 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4360 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4361 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4361 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4362 &:= (((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 4362 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) + ((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4363 &:= (-1 - (T((T(2 \times 3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4363 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4364 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + T(T(3))) \times T(4 \times 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4364 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 \times 6) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4365 &:= ((T((-1 - (T(2 + 3) - T(T(4)))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4365 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((7 \times 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4366 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4366 &:= ((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4367 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4367 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4368 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((3 + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4368 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4369 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((3 + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4369 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + 7) \times T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4370 &:= (-1 + T(((2^{3+4}) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4370 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4371 &:= T(((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4371 &:= T((T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4372 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((3 + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4372 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4373 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3^{T(4 \times 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)}))) & 4373 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 \times (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4374 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2 + 3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4374 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4375 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4375 &:= ((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6) \times T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4376 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4376 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + (7 - 6)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4377 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 4377 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 \times (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4378 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4378 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(6)))) - (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4379 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (T(3 + 4) + T(T(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4379 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4380 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3 + 4) + T(T(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4380 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4381 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4381 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4382 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4382 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T((7 + 6 - 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4383 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3^4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4383 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4384 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + T(3))) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4384 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4385 &:= (((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4385 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4386 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4386 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4387 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4387 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4388 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 4388 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
4389 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) \times (4 - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 4389 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4390 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 4390 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6)) - T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4391 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 4391 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4392 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3) \times 4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 4392 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4393 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (4 \times T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4394 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (3 \times 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4395 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times 3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4396 &:= (T(((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times 4)) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4397 &:= ((-1-2) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4398 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4399 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2 \times 3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4400 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T((T(3+4) - T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4401 &:= (T((-1+2 - (T(3+4) - T(T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
4402 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T((3 \times 4)) + T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4403 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4404 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - ((4^5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4405 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T(3 + T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4406 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4407 &:= (-1-2 + ((3+4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4408 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4409 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) \times T((T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4410 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4411 &:= (-1+2 + ((3+4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4412 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3))) \times 4)) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4413 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4414 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4415 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4416 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4417 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4418 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) \times (4 + T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4419 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4420 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4421 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4422 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(T(T(3)))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4423 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4424 &:= (-1 + ((T(2+3) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4425 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) - T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
4426 &:= (-1+2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4427 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 + T(T(3))) \times 4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4428 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4429 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4430 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4431 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4432 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times ((3+4) - T(T((5+6)))) + 7+8+9)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4393 &:= ((-9-8 + T((T(7) + T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4394 &:= ((-9-8 + (T(T(7)) \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4395 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times T(7))) \times T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4396 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) + T(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4397 &:= (-9-8) \times (T(7) + T(T(6))) + T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4398 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((T(7+6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4399 &:= (-9+8 + (((T(T(7)) - 6)/5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4400 &:= (((-9+8 + T(T(7))) \times (6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4401 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) \times (7 - T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4402 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4403 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4404 &:= (((-9-8) \times (T(7) \times 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4405 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times T(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4406 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - T(7+6)) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4407 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4408 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4409 &:= ((-9+8 + T((T(7) + T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4410 &:= (T((-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4411 &:= ((T(-9-8 + T(7)) \times T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4412 &:= (T(T(-9-8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4413 &:= ((T(-9+8 + T(7)) \times 6) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4414 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4415 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4416 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 - T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4417 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + T((T(6) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4418 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6))) - T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4419 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4420 &:= ((-9-8) \times (T(T(7)) - T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4421 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4422 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4423 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4424 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times (6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4425 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4426 &:= (T((-9+8 + (T(7) + T(6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4427 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4428 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7+6)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4429 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4430 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7) + T(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4431 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + (7-6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4432 &:= (T(T(-9-8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4433 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(3))) \times ((4 + T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4434 &:= ((-1 + T((2 - (T(3 + 4) - T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4435 &:= (T((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4436 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) \times (T(T(4))/5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4437 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4438 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3)) \times (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4439 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 \times T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4440 &:= ((T(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4441 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3 + 4) + T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4442 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4443 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4444 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4445 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4446 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(3 + 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4447 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4448 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4449 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4450 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4451 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4452 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4453 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T((4 + T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4454 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4455 &:= (T(((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(4))) - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4456 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4457 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4458 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4459 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4460 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T(T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4461 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4462 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4463 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4464 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times ((3 \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4465 &:= T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4466 &:= T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4467 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4^5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4468 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4469 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4470 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(3 + 4) + T(T(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4471 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4472 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4433 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (T(7 \times 6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4434 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4435 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4436 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4437 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4438 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4439 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4440 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4441 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) - (7 - T(T(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4442 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8 \times 7)/T(6)))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4443 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4444 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4445 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4446 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4447 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4448 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4449 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4450 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4451 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - 7) + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4452 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4453 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) - 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4454 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4455 &:= ((-9 - 8 - T(7)) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4456 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4457 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4458 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4459 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4460 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4461 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (T(7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4462 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 \times 7)/T(6))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4463 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T((6 \times T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4464 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4465 &:= T((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4466 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4467 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4468 &:= (-9 - (((T(T(8)) + 7) \times 6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4469 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + T(T(6)))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4470 &:= (((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(7 + 6))) + T(T(T(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4471 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4472 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4513 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4514 &:= ((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - (T(4) \times (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4515 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4516 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4517 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4518 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4519 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4520 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3 + 4)))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4521 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - 4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4522 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4523 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4524 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(3 + 4)) \times 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4525 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4526 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4527 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4528 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4529 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4530 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4531 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4532 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4533 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4534 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4535 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4536 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4537 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4538 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T((T(T(4)) + T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4539 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T((T(3) + 4)) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4540 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4541 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4542 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4543 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4)) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4544 &:= (-1 - (((T(2 \times 3) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4545 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4546 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4547 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4548 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((T(3) \times 4) - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4549 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4550 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4551 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4552 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4513 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4514 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4515 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(7))) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4516 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T(((T(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4517 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4518 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((T(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4519 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4520 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4521 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4522 &:= -9 + T(8) - (T(T(7) + T(6)) - T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4523 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4524 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4525 &:= ((T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4526 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((7 \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4527 &:= (-9 + ((8 + T(7)) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4528 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4529 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((T(7 + 6) + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4530 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4531 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4532 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4533 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4534 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4535 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4536 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4537 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8)))/(7 + 6) - T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4538 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4539 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4540 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4541 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) - (7 - T(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4542 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4543 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4544 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4545 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4546 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4547 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4548 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4549 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4550 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4551 &:= (((-9 - T(8 + 7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4552 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4553 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) & 4553 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + T(((T(6) \times 5) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4554 &:= (-1 + (((2^{T(3)}) \times T(T(4))) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 4554 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4555 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) - (T(4) \times (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4555 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4556 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4556 &:= ((-9 + T((T(T(8+7)))/T(6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4557 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 4557 &:= ((((-9-8) \times 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4558 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((T(3) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 4558 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4559 &:= (-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4559 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4560 &:= T(((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 4560 &:= T(((-9 + (8 \times (7 + T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4561 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(((T(3) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 4561 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - (7 - T(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4562 &:= (-1-2) \times T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 4562 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4563 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 4563 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4564 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 4564 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(((7 + T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4565 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times T(4)) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 4565 &:= ((T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + 5) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4566 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)) - 4) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 4566 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (7+6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4567 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4567 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4568 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 4568 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (5 \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4569 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 4569 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4570 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 4570 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((7 \times (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4571 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times 4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 4571 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) - ((T(6) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4572 &:= ((-1-2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 4572 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4573 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 4573 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6) - 5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4574 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) \times 4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 4574 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((T(7+6) + 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4575 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3))) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4575 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7+6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4576 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4576 &:= ((-9 + (T((T(8) + (7+6))) \times 5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4577 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4577 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4578 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 4578 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4579 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 4579 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4580 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 4580 &:= (((-9 + ((8+7) \times T(6))) \times T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4581 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 4581 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4582 &:= ((-1-2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4582 &:= (-9-8 - (T(T(7)) - ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4583 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4583 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4584 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4584 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4585 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4585 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7+6)))) + (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4586 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 4586 &:= (T(((-9 \times (8+7)) + T(T(6)))) - (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4587 &:= ((-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 \times 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 4587 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4588 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 4588 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4589 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(3) + 4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 4589 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7+6)) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
4590 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) & 4590 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4591 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 4591 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4592 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 4592 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4593 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3+4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4594 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3+4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4595 &:= (T((T((-1+T(2+3))) - T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4596 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4597 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4 \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4598 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times 4)) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4599 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4600 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times 3))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4601 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) - (T(4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4602 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) \times 4)) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4603 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4604 &:= (-1 - (((2 - T(3)) \times T(T(4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4605 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times T(T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4606 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4607 &:= ((-1+2+T(3)) - (T(4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4608 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4609 &:= (-1+2 - (3 \times (4 - T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4610 &:= (T(-1+2+3) - (T(4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4611 &:= ((-1+2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4612 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4613 &:= ((-1-2 + (3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4614 &:= (((-1+2) \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
4615 &:= (T((T((-1+T(2+3))) - T(4))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4616 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4617 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4618 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4619 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4620 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4621 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
4622 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times (4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4623 &:= (T((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4624 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
4625 &:= ((-1+T((2 \times (3+T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4626 &:= (T((T((-1+T(2+3))) - (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4627 &:= ((-1+2+T(((3^4)+T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4628 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) - (T(4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4629 &:= (-1-2 + (3 \times (4 + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4630 &:= ((-1+2-3) \times (T(4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4631 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4632 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (4 + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4593 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4594 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7+6)+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4595 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) - T(T(7)+6)) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4596 &:= (((-9 - T(T(8)-7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4597 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4598 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4599 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4600 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (6+5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
4601 &:= (T((-9 + ((8 + (7+6)) \times 5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4602 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4603 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4604 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4605 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (T(7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4606 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - (7 - T(6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4607 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7+6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4608 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4609 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4610 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) - (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4611 &:= (-9 - ((8 - T(7)) \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4612 &:= (-9 + (T(T((8 - (7 - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4613 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4614 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (T(7) - T(6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4615 &:= (T((-9+8 + (T(7+6)+5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4616 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4617 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 \times T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4618 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T((T(7) - (6-5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4619 &:= (-9+8 + (7 \times (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4620 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4621 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(((8 + (7+6)) - T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4622 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (T(6 \times 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4623 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - T(((6 \times T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4624 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (5 + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4625 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4626 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(7)) \times T(T(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4627 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
4628 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7+6)+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4629 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4630 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - T(6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4631 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T(7+6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4632 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4673 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times 4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4674 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T((T(T(4))/5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
4675 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4676 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4677 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4678 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4679 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4680 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4681 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4682 &:= -1 + T(T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4683 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4684 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4685 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (3 + T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
4686 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2+3))) - (4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
4687 &:= ((-1+2 + T((T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4688 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4689 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T((T(3) + T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4690 &:= ((T(T((-1+2 + T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4691 &:= (T((-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
4692 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4693 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4694 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4695 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2+3))) \times T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
4696 &:= (-1+2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4697 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4698 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4699 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4700 &:= (T((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4701 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2+3))) - 4) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4702 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times (T(4) - T(T((5+6)))) + T(7+8+9)) \\
4703 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4704 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4705 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + (3+4)))) \times 5) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4706 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(4) \times (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4707 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4708 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4709 &:= ((-1 + ((2+3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4710 &:= (((-1+2 \times 3) \times T(T(4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4711 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + T((T((T(T(4))/5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
4712 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T((5+6))) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
4673 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7+6) + 5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4674 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4675 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
4676 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
4677 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4678 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T((7 + T(6)))) + T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4679 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((T(7) \times T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4680 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7+6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
4681 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4682 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4683 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7+6) - 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4684 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4685 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(7+6) - 5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4686 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4687 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4688 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4689 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4690 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4691 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T((T(7) + 6 + 5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4692 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7+6)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4693 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4694 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(7+6) + 5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4695 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4696 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4697 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4698 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4699 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8+7)) - (6^5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4700 &:= (T((-9 + ((T(8) - T(7)) \times (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4701 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - ((7+6) \times T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4702 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (T(6) + (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4703 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) + T(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4704 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4705 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4706 &:= (T((-9 \times (8+7)) + T(T(6)))) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1) \\
4707 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7+6) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4708 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((7 + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4709 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4710 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4711 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - T(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4712 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (T(6) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4753 &:= T((-1+2+(T(3)+(T(T(4))+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4754 &:= (-1+2+T(((3+4)+T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
4755 &:= ((T((-1+T(2+3))) \times T(4+5))+6+7+8+9) \\
4756 &:= (-1+2+(((T(T(T(3))))+T(T(4))) \times T(5))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4757 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(3)+T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4758 &:= (-1 \times 2+(T((T(3)+T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4759 &:= (-1+(T((2 \times 3+T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4760 &:= (T((-1+2+3) \times 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4761 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(3)+T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
4762 &:= (-1 \times 2-(T(T((T(T(3))-T(4))))-(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4763 &:= (-1-(T(T((T(2+3)-4)))-(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4764 &:= (-1 \times (T(T((T(2+3)-4)))-(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4765 &:= (-1+2-(T(T((T(T(3))-T(4))))-(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4766 &:= (T((-1+2 \times T(3)))+(T(4) \times (5+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4767 &:= (-1-2+((3 \times T(T(T(4))))+(5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
4768 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3+T(4)))+(T(T(5))+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4769 &:= (-1-(((T(2+3)-T(T(4))) \times T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
4770 &:= ((T(-1+2+3) \times (4 \times T(T(5))))-(6+7+8+9)) \\
4771 &:= (T(T((-1+(2 \times (3+4)))))+(T(T(5))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4772 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3+T(4)))+(T(T(5))+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4773 &:= (T((-1-2) \times (T(T(3))-T(T(4))))-(T(5)+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4774 &:= (-1+((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4)))-(T(T(5))+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4775 &:= ((-1-T((T(2+3)+4))) \times (5-(6+7+8+9))) \\
4776 &:= ((-1-2)-(T(T(3))-(T(4) \times (T(5)+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4777 &:= (((-1+T(2+3)) \times (T(T(T(4)))/5))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
4778 &:= (T((-1-(2 \times (T(3)-T(T(4))))))-(5-(6+7+8+9))) \\
4779 &:= ((T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) \times 4)+T((T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
4780 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3)))+T((T(T(4))-(5-(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4781 &:= (-1+(2 \times (T((T(T(3))-T(4)))+(5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4782 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(3))+(T(4) \times (T(5)+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4783 &:= (T(((((-1+2-T(T(T(3))))/T(4))+T(T(5))))+6+7+8+9) \\
4784 &:= (-1-(T(2+3)-(T(4) \times (T(5)+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4785 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3))))-T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4786 &:= (-1+2+(3 \times (T(T(4))+T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
4787 &:= (-1+(T(((2 \times T(T(3)))+T(T(4))))+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
4788 &:= (T((-1-(2 \times (T(3)-T(T(4)))))))+5+6+7+8+9) \\
4789 &:= (-1+((2+3) \times (T(T(4))+T((T(5+6))-(7+8+9)))) \\
4790 &:= (((-1+T(T(2+3))) \times T(4))+(T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
4791 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3)+(T(4) \times (T(5)+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
4792 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3))))-((T(T(T(4)))/5)+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
4753 &:= T((-9+8)-(T(7)-(6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4754 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+T(T(6))))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4755 &:= (-9+((8 \times (T(7) \times T(6)))+(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4756 &:= ((T(-9+8+7) \times (T(T(6))-5))+4+3+2+1) \\
4757 &:= (-9+(T(8)+((T(7+6))-5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4758 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7)))+(T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4759 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(7+T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4760 &:= ((((-9+T(T(8)))-7-6) \times 5)+T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4761 &:= ((((-9-8) \times 7) \times T(6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4762 &:= (-9+8+(T((7+(6 \times T(5))))+4+3+2+1)) \\
4763 &:= (-9+((T(T(8)) \times 7)+((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
4764 &:= (-9+((T(8)+7) \times (T(T(6))-T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4765 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T(T(7+6))-T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4766 &:= (-9-(T((T(8)+(T(7)+6)))-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4767 &:= ((-9+(T(T(8)) \times 7))-(6-T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4768 &:= ((-9+(8 \times T(T(7))))-(6+5-T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4769 &:= ((-9+(T(8) \times ((7+6)+T(T(5)))))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
4770 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7)))+(T(T(6))+T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
4771 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8)-(T(T(7))-(6+5))))+T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4772 &:= (-9+(T(T(8+7))+(6-T((T(5)+T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4773 &:= (-9+((T(T(8)) \times (T(7)-T(6)))+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4774 &:= (-9+((T(T(8)) \times 7)+(T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4775 &:= (-9-(8 \times (7-((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4776 &:= ((-9 \times T((T(8)-7-6)))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
4777 &:= (((-9-8-T(T(7))) \times 6)+(T(T(T(5)))+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4778 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T(T(7+6))-(T(T(5))-T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4779 &:= (-9+(T(8) \times ((7+6)+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
4780 &:= (-9+(T(8)+T((7+(6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
4781 &:= ((T(-9+8+7) \times T(T(6)))-(T(5)+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4782 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times (7+6))-(T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4783 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T(T(7+6))-(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4784 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6)))+T(T(T(5))))-T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4785 &:= ((T(-9+8+7)+T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4786 &:= (-9+((T(T(8)-7) \times (6+5))+4+3+2+1)) \\
4787 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7)))+(T(T(6))-(T(T(5))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4788 &:= (T(-9+T(8))+(T((T(7)+T(6+5)))-T(4+3+2+1))) \\
4789 &:= (T(-9+T(8))+(T(T(7)) \times (6+5))-T(4+3+2+1)) \\
4790 &:= (-9+((8 \times T(T(7)))+(6+5)+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
4791 &:= (-9+((8+(T(T(7))+T(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
4792 &:= ((-9+(T(8) \times T(7+6)))-(T(5)-T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4833 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3 \times 4) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4834 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3 \times 4) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4835 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T((T(3 + 4) - T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4836 &:= (T((-1 + 2 - (T(3 + 4) - T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4837 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3 \times 4) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4838 &:= (-1 - (T((2 + T(T(3)))) + ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4839 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4840 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4841 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4842 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + 4) \times T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4843 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + 4) \times T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4844 &:= ((-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times T((T(4) + T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4845 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(3 + 4))) \times T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4846 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + 4) \times T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4847 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4848 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4849 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4850 &:= (-1 + T((2 + (T(3) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4851 &:= T(((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4852 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(T(3))) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4853 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4854 &:= ((T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) \times (4 + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4855 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4856 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4857 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T((T(4) \times 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4858 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3^4) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4859 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4860 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4861 &:= (T((((-1 + 2) \times 3^4) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4862 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4863 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4864 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) \times (4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\
4865 &:= (((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) \times T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4866 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4867 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4868 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4869 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) \times (T(4) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4870 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4871 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4872 &:= ((-1 - T(T(2 \times 3))) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4833 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - ((T(7) \times T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4834 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T((T(7) - (6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4835 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4836 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4837 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7 + 6) - T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4838 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4839 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4840 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4841 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T((6 + T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4842 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) - (T(7) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4843 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(T(((7 + T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4844 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4845 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4846 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7) + T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4847 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4848 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) \times T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4849 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4850 &:= (-9 + 8 + T((T((T(7) - (6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4851 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4852 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 + 7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4853 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4854 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4855 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4856 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(T(6))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
4857 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (T(7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4858 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4859 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4860 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8))/7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4861 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8))/(7 - (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4862 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(((7 - 6) + T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4863 &:= (-9 + (((8 - T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4864 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4865 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4866 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(T(6))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4867 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + 6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4868 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4869 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4870 &:= (((-9 + T((8 + (7 + 6)))) \times T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4871 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7) + 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4872 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 - 6))) \times (T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4873 &:= (((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4874 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times T((T(4) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4875 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4876 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(4 \times 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4877 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4878 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4879 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4880 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4881 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4882 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) + ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4883 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) + ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4884 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T((T((T(T(4))/5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4885 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(T(3))) + ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4886 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4887 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + T((T((T(T(4))/5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4888 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T((T((T(T(4))/5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4889 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4890 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4891 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4892 &:= (-1 - ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4893 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4894 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3)^4 + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4895 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4896 &:= ((T(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4897 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3)^4 + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4898 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4899 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
4900 &:= ((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times (T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4901 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4902 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4903 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4904 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) \times T((T(4) + T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4905 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(3 + 4))) \times T(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
4906 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3 + 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4907 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 + T(T(3))) \times 4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4908 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3 + T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4909 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4910 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T((4 + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
4911 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4912 &:= ((-1 - T(2 + 3)) \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) - T(7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4873 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - T(T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4874 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4875 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4876 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) - T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4877 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4878 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T((T(7) - (6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4879 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4880 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4881 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4882 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 + 6) \times T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4883 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4884 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4885 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6)))) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4886 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) - (6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4887 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times T((7 - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
4888 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) + (6 \times T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4889 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4890 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(((T(7) - T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4891 &:= ((-9 + T((8 + T(7 + 6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4892 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4893 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) + 7) \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4894 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(((T(6) \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4895 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(7 + 6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4896 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4897 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(((7 - 6) + T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4898 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4899 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4900 &:= (((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 + 6))) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4901 &:= (T(((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T(6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4902 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) - (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4903 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4904 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6) + T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4905 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4906 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T((6 + T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
4907 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4908 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4909 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4910 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4911 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T(T(7) - 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
4912 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4993 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times ((T(4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4994 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) + ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4995 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
4996 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times ((T(4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4997 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4998 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
4999 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) \times (4 - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5000 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T(3 + T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
\\
5001 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5002 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3 + T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5003 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3 + T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5004 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5005 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5006 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - ((4^5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5007 &:= (-1 - ((2 + T(3)) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5008 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - T(3)) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5009 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((T(T(3)) - 4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5010 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5011 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5012 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5013 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5014 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5015 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5016 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - T((4 \times T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5017 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5018 &:= (-1 - (T(T((T(2 + 3) - 4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5019 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times (3 + 4)) - 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5020 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5021 &:= -1 - 2 - T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5022 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (3 \times T((4 \times T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5023 &:= (((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5024 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5025 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5026 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (3 \times T((4 \times T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5027 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5028 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5029 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5030 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - T(4))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5031 &:= (T((-1 + 2 - 3) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4993 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4994 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4995 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 \times 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4996 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((T(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4997 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4998 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times 7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
4999 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5000 &:= (((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 + 6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
\\
5001 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8) - 7) + T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5002 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) - (T(T(6)) - T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5003 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + ((7 \times 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5004 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5005 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5006 &:= ((-9 + T((8 + (T(7 + 6) + T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5007 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5008 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (7 - 6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5009 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5010 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T((7 + T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5011 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5012 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (((7 \times 6) \times T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5013 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5014 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5015 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) - T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5016 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(7)) \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5017 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5018 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5019 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5020 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(T(7))) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5021 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 + 7) - 6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5022 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T((T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5023 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5024 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5025 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) + T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5026 &:= (T((T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5027 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5028 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T(6 \times 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5029 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((7 \times 6) \times T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5030 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5031 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T((T(7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

- 5032 := (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) × (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5033 := (-1 - (2 × (3 - (4 × T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5034 := (-1 × 2 × (3 - (4 × T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5035 := (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) × T(4))) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5036 := (-1 - (T(2 × T(3)) + ((4 - T(5)) × T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5037 := (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - T(((T(4)/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5038 := (-1 × 2 + (T(T(3)) × (T(4 × 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5039 := (-1 + (T(2 + T(3)) × (4 × (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5040 := ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) × T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 5041 := (-1 + (2 × (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5042 := (-1 × 2 - (T(3) - T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5043 := ((-1 - (2 × 3)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5044 := ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5045 := (-1 + (2 × (3 + (4 × T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5046 := (T((-1 + (2 × T(T(3)))) + ((4 + 5) × T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5047 := (-1 - 2 + T(((T(3) - T(4)) × (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5048 := ((-1 + 2 - 3) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5049 := (-1 + T(((2 + 3) × (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5050 := T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5051 := (-1 + (2 × (T(3) + (4 × T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5052 := ((-1 - 2) × (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5053 := (((-1 + 2) × 3) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5054 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5055 := (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5056 := (T(((-1 + 2) × 3)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5057 := (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5058 := (-1 × 2 - ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) × (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5059 := (-1 - ((T(2 + 3) - 4) × (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5060 := (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) × (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5061 := (T(T((-1 + 2 × T(3)))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5062 := (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + T((T((T(T(4))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5063 := (((-1 - (2 × T(T(T(3)))) × (4 - T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5064 := (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5065 := (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) × T(4))) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5066 := (((-1 + T(T(2 + T(3)))) × T(4)) - (T((5 + 6) × (7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5067 := (-1 - 2 + (3 × (T(T(T(4))) + (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5068 := (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5069 := ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4)))) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5070 := (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 5071 := (-1 + ((2 + T(3)) × (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 5032 := (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + T((6 × (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5033 := (-9 - 8 + (((7 × 6) × T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 5034 := ((T(-9 + T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 5035 := (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 + (T(6 × 5) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5036 := (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
- 5037 := (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6) - (T(T(5)) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5038 := (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) × T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5039 := (-9 + 8 + ((7 × 6) × T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5040 := ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6)) × T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 5041 := (-9 + T(((8 - 7) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5042 := (((-9 + 8) - 7) + T(((6 × T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5043 := (((-9 + 8) × 7) + T(((6 × T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5044 := ((T(-9 + T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 5045 := (-9 - (T(((8 + 7) + T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
- 5046 := ((-9 × ((8 + 7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5047 := (-9 - (8 × (T(7) - (T(6 + 5) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5048 := ((-9 + (8 × T(T(7)))) - (T(6) - T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5049 := (-9 × (((T(8) - 7) × T(T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5050 := T(((-9 × (8 - (7 + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 5051 := (-9 - (((T(8) - T(7 + 6)) × T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5052 := (-9 + (T(8 × 7) + (T(T(6)) × (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5053 := (((-9 - 8) × T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) × T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5054 := (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5055 := (((-9 - T(8)) × (T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5056 := ((-9 × (8 - T(T(7)))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5057 := (-9 + (T(8) + (((7 × 6) × T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5058 := (-9 × (T(8) + (7 - ((6 + 5) × T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5059 := ((-9 + 8) - (((7 + T(6)) - T(T(5))) × T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5060 := (T(((-9 + T(8 + 7)) - (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
- 5061 := (-9 + (T((8 + T(7 + 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5062 := ((-9 × T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5063 := (-9 + ((T(T(8)) × 7) + (T(6 × 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5064 := ((T(-9 + T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + (T(5) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5065 := (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5066 := (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
- 5067 := (-9 + (T(8) + ((7 × 6) × T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5068 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) × (6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5069 := (-9 + ((8 × T((7 + T(6)))) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 5070 := (T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) × (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 5071 := (-9 + ((T(8) + (T(T(7)) + T(6 + 5))) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))

$$\begin{aligned}
5112 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) - (T(4) - T(5))) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5113 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5114 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5115 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 + 5)))) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5116 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5117 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5118 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5119 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5120 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (3 + T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5121 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - (4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5122 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3)) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5123 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5124 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (T(4) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5125 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5126 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5127 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5128 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5129 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(T(3))) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5130 &:= (T((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5131 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5132 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5133 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5134 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5135 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5136 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (4 - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5137 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5138 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5139 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5140 &:= (((-1 + T(T((2 + (3 + 4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5141 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5142 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T((T(3) \times T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5143 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5144 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5145 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) \times T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5146 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5147 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5148 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3) + T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5149 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3) + T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5150 &:= (-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5151 &:= T((T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5112 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) + (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5113 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times 7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5114 &:= (((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7))) + T(T((T(6) - 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5115 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5116 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5117 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5118 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) \times 7)) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5119 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(6 \times 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5120 &:= ((T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) \times 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5121 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + T(7)) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5122 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((T(7) + ((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5123 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5124 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7) + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5125 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(7) + T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5126 &:= ((-9 \times T((8 + (7 + 6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5127 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5128 &:= (T(((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T(T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5129 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8 + 7)) - T((6 + T(T(5)))))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5130 &:= ((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5131 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5132 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5133 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5134 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5135 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5136 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5137 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5138 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5139 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T((T(7) - (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5140 &:= (((-9 + T(T((8 + 7) - 6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5141 &:= (T((-9 + (T(T(8 + 7))/T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5142 &:= (-9 + T((8 - (T(7) - (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5143 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5144 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T((T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5145 &:= ((((-9 - T(8)) \times T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5146 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5147 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5148 &:= ((((-9 \times T(8)) - T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5149 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T((T(6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5150 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5151 &:= T(((((-9 - (8 - 7)) + T(T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5152 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T((T(3) + T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5153 &:= (-1 - (T((2^{T(3)})) - ((4 + T(T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5154 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5155 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5156 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5157 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5158 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5159 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - T(T((T(4) \times 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5160 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((T(T(4)) \times T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5161 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5162 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5163 &:= (T((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5164 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (4 + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5165 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5166 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T((T(T(4))/5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5167 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (4 + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5168 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5169 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) - 4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5170 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5171 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5172 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3)^4)) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5173 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5174 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5175 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5176 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5177 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5178 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5179 &:= (-1 - (T((2^{T(3)})) - T(T((T(4) + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5180 &:= (-1 \times (T((2^{T(3)})) - T(T((T(4) + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5181 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5182 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5183 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5184 &:= ((T((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5185 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3)^4) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5186 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5187 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5188 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(3)^4)) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5189 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (4 \times T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5190 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5191 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{T(3)} + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5152 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5153 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) + T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5154 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) - (6 - T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5155 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7 + 6) + T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5156 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T((T(7) + 6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5157 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + T((T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5158 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5159 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - T((T(6) \times (T(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5160 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5161 &:= (T((-9 + (T(T(8 + 7))/T(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5162 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5163 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 \times T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5164 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7) \times (T(6) + T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5165 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5166 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5167 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5168 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5169 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7) + T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5170 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5171 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (7 + T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5172 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5173 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times T(6 \times 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5174 &:= T(-9 \times T(8) + T(T(7))) + T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5175 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T((7 + 6 - 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5176 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5177 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7))) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5178 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5179 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (T(7) + T(T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5180 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6)) \times (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5181 &:= ((-9 \times T((8 + (7 + 6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5182 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5183 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5184 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) + T(7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5185 &:= ((T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5186 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5187 &:= (-9 + ((T((8 + T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5188 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5189 &:= ((-9 + T((8 + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5190 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times T(7)) + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5191 &:= ((-9 \times T((8 + (7 + 6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5232 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 5232 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + ((6 \times 5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5233 &:= ((-1-2) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 5233 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 \times T(6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5234 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2+3))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 5234 &:= ((-9 + T((8 + (T(7) + T(6+5)))))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5235 &:= ((T((-1 \times 2 + T(3+4))) \times T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) & 5235 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) \times T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5236 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))) & 5236 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5237 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 5237 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 - T(6 \times 5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5238 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 5238 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5239 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5239 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T((7+6-5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5240 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 5240 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7+6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5241 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 5241 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T(((T(7) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5242 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 5242 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + T(((6 \times 5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5243 &:= (T(((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 5243 &:= (T(((-9 + T((8 + (7+6)))) - T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5244 &:= ((-1-2-3) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5244 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5245 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5245 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + (T(6 \times 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5246 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5246 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6-5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5247 &:= (-1-2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 5247 &:= (-9 \times (T((T(8) + 7)) + (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5248 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 5248 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5249 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) \times (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 5249 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - T(T(7+6)) + T(T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5250 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 5250 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5251 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 5251 &:= (-9 + ((T(T((8-7+6))) + T(T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5252 &:= (-1 + T((T(T(2 \times 3) \times 4))/(5+6+7+8+9))) & 5252 &:= (-9 + 8 + T(((7 \times 6) + 5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5253 &:= T((-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 5253 &:= T((-9 - (T(8+7) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5254 &:= (-1+2 + T((T(T(T(3)) \times 4))/(5+6+7+8+9))) & 5254 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (T(7) + T(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5255 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5255 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7+6) \times T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5256 &:= (T(((-1+2) \times 3)) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5256 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5257 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 5257 &:= (-9 - (((8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 - T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5258 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5258 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5259 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5259 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5260 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((4 + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5260 &:= (T((-9-8 + T(7+6))) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5261 &:= (T(((-1+2) \times 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5261 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + 7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5262 &:= ((-1+2 + T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5262 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(T(8)) \times 7)/T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5263 &:= (T(((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 5263 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5264 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3+4)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5264 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7+6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5265 &:= ((T(-1+2+3) \times (4 \times T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 5265 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5266 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 5266 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6-5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5267 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 5267 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(7) \times T(T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5268 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 5268 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5269 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5269 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T((7+T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5270 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) - (T((T(4) + T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 5270 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5271 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5271 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(T(7))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5272 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times (4+T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 5272 &:= (-9 + (T((T((T(8)+7))/(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5273 &:= ((-1-2+T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5273 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)+6)+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5274 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5274 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) - 7) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5275 &:= ((-1 - T(((2+3) \times 4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))) & 5275 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7+6)) \times 5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5276 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5276 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5277 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5277 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 \times (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5278 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5278 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5279 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 5279 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7+6) + 5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5280 &:= (T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) \times (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))) & 5280 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5281 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 5281 &:= (T((-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5282 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (T(3) + T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 5282 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5283 &:= (T((-1-2 + ((3+4) \times T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9) & 5283 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (7 \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5284 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T((T(T(3)) - 4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 5284 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(7+6) + (T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5285 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) - 4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 5285 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) \times T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5286 &:= (T((-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 5286 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5287 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 5287 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
5288 &:= (T((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 5288 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 \times T(6)))) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
5289 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 5289 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5290 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (T((4+T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 5290 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) - T(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5291 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) \times (T(4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 5291 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5292 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 5292 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7)) - T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5293 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4) - T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 5293 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5294 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) \times T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 5294 &:= T(-9 \times T(8) + T(T(7))) + T(T(6)) + T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5295 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5295 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7+6))) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5296 &:= -1+2 \times T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9) & 5296 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) - (5 + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5297 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T((4+(5+6))) \times (7+8+9)))) & 5297 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T((7+T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5298 &:= (T((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 5298 &:= (-9 - (T(((8 \times 7) + 6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5299 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5299 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (T(7) + T(6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5300 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3))) + (4 \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5300 &:= (((T(-9+8+T(7)) - T(6)) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5301 &:= (T((T((-1+T(2+3))) - 4) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5301 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7+6)))) - (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5302 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((T(T(3)) \times T(4)) + (5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) & 5302 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - 7)) \times (T(6) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5303 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 5303 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5304 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times T((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 5304 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7+6) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
5305 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5305 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5306 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(4) - ((5+6) \times T(7+8+9)))) & 5306 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5307 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 5307 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5308 &:= (-1-2 + (T((3+T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5308 &:= (T((-9 + T((8 + (7+6)))) - T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5309 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) & 5309 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(T((7+6-5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5310 &:= (((-1+T((2+(3+4)))) \times T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9) & 5310 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5311 &:= (T(((((-1+2) \times 3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 5311 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6-5) + T(4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5312 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5313 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5314 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5315 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5316 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5317 &:= (((-1 - 2) - T(T(3 + 4))) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5318 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5319 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5320 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) - 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5321 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times (3 - T(T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5322 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5323 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5324 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5325 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5326 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5327 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5328 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5329 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(4 + 5))) - (T(6) - T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5330 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5331 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times (3 - T(T(4)))))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5332 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5333 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5334 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5335 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5336 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5337 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5338 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times 3 + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5339 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5340 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(3 + 4))) \times T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5341 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T((T(T(3)) + 4)) \times T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5342 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(4) + T((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5343 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5344 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5345 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T((4 + T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5346 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5347 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5348 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T((T(T(4))/5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5349 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5350 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5351 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5312 &:= -9 - 8 \times T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5313 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5314 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5315 &:= ((-9 \times T(((8 + 7) - 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5316 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + T(7)) \times 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5317 &:= T(-9 \times T(8) + T(T(7))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5318 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5319 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5320 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times ((7 + 6) \times T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5321 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5322 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(8) + T(7)) \times 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5323 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5324 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5325 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5326 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - ((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5328 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (6 \times (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5329 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T((7 + 6 - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5330 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5331 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7 + 6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5332 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - T((T(6) \times (T(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5333 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5334 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5335 &:= ((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T(T(6)) - 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5336 &:= ((-9 + (T(((8 + 7) - 6)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5337 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) + T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5338 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(T(7)) - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5339 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7 + 6) + (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5340 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) \times T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5341 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5342 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5343 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5344 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5345 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5346 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5347 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T((T(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5348 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + 6))) - (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5349 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times 6) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5350 &:= ((T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))) \times 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5351 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5352 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5353 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5354 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times 3) - 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5355 &:= (-1 + T(((2^{T(3)}) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5356 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5357 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((3 - (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5358 &:= T(-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5359 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) + T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5360 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5361 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5362 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5363 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5364 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 + 4 + 5) - (6 \times T(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5365 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5366 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times (3 - T(T(4)))))) + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5367 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5368 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - T((T((4 \times T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5369 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) \times T(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5370 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5371 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5372 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5373 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\
5374 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5375 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + ((T(T(4)) \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5376 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\
5377 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\
5378 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(3 + 4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5379 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(3 + 4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5380 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (4 \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5381 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((3^4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5382 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5383 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5384 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5385 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5386 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5387 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(4)))/5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5388 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3)^4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5389 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3)^4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5390 &:= ((T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)))/T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5391 &:= (T((-1 - (2 \times (3 - T(T(4)))))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5352 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) \times (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5353 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5354 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 \times (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5355 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5356 &:= T((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5357 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5358 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + 7) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5359 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - T(7)) \times (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5360 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5361 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5362 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5363 &:= (T((T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5364 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (T(7) - (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5365 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times T(7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5366 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5367 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (T(7) + 6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5368 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5369 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5370 &:= ((-9 \times T((T(8 + 7)/6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5371 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5372 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) + ((T(6) - T(T(5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5373 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5374 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times T(6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5375 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5376 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5377 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) + T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5378 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + 6))) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5379 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5380 &:= ((-9 \times T((T(8 + 7)/6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5381 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5382 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) \times T(7)) - (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5383 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times ((7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5384 &:= (((-9 \times 8 \times T(7))/6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5385 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5386 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5387 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5388 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(7) + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5389 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5390 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) - T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5391 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 + 7) - 6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5392 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3))^4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5393 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5394 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T((T(T(4)))/5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5395 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5396 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5397 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5398 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times 4) \times (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5399 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) \times (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5400 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) \times (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5401 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(3 + 4) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5402 &:= ((-1 - T(2 + T(3))) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5403 &:= (T(((T(-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5404 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5405 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5406 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5407 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5408 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5409 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (4 + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5410 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(4)) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5411 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5412 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times (4 + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5413 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5414 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5415 &:= (T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)) \times (4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5416 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5417 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5418 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) \times (4 - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5419 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5420 &:= ((-1 + T((2 \times (T(3) \times (4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5421 &:= (T((-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + T(4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5422 &:= (-1 - (2 \times T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5423 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5424 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T((T(T(3)) - 4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5425 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5426 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5427 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5428 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5429 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + 3)) \times T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5430 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5431 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5392 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (6 \times 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5393 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (7 - 6))) - T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5394 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5395 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5396 &:= ((-9 + T((8 + (T(7 + 6) + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5397 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5398 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5399 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T((7 + 6 - 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5400 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5401 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5402 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7))) - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5403 &:= (-9 - (((T(8) - T(7)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5404 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5405 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5406 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5407 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5408 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) + 6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5409 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5410 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5411 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (7 + 6))) + (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5412 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5413 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5414 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5415 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((7 + T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5416 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5417 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5418 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times 6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5419 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) + T((T(6) - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5420 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5421 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((T(6) - T(T(5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5422 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5423 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (7 - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5424 &:= (-9 - (T(8 \times 7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5425 &:= ((-9 \times T((T(8 + 7)/6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5426 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (7 + 6)))) - (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5427 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T((7 + 6 - 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5428 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5429 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + ((7 - 6) - T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5430 &:= (-9 - (T((8 + T(7))) - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5431 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((7 - 6) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5432 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T((T(3)+4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5433 &:= ((-1+2-3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5434 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5435 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5436 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5437 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(T(4))+T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5438 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5439 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5440 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((T(4)+T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5441 &:= (T(((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5442 &:= ((-1+2+T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5443 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5444 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - T(T((4+T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\
5445 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3))) - T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5446 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5447 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5448 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) \times ((T(T(4))/5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5449 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5450 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) - T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5451 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5452 &:= -1+2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(5+6)) - T(7+8+9) \\
5453 &:= ((-1-2+T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5454 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5455 &:= T(T(-1+T(2+3))) - T(T(4)) - T(T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
5456 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
5457 &:= (-1-2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5458 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5459 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times (T(T(3))) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5460 &:= ((-1+2+T(3)) \times T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5461 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5462 &:= (T((T((-1+T(2+3))) - 4)) + ((5+6) + T(7+8+9))) \\
5463 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5464 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
5465 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5466 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(T(3))) - (T((4+T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5467 &:= (-1-2) \times T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times T(T(T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5468 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T((4+T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5469 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T((T(T(4))/5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5470 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) + T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5471 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) \times ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5432 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) \times (T(7) - T(6)))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5433 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times T(7)) - T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5434 &:= (T((-9-8+(7 \times T(6)))) - T(T((T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5435 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8)-7-6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5436 &:= ((-9+T((8 \times (7+6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5437 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (7+T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5438 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - ((T(6) - T(T(5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5439 &:= ((-9+T((8 \times (7+6)))) - (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
5440 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5441 &:= ((-9+T((8+(T(7+6)+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5442 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
5443 &:= (-9-8+T((T(7)+(T(6+5)+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5444 &:= ((-9+(T(8) \times T((T(7)-(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5445 &:= (T(T((-9+T(8))-7-6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5446 &:= (-9+(T((8 \times (7+6)))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
5447 &:= (-9+(T(((T(8)-T(7)) \times (6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5448 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times (T(7)+T(T(6)))) - (5+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5449 &:= ((-9+((T(T(8))+7) \times 6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5450 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+(7 \times (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5451 &:= (-9+((T(T(8))-T(T(7))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5452 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7+6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5453 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) - T((T(5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5454 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - 5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5455 &:= (((-9 \times (8-7-6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5456 &:= ((-9+T((8 \times (7+6)))) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
5457 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8)+T(7+6))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5458 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7)+T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5459 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5460 &:= T(((((-9+8) \times 7) + T(T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5461 &:= (-9+(T((8+(T(7+6)+5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5462 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5463 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (T(7) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5464 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5465 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6))) \times T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5466 &:= (-9+(T((8 \times (7+6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5467 &:= ((((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5468 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5469 &:= ((-9+((T(T(8))-T(7)) \times (6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5470 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+(7 \times (6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
5471 &:= ((-9+(T(8) \times ((7+6) \times T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5472 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) \times ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5473 &:= (T((-1-2+T((T(3)+4)))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5474 &:= ((-1+T((T(T(2+3)) - T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5475 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5476 &:= ((-1+(2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5477 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2+3)) - T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
5478 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5479 &:= (-1 + ((2+T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5480 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5481 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5482 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5483 &:= -1-2+T(T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5484 &:= -2+T(T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5485 &:= T(-1+T(2 \times (3+4))) - 5+6+7+8+9 \\
5486 &:= T(T(T(-1+2) \times 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5487 &:= -1+2+T(T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5488 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5489 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - T((4+T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5490 &:= (T((-1+T((2+(3+4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
5491 &:= (T((T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5492 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5493 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+T(3))) - (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5494 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+T(3))) - (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5495 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
5496 &:= (T((T((-1+T(2+3))) - 4) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5497 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((T(3)^4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5498 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5499 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5500 &:= ((-1+T((2+T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5501 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5502 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3) + (4 \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5503 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5504 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T((4 \times T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
5505 &:= (T((-1+T((2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5506 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4+T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5507 &:= (-1 + (T(2+T(3)) \times T((4 - ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
5508 &:= T(-1+2+T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5509 &:= ((-1+T(T((2 \times (3+4)))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5510 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5511 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5472 &:= ((-9+8+T(7)) - ((T(6) - T(T(5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5473 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + T(((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
5474 &:= ((-9+T(T(8))) - (T(7 \times 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5475 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5476 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - T(T(6))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5477 &:= (((-9+T((8+T(7)))) \times 6) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5478 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(6))) + (T(5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5479 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5480 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 \times 7) - T(T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5481 &:= ((-9+T(T(8))) - ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5482 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5483 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6))) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5484 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5485 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + ((7 - (6+5)) \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5486 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5487 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (T(7) + T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5488 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) + T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5489 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T((T(7) - (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5490 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5491 &:= ((-9-8) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5492 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((T(6) - T(T(5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5493 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T(((T(7) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5494 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times (7 \times T(6))) - (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5495 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5496 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5497 &:= (((-9+T((8+T(7)))) \times 6) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5498 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5499 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times ((T(7) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5500 &:= (((-9+T(8+7)) - (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5501 &:= ((-9+T(((8+(7+6)) \times 5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5502 &:= (((-9+T((T(8)+7))) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5503 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + T((T(6) \times 5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5504 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times (7 \times T(6))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5505 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) + 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5506 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7+6) + T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5507 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5508 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((T(T(7) - (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5509 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T((T(7) - (6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5510 &:= (T(T((-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T(6+5)))))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5511 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5512 &:= (T((-1-2+T((T(3)+4))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
5513 &:= (-1 - (T(T((T(2+3)-4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5514 &:= (-1 + (T((T((2 \times (3+4))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5515 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5516 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4 + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5517 &:= ((-1-2) - ((3 \times 4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5518 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 \times 4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5519 &:= (-1 + (T((2+T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5520 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5521 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5522 &:= ((-1-2) - ((T(T(T(3))) - T(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5523 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5524 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (4 - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5525 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3))) - T(4))) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5526 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5527 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (4 - (T((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5528 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2+T(3))) \times (4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5529 &:= ((-1+T(T((2 \times (3+4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5530 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5531 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T((3 \times 4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5532 &:= ((-1-2+T(((3+4) \times T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5533 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(((3+4) \times T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5534 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5535 &:= (T(T((-1+(2 \times 3+4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5536 &:= ((-1+2+T(((3+4) \times T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5537 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - T((T(4 \times 5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
5538 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (T((T(4) + (5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5539 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3+4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5540 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5541 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(3)) - T(T((4+T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\
5542 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - T(T((4+T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\
5543 &:= (-1 + (T(2+T(3)) \times (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5544 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5545 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5546 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4 - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5547 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(3)) + T(T((4+T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5548 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T((T(4) + (5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
5549 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5550 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5551 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4 + T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5512 &:= ((-9 + (T((8+T(7))) \times 6)) - (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5513 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5514 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) - (6 - (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5515 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 \times (6+5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5516 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (7+6))) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5517 &:= ((-9+8) \times ((T(7) \times T(6)) - T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5518 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7) \times T(T(6))) - (5 \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5519 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + 7)) \times 6) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5520 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6))) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5521 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (7+6))) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5522 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5523 &:= T(T((-9) - 8 + T(7))) + T(T(6)) + T(T(T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
5524 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7 \times T(6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5525 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 \times 7) - T(T(6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5526 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5527 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (T(7) - (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5528 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5529 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5530 &:= (((T(-9+T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5531 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
5532 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + T((T(6) + (5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5533 &:= (((-9 - (T(T(8)) + T(7))) + 6^5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5534 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (7 - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5535 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5536 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5537 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5538 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + T(T((T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5539 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + 7)) \times 6) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5540 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (T(7) - 6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5541 &:= (-9 - (T((8+T(7))) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5542 &:= ((-9-8) \times (T(T(7)) - (6 + (T(T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5543 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5544 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5545 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5546 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 + (7+6)) \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5547 &:= ((-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) \times 6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5548 &:= (-9-8 + T(((T(7) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5549 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5550 &:= (T(T((-9+T(8)) - 7 - 6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5551 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5552 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5553 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5554 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5555 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5556 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5557 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5558 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4 \times 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5559 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5560 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5561 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5562 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(((3 \times T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5563 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((3 \times T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5564 &:= (-1 + T((T(2 + 3) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5565 &:= T((T((-1 + 2 \times T(3))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5566 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(((3 \times T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5567 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + ((4 \times T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5568 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5569 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5570 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5571 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5572 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4 \times 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5573 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5574 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5575 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5576 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - ((4 + T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5577 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + 4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5578 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5579 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4 + 5))) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5580 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (T(4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5581 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5582 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 - ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5583 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5584 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4^5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5585 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5586 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5587 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5588 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5589 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5590 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5591 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) \times ((4 - 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5552 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5553 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5554 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T((T(7) - (6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5555 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)))/T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5556 &:= (-9 + T(((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5557 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5558 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T((T(6) \times (T(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5559 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5560 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5561 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (7 + 6))) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5562 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5563 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7 + 6) \times 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5564 &:= (-9 + 8 + T(((T(7) - T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5565 &:= T(T((-9 + 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5566 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5567 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5568 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5569 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5570 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5571 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (7 + 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5572 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5573 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5574 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5575 &:= (T(T((-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T(6 + 5)))))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5576 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5577 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5578 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5579 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5580 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5581 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (7 + 6))) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5582 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5583 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5584 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5585 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - (6 + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5586 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T((T(6) \times (T(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5587 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times T(T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5588 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5589 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5590 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 \times 7) - T(T(6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5591 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 \times (7 + 6)) + T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5592 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(((3+4) \times T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5593 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(((3+4) \times T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5594 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5595 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times 3 + 4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5596 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5597 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + ((T(4)/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5598 &:= (T((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5599 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5600 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5601 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - 4) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5602 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5603 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times ((T(4)/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5604 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5605 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5606 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5607 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5608 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((3 - T((4 + T(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5609 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(T(4)))/5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5610 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5611 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - 4) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5612 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5613 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5614 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5615 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5616 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5617 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5618 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5619 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5620 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5621 &:= (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - 4) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5622 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + 4) \times T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5623 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3 + 4) \times T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5624 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5625 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5626 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + 4) \times T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5627 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5628 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5629 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5630 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5631 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5592 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T(((T(7) - T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5593 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((7 + (T(6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5594 &:= (-9 - (T(8 \times 7) + (6 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5595 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) + T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5596 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5597 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (6 - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5598 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5599 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5600 &:= (T(T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6))) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5601 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5602 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5603 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((T(7) + 6) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5604 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5605 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5606 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5607 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5608 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) - (T(6) - T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5609 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7 + 6) + T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5610 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5611 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5612 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5613 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 \times T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5614 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + T(((6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5615 &:= (-9 + (8 \times T((T(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5616 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times ((7 \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5617 &:= (((-9 + T((T(8) + 7))) \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5618 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((7 + (6 \times T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5619 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) + T(T(6)))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5620 &:= (T(T((-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T(6 + 5)))))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5621 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5622 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + 7))) \times (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5623 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) - (6 - T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5624 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5625 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + T(7)) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5626 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((T(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5627 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5628 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5629 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5630 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) + T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5631 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - (T(T(7)) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5632 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)}) \\
5633 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + T(3))) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5634 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5635 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5636 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5637 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5638 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5639 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times T(T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5640 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5641 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5642 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5643 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((3^4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5644 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5645 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5646 &:= (T(((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5647 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3^4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5648 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5649 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5650 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5651 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - ((4^5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5652 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5653 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5654 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5655 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5656 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5657 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5658 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5659 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + ((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5660 &:= ((T(((((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(T(4)))) \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5661 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T((T(T(4))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5662 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4)) + (T((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5663 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
5664 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(4)) - T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5665 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5666 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5667 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5668 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5669 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5670 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - 3) \times T(4))) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5671 &:= T((-1 \times 2 + (T((3 + 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5632 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times T(T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5633 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5634 &:= (-9 - (T(8 \times 7) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5635 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5636 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7 + 6)) + T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5637 &:= (((-9 + T((T(8) + 7))) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5638 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5639 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5640 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(7))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5641 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (T((6 \times T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5642 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times T(T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5643 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5644 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T((T(7 + 6)) + T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5645 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5646 &:= (((-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(T(7)))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5647 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5648 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(T(((7 - 6) \times 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5649 &:= (-9 - (T(8 \times 7) + (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5650 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5651 &:= (-9 - (T(8 \times 7) - ((6 + T(T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5652 &:= (((-9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(7))))/6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5653 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5654 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5655 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5656 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5657 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5658 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5659 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5660 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7 + 6)) + T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5661 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5662 &:= (-9 + T(((T(8 \times 7) - 6)/(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5663 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times T(7)) - (T(6) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5664 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(7 + 6)) + T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5665 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7 + 6) - T(5)))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5666 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5667 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) \times (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5668 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5669 &:= (T(((((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5670 &:= (-9 + 8 + T((T(7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5671 &:= T(((((-9 + 8) - 7 - 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5672 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(3) - (4 \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
5673 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T((T((4 \times T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5674 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5675 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5676 &:= ((-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5677 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5678 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5679 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5680 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5681 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5682 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5683 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5684 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5685 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5686 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (T(T((3 \times 4)) - 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5687 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times ((4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5688 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5689 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5690 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3 + 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5691 &:= (T(((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times 4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5692 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5693 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5694 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5695 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5696 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T((3 + 4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5697 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5698 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5699 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)} - T(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5700 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5701 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
5702 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5703 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5704 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times T(T(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
5705 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5706 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5707 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5708 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5709 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4) - T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5710 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
5711 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
5672 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5673 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7) \times T(T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5674 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 - 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5675 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5676 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5677 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5678 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5679 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (7 + (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5680 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7 + 6) + T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5681 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5682 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5683 &:= (-9 - (T((8 - 7 + 6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5684 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) - T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5685 &:= (T(T((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5686 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5687 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5688 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (((7 + 6) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5689 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5690 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5691 &:= (-9 - (((T(T(8)) - T(T(7))) \times 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5692 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5693 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) + (6 - T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5694 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(8) - 7) \times 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5695 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5696 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
5697 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5698 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5699 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5700 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5701 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5702 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5703 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) - T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5704 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5705 &:= (T(T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6))) - (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5706 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7 - 6) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5707 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5708 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7 + 6) + T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5709 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(7 + 6) + T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5710 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7 + 6))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5711 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5712 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5713 &:= (T(((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5714 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3+4)))))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
5715 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5716 &:= (T(T(((-1+2+3) \times 4))) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5717 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (T(3) + T(4+5)))))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
5718 &:= (T((-1-2 + ((3+4) \times T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5719 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) + (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5720 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))))) - T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5721 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5722 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5723 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 - T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\
5724 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5725 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5726 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))))) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5727 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3 + T(4))) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5728 &:= (T((-1+2 + (3^4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5729 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (T(T(3)) \times (4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5730 &:= ((T((-1 \times 2 + T(3+4))) \times T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5731 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5732 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5733 &:= (T(((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))))) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5734 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5735 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5736 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3))) - 4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5737 &:= (-1 - (2 \times T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5738 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5739 &:= ((T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) \times 4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5740 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2+3))) \times T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5741 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
5742 &:= ((-1-2 + (T(3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5743 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5744 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5745 &:= ((T(((-1+2) \times 3)) \times T(T(4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5746 &:= ((-1+2 + (T(3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5747 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + ((3+4) \times T(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
5748 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4+5)))))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
5749 &:= ((-1+2 + T((T(T(T(3))) - (4 + T(T(5)))))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5750 &:= ((-1+2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5751 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) - (4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5712 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5713 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5714 &:= (-9-8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5715 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + T(7)) - (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5716 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T(6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5717 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5718 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5719 &:= (((-9/(8+7) - 6) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5720 &:= (T(T(T((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6+5)))))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5721 &:= ((((-9+8+7)/6) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5722 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5723 &:= (T(((-9+8) \times (7+6)) + T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1) \\
5724 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5725 &:= (-9+8 + (T((T(7+6) + T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5726 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5727 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) + T(7))) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5728 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(6 \times 5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5729 &:= (-9+8 + (((T(7) \times T(6)) - T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5730 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times (T(7) + 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5731 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5732 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7+6))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5733 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5734 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5735 &:= (T(T((T(-9+8+7) - 6))) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5736 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5737 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6) + (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5738 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5739 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (7 \times 6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5740 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5741 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5742 &:= (((-9 + T((T(8) + 7))) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5743 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(7) \times T(T(6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5744 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5745 &:= (((-9-8 + T(T(7))) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5746 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) - T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5747 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + ((6 + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5748 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(8) - T(7)) \times T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5749 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (7 \times 6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
5750 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + T(6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5751 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + T(7)) \times (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5792 &:= ((-1 - T(2+3)) \times (4 - (T((5+6)) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
5793 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\
5794 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\
5795 &:= (-1 - (T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5796 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5797 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5798 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(3))) \times ((4 + T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5799 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times (T(3) \times 4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5800 &:= ((-1 - T(T(2 \times 3))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5801 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5802 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T((T(T(3)) + T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5803 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5804 &:= (-1 - (T(((2-3) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5805 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3+4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5806 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5807 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + ((3+4) \times T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5808 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5809 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5810 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2+3))) \times T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
5811 &:= (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5812 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5813 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5814 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - T((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5815 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5816 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5817 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5818 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + T(T((4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
5819 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5820 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5821 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + ((3+4) \times T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5822 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(T(4)))/5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5823 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T((5+6))) - (7+8+9)))) \\
5824 &:= (-1 - ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5825 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5826 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5827 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5828 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5829 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5830 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2+3))) \times T(T(4))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5831 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times (4 + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5792 &:= (T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + ((6 + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5793 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times ((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5794 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5795 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5796 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5797 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5798 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5799 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5800 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5801 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5802 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5803 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5804 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(T(6) + T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5805 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5806 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
5807 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5808 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5809 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5810 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5811 &:= (T(((((-9+8) - 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5812 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
5813 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7+6) + T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5814 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - ((T(6) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5815 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7+6))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5816 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + (7+6)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5817 &:= (-9 + ((T((8 + T(7))) \times 6) + T(5 + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5818 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + ((7+6) \times 5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5819 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5820 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) - T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5821 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5822 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5823 &:= ((-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(7))) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5824 &:= ((-9 + 8 + ((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5825 &:= (T((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5826 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) - (6 \times (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5827 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7) + T(6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5828 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7) + 6) - 5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
5829 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5830 &:= ((((-9+8) - 7 - 6) + T(T(5))) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5831 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T((T(7) - (6+5)))))) - T(4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5832 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(3)) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5833 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times 3 + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5834 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5835 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
5836 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5837 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
5838 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5839 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5840 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T((4+T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5841 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5842 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5843 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
5844 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times T(T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5845 &:= ((T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
5846 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + (T((T(4) \times (5+6))) - T(7+8+9)))) \\
5847 &:= ((-1-2) - ((3+T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5848 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5849 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) \times (T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5850 &:= (((-1-2) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
5851 &:= (-1+2 - ((3+T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5852 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5853 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) + T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
5854 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5855 &:= ((-1+T((2 \times (T(3) \times (4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5856 &:= (T((-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5857 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5858 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4) - (5+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5859 &:= (((-1-2) - T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5860 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5861 &:= (T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5862 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5863 &:= (T(((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5864 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) \times T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5865 &:= ((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) \times T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
5866 &:= T(T(T(-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5867 &:= -1+2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
5868 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
5869 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
5870 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + ((T(T(4)) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
5871 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
5832 &:= ((-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5833 &:= (T((((-9 + 8) \times (7+6)) + T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5834 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7+6) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5835 &:= ((-9-8+T((7+T(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5836 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7 - (6+5)) \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5837 &:= ((-9+T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5838 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + T((T(7) + (T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
5839 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5840 &:= (((-9+T(T(8))) - (7+T(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5841 &:= (((-9 \times T((T(8)+7)))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5842 &:= (((-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
5843 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7+6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5844 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7)) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5845 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5846 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5847 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T((T(6) - 5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5848 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5849 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(T(6) + T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5850 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5851 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5852 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5853 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5854 &:= ((-9 + ((T(T(8)) + 7) \times (6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
5855 &:= (((T(-9+T(8)) + (7+6)) \times T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5856 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5857 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(7+6) + T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5858 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
5859 &:= (-9 \times ((8+7) - T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5860 &:= ((-9+T((T(8) + ((7+6) - T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
5861 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + (7+6)) \times T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
5862 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5863 &:= (-9-8 + ((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
5864 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
5865 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) + (7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
5866 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T((6 \times T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5867 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T((7+6-5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
5868 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
5869 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(T(6) + T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
5870 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7+6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
5871 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + (7+6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5912 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5912 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7))) - T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5913 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((T(T(3)) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5913 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (7 \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5914 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5914 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5915 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5915 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(T(6)) + (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5916 &:= (T((-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 5916 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5917 &:= (-1 - (((2 - T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5917 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5918 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5918 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5919 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T((3 \times 4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5919 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7) \times 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5920 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5920 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5921 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5921 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - (7 + T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5922 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5922 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) - 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5923 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5923 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + (T(6) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5924 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5924 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + ((7 - 6) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5925 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 + (3 + 4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5925 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5926 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5926 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + (7 + 6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5927 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 5927 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5928 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(3))) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5928 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5929 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 5929 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5930 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5930 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(8) - T(T(7 + 6)))/5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5931 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5931 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8 + 7) - (6 + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5932 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T((4 + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5932 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T((7 + 6 - 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
5933 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - T((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5933 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5934 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - T((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5934 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5935 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(3)^4) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5935 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(T(6)) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5936 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 - 3) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5936 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5937 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5937 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7 + 6) + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5938 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5938 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) - 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5939 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5939 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5940 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 5940 &:= (T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
5941 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5941 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T((T(7) - (6 + 5)))))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5942 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times 4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5942 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5943 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5943 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T(((T(7) - T(6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5944 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)}) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5944 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5945 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5945 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5946 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 - T((4 \times T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5946 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5947 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5947 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5948 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times T(3))) - (T(4) \times T((T((5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 5948 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
5949 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (T(T(3)) - 4)) \times T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 5949 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
5950 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + (T(3) + T(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5950 &:= (T((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
5951 &:= -1 - 2 - T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 5951 &:= ((T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (T(6) + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6031 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6032 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + ((T(4)/5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6033 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T((T(3) \times 4)) - T(T((5+6)))))) + T(7+8+9) \\
6034 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3+4)))) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6035 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) + T(4))) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6036 &:= ((T((-1+T(2 \times T(3)))) \times (T(4)/5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
6037 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))))))) \\
6038 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6039 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6040 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3))) + T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6041 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (4 - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6042 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3+4) - T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6043 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3+4) - T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6044 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (T(3) + 4 + 5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6045 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4 + 5))) \times T(6+7+8+9)) \\
6046 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3+4) - T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6047 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6048 &:= (T((-1+2+(T(3)+T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6049 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (4 + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6050 &:= ((-1-2+T(3+4)) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
6051 &:= (-1+2+((T(T(3))+4) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6052 &:= (-1+2-((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6053 &:= (-1 - (T(((2 \times T(T(3))) - 4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6054 &:= (-1 \times (T(((2 \times T(T(3))) - 4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6055 &:= (((-1-2+T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6056 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(3^4))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6057 &:= ((-1-2+(T(T(3+4)) \times T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6058 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3+4)) \times T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6059 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(T(3+4))) \times (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
6060 &:= ((T(T((-1+2) \times (3+4))) \times T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6061 &:= ((-1+2+(T(T(3+4)) \times T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6062 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6063 &:= -1 \times 2 \times T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
6064 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6065 &:= (((-1+T(T(2+3))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6066 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6067 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6068 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6069 &:= ((-1+T((T(T(2+3)) - T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6070 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6031 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6032 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6033 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7 \times 6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6034 &:= ((-9+8) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6035 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6036 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (7+6))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6037 &:= ((-9+8+(T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6038 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(6) - 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
6039 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6040 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6041 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8+7))/6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6042 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6043 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7+6)) + T(5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6044 &:= ((-9+8) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6045 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((7+T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6046 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6047 &:= (-9+8+(T(7) \times (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6048 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) \times (7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6049 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + T((T(7+6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6050 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + T(7))) \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6051 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (T(T(7)) + 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6052 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6053 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6054 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6055 &:= ((T((-9+8+7) + T(6))) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
6056 &:= (((-9+T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) - T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6057 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (6 - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6058 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(6) - 5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
6059 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T((T(7+6) + T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
6060 &:= (((-9+T(T(8))) - T(T(7) - 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6061 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6062 &:= ((-9+T(8)) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6063 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(6) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6064 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (T(7) + (6 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6065 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(6) + (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6066 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (6 \times (T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6067 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6068 &:= (-9 - (T((8-7+6) - T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
6069 &:= (((-9 - T(8+7)) \times T(6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6070 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6071 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6072 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3 + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6073 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6074 &:= ((-1 + T((T((2 \times (3 + 4))) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6075 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6076 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6077 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6078 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6079 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6080 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6081 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6082 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6083 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T((T(T(4)) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6084 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 + 3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6085 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6086 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + 4))) - T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6087 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3 + 4)) \times (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6088 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3 + 4)) \times (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6089 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6090 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6091 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6092 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6093 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + T(((T(4)/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6094 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4)))) - T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6095 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6096 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T((T(T(4))/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6097 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6098 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6099 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((T(T(4)) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6100 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6101 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((3 + 4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6102 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(((T(3 + 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6103 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((T(3 + 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6104 &:= (-1 + T((2 + (T((3 + 4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6105 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6106 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(((T(3 + 4) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6107 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + T(4)) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6108 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6109 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T((T(T(4)) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6110 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6071 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (T((T(7) + 6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6072 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6))) \times (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6073 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((7 + T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6074 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6075 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6076 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6077 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6078 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6079 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times ((T(T(7)) \times 6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6080 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (7 + 6)))) \times (T(5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6081 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6082 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times T(T(6))) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6083 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times T(T(6))) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6084 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) \times T((T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6085 &:= (-9 + (((8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6086 &:= ((-9 + T((T(T(8 + 7))/T(6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6087 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6088 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6089 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((7 + T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6090 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6091 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - (7 - T(6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6092 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7 + 6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6093 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6094 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(((T(7) - 6) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6095 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6096 &:= (-9 + T(((8 \times T(7)) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6097 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6098 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6099 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6100 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6) + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6101 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6102 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6103 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7 + 6) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6104 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6105 &:= T((-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6106 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6107 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6108 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6109 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6110 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + 6)) \times T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6111 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6112 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T((T(T(4)) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6113 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6114 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6115 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6116 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6117 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3 + 4)) \times T(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6118 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3 + 4)) \times T(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6119 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6120 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times T(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6121 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3 + 4)) \times T(5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6122 &:= (-1 - 2) \times T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6123 &:= -1 - 2 + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6124 &:= -1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6125 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9 \\
6126 &:= -1 + 2 \times T(T(3 \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6127 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6128 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(3 + 4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6129 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(3 + 4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6130 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6131 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T((3 + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6132 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6133 &:= (((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6134 &:= (-1 + (T((T((2 \times (3 + 4))) + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6135 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6136 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6137 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3 + T(4)) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6138 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6139 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6140 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6141 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6142 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6143 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6144 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6145 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6146 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6147 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3) \times (T(4) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6148 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + 4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6149 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times T(T(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6150 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - T((T(T(T(4)))/5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6111 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6112 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (6 - (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6113 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (T(6) + (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6114 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6115 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6116 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6117 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + T(7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6118 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6119 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6120 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6121 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times T(7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6122 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(T(6)) - T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6123 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6124 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7 + 6) + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6125 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6126 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6127 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6128 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6129 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6130 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times T(6))) \times T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6131 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - ((6 \times 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6132 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6133 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6134 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T((T(7) + T(6))) \times 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6135 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6136 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6137 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6138 &:= ((-9 - (T(T(8)) + 7)) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6139 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6140 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6141 &:= (-9 - ((T(8 \times 7) - T(T(6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6142 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6143 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6144 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6145 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7 + 6) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6146 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6147 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times T(((7 + T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6148 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6149 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6150 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6151 &:= (-1+2-(T(3) \times (T(4) - T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6152 &:= (((-1+2-3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
6153 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6154 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6155 &:= ((-1+T((T(T(2+3)) - 4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6156 &:= (T((T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) - T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6157 &:= (-1-2+((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6158 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6159 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6160 &:= ((T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
6161 &:= (-1+2+((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6162 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3+4))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6163 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3+4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6164 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6165 &:= ((T((T(T(-1+2+3)) - 4)) \times 5) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
6166 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) + (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6167 &:= (-1+2+(T(3) + (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6168 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times T(T((T(T(4))/5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
6169 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6170 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6171 &:= ((-1 - T(T(2+3))) \times (4 - T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6172 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (4 \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
6173 &:= (-1+2+((3+T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
6174 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6175 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
6176 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (4 + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6177 &:= ((-1-2+(T(3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6178 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6179 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6180 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6181 &:= ((-1+2+(T(3) \times T(T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6182 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3)) + (4 \times T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
6183 &:= ((-1+2-3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6184 &:= ((T((-1+2) \times 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
6185 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) - (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
6186 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) - (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
6187 &:= (-1+2-(T(3) \times (4 - T((T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
6188 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6189 &:= ((-1+2+3) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
6190 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
6151 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6152 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6153 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6154 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
6155 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(6) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6156 &:= (-9 \times ((8+T(7)) - (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6157 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7+6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6158 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6159 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6160 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6161 &:= ((T(-9+8+7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6162 &:= (T(T((-9+(8+(7+6)))) + T(T((T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6163 &:= (-9-8+((T(T(7))+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6164 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6165 &:= ((-9+8+(T(T(7))+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
6166 &:= (-9+(T((T(8)+T(7))) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6167 &:= (((-9+8+7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
6168 &:= (((-9 - (T(8)+7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6169 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6170 &:= ((-9 - T((T(8)+(7+6))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
6171 &:= (-9-8 - (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6172 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6173 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6174 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6175 &:= ((-9+(8 \times (7+6))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6176 &:= ((-9+(8 \times T((T(7)+6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
6177 &:= (-9+(T((8 \times (7+6))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6178 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6179 &:= (-9+8+((T(T(7))+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6180 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
6181 &:= (T(((9 \times (8+7)) + T(T(6)))) - (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6182 &:= ((-9+(T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (6+5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6183 &:= (T((-9+(8+(7+6)))) + T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6184 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8+7)) - (6^5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6185 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6186 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6187 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6188 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6189 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times (7+6)) + T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
6190 &:= ((-9+(T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6191 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6191 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((6 \times 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6192 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6192 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6193 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (T((T(4) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6193 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T((7 + T(6))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6194 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6194 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T((7 + T(6))) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6195 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6195 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6196 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T((3 \times 4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6196 &:= (T((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6197 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(4)) \times T((5 + 6))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6197 &:= ((-9 + T((T((8 + (7 + 6))) - T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6198 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6198 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 + (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6199 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6199 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6200 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(4) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 6200 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6201 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6201 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6202 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) + (4 - T(T(5)))))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6202 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6203 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6203 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6204 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 - (3 + 4)) + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6204 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6205 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6205 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6206 &:= T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6206 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6207 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6207 &:= (-9 + T((T((8 + (7 + 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6208 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6208 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6209 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6209 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6210 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6210 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6211 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6211 &:= (T(((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + T(T(6)))) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6212 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6212 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6213 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6213 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6214 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6214 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6215 &:= (-1 + T((T(2 \times 3) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6215 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6216 &:= T((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6216 &:= T((-9 + T(((8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6217 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6217 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (6 + 5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6218 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times T(3))) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6218 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6219 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6219 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (7 + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6220 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6220 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6221 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6221 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T((T(7) + 6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6222 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6222 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6223 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6223 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7 + 6) + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6224 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6224 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6225 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6225 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6226 &:= -1 + 2 \times T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 6226 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6227 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6227 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6228 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (4 - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 6228 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6229 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6229 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6230 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 6230 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7 \times 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6231 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3 \times 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6232 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6233 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6234 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(4) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6235 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6236 &:= (-1 \times (2^{T(3)} - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6237 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6238 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6239 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(3)) \times T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6240 &:= ((T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6241 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6242 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6243 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6244 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6245 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6246 &:= (T((T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) - (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
6247 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(T(3))) - T((T(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6248 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6249 &:= (((-1 \times T(T(T(2 + 3))))/T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6250 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6251 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3 \times 4))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6252 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6253 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + T(3))) + (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6254 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6255 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (T(T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6256 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6257 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6258 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6259 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6260 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6261 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((T(3) \times 4) - T(T((5 + 6)))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6262 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6263 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6264 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6265 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 + T(3)))) \times T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6266 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - ((4^5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6267 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6268 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6269 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6270 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6231 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6232 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6233 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6234 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6235 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6) + (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6236 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6237 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6238 &:= ((-9 \times T((8 - 7) + T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6239 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times 6) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6240 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6241 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T((T(7) + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6242 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) + 6^5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6243 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6244 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6245 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6246 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - ((7 + T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6247 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6248 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6249 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times T(7)) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6250 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6251 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((6 \times T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6252 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6253 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6254 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6) + T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6255 &:= (-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) - (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6256 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + T((T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6257 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + 6^5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6258 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6259 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6260 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6261 &:= (((-9 \times T((8 + T(7))))/6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6262 &:= (-9 + (T((T((8 + (7 + 6))) - T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6263 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6264 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times T(7)) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6265 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6266 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((T(6) \times 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6267 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times 6) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6268 &:= (T((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T(T(6)))) - (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6269 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6270 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times (T(7) - 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6271 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
6272 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6273 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times 4)) - T(T((T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6274 &:= (-1 - ((T(2^{T(3)}))/4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6275 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 + T(3)))) \times T(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6276 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6277 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6278 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6279 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6280 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6281 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(T(4))) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6282 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6283 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times 4)) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6284 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6285 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6286 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (4 + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6287 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6288 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6289 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6290 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6291 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6292 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6293 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6294 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6295 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6296 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T((T(T(3)) + T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6297 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) + 4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6298 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6299 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6300 &:= (T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
6301 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6302 &:= (((-1 - T(T(2 \times 3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6303 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6304 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6305 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6306 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6307 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6308 &:= (-1 - (T((2 - (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6309 &:= (-1 - (((2 - T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
6310 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
6271 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6272 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6273 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7 + 6) + T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6274 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (7 + (6 \times T(T(5)))))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6275 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 - (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6276 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (T(7) \times T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6277 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6278 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6279 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(5))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6280 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6281 &:= ((-9 \times ((T(T(8)) - T(T(7 + 6)))/5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6282 &:= (T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6283 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((7 \times (T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
6284 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6285 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7 \times 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6286 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T((T(7) + 6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6287 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6) + 5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6288 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((6 \times T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6289 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) - T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6290 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) + T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6291 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(T(7)) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6292 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6 + 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6293 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6294 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times 7) + T(((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6295 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(7 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6296 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((6 \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6297 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6298 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6299 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + 7)) + (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6300 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6301 &:= ((-9 \times T(8 + 7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6302 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6303 &:= (((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7)))/6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6304 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6305 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (T(7) - T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6306 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
6307 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6) + (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6308 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
6309 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7 + 6) - T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
6310 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6791 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3 \times 4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6792 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3) + 4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6793 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3) + 4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6794 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times 3 + 4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6795 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) - (4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6796 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3) + 4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6797 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
 6798 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6799 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6800 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6801 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6802 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6803 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6804 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6805 &:= (T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6806 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6807 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6808 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6809 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6810 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6811 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6812 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6813 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + ((4 + T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6814 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + ((4 \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6815 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6816 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6817 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6818 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6819 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(4) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
 6820 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 6821 &:= (T((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) - T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 6822 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3 + 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6823 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6824 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3 + 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6825 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3 + 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6826 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6827 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + ((4 + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 6828 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6829 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
 6830 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - 4) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6791 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - ((7 - 6) - T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6792 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7 + 6)) \times (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6793 &:= (T(((-9 + T((8 + (7 + 6)))) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6794 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 6795 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8) - 7) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6796 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6797 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7 \times 6) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6798 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6799 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T((7 + T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6800 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6801 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6802 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6803 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6804 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8))/7) \times (6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6805 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6806 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6807 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(((6 + T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6808 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6809 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T((7 + T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6810 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6811 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6812 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6813 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7 + 6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6814 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (7 + 6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 6815 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6816 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6817 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6818 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (T(6) \times T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6819 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6820 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 6821 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6822 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8) - 7) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6823 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (7 + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
 6824 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7 + 6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
 6825 &:= (T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6826 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(T(7) - 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6827 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6828 &:= (((-9 \times (T(8) \times T(7)))/T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
 6829 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 6830 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6871 & := (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6872 & := ((-1 + T((2 \times (T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\6873 & := (T((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\6874 & := (-1 - ((2+3) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\6875 & := ((-1 \times (2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\6876 & := (((-1+2) \times 3)^4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\6877 & := (-1+2 + (3^4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\6878 & := (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6879 & := ((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\6880 & := (-1+2 + ((T(T(3)) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6881 & := ((-1-2) - (T(T(3+4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\6882 & := (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3+4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\6883 & := (((-1+2+T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\6884 & := (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\6885 & := (-1+2 - (T(T(3+4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\6886 & := (T((-1+(2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\6887 & := (-1+2 + (T(3+T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6888 & := (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\6889 & := (-1 \times 2 - ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6890 & := (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\6891 & := ((-1-2) \times (T(3+4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6892 & := (-1+2 - ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6893 & := ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\6894 & := (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (4 + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\6895 & := ((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\6896 & := (-1 - (T((T(T(2+3)))/T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6897 & := (-1 \times (T((T(T(2+3)))/T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6898 & := (T((-1+T((2+3+T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\6899 & := (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\6900 & := (-1-2 + T((3 \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\6901 & := (-1 \times 2 + T((3 \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\6902 & := (-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\6903 & := T(((-1+2) \times (3 \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\6904 & := (-1+2 + T((3 \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)))) \\6905 & := (-1 + (T(((2^3+4) - T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\6906 & := (T((((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\6907 & := ((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\6908 & := (-1 - (T((T(2+3) - 4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\6909 & := ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\6910 & := (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6871 & := (-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6872 & := (T((-9+T(8+7))) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\6873 & := ((-9 \times (T(8) + (T(7) - T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\6874 & := ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6875 & := ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6876 & := (T((-9+T(8+7))) + (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\6877 & := ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\6878 & := (T((-9+(T(8+7)+6))) - (T(5)+4+3+2+1)) \\6879 & := ((-9 \times (T(8)+7)) + (6+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6880 & := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7+T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\6881 & := ((-9+T(8)) - (T((7+T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6882 & := (T((-9+T(8+7))) + T((T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6883 & := (((-9 \times (T(8) \times T(7)))/T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\6884 & := ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\6885 & := ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7+6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\6886 & := (((-9-8) \times (T(7)-6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\6887 & := (-9+8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6888 & := (T((-9+(T(8+7)+6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\6889 & := (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\6890 & := ((-9 \times ((8+7) \times 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\6891 & := (-9 + (T((T(8)-7-6)) \times (T(5)+4+3+2+1))) \\6892 & := (T((-9+T(8+7))) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\6893 & := ((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7)+6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\6894 & := ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6895 & := (((-9 + (T(8) \times (7+6))) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\6896 & := (T((-9+(T(8) + (T(7+6) - T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\6897 & := (-9 + (T(8+7) + T(((6+T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\6898 & := (T((-9+(T(8+7)+6))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\6899 & := (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\6900 & := (-9 - (T(8+7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6901 & := (T((-9+(T(8) + T(7+6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\6902 & := ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6903 & := T((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) + (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6904 & := ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\6905 & := (((-9-8) \times T(7)) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\6906 & := ((-9 - (8+7)) + ((6+T(T(5))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\6907 & := ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\6908 & := ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7+T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\6909 & := (((-9+T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\6910 & := (((-9-8) \times 7) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6911 &:= (((-1 - T(2+3)) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6911 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
 6912 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3+4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6912 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (T(7+6) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6913 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3+4))) + (T(T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 6913 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6914 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6914 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6915 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) + (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6915 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 6916 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + 4 + 5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 6916 &:= (-9 - (T(8 \times 7) - (6 + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6917 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) - T(T(5)))))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 6917 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
 6918 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3+4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6918 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 6919 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3+4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6919 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 6920 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (T((4 + T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 6920 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 6921 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 6921 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) + T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6922 &:= (-1 + ((2³⁺⁴) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6922 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6923 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6923 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6924 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6924 &:= (((-9 \times 8 \times T(7))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 6925 &:= ((-1 - T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 6925 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7+6)))) + T((T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6926 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6926 &:= (((-9 - T(8+7)) \times 6) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6927 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 6927 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - 6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 6928 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 6928 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6))) + (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 6929 &:= (-1 + ((T(2+3) - 4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 6929 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6930 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4))) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 6930 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 6931 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 6931 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) + ((7+6) + T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 6932 &:= (-1 + (T(((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 6932 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (6 - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6933 &:= (T(((1-2) \times (T(3) - T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) & 6933 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 6934 &:= ((-1 + T(2+3)) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6934 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7+6) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6935 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 6935 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7-6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6936 &:= (T((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) - T(T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6936 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 6937 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (4 + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6937 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7-6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6938 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6938 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) + 6 + 5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 6939 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6939 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times 7) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6940 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 6940 &:= ((-9 + T((T(T(8)))/(7+6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 6941 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6941 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - (T(7+6) - T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 6942 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6942 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T(7))) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6943 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) + (T(4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6943 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6944 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3+4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6944 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6945 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3+4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6945 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 6946 &:= (-1 + 2 - (3 \times (T(4) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6946 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + ((6 \times T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 6947 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) + (4 - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6947 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))))) \\
 6948 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3+4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6948 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) + 7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 6949 &:= ((T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)))/T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 6949 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7+6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 6950 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) + (T(4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6950 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6951 &:= (((-1-2-3) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6951 &:= (((-9-T(8)) \times 7) + (6+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6952 &:= (((-1+2-T(T(T(3))))/T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6952 &:= ((((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6953 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 6953 &:= (T((-9+(T(8+7)+6))) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
6954 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3+4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6954 &:= ((-9+((T(T(8))-T(7)) \times (6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
6955 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 6955 &:= ((-9+T(T(8+7))) - (T(6) + (5 \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6956 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) + (4 - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6956 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6957 &:= (-1-2+((T(T(T(3))) - 4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6957 &:= ((-9 \times (8+T(7))) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6958 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 6958 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6959 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) \times ((4-5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6959 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6960 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3+4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6960 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + (T(6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6961 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6961 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7+6)))) - (5+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6962 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2+3))/T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6962 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)-6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6963 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - (4 + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6963 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7+6)) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6964 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) - (4 + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6964 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6965 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+T(3))) + (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 6965 &:= (-9 - (T((8+(7+6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6966 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + (3+4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6966 &:= (((-9-T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6967 &:= (((-1+2-3) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6967 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6968 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - (T(4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6968 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
6969 &:= ((-1+2-(3+4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6969 &:= ((-9-8+(T(T(7)) \times (6+T(5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6970 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((T(4)+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6970 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + (6+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6971 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T((T(3+4) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 6971 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7+6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
6972 &:= (-1-2+((T(3)+4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6972 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times T(7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6973 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3)+4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6973 &:= (T((-9+(T(8+7)+6))) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6974 &:= ((-1+2 \times T(3)) \times (4+T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 6974 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6975 &:= (T(((T(-1+T(2+3)) - (4+5))) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6975 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8)-7-6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6976 &:= (-1+2+((T(3)+4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6976 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((T(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6977 &:= ((-1+2-(3-4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6977 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7+T(T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6978 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((T(4)+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6978 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6979 &:= ((-1-(2-(3+4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6979 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (T(7)+6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6980 &:= ((-1 \times (2-(3+4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6980 &:= (((T(-9+T(8)) + T(7+6)) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
6981 &:= (T(-1+2+3) - (4 - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 6981 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7+6)))) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
6982 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6982 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (6 - (5 \times T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6983 &:= (-1 - (T((2+T(T(3)))) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))))) & 6983 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (T(T((7+6-5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6984 &:= (-1 \times (T((2+T(T(3)))) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))))) & 6984 &:= (-9-8-(T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
6985 &:= (T((-1-(2-(3+4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6985 &:= (-9 - ((T(8 \times 7)/6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6986 &:= (T((-1+((2^{T(3)}) + T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 6986 &:= ((-9+T((8 \times (7+6)))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6987 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6987 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
6988 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3+4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 6988 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
6989 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6989 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7+6))) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
6990 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - ((4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 6990 &:= (-9-8-(T(T(7)-6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6991 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 6992 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) - (4 - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 6993 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + (4 + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 6994 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 6995 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + (T(4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 6996 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + 4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 6997 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + ((T(4) + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 6998 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 6999 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + (T(4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7000 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7001 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3 + 4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7002 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(4) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7003 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 7004 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3 + 4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7005 &:= (T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 7006 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7007 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7008 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (T(4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7009 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(4) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7010 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7011 &:= (T((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 7012 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7013 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7014 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7015 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 7016 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7017 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 + 3 + T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\ 7018 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7019 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7020 &:= (-1 + T((T((T(2 \times 3) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7021 &:= T((-1 + 2 + (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7022 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7023 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7024 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7025 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\ 7026 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\ 7027 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\ 7028 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\ 7029 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6991 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((7 + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 6992 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 6993 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 6994 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 6995 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 6996 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 6997 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 6998 &:= (-9 - (T(((8 - 7) + T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 6999 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7000 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7001 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7002 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7003 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) + 6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7004 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7005 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7006 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7007 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7) - 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7008 &:= ((-9 \times T((8 - 7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 7009 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7010 &:= (-9 - (T((8 + (7 + 6))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7011 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7012 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 7013 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7014 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7015 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7016 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7017 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7018 &:= ((-9 \times T((8 - 7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7019 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7020 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 7021 &:= T(((((-9 + 8) - 7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\ 7022 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7023 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + 6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7024 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + ((7 - 6) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\ 7025 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7 + 6)) \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 7026 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 7027 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7028 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\ 7029 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7030 &:= (-1+2-(T(T(T(3)))-T(T((T(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7031 &:= (((-1+T(2+3)) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7032 &:= (-1-2+((T(3) \times T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7033 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7034 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + (4 + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7035 &:= ((-1+2+T(3)) \times (T(T(4+5)) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7036 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7037 &:= ((-1+T((2+T((T(3)+4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7038 &:= (T((-1+(T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7039 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7040 &:= ((-1+2 \times T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7041 &:= (T((-1+(T(T(2+3))/T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7042 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(T(3))-T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7043 &:= (-1-(2 \times (T((3 \times 4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7044 &:= (-1+(T(2+3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7045 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7046 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - ((4+T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7047 &:= (((-1-2+T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7048 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T((T(4)+5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7049 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - T((T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7050 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7051 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3)+4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7052 &:= (-1+(T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7053 &:= (T((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7054 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7055 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) + (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7056 &:= (T((-1+((2^{T(3)} + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7057 &:= (-1+2+((3^4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7058 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7059 &:= ((-1-2-3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7060 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7061 &:= (-1+(2 \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7062 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7063 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7064 &:= (-1+2-(T(T(T(3))) - (4 + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
7065 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7066 &:= (T((-1+(2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7067 &:= (-1+2+(T(3+T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7068 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7069 &:= ((-1+((2+3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7030 &:= (T((-9+8) - (T(7) - T(6+5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7031 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + T(7)) \times ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7032 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - 7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7033 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7034 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7) - 6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7035 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7036 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7037 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7038 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T((T(7) + 6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7039 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7040 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7041 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8+7)/6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7042 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8)+7)) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7043 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7044 &:= ((-9+8+(T(7) \times T(6))) \times (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
7045 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7+6)))) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7046 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8)+7)) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7047 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7048 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7049 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7 + T(T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7050 &:= (T(-9+8+7) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7051 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8+7)/6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7052 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7053 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7 - 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7054 &:= (T(((((-9-8) \times 7) + T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
7055 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T(6) + (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7056 &:= ((-9+8+T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7057 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T(((7-6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7058 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7059 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times (7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7060 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6))) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7061 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7+6))) + T(T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7062 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7063 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7064 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7065 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (6 \times (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7066 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times 7) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7067 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T(((7-6) + T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7068 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7069 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7+6) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7110 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + 4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7111 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3 + T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7112 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - T((T(4 \times 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7113 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7114 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7115 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7116 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7117 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7118 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7119 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7120 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7121 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7122 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7123 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7124 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times (3 + 4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7125 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7126 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7127 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7128 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7129 &:= ((T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)))/T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7130 &:= ((-1 + 2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7131 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7132 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 + (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7133 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4 \times 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7134 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 - (3 + 4)) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7135 &:= (T((T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))) - 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7136 &:= ((-1 - T(2 + 3)) \times ((4 + T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7137 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7138 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7139 &:= (-1 + T((2 + (3 \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7140 &:= T((-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7141 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7142 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + ((4 \times T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7143 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3 + 4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7144 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3 + 4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7145 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7146 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7147 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4 \times 5)/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7148 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (4 + (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7149 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7110 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7111 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7112 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7113 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7114 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7115 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7116 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7117 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7118 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7119 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7120 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7121 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 \times (7 + 6)) + T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7122 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T(6) - (T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7123 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7124 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7 + 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7125 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) \times T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7126 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7127 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (6 - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7128 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) - T(7)) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7129 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7130 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7131 &:= (-9 + T(((8 \times (7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7132 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7133 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(T(((7 - 6) \times 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7134 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7135 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7136 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7137 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7138 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7139 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7140 &:= T((T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7141 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7142 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7143 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7144 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7 \times T(T(6))) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7145 &:= (T((T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) + T(T(6)))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7146 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7147 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7148 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7149 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7) - 6) \times T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7150 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - ((4 \times 5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7150 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7151 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - ((4 + T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7151 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) + (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7152 &:= (-1 \times (T((T(T(2+3))/T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7152 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7153 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T((3 \times 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7153 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7154 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - T((4 + T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 7154 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7155 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7155 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7156 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7156 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7157 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7157 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7158 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7158 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7159 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7159 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7160 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 7160 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7161 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7161 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7162 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7162 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7163 &:= (-1 - (T((T(2+3) - 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7163 &:= ((((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7164 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(4)) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7164 &:= (((-9 \times 8 \times T(7))/T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7165 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 7165 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7 - 6) + T(T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7166 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7166 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7167 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(((3 - 4) + T(T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7167 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7))) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7168 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + T((T(4 \times 5)/(6+7+8+9)))) & 7168 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7169 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 7169 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7170 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 7170 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T(6) + (5 + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7171 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 7171 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) + (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7172 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + ((T(4)/5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7172 &:= (((-9 + T((8 + T(7)))) \times (6+5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7173 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3+4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7173 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 \times 6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7174 &:= (-1 + (T(((2^{T(3)}) + T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 7174 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7175 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 7175 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7 - 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7176 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7176 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7177 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((3 \times 4))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7177 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7178 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7178 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7179 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 7179 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7180 &:= ((T(T(T(-1+2+3)))/4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7180 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)+6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7181 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 7181 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7182 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 7182 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7183 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7183 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7184 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7184 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) + (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7185 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 7185 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - ((6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7186 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3+4) - (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7186 &:= (((-9 - T(T(8) - 7))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7187 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T((T(4)+5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7187 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7 + 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7188 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 7188 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T(T(((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7189 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (4 + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7189 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7-6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7190 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + ((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7190 &:= (T(T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6))) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7191 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 7191 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T((T(7) + 6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7192 &:= ((-1 - T(T(2 \times 3))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7192 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7193 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7193 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7194 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 7194 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7195 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 7195 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7196 &:= (-1 \times (2^{T(3)} - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 7196 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7197 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 7197 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7198 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7198 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7199 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7199 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 - 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7200 &:= ((T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7200 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7201 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7201 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7202 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7202 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 + 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7203 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3 + 4) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7203 &:= (-9 - (((T(8) \times T(7))/T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7204 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7204 &:= (((-9)/(8 + 7) - 6) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7205 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7205 &:= (T(T(T((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7206 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7206 &:= (-9 - (T(((8 + 7) - 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7207 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(4) + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7207 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7208 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 7208 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7209 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) \times 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7209 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7210 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 \times 3))) - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7210 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7211 &:= (-1 - (T((T(T(2+3))/T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7211 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7212 &:= (-1 \times (T((T(T(2+3))/T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7212 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7213 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7213 &:= (-9 - (T((8 - 7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7214 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7214 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 - 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7215 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7215 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7216 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7216 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 - 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7217 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 7217 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7218 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7218 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7219 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7219 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7220 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7220 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) + T(T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7221 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7221 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7222 &:= (-1 - ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7222 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7223 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7223 &:= (-9 - (T((8 - 7 + 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7224 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 + 3 + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7224 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7225 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7225 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7226 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7226 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7227 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7227 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) + T(7))) \times (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7228 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7228 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7229 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3)) \times T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7229 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7230 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7231 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3) + 4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7232 &:= (((-1 + 2 - (3 - 4)) + T(T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7233 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3+4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7234 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7235 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7236 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7237 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7238 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + ((4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7239 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7240 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7241 &:= (((-1 - T(T(2+3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7242 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7243 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + T(T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7244 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7245 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3)) \times T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7246 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + 4) \times T(T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7247 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7248 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7249 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + ((4 \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7250 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - T(T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7251 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7252 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7253 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7254 &:= (((-1 - 2) - T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7255 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7256 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7257 &:= (-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7258 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7259 &:= (-1 + T((2 \times (T(T(3)) + (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7260 &:= T(T(T((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7261 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7262 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7263 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7264 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7265 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7266 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7267 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7268 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7269 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7230 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7231 &:= (-9 - ((T(8+7)/6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7232 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7233 &:= ((T(-9+T(8))/(7-T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7234 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7235 &:= (T(T(T(-9+8+7) - 6)) - (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7236 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7237 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7238 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7239 &:= (((-9+T(8)) - T(7)) \times (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7240 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7241 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - (7 - T(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7242 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7243 &:= (-9 - 8 + T(T(((7-6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7244 &:= ((-9 - (8-7+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7245 &:= ((-9+8+7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7246 &:= (((-9+8) - 7 - 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7247 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7248 &:= (((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7)))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7249 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7250 &:= (-9 - (((8-7)^{T(6)}) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7251 &:= (-9 + T(T(((8+T(7)) - (6+5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7252 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7253 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7254 &:= (((-9+T(8)) - T(7)) \times (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7255 &:= (T(T(T(-9+8+7) - 6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7256 &:= ((-9 - (8-7-6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7257 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7258 &:= (((-9+8) - 7+6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7259 &:= ((-9/((8+7) - 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7260 &:= T(T(T((-9+T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7261 &:= (((-9+8+7)/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7262 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7263 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) \times 7)/T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7264 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7265 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7)) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7266 &:= ((-9+8+T(7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7267 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7268 &:= (((-9+8) - 7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7269 &:= ((T(-9+T(8))/(7 \times 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7270 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7271 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((3^4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7272 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(3) \times 4)) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7273 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7274 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7275 &:= (((-1+2 + T(3)) \times T(T(4+5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7276 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7277 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(2+3))/T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7278 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7279 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7280 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7281 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7282 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7283 &:= (((-1+2-3) + T((4 + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7284 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7285 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - (T(4) - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7286 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7287 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T((T(3) + 4 + 5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7288 &:= (T((-1+2 + T(3))) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7289 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + T(3))) \times T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7290 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7291 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - (4 - (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7292 &:= ((-1+2 - (3-4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7293 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T((T(4) + 5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7294 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2+3 + T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7295 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
7296 &:= ((-1 - T(2+3)) \times ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7297 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7298 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4+5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7299 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7300 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + T(2+3))) + T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7301 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7302 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7303 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7304 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7305 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (T(4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7306 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7307 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3))/T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7308 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
7309 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + ((4 \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7270 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7271 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7272 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7273 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7274 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7275 &:= (T(-9+8+7) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7276 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - ((6 \times 5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7277 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7278 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7))/T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7279 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7+6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7280 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7281 &:= ((-9+8+T(7)) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7282 &:= (((-9 + T((8+T(7)))) \times (6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7283 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7284 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7285 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (7 \times 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7286 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7-6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7287 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7288 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7-6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7289 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7290 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - T(7)))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7291 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + ((6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7292 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7293 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7294 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7295 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8)) - 7)/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7296 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7297 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7298 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7299 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times (T(7) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7300 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7+6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7301 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7302 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7303 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7304 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + 7)) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7305 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7306 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7+6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7307 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(7) - T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7308 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7309 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T(((7-6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7350 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) + T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7351 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3)) \times (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7352 &:= (-1+2+(T(3)+(T(T(4))+(T(T(T(5))))+6+7+8+9))) \\
7353 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))+(4+T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7354 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3))))-(T(T(4))-(5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7355 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3))+(T(4)+(T(T(T(5))))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7356 &:= (T((-1+(T(T(2+3))/T(4)))+(T(T(T(5))))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7357 &:= (-1+((2^{3+4})+(T(T(T(5))))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7358 &:= (-1 \times 2 - ((T(3)+T(4)) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7359 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3))))-(4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7360 &:= ((T(T(T(-1+2+3)))/4)+(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7361 &:= (-1+((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))+(T(T(T(5))))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7362 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(T(3))-(T(T(4)) \times (T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7363 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4)) + T((T(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
7364 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))+T((4+T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7365 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)))+T(T((T(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7366 &:= (T((-1+2+3) \times 4)+(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7367 &:= (-1+(T(((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))-T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7368 &:= (T((-1-2) \times (T(3)-T(4+5))))+T(6+7+8+9) \\
7369 &:= -1+T(T(T(2+3)))+T(T(4))+T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
7370 &:= (-1+(T((T(T(2+3))-4)+(T(T(5))+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7371 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))+T(T((T(4)-(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7372 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3))))-(T(4)-(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7373 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3)))+(T(T(4))+(T(T(T(5))))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7374 &:= ((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times 4)+(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7375 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)))+(5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7376 &:= ((-1+(2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times ((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
7377 &:= (-1-(2 \times (T(T(3+4))-T((T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7378 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3+4)))+(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7379 &:= (-1+(T(T(2+3))+T(T((T(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7380 &:= (-1+T((2-(T(T(3)))-(4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7381 &:= T((-1+2+(T(3) \times (T(T(4))-(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7382 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3+4)))+(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7383 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3))-4)+(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7384 &:= ((T(T(T(-1+2+3)))/T(4))+(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7385 &:= ((-1+2+(T(T(3)) \times T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7386 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3))))+(4+(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7387 &:= (-1-((2 \times (T(3)-T(T(4))))-(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7388 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3)-T(T(4))))+(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7389 &:= (((-1+T(T(2+3))) \times T((T(T(4))/5)))-T(6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7350 &:= ((T(-9+T(8))-T(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7351 &:= (T(((((-9+8)-7)+T(6)))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7352 &:= ((-9+8)-(T(7)-T((T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7353 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7)-T((T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7354 &:= (-9-(T(T(8))-(T(7)+T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7355 &:= ((-9+(8 \times (7+6)))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7356 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7))+(T(T(6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7357 &:= ((-9-(8+7))+T((T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7358 &:= (T((-9+(T(8+7)+T(6))))+(T(T(5))-T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7359 &:= (((-9+(T(T(8))+7)) \times (6+5))+T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7360 &:= (-9+8+(T(7+6)+(T(T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1))) \\
7361 &:= (-9+(T(T(8+7))+(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7362 &:= (-9-(T(8+7)-(T(T(6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7363 &:= ((-9 \times 8+T(T(7)))-(T(T(6))-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7364 &:= (-9-8+T(((7-6)+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7365 &:= (T(((9+T(8))-7-6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7366 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7))+(T(T(6))+(T(T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1))) \\
7367 &:= (-9+(T(T(8+7))+(6+T(T(5)))-(4+3+2+1))) \\
7368 &:= (-9+(T(8)+(T(7+6)+(T(T(T(5)))-(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7369 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7)-T(6)))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7370 &:= ((-9+8+T(((7+6)+T(T(5)))))-T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7371 &:= (T(-9+8+7) \times (T(T(6))+T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7372 &:= (-9+T((((8-7)^{T(6)})+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7373 &:= (((-9+8)-7)+T((T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7374 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7)+T((T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7375 &:= (T(((9+T(8))-7-6))+T(T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1)) \\
7376 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times T(6))+(T(T(T(5)))-(4+3+2+1))) \\
7377 &:= (-9+(T(T(8+7))+(6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7378 &:= (-9+(T(8)+(T(7+6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7379 &:= (T(-9+T(8))-(T(7)+(T(T(6))-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7380 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7)-6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7381 &:= T(((((-9+8+7)/6)+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7382 &:= (-9+(T((T(8+7)+(6-5)))+4+3+2+1)) \\
7383 &:= (-9-(T(8)-((T(7) \times 6)+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7384 &:= ((-9+((T(T(8))+7) \times (6+5)))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
7385 &:= (T(-9+T(8))-(T(T(7)-6)-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7386 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times T(6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7387 &:= ((-9+8+7)+T((T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7388 &:= (-9+(T(8)+(T(7+6)+(T(T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7389 &:= (-9-8+(T(7+6)+(T(T(T(5)))+T(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7390 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7390 &:= (-9-8 + ((7 \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7391 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7391 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7392 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 7392 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7393 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times ((T(4)/5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7393 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7394 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7394 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) + 7) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7395 &:= (T((-1+2+3) + T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7395 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7396 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (4^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) & 7396 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7397 &:= ((-1-2) - (T((T(T(3))+4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7397 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T((T(6)-5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7398 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((T(T(3)) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7398 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7399 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7399 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T((T(7) + (6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7400 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 7400 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 + T(T(6))) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7401 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2+3) + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7401 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (7 - T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7402 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7402 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7403 &:= ((-1-2+T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7403 &:= (-9-8 + (((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7404 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T((4+T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7404 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) + 7) \times (6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7405 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7405 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7406 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7406 &:= (-9+8 + ((7 \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7407 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7407 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7408 &:= ((-1 - T(2+3)) \times ((T(4)/5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7408 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T(((7-6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7409 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2+3+T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7409 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7410 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) & 7410 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7411 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) & 7411 &:= (-9-8 + ((T(7) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7412 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) - T(T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7412 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7413 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) & 7413 &:= (T((-9-8 + (T(7)+6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7414 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (4 + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7414 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7415 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) - 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7415 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7416 &:= (T((T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) - T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 7416 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - T(7+6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7417 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7417 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7418 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7418 &:= ((-9-8 + T(T(7))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7419 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (T(T(3)) \times T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 7419 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7420 &:= (T((-1 + ((2+3) \times 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7420 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7+6)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7421 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7421 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) + (7 \times (6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7422 &:= ((-1-2) - (T((T(3) \times 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7422 &:= (((-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7423 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(3) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7423 &:= (T((-9-8 + (T(7)+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7424 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(T((T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 7424 &:= (((-9+8) - T(T(7))) + (6^5 + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7425 &:= (((-1+T((2+T(3+4)))) \times T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 7425 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) - T(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7426 &:= (T((-1+2+3) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7426 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7427 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7427 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7428 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7428 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7429 &:= (T((-1+T(2+T(3)))) + ((4+T(T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7429 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) - (6 - T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7470 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7470 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7471 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 7471 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((T(7) - (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7472 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T((T(3) + 4 + 5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 7472 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7473 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 7473 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) \times 7)/T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7474 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 7474 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7475 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7475 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7476 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7476 &:= (T(((9 + T(8)) - 7) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7477 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7477 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
7478 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7478 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) \times (6 \times 5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7479 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) - T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7479 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7)/T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7480 &:= (T((-1+2+3) \times 4) \times T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 7480 &:= (T((-9+8+T(7)) - (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7481 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - ((4 + T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7481 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7482 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7482 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7483 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(T((T(4)+5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7483 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7484 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) + (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7484 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7485 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) + (4 \times (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7485 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7486 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + 4 + 5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 7486 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (T((T(6) - 5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7487 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + ((4 + T(T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7487 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + ((6 + T(T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7488 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T((T(4)+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7488 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7 \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7489 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T((T(4)+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7489 &:= ((-9 \times T(8+7)) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7490 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 7490 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7491 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + T(T((T(4)+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7491 &:= (T(T((-9+8+T(7)) - T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7492 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + T(T((T(4)+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7492 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + T((T(6)+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7493 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7493 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7494 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(T((2 - (3 - 4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7494 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) - (T(7) + (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7495 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7495 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7496 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) - ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7496 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7) - 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7497 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7497 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7498 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 7498 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7499 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7499 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + ((6 + T(T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7500 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) \times (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7500 &:= ((-9 - (T(8+7) + T(6))) \times (5 - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7501 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2+3+T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 7501 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T((T(6) - 5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7502 &:= (-1 + T((2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7502 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7503 &:= T(((9 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 7503 &:= T((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7504 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7504 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 - 7) + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7505 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 7505 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7506 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7506 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) \times 6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7507 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + 4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 7507 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7508 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7508 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
7509 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7509 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7510 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(3 + 4)))) \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7511 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7512 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7513 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7514 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 \times T(3 + 4))) \times 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7515 &:= (-1 \times (T(((2 + 3) \times 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7516 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7517 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7518 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7519 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3 + T(4)) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7520 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7521 &:= (T(T((T(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7522 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T((T(4) + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7523 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (4 + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7524 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7525 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7526 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (4 + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7527 &:= ((-1 + T((2 \times (T(3) + T(T(4)))))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7528 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7529 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7530 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7531 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7532 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T((T(3) + 4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7533 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7534 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T((4 + T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7535 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7536 &:= (T(((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7537 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (T(3) + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7538 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7539 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T((T(T(4))/5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7540 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7541 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((3^4)) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7542 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7543 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7544 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7545 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7546 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3)^4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7547 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (4 + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7548 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7549 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7510 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7511 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T((7 + T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7512 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7513 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + 6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7514 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 - 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7515 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7516 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 + 7)/6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7517 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7)/6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7518 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7519 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) \times 6) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7520 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - T(7 + 6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7521 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (6 \times T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7522 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7523 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7524 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7525 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7526 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 + 7) - (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7527 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7528 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7529 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) \times 6) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7530 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7531 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7) + 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7532 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7533 &:= (-9 \times (T((T(T(8))/(7 + 6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7534 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7535 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(7))) \times (T(6 + 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7536 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7537 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7538 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7539 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7540 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7) - 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7541 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7542 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7543 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T((7 + (6 \times 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7544 &:= (-9 - (T((T(8) + (7 + 6))) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7545 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8))/7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7546 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7547 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7548 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7549 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 \times 7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7550 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) + (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 7551 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 - (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7552 &:= ((-1-2 + T((T(3) + T(T(4)))))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
 7553 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 7554 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7555 &:= (T((-1-2+T(3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 7556 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 7557 &:= (-1-2 + ((3 \times 4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 7558 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times 4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 7559 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2+3))/T(4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 7560 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3 \times 4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 7561 &:= (-1+2 + ((3 \times 4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 7562 &:= ((-1-2) - (((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 7563 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times 3 + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7564 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times T((T(4 \times T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
 7565 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7566 &:= (-1+2 - (((T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 7567 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + (T(T((4+(5+6)))) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
 7568 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(3) + T(T(4)))))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
 7569 &:= ((-1-2) - (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7570 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 7571 &:= (T((-1+(T(T(2+3))+4)) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 7572 &:= (-1 \times (T((T(2 \times 3) - 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7573 &:= (-1+2 - (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7574 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 7575 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + T((4 - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 7576 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 7577 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7578 &:= (T(((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7579 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T((4+(5+6)))) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
 7580 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7581 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 7582 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 7583 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 7584 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + T((T(4) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 7585 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - ((4 \times 5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 7586 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - ((4+T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 7587 &:= (-1-2 + (T(((3+4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 7588 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(((3+4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 7589 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3)))) - ((4 - T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7550 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 7551 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times ((7 - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7552 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7553 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7554 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T(((7+6) + T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
 7555 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T(6) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7556 &:= ((T((-9+T(8+7)))/T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 7557 &:= (T(-9-8+T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7558 &:= (T((-9+(T(8+7)+6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 7559 &:= (-9 + (8 \times T((7+(T(6)+(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 7560 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7))/6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 7561 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7562 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7563 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7564 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7+6) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 7565 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) + (6 - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 7566 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7567 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7568 &:= (-9-8 - (T(T(7)) - (T((6+T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7569 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 7570 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times 7) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7571 &:= (T((((-9+T(8)) \times 7) - T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 7572 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7)/6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7573 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7574 &:= -9+8 - (T(T(7) + T(6)) - T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 7575 &:= (-9+8) \times (T(T(7) + T(6)) - T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 7576 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 7577 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7+6) + T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 7578 &:= (-9-8 - (T(T(7)) - T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 7579 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + T((T(6+5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7580 &:= ((-9+T(8+7)) - (T(T(6)) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 7581 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 7582 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7583 &:= (T((((-9+8+7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 7584 &:= (((T(-9+T(8))/7) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 7585 &:= (T((-9-8+(7 \times 6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 7586 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (T(6) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 7587 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7+6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7588 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 7589 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7590 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - T(4+5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 7590 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7591 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 7591 &:= (T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7)) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7592 &:= (-1 - ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7592 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7+6) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7593 &:= (((-1 \times T(T(T(2+3))))/T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7593 &:= ((T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) \times 6) + (T(5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7594 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (4 - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7594 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7595 &:= ((-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 7595 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(T(7)) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7596 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7596 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 \times 6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7597 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7597 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (T(7+6) + T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7598 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7598 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - (6 \times T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7599 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + 4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 7599 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7600 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7600 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7601 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) & 7601 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7602 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(((3-4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7602 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7603 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - ((T(4)/5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7603 &:= (T((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T(T(6)))) + T((5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7604 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + ((4-5) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7604 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7605 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times 3 + 4 + 5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 7605 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7+6) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7606 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7606 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + (6 \times T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7607 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7607 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7608 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7608 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(7+6) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7609 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7609 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7+6) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7610 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (T(4) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) & 7610 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 + T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7611 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7611 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (7+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7612 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7612 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7613 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7613 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7614 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7614 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (7 \times (6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7615 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7615 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7616 &:= ((-1 - T(2+3)) \times (4 - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7616 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7617 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7617 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7618 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 7618 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7619 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times (3+4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7619 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7620 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(((3+4) + T(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 7620 &:= (((-9 + T((T(8) + (7+6)))) \times 5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7621 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7621 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((7 + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7622 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) & 7622 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - (T(T(7)) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7623 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((3 + T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 7623 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times T(T(7))) - T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7624 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((3 + T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 7624 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7625 &:= (-1 + T((T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T(4+5+6+7+8+9))) & 7625 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7+6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7626 &:= T((((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) & 7626 &:= T((-9 \times 8 + ((7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7627 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((3 + T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 7627 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7628 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7628 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7629 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7629 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7630 &:= (((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7630 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7631 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3 + T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7631 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7632 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7632 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7633 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7633 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T((6 + T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7634 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7634 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + ((6 + T(T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7635 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3 + T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7635 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7636 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7636 &:= (-9 + (T((T(T(8 + 7)) / T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7637 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7637 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 - 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7638 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7638 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7639 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7639 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 - 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7640 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7640 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7641 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7641 &:= (-9 - (((T(8) - T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7642 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7642 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7643 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) + (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7643 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7644 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)) - T(4)) + T(T(T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7644 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7645 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7645 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7646 &:= (-1 - (T((T(T(2 + 3)) / T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7646 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7647 &:= (-1 \times (T((T(T(2 + 3)) / T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7647 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7648 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7648 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7649 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7649 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((7 + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7650 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7650 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 \times T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7651 &:= (T((-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7651 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 + 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7652 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7652 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7653 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7653 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7654 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7654 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7655 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7655 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7656 &:= (T((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T((T(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7656 &:= ((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7657 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 + T((T(4) + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7657 &:= (-9 + (T(T((8 - 7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7658 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7658 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7659 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7659 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7660 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(((3 + 4) + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7660 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
7661 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7661 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7662 &:= ((-1 + T(((T(T(T(2 + 3))) / T(T(4))) - 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7662 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7663 &:= (T(((((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7663 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7664 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7664 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7) - 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7665 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7665 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((7 + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7666 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + T(T((T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7666 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 - 6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7667 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T((T(3) + 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7667 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7668 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7668 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7 \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7669 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7669 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7670 &:= ((T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7671 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T((T(T(4))/5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7672 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7673 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7674 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7675 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7676 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7677 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(3)) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7678 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7679 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7680 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (T(4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7681 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + 4)) + T(T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7682 &:= ((-1 - 2 + ((3 + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7683 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(T((T(4) + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7684 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7685 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7686 &:= (((-1 + T(2^{T(3)})) \times 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7687 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + (4 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7688 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7689 &:= ((-1 + (T(2^{T(3)})) \times 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7690 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7691 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7692 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7693 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7694 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3 + 4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7695 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7696 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7697 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7698 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3 + 4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7699 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7700 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7701 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7702 &:= (((-1 + 2 - T(T(T(3))))/T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7703 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7704 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7705 &:= ((-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7706 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) + (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7707 &:= (((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7708 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7709 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7670 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7671 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7672 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7673 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 \times 6))) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7674 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7675 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((7 + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7676 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) - T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7677 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + T((6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7678 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((T(7) + (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7679 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + T(T(6))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7680 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7681 &:= (T(((((-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - T(6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7682 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7683 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 \times 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7684 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7685 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) - (T(6) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7686 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7687 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7688 &:= (((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7)))/6) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7689 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(7) \times T(T(6))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7690 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7691 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7692 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7693 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((7 + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7694 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times ((7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7695 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7696 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7697 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7698 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7 + 6) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7699 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7700 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7701 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7702 &:= ((-9 - T(8 + 7)) + (6^5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7703 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((T(T(7)) + 6) \times T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7704 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times ((7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7705 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7706 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7707 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7708 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) + 7)) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7709 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7750 &:= T((-1 - (T(2+3) - (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7751 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3+4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7752 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7753 &:= (T((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7754 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3+4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7755 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7756 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7757 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (4 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7758 &:= (T((-1+2+(T(T(3)) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7759 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + 4) + T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7760 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7761 &:= (T((-1 + (2 + (3+4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7762 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7763 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7764 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(4)) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7765 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7766 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7767 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7768 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7769 &:= (-1 + (T(((2^{T(3)}) + T(T(4))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7770 &:= (T((-1+T((2+3+T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7771 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7772 &:= ((-1-2 + ((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7773 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(T(3)) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7774 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7775 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7776 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7777 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3) + T(4)) - T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
7778 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7779 &:= ((T((-1 + (2 \times T(3)))) \times (4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7780 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7781 &:= (((-1+T(2+3)) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7782 &:= (-1-2 + ((T(3) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7783 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7784 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7785 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) + 4) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7786 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 \times (3+4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7787 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + T(((T(4))/5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7788 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7789 &:= (-1 - (T((2^{T(3)})) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7750 &:= T(((9 - T((8-7) + T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7751 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(7)) \times T(6 \times 5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7752 &:= ((((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7753 &:= (-9 - 8 + (7 \times ((T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7754 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(6))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7755 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7+6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7756 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7757 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + ((6-5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7758 &:= ((((-9+8) - 7) + 6^5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7759 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T(((7-6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7760 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7761 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - T(T(7))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7762 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7763 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)))/6) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7764 &:= (((-9-8+T(T(7))) \times (T(6)-5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7765 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
7766 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7767 &:= (-9 + ((8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7768 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7769 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) + T(T((T(6) - 5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7770 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 \times T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7771 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T((T(7) + 6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7772 &:= (((-9+8+7) + 6^5) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
7773 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7) + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7774 &:= (-9-8 + (T(7+6) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7775 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8+7) - (T(T(6)) \times 5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7776 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7777 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7778 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7779 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) + 6^5 + 4+3+2+1) \\
7780 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7-6) + T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7781 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7782 &:= (((-9+8+7) + T(T((T(6) - 5)))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7783 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7) + 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7784 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7785 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7786 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7787 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7788 &:= (T((-9-8 + (T(7) + T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7789 &:= (T((-9-8 + (7 \times T(6)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7790 &:= (-1 \times (T((2^{T(3)})) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7791 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4 + 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7792 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7793 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7794 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
7795 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7796 &:= (T((-1 + 2 \times T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7797 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - T(T(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7798 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7799 &:= (-1 + ((T(2+3) \times T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7800 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7801 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((3 - T(T(4))) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7802 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3))/T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7803 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7804 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7805 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7806 &:= (((T(-1 + 2 + 3) - 4)^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
7807 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3^4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7808 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7809 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(4) \times T(T((T(T(5))/ (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))) \\
7810 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times (T(4) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7811 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T((3 \times 4)) + T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7812 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/ (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7813 &:= (((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7814 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + T(3)) \times T(T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7815 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4 \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7816 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7817 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3 + T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7818 &:= (((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) + (4^5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7819 &:= ((T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (4^5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
7820 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7821 &:= (-1 + 2 - ((T(T(3)) - 4) \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7822 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7823 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7824 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
7825 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7826 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7827 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7828 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T((T(4) \times 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
7829 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
7790 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7791 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - 7) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7792 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
7793 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(7)) + 6^5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7794 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (((7 + 6) - 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7795 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7796 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7797 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7798 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 \times 6))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7799 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + 6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7800 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7801 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + (T(7 + 6) + T(5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7802 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7803 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7804 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T((T(7) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7805 &:= (T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7806 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(7) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7807 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7808 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7809 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7) - (6 - T(T(5)))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7810 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7811 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + T((6 + T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7812 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + T((T(6 + 5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7813 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7814 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7815 &:= (((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7))))/6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7816 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7817 &:= (-9 + (T(8 + 7) + (6 + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7818 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7819 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7820 &:= ((T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7821 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7822 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7823 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6^5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7824 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7825 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
7826 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7 + 6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
7827 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7828 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) - (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7829 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7 \times 6) - T(T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7830 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (T(T(4+5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7830 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - ((7 - (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7831 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) \times (T((T(4) \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9))) & 7831 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7832 &:= (-1 - 2 + (((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7832 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (T(6) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7833 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7833 &:= (((-9 - 8 - T(7)) \times T(6)) + T((T(T(T(5))))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7834 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7834 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7835 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7835 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7836 &:= (-1+2 + (((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7836 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7837 &:= ((T((-1+2 + T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7837 &:= ((-9+8+7) + (6^5 + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7838 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 7838 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7) + 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7839 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 7839 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7840 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7840 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(((7+6) + T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7841 &:= (T((-1-2 + T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7841 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7842 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(((T(T(3)) + 4) \times 5))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 7842 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + T((T(T(T(5))))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7843 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) - T(T(5)))))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7843 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (T(7) + T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7844 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2+3 + T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7844 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7+6)))) - (5 \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7845 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7845 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7) + 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7846 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(3) + 4 + 5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 7846 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) + (T(5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7847 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) - T(T(5)))))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7847 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7848 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))) & 7848 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - ((7+6) - (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7849 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 7849 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7850 &:= (((((-1-2) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 7850 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6-5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7851 &:= (T((-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 7851 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7852 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7852 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7853 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 7853 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((7+6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
7854 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))))) & 7854 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times T((6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7855 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7855 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) - T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7856 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7856 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + ((6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7857 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T((T(4+5) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 7857 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7))))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7858 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7858 &:= (T(-9+8 + T(7)) + (T((T(6) - 5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7859 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) & 7859 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7+6) - T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7860 &:= ((T((-1+2 + T(T(3)))) + 4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)) & 7860 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) - 7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7861 &:= (T(((-1+2+3) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7861 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7862 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7862 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7863 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(T((5+6))) - T(7+8+9)))) & 7863 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (((7-6) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7864 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + T(3)))) + ((4 + T(T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7864 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7865 &:= (((-1 + T(2+3)) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7865 &:= ((T((T(T(-9+8+7)))/T(6))) \times T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7866 &:= (((-1 + T(2^{T(3)})) \times 4) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7866 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7867 &:= ((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7867 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7868 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 7868 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) + (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7869 &:= (-1 + ((T(2^{T(3)})) \times 4) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 7869 &:= (T(-9+8 + T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7870 &:= (((T((-1+2+T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7870 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) - (6 - (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7871 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T((T(T(4)) + T((5+6)))) + T(7+8+9))) & 7871 &:= (-9 + ((8 + T((T(7) + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
7872 &:= (((-1-2) \times (T(3) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7872 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7873 &:= -1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9) & 7873 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7874 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 7874 &:= (-9 + 8 + T((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7875 &:= T((-1 + (2 \times (T(3+4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7875 &:= T(((-9 - 8 + T(7)) - (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7876 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((((T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 7876 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7877 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times 3) - 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7877 &:= (((-9 + T(8+7)) + 6^5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
7878 &:= (T((T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) - 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7878 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7879 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7879 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7880 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7880 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7881 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3 - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 7881 &:= (T(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7882 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T((((4+5) - 6) \times (7+8+9)))) & 7882 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7883 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))) & 7883 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) + (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7884 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 7884 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) + (6 - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7885 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7885 &:= (T((T((T(-9+8+7) - 6)) + 5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
7886 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) - (4 - T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7886 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7887 &:= (((-1-2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 7887 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7888 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7888 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7889 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2+3+T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7889 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + T(6)) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7890 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3+4))))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 7890 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times (7 - T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7891 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7891 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7) - 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7892 &:= (T((-1-2 + T(T(3)))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7892 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) + (T((T(6) - 5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7893 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7893 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7) + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7894 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7894 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7895 &:= (((-1 - T(T(2+3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7895 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7896 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 + (3+4))))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 7896 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7897 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7897 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7898 &:= ((-1-2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7898 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7899 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7899 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 - 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7900 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 7900 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7901 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((3^4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 7901 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7902 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7902 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) + ((7 - (6 + 5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7903 &:= (((-1+2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 7903 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
7904 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (T(3) + 4 + 5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 7904 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7905 &:= (T(((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)) + T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 7905 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7 \times 6))) - (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7906 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T((T(3+4) - T(5))))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 7906 &:= ((((-9+8) - T(7)) \times T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7907 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 7907 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
7908 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 7908 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (((7 - 6) + T(T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
7909 &:= (-1 + (((T(2+T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 7909 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7910 &:= ((T((-1-2+T(T(3))))+T(T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7911 &:= (((-1-2) \times (3-T((T(T(4))+T(5)))))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7912 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3)))+(T((T(T(4))+T((5+6))))+T(7+8+9))) \\
7913 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3))))+(T(T(T(4)))/5)+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7914 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))+(T((4+T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7915 &:= (T((-1+((2+3) \times 4)))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7916 &:= ((-1+(2 \times (T(T(3+T(4))))+5))-T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7917 &:= (-1-2+((3 \times T((T(T(4))+T(5))))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7918 &:= (-1 \times 2+((3 \times T((T(T(4))+T(5))))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7919 &:= (-1+((2+T(3)) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
7920 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3))))+T(4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7921 &:= (-1+2+((3 \times T((T(T(4))+T(5))))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7922 &:= (-1-(((2 \times T(3))-T(4+5)) \times T(T(6)))-T(7+8+9)) \\
7923 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3))))-(T(T(4))-(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7924 &:= (-1+((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4)))+(T(5)+6+7+8+9))) \\
7925 &:= (-1+(T(T(2+T(3)))+T(T((T(4+5)-(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7926 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))+T(T((4+(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7927 &:= -(T(1 \times 2 \times T(T(3)))-T(T(T(4)))-(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7928 &:= ((-1+T((2^{3+4})))-(T((5+T(6)))-(7+8+9)) \\
7929 &:= ((-1+T((T(T(2+3))+T(4))))-(T(T(5))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7930 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3))-T((T(4)+T(T(5))))-T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7931 &:= ((-1-2)-(T(T(T(3)))-((T(T(T(4))) \times 5)+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7932 &:= (-1-2+((T(T(3)) \times T(4))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7933 &:= (T((((-1-2) \times T(3))+T(T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7934 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))+(T(4 \times 5)+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7935 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3)+T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7936 &:= (-1+2+((T(T(3)) \times T(4))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7937 &:= (-1-(2 \times (T(3^4))-(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7938 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3^4))-(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) \\
7939 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times 3)))+(4+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7940 &:= (T((-1+T(2 \times 3)))+(T(T(T(4))) \times 5)+6+7+8+9) \\
7941 &:= (-1+(((2+3) \times T(T(T(4))))+(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
7942 &:= (-1-2+((T(T(T(3)))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7943 &:= (-1 \times 2+((T(T(T(3)))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7944 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))+(T(T(4))+T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7945 &:= ((T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3)))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7946 &:= (-1+2+((T(T(T(3)))-4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7947 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(T(3))))-(T(4)-(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7948 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3)))+(T((4+T(T(5))))-(6+7+8+9))) \\
7949 &:= ((-1+(T((2 \times T(3+4))) \times 5))-(6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7910 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-(T(7)-(T(6)+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7911 &:= ((-9+T((8+T(7))))-(6-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7912 &:= (((-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(T(6))+5))+T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7913 &:= (T((-9+(T(8+7)+(T(6)+5))))-T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7914 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-((7+6)-(T(T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1))) \\
7915 &:= (-9-(((8 \times 7) \times (6-T(T(5))))-T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7916 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-((7-6)-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7917 &:= (-9+(T(((8+7)+T(6)))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7918 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)))+((7-6)+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7919 &:= ((-9+8)-(T(T(7)+6)-T((T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1))) \\
7920 &:= (T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6))) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7921 &:= (-9+((T(8+7) \times T(6+5))+4+3+2+1)) \\
7922 &:= (((-9 \times 8)-7)+T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7923 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6))-(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7924 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T(7)-(T(6)-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7925 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7))-(6-(5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7926 &:= (T(((9+8+7) \times 6))+T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7927 &:= (-9-(T(8+7)-(T((6+T(T(5)))+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7928 &:= (-9-(T(8)+(T(7)-T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7929 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8)-T(7)))+T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7930 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)))+((7+6)+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7931 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-(7-(T(6)+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7932 &:= ((-9 \times T(8))+T((7+(T(6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7933 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6))+(5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
7934 &:= ((-9 \times (8-(T(7)+6)))+(5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7935 &:= ((-9 \times (8-T(7 \times 6)))-T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7936 &:= ((-9-(8 \times 7))+T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7937 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7))+(6+(5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7938 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7939 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(T(7)-(6-T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7940 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)))+((7+6)+(T(T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1))) \\
7941 &:= (T(((9+8+7) \times T(6)))-(5+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7942 &:= ((-9+T((T(8+7)+6)))-(5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7943 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6))-5+4+3+2+1) \\
7944 &:= ((-9+T((T(8)+T(7+6))))-(T(T(5))+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7945 &:= (-9+(T(T(8))+(7+(T(6)+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7946 &:= (T((-9-(T(8)-T(7+6+5))))-T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7947 &:= (-9+(T(8) \times (T(7+6)+(T(T(5)))+4+3+2+1))) \\
7948 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (6+T(5)))+4+3+2+1) \\
7949 &:= (-9-(T(8)+(7-T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7950 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) + T(4 \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
7951 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T((4+T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7952 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7953 &:= ((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7954 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T((T(4)+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7955 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7956 &:= (T(T((-1+(2+(3+4)))))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
7957 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(T((T(4)+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7958 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7959 &:= (-1+(T(T(2 \times 3)) + (4+(T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7960 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7961 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7962 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
7963 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7964 &:= (-1+(T(2+3) \times (T((T(T(4))/5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7965 &:= (T((-1+T((2+(3+4)))))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7966 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7967 &:= (-1+(T((2+T((T(3)+4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7968 &:= (T((-1+(T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
7969 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(3) - (4 - T(T(5)))))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
7970 &:= ((-1+T((T((2-(3-4))) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7971 &:= (T(((T(-1+T(2+3)) \times (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7972 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(3) + T((T(4)+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
7973 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T((4+T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
7974 &:= (-1+((2+3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
7975 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
7976 &:= ((-1+T((2 \times 3 + T((4+(5+6)))))) - (7+8+9)) \\
7977 &:= (-1+(T((2 \times T(3) + T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7978 &:= (T((-1+(2^{3+4}))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
7979 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
7980 &:= (((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
7981 &:= (((-1+2+3)^4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7982 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (4+(T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7983 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
7984 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T((4+T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7985 &:= (((-1+T(T(2+3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7986 &:= ((-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
7987 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
7988 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7989 &:= (-1+((T(2 \times 3) - 4) \times (5+T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
7950 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7951 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + (T(7) + (6+T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7952 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7953 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7954 &:= (-9+(T((T(8) + (7-6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7955 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7 \times 6) - 5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7956 &:= (-9-8-(T(7) - T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7957 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7958 &:= (-9+8+(T(7) + (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7959 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7960 &:= (((-9+T(8 \times 7)) - 6) \times 5) + T(4+3+2+1) \\
7961 &:= (T(((T(-9+8+7) \times T(6))) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7962 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T((6+T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
7963 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7964 &:= (-9+(T((T(8) + (7-6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7965 &:= ((-9+T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7966 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7967 &:= (-9+(T((T(8) - 7-6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7968 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7) \times 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7969 &:= ((-9+T((T(8) + T(7+6)))) - (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
7970 &:= (((-9+8) - (7 \times (6 - T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7971 &:= (-9+(T(T(8+7)) + (6 \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7972 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7973 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7974 &:= (((-9+(T(8)+7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7975 &:= ((T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6))) \times T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
7976 &:= (T((-9+(T(8)+7))) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7977 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
7978 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) - (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7979 &:= (-9+((8 \times T(7+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
7980 &:= ((-9+T((T(8+7)+6))) - (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
7981 &:= (T(((T(-9+(8 \times 7)) + T(6+5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
7982 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) + (T(T(6)) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7983 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) \times ((7+6) - (T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
7984 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
7985 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + ((7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7986 &:= (T(((T(-9+8+7) \times T(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
7987 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - (T(7+6) - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
7988 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
7989 &:= ((-9+T((T(8) + T(7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8069 &:= (-1 + (T((2+3) \times T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8070 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times T(4+5))) \times (6+7+8+9)) \\
8071 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8072 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8073 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8074 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T((T(T(3)) + 4))) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8075 &:= (((-1 - 2 + T((3 + T(T(4)))))) \times 5) - T(6+7+8+9) \\
8076 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8077 &:= (-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
8078 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8079 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))) + T((T(T(4)) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
8080 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8081 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
8082 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(4) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
8083 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
8084 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T((2 - (3 - 4)))))) \times (5 + 6+7+8+9)) \\
8085 &:= (T(T((T(-1+2+3) - 4))) \times (5 + 6+7+8+9)) \\
8086 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8087 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T((3 + T(T(4)))) \times 5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8088 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))))) \times (4+5)) - (6+7+8+9) \\
8089 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8090 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8091 &:= ((T(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8092 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3)^4 + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8093 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (5 + 6+7+8+9)) \\
8094 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (T((4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8095 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(((3+4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
8096 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times (4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
8097 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8098 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8099 &:= ((T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) \times 4) + 5 + 6+7+8+9) \\
8100 &:= (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8101 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(4+5) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8102 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8103 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
8104 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
8105 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
8106 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4))) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8107 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - T((T((5+6)) - (7+8+9)))))) \\
8108 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (4 \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8149 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8150 &:= ((-1 - T((T(2 + 3) + T(4)))) \times (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8151 &:= (-1 + 2 - (((3 - T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8152 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8153 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8154 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (T(T(T(3))) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8155 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + 4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8156 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+T(4)})) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8157 &:= (-1 + (T(((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4))) - 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8158 &:= (T(((((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8159 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (T(3) \times T(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8160 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8161 &:= ((-1 + (2^{T(3+4)-T(5)})) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8162 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T((T(4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8163 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8164 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) \times ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8165 &:= ((T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8166 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8167 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - (T(4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8168 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8169 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8170 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8171 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8172 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8173 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8174 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8175 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + T(T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8176 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times ((3 + 4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8177 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8178 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8179 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8180 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) - (4 - T(5)))))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8181 &:= (T((-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T(T(4 + 5)))))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8182 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8183 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
8184 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8185 &:= ((((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8186 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8187 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 + T(4)) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8188 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((3 + T(4)) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8149 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8150 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - T(7 + 6)) \times (5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8151 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + T((T(7) + 6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8152 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8153 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8154 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8155 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8156 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8157 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8158 &:= (T(((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + T(T(6)))) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8159 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8160 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T(6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8161 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8162 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8163 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8164 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8165 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8166 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (6 \times T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8167 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 + 7) + 6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8168 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(T(7)) - T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8169 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8170 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7) - 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8171 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) + 6^5) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8172 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(7 + 6) + (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8173 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8174 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8175 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(7 \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8176 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + 7))) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8177 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8178 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8179 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7 + 6))) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8180 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8181 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8182 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8183 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (T(7) - (6 + 5)))))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8184 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8185 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7 \times 6))) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8186 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5)))))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8187 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8188 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(T(7) + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8189 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8190 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times 3))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8191 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((3 + T(4)) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8192 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8193 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8194 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + ((4^5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8195 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8196 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8197 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8198 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - (T(4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8199 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + 4)) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8200 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8201 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + T((T(T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8202 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8203 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
8204 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + ((4 \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8205 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8206 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8207 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8208 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8209 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8210 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8211 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4)) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8212 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8213 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8214 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8215 &:= (T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8216 &:= (((-1 + 2)^{T(T(T(3)))}) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8217 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8218 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8219 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8220 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8221 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3+4)-T(5)}) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8222 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8223 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8224 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8225 &:= ((T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8226 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8227 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8228 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8309 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(3)) \times T(T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8310 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8311 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(3 + 4) - T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8312 &:= ((-1 + T((2 \times (T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8313 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (3 \times T(4 + 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8314 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(((3 \times 4) + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8315 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8316 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8317 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8318 &:= (T((T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8319 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8320 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - T(4)) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8321 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3 + T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8322 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8323 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8324 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8325 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8326 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8327 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8328 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - ((4 + 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8329 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8330 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8331 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8332 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(3) + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8333 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8334 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) + 4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8335 &:= (T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8336 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3 + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8337 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8338 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8339 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4 + 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8340 &:= (T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) + T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8341 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T((T(3 + 4) - T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8342 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8343 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T((3^4) - T(T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8344 &:= ((-1 + (T((2^{T(3)}) \times 4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8345 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8346 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3 + T(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8347 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T((5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8348 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T((3 \times 4)))) + (T(T((5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8309 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8310 &:= ((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + (6 \times T(T(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8311 &:= (T(((((-9 + 8) - 7) + T((T(6) - 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8312 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8313 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(((7 + T(6)) \times 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8314 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8315 &:= (((-9 + T(((8 + 7) + T(6)))) \times T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8316 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) \times (T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8317 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - (6 - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8318 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7) + T((T(6) + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8319 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8320 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8321 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 + 7) - 6) + T(T(5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8322 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) + T(7))) \times (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8323 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8324 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8325 &:= (((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7))))/6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8326 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) \times (6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8327 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8328 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (7 - 6)))) \times (T(T(5))/4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8329 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8330 &:= (T((T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))/6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8331 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) - 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8332 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7) + T((6 - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8333 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8334 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8335 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8336 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8337 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 + 6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8338 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 \times T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8339 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8340 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - T(7)) \times 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8341 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8342 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + T(T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8343 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7) - (6 + 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8344 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8345 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times T(7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8346 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((T(7) \times 6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8347 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8348 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8389 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) & 8389 &:= ((-9-8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8390 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))))) \times T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9) & 8390 &:= (-9-8 + (T(T(7)) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
8391 &:= (T(T((-1 + (2 + (3+4)))))) + (T(T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9) & 8391 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + (T(7)+6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8392 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) & 8392 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - (6+T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8393 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8393 &:= ((-9+8) - (T((7+T(6))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
8394 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8394 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times (7 \times 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8395 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8395 &:= (T((-9-8 + (7 \times T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8396 &:= (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8396 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
8397 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8397 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) + (7 - (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
8398 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8398 &:= (-9-8 + (T((T(7) - (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
8399 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4))) - T(5+6+7+8+9) & 8399 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1))))) \\
8400 &:= ((-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9) & 8400 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) + (7 \times T(6+5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
8401 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T((T(3+4) - T(5)))))) + 6+7+8+9) & 8401 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (T(6) + T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8402 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + 4+5))) - (6 - (7+8+9))) & 8402 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7+6))) + T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1))) \\
8403 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) + 4+5)) - (6 - (7+8+9))) & 8403 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8404 &:= T(-1+T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9) & 8404 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
8405 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 8405 &:= ((-9+8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8406 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3+T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 8406 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7)) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
8407 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 8407 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(7) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
8408 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (T(3) + (T(T(4)) + T((5+6)))))) + 7+8+9) & 8408 &:= T(-9 \times T(8) + T(T(7))) + T(T(6)) \times T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
8409 &:= ((T((-1-2 + T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8409 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8410 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) & 8410 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8411 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8411 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(7+6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8412 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(T(3)) - 4) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 8412 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
8413 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - 4) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 8413 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8414 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + 4+5)) + 6+7+8+9) & 8414 &:= (-9+8 + (T((T(7) - (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
8415 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9) & 8415 &:= (T((-9+8 + (T(7) + 6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8416 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) - 4) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) & 8416 &:= ((-9 - ((8+7) \times 6)) + T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1))) \\
8417 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3 \times 4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))) & 8417 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) + (T(T(6+5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
8418 &:= (T((-1+2 + T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8418 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) + (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
8419 &:= ((T(T((-1+2 + T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 8419 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7+6)) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
8420 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 8420 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) + (6 \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
8421 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3+T(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 8421 &:= (((-9+T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
8422 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(T(3))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 8422 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8423 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) + T((4+(5+6)))) \times (7+8+9))) & 8423 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7+6) - T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8424 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))) & 8424 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - ((7 \times T(T(6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8425 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T((T(T(4)) - T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8425 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) \times (7+6))) \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
8426 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3+T(4)))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 8426 &:= (T((-9+8 + (T(7) + T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
8427 &:= (-1-2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(4) \times 5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8427 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8428 &:= (T((((-1-2) \times T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8428 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8429 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) - T(4))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8430 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2+3)) + T(T(4)))) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8431 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(3+4) - T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
8432 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8433 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8434 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8435 &:= ((T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8436 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8437 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8438 &:= T(-1 + T(T(2+3))) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9) \\
8439 &:= ((T((-1 + T(T(2+3))))/T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8440 &:= (((-1 + T(2 \times T(3+4)))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
8441 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3+T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
8442 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
8443 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T((4+T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8444 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times T(3+4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8445 &:= ((-1 + T(((2^{3+4}) + 5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8446 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8447 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T((4+T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8448 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8449 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8450 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8451 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8452 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8453 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + 4+5))) - (T(T(6)) - T(7+8+9))) \\
8454 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8455 &:= (T((-1 - 2 - 3) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
8456 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8457 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (3 \times T(4+5)))) - (T(6) + T(7+8+9))) \\
8458 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + ((5 \times 6) + T(7+8+9))) \\
8459 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8460 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8461 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8462 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8463 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3) + T((T(4) + 5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8464 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
8465 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
8466 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3)) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
8467 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + T((T(4) + 5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8468 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T((4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8429 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8430 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7 - 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8431 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) - (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
8432 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (T(7) - (6 + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8433 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8434 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8435 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7+6)) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1) \\
8436 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8437 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
8438 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8439 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1) \\
8440 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8441 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8442 &:= (-9 \times (8 - T((7 + (T(6) + (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8443 &:= (T((T(T(-9+8+7)) + (6 - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
8444 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
8445 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (6 - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8446 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
8447 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7+6))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8448 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) \times 6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8449 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8450 &:= (T(((9+8+7) \times 6)) \times T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
8451 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (T(7) + T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1) \\
8452 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 7 + 6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8453 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) - T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8454 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8455 &:= (((-9+8+T(T(7))) \times T(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
8456 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + (7+6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
8457 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
8458 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + 6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8459 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7)) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
8460 &:= ((-9 - T(8)) \times (T(7) - (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8461 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8+7))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
8462 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7)) + (6 + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8463 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - ((7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8464 &:= (-9 - 8 - (T(7) + (6 - T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
8465 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) - (5 + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
8466 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
8467 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7+6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
8468 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

8469 := $((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8470 := $((-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8471 := $(-1 + ((2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T((4 + (5 + 6)))))) \times (7 + 8 + 9))$
8472 := $(-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8473 := $(T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8474 := $(-1 + ((2 \times T(((T(T(3)) \times 4) + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8475 := $(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8476 := $((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + T((T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8477 := $(-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8478 := $(-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8479 := $((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8480 := $(T((T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) + T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8481 := $(T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8482 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8483 := $(((-1 + 2 - 3) + T((T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8484 := $(-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + T((4 + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8485 := $(T((T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8486 := $((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + (4 + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8487 := $((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8488 := $((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T((T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8489 := $(((-1 + 2 + 3) + T((T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8490 := $(T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8491 := $(T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8492 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8493 := $(-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8494 := $(-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8495 := $(T(-1 + 2 + 3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8496 := $(T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8497 := $(-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8498 := $(-1 + (T((2 \times (T(T(3)) + T(4 + 5)))) + (T(6) - T(7 + 8 + 9))))$
8499 := $(-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8500 := $((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8501 := $(-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4))) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))))$
8502 := $((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8503 := $(T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8504 := $(-1 + ((2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8505 := $((T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8506 := $(T(((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8507 := $(-1 + 2 + (T((3 + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8508 := $((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$

8469 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8470 := $((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8471 := $(((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + 6)) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8472 := $(-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8473 := $(((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8474 := $((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8475 := $((-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8476 := $(-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8477 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 - 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8478 := $(-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8479 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8480 := $((((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7 + 6)) \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8481 := $(-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8482 := $(T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(T(6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8483 := $(-9 - (T(8) - ((7 + 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8484 := $(-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8485 := $(T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) - 6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8486 := $(-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8487 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (T(6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8488 := $((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7) + 6 + 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8489 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + ((7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8490 := $(((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8491 := $(((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + 6)) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8492 := $((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) + (6 \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8493 := $(-9 - (T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8494 := $((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8495 := $(T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8496 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8497 := $((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8498 := $(-9 - 8 + T((T(T((7 - 6) \times 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8499 := $((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - (T(5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8500 := $(T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8501 := $(((-9 + 8) - 7 - 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8502 := $(((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8503 := $(T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) - (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8504 := $(-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8505 := $((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8506 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + T((T(7) - (T(6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8507 := $((-9 + 8) - (T(7) - (T(6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8508 := $((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - (T(6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$

$$8509 := ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8510 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8511 := (T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8512 := (-1 - 2 + T(((3 \times T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8513 := (-1 \times 2 + T(((3 \times T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8514 := (-1 + T((2 \times ((3 \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8515 := T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - (T(4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8516 := (-1 + 2 + T(((3 \times T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8517 := (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8518 := (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8519 := (-1 + ((2 + T(3)) \times (T(T(4 + 5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8520 := ((T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8521 := (T(((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8522 := (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8523 := (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(4 \times 5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8524 := (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4))) + T((T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8525 := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8526 := (T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times T(T((T(4 \times 5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8527 := (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times T(T((T(4 \times 5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8528 := (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - ((4 \times T(T((5 + 6)))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8529 := (-1 + (T(2 + 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8530 := (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8531 := T(-1 + 2 \times T(T(3)) - (T(T(4)) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8532 := ((-1 - 2 + T(T(3))) \times ((4 + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8533 := (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8534 := (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + T(((4 \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8535 := (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8536 := (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3 + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8537 := (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8538 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8539 := ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8540 := (T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$$

$$8541 := ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8542 := (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3) + (4 + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8543 := ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8544 := (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T((T(T(4)) - T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8545 := (T((T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$8546 := (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + (4 + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$8547 := (-1 - 2 + (3 \times T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8548 := (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T((T(4 + 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$$

$$8509 := (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8510 := ((-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8511 := ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8512 := (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8513 := (((-9 + 8) - 7 + 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8514 := (T((T(-9 + T(8))/7) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8515 := T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8516 := (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8517 := ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8518 := ((-9 + 8) - (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8519 := (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8520 := (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8521 := ((-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8522 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 + T((T(6) - 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8523 := (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (7 + (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8524 := (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8525 := (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8526 := ((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8527 := ((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8528 := (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T(6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8529 := ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8530 := (T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8531 := (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8532 := ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8533 := ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7))/T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8534 := (-9 \times 8 + (T(7 + 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8535 := (-9 - (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8536 := (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8537 := (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8538 := (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8539 := ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8540 := (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$$

$$8541 := (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7 \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8542 := (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (6 + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8543 := (-9 + (T(8) + ((7 - 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8544 := ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 + T(T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$$

$$8545 := ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8546 := (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + 6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$8547 := (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T(6) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$8548 := (-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (6 + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8549 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8550 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) + T(4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8551 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times T((T(4+5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
8552 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8553 &:= -1 - (T(2 + T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8554 &:= -1 + (T(2 \times T(3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8555 &:= -1 - T(2 + T(T(3))) \times (-5 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8)) \\
8556 &:= -T(2 + T(T(3))) \times (-5 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8)) \\
8557 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2+3))) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9) \\
8558 &:= T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9) \\
8559 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2+3)) + T(4)) + T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8560 &:= T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) + T(4)) + T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8561 &:= T(-1 + 2^{T(3)} + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
8562 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(3)) + T(T(4) + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8563 &:= -1 - 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8564 &:= -1 + T((2+3) \times T(4)) + T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
8565 &:= T(-1 + 2 + 3 + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8566 &:= T(T(T(3 \times ((-1) + 2)))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8567 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8568 &:= (-1 - 2) \times T(3) \times (4 - T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8569 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2+3)) + T(4)) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
8570 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(3+4)) + T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8571 &:= T((-1 + T(2+3)) \times 4) + T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8572 &:= (-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
8573 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8574 &:= (-1 - (((2 - T((3 + T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8575 &:= ((T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(4))) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8576 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) - T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
8577 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3+4)) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8578 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3+4)) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8579 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 \times (3+4)) + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8580 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times T(3)) \times T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8581 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(3+4)) - T(T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8582 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T((3 + T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8583 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8584 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3)^4 + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8585 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + T((T(T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
8586 &:= ((T(((-1 + 2) \times 3))^4 + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
8587 &:= ((-1 - T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times (4 - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
8588 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8549 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - T(7)) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8550 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8551 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times ((7 + 6) \times T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8552 &:= -9 - (T(T(8)) - T(T(7)) - T(6) - T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8553 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8554 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8555 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7 + 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8556 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8557 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8558 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8559 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (7 + T((6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8560 &:= (-9 - (T((8 + (7 + 6))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8561 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) + T(6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8562 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8563 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + 6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8564 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times (7 + T(T(6)))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8565 &:= ((-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8566 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8567 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8568 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times ((7 - 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8569 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8570 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8571 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7 - 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8572 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - 7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8573 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8574 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8575 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7 + 6)) \times T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8576 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8577 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8578 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7))/6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8579 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8580 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8581 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + 6)) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8582 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8 + 7) + 6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8583 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8584 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6))) - (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8585 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8586 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - ((7 + 6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8587 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T(((7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8588 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (7 - (6 \times (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8589 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - ((4 \times T(T((5+6)))) - (7+8+9)))) \\
 8590 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(((3+4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8591 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times T(3)))) \times (4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8592 &:= (-1 + (T(((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8593 &:= (T((((-1+2) \times (3+4)) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8594 &:= (-1+2 + (T(((3+4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8595 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times 3 + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8596 &:= -1 - 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 8597 &:= -1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 8598 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8599 &:= ((T(T((-1+2 + T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8600 &:= ((-1 + T((2^{3+4}))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8601 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 8602 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8603 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8604 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8605 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8606 &:= ((T((-1 + (2 \times T(3)))) \times T(4)) - (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8607 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8608 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8609 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8610 &:= ((T((((-1+2) \times 3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8611 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8612 &:= ((-1+2 + T((T(3+4) + (5 \times T(6)))) - T(7+8+9)) \\
 8613 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 8614 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 8615 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) - (4 - T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 8616 &:= (T((-1 - (T((2 \times T(3))) - T(T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 8617 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 8618 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + (6 \times (7+8+9)))) \\
 8619 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T(4))) - (T((5+6)) - T(7+8+9))) \\
 8620 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8621 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8622 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((T(T(3)) + 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8623 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/ (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8624 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8625 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8626 &:= (-1+2 - ((T(T(3)) + 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8627 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8628 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8589 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7+6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8590 &:= (((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7+6)))) - T(T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8591 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8592 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8593 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 8594 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8595 &:= ((-9 - T((T(8) + 7))) \times (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8596 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) + T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8597 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(((7+6) + T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 8598 &:= (((-9 \times T(8+7))/6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8599 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7+6))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 8600 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) \times (T(6 \times 5) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8601 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8602 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7 \times 6) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8603 &:= (T((T(-9+8+7) + T(6))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8604 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + T(6+5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8605 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8606 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8607 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8608 &:= -9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) - T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8609 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8610 &:= ((T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) - T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8611 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8612 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7) \times T(T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8613 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 8614 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (6+5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8615 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times T(6+5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8616 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - T(7+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8617 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8618 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8619 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8620 &:= (T(((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 8621 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (T(T(7)) + T(6 \times 5))) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 8622 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8623 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times ((7 - 6) - T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 8624 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8625 &:= (((-9+8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8626 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - T(7+6)) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 8627 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8+7) + 6+5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8628 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T(7+6))) \times (T(T(5))/(4+3+2+1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8629 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + ((4^5) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8629 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8630 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times (4 + T((5+6)))) + T(7+8+9)) & 8630 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8631 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) & 8631 &:= (T(((9 \times 8) - (T(7) - T(T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8632 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 8632 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (6 + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8633 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+T(3))) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8633 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8634 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) \times (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 8634 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7+6))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8635 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 8635 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + (7 \times T(6)))) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8636 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 8636 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + (T(7+6) \times 5))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8637 &:= (((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8637 &:= (-9 + T((T(8+7) + (T(6+5) - T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8638 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8638 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8639 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T(T(3+4))) - T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8639 &:= (-9 + (8 \times T((T((7+6-5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8640 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4+5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8640 &:= ((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8641 &:= (((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8641 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T(T((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8642 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 8642 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(((7+6) + T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8643 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))) & 8643 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) + (6 - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8644 &:= (-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))) & 8644 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8645 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5+6+7+8+9))) & 8645 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8646 &:= T(((9 + 2 + (3 \times T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) & 8646 &:= T(((9 \times 8) - (T(7) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8647 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times (5 - (6+7+8+9))))) & 8647 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8+7) + 6+5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 8648 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8648 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 8649 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))) & 8649 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) \times ((7 + T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8650 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3) \times T(4)) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) & 8650 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8651 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T((T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9)))) & 8651 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 - T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8652 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8652 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8653 &:= (T((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times 4) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 8653 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8654 &:= ((T((-1+2+T(3))) \times (T(T(T(4)))/5) + 6+7+8+9) & 8654 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) \times (7+6))) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
 8655 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) & 8655 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T((T(6) - 5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8656 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3+4)-T(5)} + T(6+7+8+9))) & 8656 &:= (T(((9 \times T(8)) + (T(7+6) \times 5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
 8657 &:= (-1 - (T((2 - (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 8657 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8658 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 - (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) \times ((5+6) - (7+8+9)))) & 8658 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8659 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + (4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))) & 8659 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) - 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8660 &:= (((-1 - T(2 \times T(3))) \times (T(4) - T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 8660 &:= ((T((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8661 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4)) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) & 8661 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8662 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(3+4)) - T((T(5) - 6))) \times (7+8+9))) & 8662 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8663 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(T(3))) \times ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 8663 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T((T(T(7) + 6)/5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8664 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 8664 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8665 &:= ((T(-1+2+3) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 8665 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 + T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1))))) \\
 8666 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - (T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6)) - T(7+8+9)))) & 8666 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) \times 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8667 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 \times T(T(3))) + T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 8667 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7+6) + (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8668 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + 4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) & 8668 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 8669 := (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8670 := (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) - (T(4) - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))
- 8671 := (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8672 := (-1 + ((2 × T(T((3 × 4))) + (T(T((5 + 6))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8673 := (-1 - 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8674 := (-1 × 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8675 := (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - (4 - T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8676 := (T((-1 - (T(2 × T(T(3))) - T(T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
- 8677 := (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8678 := ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) + 4 + 5)) - (6 - T(7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8679 := (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8680 := ((-1 + 2 + 3) × (T(T(T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8681 := (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
- 8682 := ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) × (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8683 := ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8684 := ((-1 × 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8685 := ((-1 + T(T((2 × 3 + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8686 := (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) × 4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8687 := ((-1 + 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8688 := (T((T(T(T(-1 + 2 × 3)))/T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8689 := (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T((5 + 6)) × (7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8690 := (((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + T(T(T(4)))) × 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8691 := (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8692 := (-1 × (T(2 × T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8693 := T(-1 + T(2 × T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
- 8694 := ((T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) × 4) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8695 := (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8696 := (T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4))) + ((5 + 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8697 := (-1 - 2 + ((3 + T(T(4))) × (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8698 := (-1 × 2 + ((3 + T(T(4))) × (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8699 := (-1 + ((2 + 3) × (T((T(4) × 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8700 := (((-1 + 2) × 3) + T(T(4))) × (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8693 := T(-1 + T(2 × T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
- 8702 := (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3 + 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T((T(6) + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8703 := ((-1 - 2) × ((T(T(3)) × (4 - T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 8704 := (-1 × (T((2 + T(T(3))) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8705 := ((-1 + T((2³⁺⁴))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 8706 := (((-1 - 2) × (3 - T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8707 := (((-1 - 2) × T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 8708 := (T((-1 + 2) × (3 + 4))) × ((5 + 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9))
- 8669 := (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
- 8670 := ((-9 - 8 + T(T(7) + 6)) × (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 8671 := (-9 + (T(((8 × (7 + 6)) + T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8672 := (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T((6 + T(T(5)))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8673 := (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) × T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8674 := (-9 + ((T(T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8675 := (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) × T(6)) + (T(5) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8676 := (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((T(T(6)) + T(5)) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8677 := (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (6 - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 8678 := (-9 × 8 + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(6))) × (5 × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8679 := (-9 + ((T(8) × (7 + T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8680 := ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 8681 := (-9 + (((8 × T(7)) - T(6 + 5)) × T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8682 := (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8683 := (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (6 × (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
- 8684 := ((-9 × 8 + T(T(7))) × (T(6) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 8685 := (-9 + ((8 + T(T(7))) × (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8686 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8687 := ((-9 + 8) × (T(7 + 6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8688 := (-9 + ((T(T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + (T((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8689 := ((-9 + (T(T(8)) × (7 + 6))) - (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8690 := (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7) × (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 8691 := (T((-9 + ((8 × 7) + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8692 := (-9 + (T((T(8 + 7) + 6 + 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8693 := (((-9 × 8) - 7 - 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8694 := (((-9 + T(T(8))) × 7) + T((6 × (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8695 := (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) - (6 - T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8696 := (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(((7 - 6) + T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8697 := ((-9 × ((8 + 7) - 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8698 := (((-9 - (T(8) - T(7))) × 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8699 := (-9 + ((T(T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + 5 × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8700 := ((-9 × (8 - (T(7) × 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8701 := (T((-9 × T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) × 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 8702 := (((-9 - 8) × 7) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8703 := (T((-9 + (8 × 7)))/6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 8704 := (((-9 × 8 × T(7))/T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8705 := (T((-9 × 8 + T(7 + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 8706 := (-9 × 8 + T(((7 × T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8707 := (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (6 + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 8708 := ((-9 + 8) - (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))

8709 := $(-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$
8710 := $(-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))))$
8711 := $(-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9))))$
8712 := $((-1 - 2 + T((3 \times T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)$
8713 := $((-1 \times 2 + T((3 \times T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)$
8714 := $((-1 + T((T(2+3) \times (4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)$
8715 := $(T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))$
8716 := $((-1 + 2 + T((3 \times T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)$
8717 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9))))$
8718 := $((-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3))) \times T(4))) - ((5+6) + T(7+8+9)))$
8719 := $(-1 + ((2 + T(3)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))))$
8720 := $(-1 + (T((2^{3-4+5})) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
8721 := $(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + 4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9))$
8722 := $-1 + T(T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))$
8723 := $T(T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))/T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))$
8724 := $((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T((T(T(4)))/5))) - (6+7+8+9))$
8725 := $(-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9))))$
8726 := $(-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (4 \times (T(T((5+6))) - (7+8+9))))$
8727 := $(-1 - 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) + (4 \times T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))$
8728 := $((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
8729 := $(-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T((T(T(4)))/5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))$
8730 := $(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))$
8731 := $(T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
8732 := $((-1 + T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))$
8733 := $(T((T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))$
8734 := $(-1 + (((2+3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))))$
8735 := $(-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))))$
8736 := $(T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))$
8737 := $((T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
8738 := $(T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)))$
8739 := $(-1 - ((T(2+3) + 4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9))))$
8740 := $(-1 \times ((T(2+3) + 4) \times (5 - T(6+7+8+9))))$
8741 := $(-1 + (2 \times T((3 + (T(T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))))$
8742 := $((-1 + T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
8743 := $(T((T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9))$
8744 := $(-1 + (((2+T(3)) \times T(T(4+5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))$
8745 := $(T((-1+2+3) + T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))$
8746 := $(T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))))$
8747 := $((-1 + T((2 \times (T(T(3)) + T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9))$
8748 := $(T((-1 - 2 + (3 \times T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9))$

8709 := $((-9+8) \times (T(7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
8710 := $(((-9 + T((T(8) + 7))) - T(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))$
8711 := $(-9 - ((T(8) - (T(7 \times 6) + 5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))$
8712 := $(-9 \times (T(T(8)) - (T(7) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8713 := $(T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))$
8714 := $(-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))$
8715 := $((T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T(T(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))$
8716 := $(((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))$
8717 := $((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))$
8718 := $(((-9 + (T(8) \times 7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
8719 := $((-9 \times 8 + (7+6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))$
8720 := $(-9 - (T(8) + ((7+6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8721 := $(-9 \times (T((8 + (7+6))) - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$
8722 := $((-9 - (8+7)) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))$
8723 := $(T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + T(6+5))) - T(4+3+2+1))$
8724 := $(T((T(-9 + T(8))/7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
8725 := $((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T(6+5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
8726 := $(-9 + (T(T(((8+7) - 6))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
8727 := $(-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + T((T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1))))$
8728 := $(T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))$
8729 := $((-9+8) \times (T(7) + (T(6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8730 := $(-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(7+6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))))$
8731 := $(T((-9 + T(8)) - 7) + (6 + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))$
8732 := $(-9 - (T(8) + ((7-6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8733 := $(-9 - (T(8) - T(((7 \times T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1))))$
8734 := $(-9 - (T(8) - ((7-6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8735 := $(T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
8736 := $(T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (T(6) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
8737 := $(-9 + (T((8 + (7+6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))$
8738 := $(T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) + (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))$
8739 := $(T((T(-9 + T(8))/7)) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
8740 := $(T(T(-9+8+7)) - (6 - T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))))$
8741 := $((-9 \times 8 + (7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
8742 := $(-9 - (T(8) + ((7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8743 := $((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8744 := $((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8745 := $(T((-9 \times ((8+7) - T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
8746 := $(-9 - (T(8) - ((7+6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8747 := $((-9 - (8-7)) - (T(6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))))$
8748 := $(-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times 7) + T((6 \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$

8749 := ((-1 + 2 + T(((3 × 4) + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
8750 := (-1 + 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))
8751 := (T((T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) - 4)) + (T(T(5)) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8752 := (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8753 := (T((T(T(T(-1 + 2 × 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8754 := (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8755 := (-1 × (T(2 + 3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))
8756 := (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4)) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8757 := ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) × T(T(T(4)))))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8758 := (T((-1 + (2³⁺⁴))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
8759 := (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8760 := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 × 3))) + (T(T(4 + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8761 := ((-1 + 2 + (T(3) × T(T(T(4)))))) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8762 := (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8763 := (T((T(T(T(-1 + 2 × 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8764 := (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8765 := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 × 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8766 := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8767 := ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8768 := ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8769 := (-1 - ((2 - 3) × (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))
8770 := (T(T(T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8771 := ((-1 + 2 + (T(3) × T(T(T(4)))))) - (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8772 := (((-1 - 2) × T(T(3))) + ((4 + T(5)) × T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8773 := ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8774 := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + ((4 + T(T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8775 := ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) × T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
8776 := (-1 × 2 + T(((3 × T(T(T(4))))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8777 := (-1 + T((2 × (T(T(3)) + (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8778 := T((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8779 := (-1 + 2 + T(((3 × T(T(T(4))))/(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8780 := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(4) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8781 := (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8782 := (T((T(T(T(-1 + 2 × 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8783 := (-1 + ((2 × (3 × 4)) × (T((5 + 6)) + T(7 + 8 + 9))))
8784 := (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) + 4)) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
8785 := (T((T(T(-1 + 2 × 3)) + 4)) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8786 := (((-1 + T(2^{T(3)})) × 4) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
8787 := -1 + T(T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
8788 := (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))

8749 := (-9 - ((T(8 + 7)/6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8750 := (((-9 + 8) × 7) - (T(6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
8751 := (T((T(-9 + T(8))/7)) + (6 + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8752 := (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8753 := (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) - (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
8754 := (-9 - (T(8) + ((7 - 6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
8755 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
8756 := ((-9 + 8) × (T(7) - (6 + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
8757 := (((-9 + T(8)) × T(7)) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8758 := (((-9 + 8) × (7 × 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8759 := (-9 + ((T(T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8760 := ((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8761 := (-9 - 8 + T(((7 × T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8762 := ((-9 - (8 - 7 + 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8763 := (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
8764 := (((-9 + 8) - 7 - 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8765 := (((-9 + 8) × (7 + 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8766 := (T((-9 × 8) - (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
8767 := (((-9 + T((8 + T(7)))) × (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
8768 := (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
8769 := (-9 + ((T(T(8)) × (7 + 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
8770 := ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8771 := (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T((6 × T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8772 := (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + T((T(6) + 5 × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8773 := (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
8774 := ((-9 - (8 - 7 - 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8775 := (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) × (T(6) × (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
8776 := (((-9 + 8) - 7 + 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8777 := (-9 + 8 + T(((7 × T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8778 := T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8779 := (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(6) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8780 := ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - (6 + 5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8781 := (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))) + (5 × T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8782 := (-9 + (T((T(8) - 7 - 6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8783 := (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
8784 := (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) × T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
8785 := (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8786 := (((-9 + 8) - 7 - 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8787 := (((-9 + 8) × (7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
8788 := (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + T(6 + 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 8789 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/4) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8790 &:= (-1 \times ((T(2+3) - (T(T(T(4)))/5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8791 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8792 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8793 &:= (T((T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8794 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 8795 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2+3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8796 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8797 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times ((T(T(4))/5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8798 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8799 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + T((T(4) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8800 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + T((T(4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8801 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T((T((3 \times 4)) + T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 8802 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 8803 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
 8804 &:= (-1 + (T((2+3+T(T(4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8805 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3)))) + T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8806 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8807 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times (T(T(3)) + T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 8808 &:= (T((-1-2+(3 \times T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
 8809 &:= ((T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8810 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(3)) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8811 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(3)) - ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8812 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8813 &:= (T((T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))/T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
 8814 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times T(T((T(T(4))/5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
 8815 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8816 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) \times ((4-5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8817 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(3)) \times (T(4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8818 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) \times (T(4+5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8819 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3+4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 8820 &:= (((-1+2+3) + T(4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8821 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+T(4)}) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 8822 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 8823 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3) + T(4)))) - T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8824 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8825 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3+4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8826 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) - (4 - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 8827 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T((T(3) + 4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 8828 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 8789 &:= ((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8790 &:= ((T((T(-9+T(8))/7)) \times 6) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8791 &:= (-9 + ((T((T(8)+7)) - T(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 8792 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7+6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8793 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8794 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8795 &:= (T(T((T(-9+8+7) - 6))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8796 &:= (-9 - ((8 - T(T(7) + 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8797 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8798 &:= (((-9+8) - 7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8799 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (T(5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8800 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 + T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8801 &:= (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8802 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + ((6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8803 &:= (-9-8 + (T(7) \times (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8804 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) + (6 \times (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 8805 &:= ((-9+8 + (T(7) \times T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
 8806 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8807 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 8808 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(7 \times 6) - T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 8809 &:= ((-9+8 + (T(7) \times (T(6) \times T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8810 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times (6 + T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8811 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8812 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8813 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8814 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) - ((7+6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8815 &:= (T(T((T(-9+8+7) - 6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8816 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7+6)) + (5 \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8817 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6) + (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 8818 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((7+6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 8819 &:= (-9+8 + (T(7) \times (T(6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8820 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7 \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8821 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8822 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (6 - (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8823 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8824 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8825 &:= (((-9-8 + T(7+6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 8826 &:= ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8827 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8828 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7) + T(6)))) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8829 &:= ((-1-2-3) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8830 &:= (T(T(T((-1-(2-(3+4))))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 8831 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + ((4+5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8832 &:= -1 + T(T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8833 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8834 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 8835 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8836 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T((T(3+4) - T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8837 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((T(3)+T(4)))) - (T(5)+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8838 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8839 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8840 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8841 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8842 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8843 &:= (-1 + (T(T((T(2+3)-4))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8844 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5)+6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8845 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8846 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) - (5+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8847 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((T(3)+T(4)))) - (5+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8848 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((T(3)-T(4)))) \times (T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8849 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3))+4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8850 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3))+4+5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8851 &:= (T((-1+2+(3 \times T(4+5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8852 &:= ((-1+2+T(T((T(3)+(T(4)+T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8853 &:= (-1 + ((2-T(T(3))) \times ((4-5)-T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8854 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3)+T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
 8855 &:= (T((-1-2+(T(T(3))+4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 8856 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) + (5-T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8857 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(3)+T(4)))) + (5-T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8858 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 8859 &:= ((-1+T(T(T(2+3))+T(4))) - (T(T(5))-T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8860 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - (T(T(4)+T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8861 &:= (T(T((-1+T(2+3))) - (4 - ((5+6) \times T(7+8+9)))) \\
 8862 &:= ((-1-2+(T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))+T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 8863 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + ((4+T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8864 &:= (-1 + (((T(2+3)+T(T(4))) \times T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8865 &:= (T((-1+(T(T(2+3))+T(4))) + (T(5)+T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8866 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) + (T(5)-T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 8867 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 8868 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)+T(4)))) - (T(T(5))+T(6+7+8+9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8829 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(((7+6) + T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8830 &:= (((-9+8+T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + T((T(5)+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8831 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T(T(7)+T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8832 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8833 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7))+T(6+5))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 8834 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - ((T(6)-T(5)) \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8835 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8836 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8837 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (T(7)-T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8838 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7+6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8839 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T(((7+6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8840 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) \times (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8841 &:= ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) - (6 - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8842 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8843 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7)+T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8844 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8))+7)) \times (6+5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8845 &:= ((-9 \times (8-7-6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8846 &:= (-9 + ((8+T((T(7)-(6+5)))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8847 &:= (-9 + (T((8 \times (T(7)-T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8848 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8+7)+T(6)))) + (T(5) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8849 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(((7+6) + T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 8850 &:= ((-9 - (T(T(8)) - ((7+6) \times T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 8851 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8)+T(7+6)))) + T(5+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8852 &:= (-9-8 + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8853 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6 + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8854 &:= ((-9 \times ((8+7)-T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8855 &:= ((-9+8+T(((7+6) + T(T(5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 8856 &:= (T((-9 + (8+(7+6)))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8857 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(6+5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8858 &:= (-9-8 + ((T(7) \times (T(6) \times T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8859 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times 6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8860 &:= (-9-8 + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8861 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 8862 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 8863 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T((T(7)+T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8864 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (5+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8865 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 8866 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T(((7+6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 8867 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (T(T((T(6)-5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 8868 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

8869 := $((T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8870 := $(((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8871 := $(-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8872 := $(-1 - ((2 - T(T(3))) \times ((T(4)/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8873 := $((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) \times ((T(4)/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8874 := $(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T((T(T(4))/5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
8875 := $((-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8876 := $((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times (4 + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8877 := $(-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8878 := $((-1 - 2 + T((3 + (T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8879 := $((T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
8880 := $((-1 + T(((2^{3+4}) + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8881 := $(T((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8882 := $((-1 + 2 + T((3 + (T(4) + T(T(5)))))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8883 := $(T((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8884 := $(-1 + (((T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8885 := $(-1 + (T((2^{3+4}) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8886 := $(T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8887 := $(-1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - T((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
8888 := $T(-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
8889 := $(-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
8890 := $(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8891 := $(T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8892 := $((-1 - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8893 := $((-1 \times 2 + (T((3 \times 4)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8894 := $((-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)))/T(4))) \times T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8895 := $(((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8896 := $((-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times 4)) \times T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
8897 := $(((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3 + 4)))) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9))$
8898 := $(-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8899 := $((T(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8900 := $((-1 + 2 - T(T(3))) \times ((4 \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8901 := $(T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8902 := $(-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8903 := $(-1 + ((T(T(2 \times 3)) + (T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6))) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))$
8904 := $(-1 + ((T((2^{T(3)})) \times 4) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
8905 := $((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3 + 4) + T((5 + 6)))))) - (7 + 8 + 9))$
8906 := $((-1 + T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
8907 := $((-1 - 2) - (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
8908 := $(-1 - 2 + T((T((3 \times 4)) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$

8869 := $(T(((((-9 + 8) - 7) + T(6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8870 := $(((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6)) \times T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8871 := $(T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6) + T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8872 := $(T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8873 := $((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8874 := $(-9 - 8 + (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8875 := $(-9 - ((8 \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8876 := $(-9 + 8 + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8877 := $(T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8878 := $(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8879 := $(-9 + 8 + ((T(7 \times 6) - T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8880 := $((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8881 := $(-9 + ((T(8) + T(7 + 6)) \times (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8882 := $((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
8883 := $(-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
8884 := $((-9 - 8 + T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8885 := $((T(T(-9 + T(8)) - T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8886 := $(-9 + 8 + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8887 := $(T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8888 := $(T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8889 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8890 := $(-9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8891 := $(T(((((-9 + 8) - 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8892 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) - ((7 - 6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8893 := $(T((-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8894 := $(-9 - 8 + T(((7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8895 := $((T((T(-9 + T(8))/7)) \times 6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8896 := $(-9 + (T(8) + (T(7 + 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
8897 := $((-9 \times (T(8) + (7 - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8898 := $(T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8899 := $(T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (6 + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8900 := $((-9 + 8 + T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
8901 := $(-9 \times ((T(8) \times (T(7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8902 := $(-9 + T((T(((8 - 7) + T(6))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8903 := $(-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8904 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
8905 := $(T(((((-9 + T(8)) - 7 - 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8906 := $(T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 + 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
8907 := $(-9 - 8 - (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
8908 := $(-9 - 8 + (T(T(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
8909 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4) \times T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8909 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))) \\
8910 &:= (-1 + T(((2 \times (T(T(3)) \times 4) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8910 &:= (-9 + 8 + T(((7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8911 &:= T((-1 + 2 + ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8911 &:= T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7 + 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8912 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T(3 \times 4) + T(T((T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 8912 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 + 7) + (6 - 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8913 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - ((4 \times T(T((5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) & 8913 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T((7 + (T(6 + 5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8914 &:= ((T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8914 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) - (6 - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8915 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8915 &:= ((T((T(-9 + T(8)) / 7)) \times 6) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
8916 &:= (-1 \times (2^{T(3)} - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8916 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((T(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8917 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8917 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (6 + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8918 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) - T(((4 + T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8918 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8919 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) + (4 \times (T(T((5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8919 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8920 &:= ((-1 + 2 - T(T(3))) \times ((4 + T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8920 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8921 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8921 &:= (T((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8922 &:= T(-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8922 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (7 \times (6 + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8923 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8923 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8924 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8924 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7) + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8925 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{T(3)} \times 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8925 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (T(7) - T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8926 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8926 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8927 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3))) / T(T(4))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8927 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T((T(6) - 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8928 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8928 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8929 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) + 4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8929 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) + 7)) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8930 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8930 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8931 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8931 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (T(7) \times T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
8932 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times T(T((T(4 \times 5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8932 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8933 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8933 &:= ((-9 - 8 + ((T(7) + T(T(6 + 5))) \times 4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8934 &:= (T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4^5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8934 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8935 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8935 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8936 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 8936 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) \times T(T(6))) + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8937 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 8937 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (6 + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8938 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((3 + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8938 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T(((7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8939 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8939 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) - (7 - (6 \times (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8940 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + T(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8940 &:= ((-9 + T((T((T(8 + 7) / 6)) / 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8941 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8941 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8942 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8942 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (6 - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8943 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8943 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 - T(T(6))) \times (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8944 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8944 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7 + 6))) + (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
8945 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 8945 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7) \times 6) + T((T(T(T(5))) / T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8946 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 8946 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
8947 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + (T(4) \times (5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) & 8947 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
8948 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((5 + 6) - T(7 + 8 + 9)))) & 8948 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8949 &:= (-1 + ((T(2^{T(3)})) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8950 &:= (T((-1-2-3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8951 &:= (T(T((-1+2+T(3)))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
8952 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8953 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T((T(3+4) + T((5+6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
8954 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2+3)) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8955 &:= (((T((-1 + T(T(2+3))))/4) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
8956 &:= ((-1-2) - (T(T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8957 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8958 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8959 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) \times (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8960 &:= (((-1+2+3)^4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8961 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (4 \times (T(T((5+6))) + 7+8+9))) \\
8962 &:= (((-1-2) \times T(3)) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8963 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T((T(4)/5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
8964 &:= ((-1+2+3) \times (T(T((T(4)/5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
8965 &:= ((T(-1+2+3)^4) - T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
8966 &:= (-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8967 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
8968 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8969 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(3+4)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8970 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2 \times 3))) \times (4+5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8971 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8972 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8973 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8974 &:= ((-1-2-3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8975 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8976 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
8977 &:= (-1-2 + (T((T(3) + (4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8978 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8979 &:= (-1 - ((2-3) \times (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8980 &:= (T((T((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8981 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) + (4 + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8982 &:= (-1-2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8983 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8984 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8985 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
8986 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
8987 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + (3 \times T(4+5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
8988 &:= (T((-1-2 + (T(3+4) \times 5)) - T(6+7+8+9))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9028 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9) \\
9029 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9) \\
9030 &:= T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9) \\
9031 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8) - 9) \\
9032 &:= -1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9033 &:= -1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9034 &:= -(T(T(1 \times 2 \times 3)) - T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9035 &:= T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + T(T(4) + T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9036 &:= T((-1 + 2) \times 3) + T(4) \times T(T(5 + 6) - (7 + 8) - 9) \\
9037 &:= -1 + 2 + T(3) + T(4) \times T(T(5 + 6) - (7 + 8) - 9) \\
9038 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3 + T(T(4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9039 &:= -1 - T(2 + T(T(3))) + T(T(4 \times T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9040 &:= (-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3))) / 4) \times 5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9041 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2 + 3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9042 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9043 &:= -1 + (2 - T(T(3))) \times (4 - T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9044 &:= -1 + T(2 + 3 \times T(T(T(4))) / (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9045 &:= T(-1 - 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9046 &:= T(-1 + 2^{T(3)}) + T(T(4)) + T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9047 &:= -1 + 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times 4 + T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9048 &:= (-1 + 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9049 &:= T(-1 \times 2 + T(T(3) + T(4))) + T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9050 &:= -1 + T(2^{T(3)}) - 4 + T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9051 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) - 4) + T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9052 &:= T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9053 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3) + T(4))) - (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
9054 &:= -1 + T(2 \times T(T(3))) \times T(4) - 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9055 &:= (-1 + T(2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9056 &:= (-1 + T(T(2 + 3))) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + 6)) + T(7 + 8 + 9) \\
9057 &:= (-1 - 2) \times (T(3) - T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(5)) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9058 &:= -1 - 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9059 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2 + 3))) - 4 \times (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9060 &:= T(-1 + T(2 \times (3 + 4))) + T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9061 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9062 &:= -1 + 2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
9063 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9064 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9065 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9066 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9067 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9028 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) \times (6 \times 5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9029 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((7 \times (T(6) - T(5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9030 &:= ((T(T(T(-9 + T(8)) / 7)) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9031 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9032 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T(T(6 + 5))) \times (T(4) - (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9033 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times T(6)) - (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9034 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 \times 7) + T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9035 &:= (T((-9 + T(8)) - ((7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9036 &:= (-9 + T(((8 \times T(7)) - (6 \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9037 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9038 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9039 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6))) - (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9040 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(7 + 6))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9041 &:= (T((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9042 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9043 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - T(T(6)))) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9044 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 - 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9045 &:= T((-9 + T(8)) - ((7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9046 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) \times 6))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9047 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9048 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9049 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9050 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7) - 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9051 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9052 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9053 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9054 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times T((T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9055 &:= (-9 - (T(T(8)) - T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9056 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(T(5))) / T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9057 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9058 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9059 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) + (T(T(6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9060 &:= (((-9 + T(T((8 + 7) - 6))) - T(T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9061 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - T((T(6) + (T(T(5)) / (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9062 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (T(7) - (T(T(6)) \times 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9063 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times (T(7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9064 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) + T((6 + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9065 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) - T((T(T(T(5))) / T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9066 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9067 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8) - 7 - 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9068 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9069 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9070 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9071 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9072 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9073 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9074 &:= (-1 + (T(((2 \times (3 + 4)) + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9075 &:= (T((-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9076 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times (T(T(4)) \times T(T((T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9077 &:= (-1 - ((T(2 \times T(3)) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9078 &:= (-1 \times ((T(2 \times T(3)) \times (4 - T(T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9079 &:= (-1 + ((2 - T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9080 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9081 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9082 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9083 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9084 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9085 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9086 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9087 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9088 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9089 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + T(((T(4)/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9090 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(T(T(4)))/5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9091 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9092 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/4) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9093 &:= (-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + (T(4) \times T((T(5 + 6)) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9094 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) - ((5 + 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9095 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 \times 3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9096 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9097 &:= ((-1 \times T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\
9098 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9099 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9100 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9101 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - ((4 \times T(T((5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9102 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9103 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + 4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9104 &:= (-1 + ((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/4) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9105 &:= ((T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9106 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9107 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - ((4 \times T(T((5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9068 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9069 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - 7)) + (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9070 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9071 &:= (-9 + 8 + (7 \times (T(6) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9072 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((T(7) - (6 + 5))) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9073 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) \times (T(7) \times (6 - T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9074 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/T(6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9075 &:= ((T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) - T(6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9076 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + 6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9077 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) + (6 \times (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9078 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9079 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9080 &:= ((T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9081 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 + 6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9082 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9083 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times T(7)) - T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9084 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6))) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9085 &:= (((-9 - T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9086 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(T(6))) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9087 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9088 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times T(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9089 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) - (T(6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9090 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) - 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9091 &:= (-9 + (T((8 - 7 + 6)) \times T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9092 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + (T((T(6) \times 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9093 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9094 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9095 &:= ((T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) - 6)) \times 5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9096 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9097 &:= (T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9098 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times T(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9099 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) - T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9100 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9101 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8 \times 7)/T(6)) \times T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9102 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9103 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(6)))) + T((T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9104 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6))) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9105 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9106 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9107 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9108 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 9108 &:= (((-9+(T(8)+T(T(7)))) \times T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9109 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 9109 &:= (-9+8+(T(T(7)+6)+T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9110 &:= (-1+(T((T(T(2+3))-4)+(5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9110 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (T(7) + (6 \times (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9111 &:= (T((-1 - (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T(T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) & 9111 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7)/T(6)) \times T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9112 &:= (-1+2+(T((T(T(3)) - (T(4) - T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) & 9112 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T((7+T(6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9113 &:= (-1+(2 \times (T(T(3)) + ((4+5) \times (T(6) \times (7+8+9))))) & 9113 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9114 &:= (((-1+T(2+3)) - T(4+5)) \times (6 - T(7+8+9))) & 9114 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9115 &:= (((-1+T((2+3+T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) & 9115 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7)) + T((6+(T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9116 &:= (T((-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (5+T(6+7+8+9))) & 9116 &:= ((-9+T(((8+7)-6) \times T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9117 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(3) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 9117 &:= -9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7) - (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9118 &:= (-1-2+(T((T(3)+T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) & 9118 &:= (-9-8-(T(T(7)) - (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9119 &:= (-1+(2 \times T(((T(3) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 9119 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9120 &:= ((-1+2-T(T(3))) \times ((4+5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 9120 &:= ((-9+(T(8)+(T(7)+T(6)))) \times T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9121 &:= (T((T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))) & 9121 &:= (-9 - ((8 - T(7+6)) \times (T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9122 &:= ((-1+T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 9122 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) + (6 \times (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9123 &:= ((-1-2+T((T(T(T(3)) - 4) - T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 9123 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9124 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(T(T(3)) - 4) - T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 9124 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9125 &:= (((-1+2+T((T(3) \times T(4))) \times 5) - (6+7+8+9)) & 9125 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times (7+6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9126 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + (T(3+4) \times 5)) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 9126 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)-7) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9127 &:= ((-1+2+T((T(T(T(3)) - 4) - T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)) & 9127 &:= (-9+((T(8) \times (T(7+6) + T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9128 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - ((4 \times T(T((5+6)))) + T(7+8+9))) & 9128 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9129 &:= (-1+(2 \times ((3 \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))) & 9129 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9130 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9130 &:= ((-9 - (T(8) - (T(7+6) + T(T(5)))) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9131 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9131 &:= ((-9+(T(T(8)-7) \times T(6))) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
9132 &:= (-1-2+(T(T(3)) \times T((4-(5-(6+7+8+9))))) & 9132 &:= (-9 - (T(8+7) - (T(T((T(6)-5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9133 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times T((4-(5-(6+7+8+9))))) & 9133 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9134 &:= (-1+(T(2 \times 3) \times T((4-(5-(6+7+8+9))))) & 9134 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(T(7)) - (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9135 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times T((4-(5-(6+7+8+9))))) & 9135 &:= ((-9-T(8)) \times (T(7) - T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9136 &:= (-1+2+(T(T(3)) \times T((4-(5-(6+7+8+9))))) & 9136 &:= (-9+(T((T(8)-7+6)) + T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9137 &:= (-1-(2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9))))) & 9137 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) + (6 \times (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9138 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9138 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9139 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 \times (5+T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9139 &:= (T((-9+(8 \times 7))) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9140 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9140 &:= (((-9-T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(T(6)))) - 5+4+3+2+1) \\
9141 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 9141 &:= (-9+((T(T(8)-7) \times T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9142 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((4 \times T(T((5+6)))) + T(7+8+9))) & 9142 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)) + (T((T(7)+T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9143 &:= (-1+(T((T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T((5+6)) + T(7+8+9))) & 9143 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) - ((7+6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9144 &:= (-1+(T((T(T(2+3)) + T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 9144 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - ((7 \times T(6)) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))) \\
9145 &:= (T((T(T(-1+2 \times 3)) + T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 9145 &:= (((T(-9+8+T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1) \\
9146 &:= ((-1+T((2+(3 \times T(4+5)))) - (6+T(7+8+9))) & 9146 &:= (-9-8-(7 \times (T((6+T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9147 &:= ((-1-2+T((3 \times T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) & 9147 &:= (-9+(((8 \times 7) \times T((T(6)-5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

- 9148 := ((-1 × 2 + T((3 × T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 9149 := ((-1 + T((T(2 + 3) × (4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 9150 := (T((((-1 + 2) × 3) × T(4 + 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 9151 := ((-1 + 2 + T((3 × T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 9152 := (-1 + (T((2 × T(T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) × (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))
- 9153 := (T((-1 - 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9154 := (T(-1 + 2 + 3) + ((4 × T(T(5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))
- 9155 := (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(5)) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9156 := (T(((T(-1 + 2 - 3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9157 := (-1 - (2 × (T(T(3)) + (T(4) × (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))
- 9158 := (-1 × 2 × (T(T(3)) + (T(4) × (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))
- 9159 := (-1 - ((2 - T(T(T(3)))) × (T(T(4)) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))
- 9160 := ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) × (T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 9161 := (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - (T(T(5)) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9162 := (-1 × (T(2 × T(3)) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9163 := (T((-1 + (2³⁺⁴))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9164 := (-1 + (T(T((2 × (3 + 4)))) + (T(T(5)) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9165 := (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4))) + (T(T(5)) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9166 := (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) × 4)) - (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9167 := ((-1 + 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5 × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9168 := (-1 × 2 × (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4))) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9169 := (-1 + (2 × ((3 × T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9170 := ((-1 + T(2 + 3)) × (T((4 + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9171 := (T(T((-1 + 2 × T(3)))) + (T(T((4 + (5 + 6)))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9172 := (T((-1 + 2 + T(3)) + ((4 × T(T(5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))
- 9173 := (-1 - ((2 × 3) × (T(T(4)) - (T((5 + 6)) × (7 + 8 + 9)))))
- 9174 := ((-1 - 2 - 3) × (T(T(4)) - (T((5 + 6)) × (7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9175 := (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4) + (T(T(5)) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9176 := T(T(-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
- 9177 := (((-1 - 2) × T(T(T(3)))) + T((4 × (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9178 := (-1 × 2 + T((3 × (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9179 := (-1 + T((T((2 + (3 + 4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9180 := T(((T(-1 + 2 + 3) × T(4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
- 9181 := (-1 + 2 + T((3 × (T(4) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9182 := (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9183 := (T((-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9184 := (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(4)) × (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9185 := (T(T(T(-1 + 2 × 3))) + (T(T(4)) × (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9186 := (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) + (T(5) × T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))
- 9187 := (-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(5) × T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))
- 9148 := (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) × (6 + T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 9149 := ((-9 × ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9150 := (((-9 - T(8)) × (T(7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 9151 := (T(((T(-9 × T(8)) + (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9152 := (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9153 := ((-9 - (T(8) × T(7))) × (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9154 := ((-9 × (T(8) - (7 × (6 + T(T(5))))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9155 := (-9 + ((8 × (7 + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9156 := (T(-9 + T(8)) + T(((7 × T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9157 := (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9158 := (-9 - (T(8) + (7 + (6 × (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9159 := ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9160 := (((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/6) - T(T(5))) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 9161 := ((-9 + T(((8 + 7) - 6) × T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 9162 := ((-9 + 8) - (7 × (T((6 + T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9163 := (((-9 + 8) × 7) × (T((6 + T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
- 9164 := (T((T(-9 + T(8)))/7) - (T(6) - (5 × T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9165 := (-9 + (((T(T(8)) + T(7)) × (6 + 5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9166 := (T((((T(-9 + T(8)) × 7) - T(6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9167 := (-9 - 8 + (T((7 + T(6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9168 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) × T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9169 := (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 + 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9170 := (T((-9 + (8 × (7 + 6 + 5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 9171 := (-9 + T((((8 + 7) - 6) × (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9172 := (-9 + (T(((8 + 7) + T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9173 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 - 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9174 := ((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) × 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9175 := (-9 - (8 × (7 + (T(T(6)) × (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9176 := (-9 + (((8 + 7) × T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9177 := (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9178 := (T((((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9179 := (-9 + 8 + ((T(7 × 6) + T(5)) × (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9180 := T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - (6 - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9181 := (T((((T(-9 + 8 + 7) × 6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9182 := ((-9 + 8) × (T(7) + (6 × (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9183 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(T(7)) × (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9184 := (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))
- 9185 := ((T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) × T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
- 9186 := (T(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))))) + T((T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
- 9187 := (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))

$$\begin{aligned}
9188 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(3) + (T(4) \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9189 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9190 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))))) \times (4 \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9191 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9192 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9193 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9194 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9195 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9196 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + 3)) - T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9197 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9198 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9199 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9200 &:= ((-1 - T(2 + 3)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9201 &:= (-1 \times (2^{T(3)} - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9202 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9203 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 + T(3))) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9204 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + T(3))) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9205 &:= ((T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9206 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9207 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((3 \times T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9208 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((3 \times T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9209 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9210 &:= (T(((T(-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9211 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times T(4 + 5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9212 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9213 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9214 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9215 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times 3 + T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9216 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) \times (4 - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9217 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3) \times (4 - T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) \\
9218 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9219 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9220 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9221 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9222 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9223 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9224 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times ((T(4) \times T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9225 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - ((T(T(T(4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9226 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9227 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9188 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9189 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (6 + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9190 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6 + 5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9191 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9192 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8 + 7) + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9193 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + 7) \times (T(6) - (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9194 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9195 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) \times (7 - T(6))) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9196 &:= ((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9197 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9198 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) \times (T(6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9199 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9200 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 \times (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9201 &:= (T(((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6))) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9202 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) - (6 \times (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9203 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9204 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9205 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((7 + T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9206 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 - 6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9207 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9208 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7 \times 6) - T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9209 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 - 6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9210 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9211 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + (6 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9212 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9213 &:= (T((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(T(7) + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9214 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9215 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 \times 6)) \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9216 &:= (-9 \times (T(T(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9217 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9218 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 - (6 \times (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9219 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9220 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((7 \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9221 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + T(7))/6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9222 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) + T(6)) - T(T((5 + 4))))) + T(T((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9223 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9224 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 + (T((6 + T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9225 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9226 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 + 7) - 6) \times T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9227 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + T(T((T(6) - 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9268 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9269 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (4 + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9270 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9271 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9272 &:= (-1-2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9273 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9274 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9275 &:= ((T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
9276 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9277 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9278 &:= ((-1-2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9279 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9280 &:= ((-1 + T(T((2 \times 3 + T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9281 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9282 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9283 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9284 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9285 &:= ((-1 + T(T((T(2+3) - 4+5))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9286 &:= (T((-1+2 + (3 \times T(4+5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9287 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9288 &:= (-1-2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9289 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + 4) + T(T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9290 &:= (-1 + (T((2³⁺⁴)) + T((T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9291 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9292 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4))) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9293 &:= (T((-1+2 + T(3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9294 &:= ((-1-2-3) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9295 &:= (T(T(-1+2+3)) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9296 &:= ((-1 - T(2+3)) \times (4 - (T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9297 &:= (-1-2 + ((T(T(3)) + (4-5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9298 &:= ((-1+2-3) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9299 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) \times (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9300 &:= (-1 \times (T(2+3) \times (T(4) - T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9301 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T((T(3)+4) - T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9302 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4))) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9303 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + (T(4) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9304 &:= ((-1+2+3) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9305 &:= (((-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
9306 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) - T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
9307 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9268 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9269 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9270 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9271 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T(T((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9272 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9273 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times (6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9274 &:= (((-9 \times 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9275 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(T(7) - 6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9276 &:= (T((-9+8 + T(7))/6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9277 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9278 &:= ((-9+8) \times (T(7) - (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9279 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times (T(T(6)) - (5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9280 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - (7 \times 6)) \times T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9281 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(((7-6) + T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
9282 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9283 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times (6 + T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9284 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 - (T(6+5) - T(T((T(4) + 3+2+1)))))) \\
9285 &:= ((-9 - ((T(8) - T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9286 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + ((7+6) + T(T(5)))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9287 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9288 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9289 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T(((7+6) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9290 &:= ((-9 - (T((T(8) + T(7))) - T(T(6)))) \times (5 - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9291 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + (6 \times (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9292 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9293 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (6 + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9294 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(7) + (T(6) + T(T(5)))) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9295 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) - (6+5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9296 &:= (((-9 - (8-7)) + T(T((T(6) - 5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9297 &:= ((-9 + T((8 \times (T(7) - (6+5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9298 &:= (((-9+8) - 7) + T(T((T(6) - 5)))) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9299 &:= (-9-8 + T(T((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9300 &:= ((-9-8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9301 &:= ((-9+8) - (T(7) - (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9302 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9303 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9304 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (7 + (6 \times (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9305 &:= (T((-9 + (8 + (7+6)))) \times T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9306 &:= (T(-9-8 + T(7)) \times (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9307 &:= (-9 + T(T(((8-7)^{T(T(6))}) + (5+4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

- 9348** := $(-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9349 := $(-1 \times 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9350 := $(-1 + (T(T((2 \times 3 + T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9351 := $(T(T(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
9352 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9353 := $(-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + T((T(T(4))/5)) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9354 := $(-1 + ((T((2^{T(3)})) \times 4) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9355 := $(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9356 := $(T((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + ((5 + 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9)))$
9357 := $(-1 - 2 + ((T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9358 := $(-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9359 := $(-1 + (2 \times (T(3) \times T(4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9360 := $((-1 + T((2 \times (3 + 4)))) \times (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9361 := $(T(T(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4))) + (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9362 := $(-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9363 := $(T((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9364 := $(-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9365 := $(-1 - (T(2 \times 3) \times ((4 + T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9366 := $(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9367 := $(-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9368 := $(-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
9369 := $(-1 \times 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
9370 := $((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9371 := $(T(T(((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9372 := $(-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
9373 := $(-1 - 2 + (T((3 + (T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9374 := $(-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times (T(5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9375 := $(-1 + (T(((2^{3+4}) + 5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9376 := $(T((-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T(4 + 5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9377 := $(-1 + 2 + (T((3 + (T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9378 := $(T((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9379 := $(-1 + ((2^{T(3)}) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
9380 := $(-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (T(4) \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9381 := $(T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
9382 := $(T((-1 + 2 \times T(3)) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
9383 := $(-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) - T(4))) \times (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9384 := $(-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
9385 := $(T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) + (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))$
9386 := $(T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + (T((T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))$
9387 := $(-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))))$
9348 := $((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 \times 6))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9349 := $(-9 + 8 + ((T(7) + 6) \times (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9350 := $((-9 + 8 + T(7 + 6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
9351 := $(-9 + ((T(8) + (7 \times 6)) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9352 := $(-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
9353 := $(-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9354 := $(-9 - 8 + (T(T(((7 - 6) + T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9355 := $(((-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
9356 := $(-9 - 8 + (T(T(7) + 6) + T((T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9357 := $(-9 + 8 + (T(7) + (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
9358 := $((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9359 := $T(-9 + T(8)) - (T(7) - T(T(6)) - T(T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9360 := $(T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
9361 := $(T((-9 + 8 + (T(7) + 6))) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9362 := $(-9 + (T((8 \times (T(7) - (6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9363 := $(((-9 + 8) - 7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9364 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9365 := $(-9 + 8 + ((T(7) \times T(6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9366 := $(-9 \times 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9367 := $(((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9368 := $(((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times T(6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9369 := $(-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
9370 := $((T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) \times T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
9371 := $(T(T((-9 + 8 + T(7)) - (6 + 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
9372 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9373 := $(-9 - (T(8) - (T(7 \times 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9374 := $(-9 + ((T(8) \times T(T(7) - 6)) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9375 := $(T((-9 - 8 + T(7 + 6))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9376 := $(T((-9 + 8 + (7 \times 6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9377 := $((-9 + 8 + 7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9378 := $(-9 \times (T(8) + ((7 \times T(6 + 5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9379 := $((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7 \times 6) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
9380 := $((-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (6 - 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
9381 := $(T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) - (6 \times (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9382 := $(T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))$
9383 := $((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7 \times 6))) + (T(T(T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9384 := $((T(-9 + T(8))/7) + (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$
9385 := $((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))$
9386 := $((-9 \times (T(8) \times (T(7 + 6) - T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))$
9387 := $(-9 + 8 + ((T(7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
9388 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9389 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9390 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) \times (4 - T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9391 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9392 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) + ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9393 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (T(4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9394 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9395 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9396 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - T(T(4))) \times T((5 + 6))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9397 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + ((4 \times T(T((5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9398 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9399 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9400 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3) + T(4)) \times (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9401 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9402 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9403 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9404 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) + (4 \times 5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9405 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9406 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9407 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3)))/T(T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9408 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9409 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9410 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) + (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9411 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9412 &:= -1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9413 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9414 &:= (-1 - (((2 - T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9415 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) - (T(T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9416 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 \times T(3))) + (4 \times (T((5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9417 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) + (T(T(T(4)))/5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9418 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9419 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9420 &:= ((T((-1 + T(2 \times 3))) \times T(4 + 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9421 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9422 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + (3 \times T(4 + 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9423 &:= (T((-1 - 2 + (T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9424 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9425 &:= ((T((T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) + T(T(4)))) \times 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9426 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9427 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(3 + 4) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9388 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7 + 6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9389 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 - 7) + T((T(6) - 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9390 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8 + 7))) - (6 - T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9391 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) + (7 - T(T(6)))) \times (5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9392 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + 7) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9393 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7 \times 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9394 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7 + 6))) + T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9395 &:= (((-9 - T(T(8))) \times ((7 - 6) - T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9396 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) \times (T(7 + 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9397 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7))))/6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9398 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8 + 7) + (T(6) + 5)))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9399 &:= (-9 + (8 \times T(((T(7) \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9400 &:= ((T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 + 6)))) + T(T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9401 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9402 &:= (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times 6) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9403 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - T(7 \times 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9404 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7 + 6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9405 &:= ((-9 - T(8)) \times (7 - (T(T(6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9406 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9407 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T(T(6 + 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9408 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((T(T(7)) + (6 - (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9409 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9410 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9411 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) \times T(7)) - T(6 + 5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9412 &:= (-9 - (T(8 + 7) - (T((6 + T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9413 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) - (T(7) - 6 - T(T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9414 &:= -9 + 8 + T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9415 &:= ((T((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))) \times T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9416 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9 + 8 + 7))/T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9417 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (T(6) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9418 &:= (T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9419 &:= (((-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) \times (6 + 5)))) \times T(4)) - T(T((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9420 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9421 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 + 6) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9422 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - ((7 + 6) - T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9423 &:= (-9 - (T(8) \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9424 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) + (6 - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9425 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) - 7 + 6) \times (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9426 &:= (((-9 - (T(8) - T(T(7)))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9427 &:= (-9 + (T(8 + 7) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9428 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))))+(5-(6+7+8+9))) & 9428 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7))+T(T(6))) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9429 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))+(T(T(T(4)))+T(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9429 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-((7+T(6))-(T(T(T(5)))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9430 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3)))+(T(T(T(4)))+T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 9430 &:= ((-9-(8 \times ((7-6)-T(T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9431 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3))))-(T(4)-(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 9431 &:= ((-9+(T((T(8)-7+6) \times T(5)))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
9432 &:= (((-1 \times 2+T(T(3+4)))-(5+6)) \times (7+8+9)) & 9432 &:= (-9+(T(8)+(T(7+6+5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9433 &:= (-1-2+(T((3+T(T(4))))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9433 &:= (((-9+T(8)) \times (T(7)+6))+T((T(T(5))+4+3+2+1))) \\
9434 &:= (-1+(T((T(T(2+3))-T(T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9))) & 9434 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-((7-6)-T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9435 &:= (T((T(-1+2+3)+T(T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))+6+7+8+9)) & 9435 &:= (-9-((T(T(8)) \times (7-T(6)))-T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9436 &:= (T(((T(-1+2) \times 3)+T(T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9))) & 9436 &:= -9+8+T(T(7))+T(T(6))+T(T(T(5)))+T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9437 &:= (-1+2+(T((3+T(T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9437 &:= (-9+8+((7+6) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9438 &:= ((-1-(T(2+3)-T(T(4)))) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 9438 &:= (((-9+8)-7)+T(6)) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)) \\
9439 &:= (-1 \times 2+(T(T((T(T(3))-T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 9439 &:= (-9+(8 \times (T(T(7)))+(6 \times T(T(5)))+T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9440 &:= ((T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9) & 9440 &:= (((-9-T(T(8))) \times ((7-6)-T(5)))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
9441 &:= (T(T((-1+(T(T(2+3))/T(4))))+(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9))) & 9441 &:= (-9+(T((T(8)-7+6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9442 &:= (-1+2+(T(T((T(T(3))-T(4)))+(T(T(T(5)))-(6+7+8+9)))) & 9442 &:= -9+T(T(8))+T(7)-T(6)+T(T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9443 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4))))-T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 9443 &:= (T((-9+(T(8+7)+(T(6)+5))))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
9444 &:= ((-1-2-3) \times (T(4)-(T((5+6)) \times (7+8+9)))) & 9444 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-((7+6)-(T(T(T(5)))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9445 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3))))+((4+T(T(T(5))))-(6+7+8+9))) & 9445 &:= (((-9-T(T(8))) \times (7-T(6)))+(5-(4+3+2+1))) \\
9446 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3))))+((T(T(T(4))) \times 5)-T(6+7+8+9))) & 9446 &:= (-9-((T(T(8))+T((T(7)+T(6)))) \times (5-(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9447 &:= (-1-2+(T(3) \times (T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) & 9447 &:= ((-9+(T(8 \times 7) \times 6))-T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9448 &:= (-1 \times 2+(T(3) \times (T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) & 9448 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)))+(7+6)+T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9449 &:= (-1+((2+3+T(4)) \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) & 9449 &:= ((-9+T(T(8)))-(7-(T(6)+T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9450 &:= (T((-1 \times (2-(3+4)))) \times T(5+6+7+8+9)) & 9450 &:= ((-9-T(T(8))) \times (7-(6+5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9451 &:= (-1+2+(T(3) \times (T(T(T(4)))+5+6+7+8+9)) & 9451 &:= (-9+((T(8+7) \times T(6+5))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9452 &:= (-1+T((2+(3 \times (T(4)+5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9452 &:= (-9+(T(T(8+7)))+(T(T(6+5))-(4+3+2+1))) \\
9453 &:= T(((T(-1-2) \times (T(T(3))-T(T(4))))+5+6+7+8+9)) & 9453 &:= T((-9-8+(T(7)+(6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9454 &:= (-1+((2+3) \times T((T((4 \times T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 9454 &:= (-9+(T(((8-7)+T((T(6)-5))))+4+3+2+1)) \\
9455 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3))))-(T(4)-(5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9455 &:= (-9+((8 \times T(T(7)))+T((T(T(6))-T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9456 &:= (-1+(T(T(T(2+3)))+(T(4)+(T(T((5+6)))-(7+8+9)))) & 9456 &:= (-9+((T(8)+T(T(7)+6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9457 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4))))+(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) & 9457 &:= (-9+(T(((8+7)+T(6)))+(T(T(T(5)))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9458 &:= (-1+((T(T(2+T(3))) \times 4)+(T(T(T(5)))-T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9458 &:= (-9+(T(T(8)))+(7-6)+(T(T(T(5)))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9459 &:= (-1+(T((T(2+3)+T(T(4)))+(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9459 &:= (-9+8+(T((7+(T(6)+T(5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9460 &:= (T(((T(-1+2+T(3)) \times T(4)))+(T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 9460 &:= (T(((T(-9+T(8))/7)-(6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9461 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3))))-(4-(5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9461 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6))))+(T(T(T(5)))-(4+3+2+1)) \\
9462 &:= (((-1+(T(2+T(3)) \times 4)) \times T((5+6)))+7+8+9) & 9462 &:= (-9+(T(T(8+7))+T(((6+5)+T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9463 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4))))+T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) & 9463 &:= (-9-(8 \times (T(7+6)-T((5 \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9464 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) \times ((T(T(T(4)))/5)+6+7+8+9)) & 9442 &:= -9+T(T(8))+T(7)-T(6)+T(T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9465 &:= (T((-1+T((2+3+T(4))))+(5 \times T(6+7+8+9))) & 9465 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7)))-(6-T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9466 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4))+(5 \times (6+7+8+9))) & 9466 &:= (T((-9+8+7) \times 6)+(T(T(T(5)))+T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9467 &:= (-1+2+(T(T((T(3)+T(4)))+(5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 9467 &:= (((-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(T(6))+T(T(5))))-(4+3+2+1))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9468 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))) - (T(5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 9469 &:= (T((-1+T(T(2+3)))) + (4 + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9470 &:= (((-1-2+T((T(3)+T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
 9471 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) + T(T((T(4)+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9472 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(T(3))) \times (4 - (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9473 &:= (-1 - (T((2+T(T(3)))) - (T((T(4)+T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9474 &:= ((T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) \times 4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 9475 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times T((T(T(4))+T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 9476 &:= (-1 + (T(((2^{3+4}) + (T(5) - 6))) + 7+8+9)) \\
 9477 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(3+4)) - (5+6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 9478 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) \\
 9479 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9480 &:= ((-1+T(2 \times 3)) \times ((4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 9481 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9482 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + (3 \times T(4+5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 9483 &:= (T((-1-2+(T(3+4) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
 9484 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) - (4 - T(T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 9485 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times T((T(3)+T(4)))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
 9486 &:= (-1+2 + ((T((T(3)+T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 9487 &:= (T((-1-2+T(T(3)))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9488 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))) + 5+6+7+8+9) \\
 9489 &:= ((-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 9490 &:= (((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(T(4)))) \times 5) + 6+7+8+9) \\
 9491 &:= (T(T((-1+2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 9492 &:= ((-1-2+(T(3) \times (T(T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 9493 &:= (T((-1+2+T(T(3)))) + ((T(T(T(4)))/5) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
 9494 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) - T(6+7+8+9)) \\
 9495 &:= (T(((-1+2+3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
 9496 &:= T(T(T(-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
 9497 &:= -1+2+T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
 9498 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 9499 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 9500 &:= (-1 + (T(T((T(2+3) - 4))) + (T(T(T(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 9501 &:= (T(T((-1 + (T(T(2+3))/T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
 9502 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 9503 &:= (-1 + ((T((2+T(T(3)))) + T((4+(5+6)))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
 9504 &:= ((-1-2+T(T(3))) \times T(((T(4)/5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 9505 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(((3+4) + T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9506 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
 9507 &:= (-1-2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
 9468 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((T(7+6) + T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9469 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7))) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9470 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7+6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 9471 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 9472 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 9473 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9474 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7+6)) + (T(5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9475 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) + (7-6)) \times (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
 9476 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9477 &:= ((-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 9478 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (6+T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 9479 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) - (6 - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 9480 &:= ((-9 + (T((T(8)+7)) + 6+5)) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
 9481 &:= (T(T((T(T(-9+8+7))/T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 9482 &:= (-9 + (T(8+7) + (T(T((T(6)-5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9483 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 9484 &:= (((-9-8) \times T(7)) + (6 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9485 &:= (((-9+8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 9486 &:= (T((T(-9+T(8))/7)) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9487 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7+6) - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9488 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (T(T(7)+6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9489 &:= (-9 + ((T(8+7) \times 6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9490 &:= ((-9+8 + (7 \times T(6))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 9491 &:= (-9 - ((8 - T(7)) \times (T(6 \times 5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 9492 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9493 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9494 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7-6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9495 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - 5+4+3+2+1))) \\
 9496 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7))) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
 9497 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T(7+6)) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9498 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((T(7) \times 6) + 5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 9499 &:= ((-9+8 + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
 9500 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + T(7+6))) \times (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
 9501 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (6 \times (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9502 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
 9503 &:= (-9 - 8 - ((7+T(T(6))) \times (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
 9504 &:= ((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9505 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8+7))) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9506 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7+6)))) + T((T(5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
 9507 &:= (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times 6) - (5+4+3+2+1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$9508 := (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))))+T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$	$9508 := (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + T(((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1))))$
$9509 := (-1 + (T(2+3) \times (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9))))$	$9509 := (-9 - (T(8) + (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))))$
$9510 := (T(-1+2 \times 3) \times (4 + T(5+6+7+8+9)))$	$9510 := (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))))$
$9511 := (-1+2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + (T(5)+6+7+8+9))))$	$9511 := (-9 - (8 \times (T(T(7)) - T((T(6+5) - (4+3+2+1))))))$
$9512 := ((-1+2+T(T(T(3)))) \times ((T(T(4))/5) + 6+7+8+9))$	$9512 := (((-9+8) - 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))$
$9513 := ((-1-2) \times ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9))))$	$9513 := (-9 \times ((T(8) \times (7+6)) + (T(5) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
$9514 := (T(-1+2+3) + (T((T(T(4))/5) \times (6 \times (7+8+9))))$	$9514 := ((-9 \times (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))$
$9515 := (((-1-2+T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(4))) \times T(T((T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$	$9515 := ((-9-8+T((T(7)+(6-T(5)))) \times T(4+3+2+1))$
$9516 := ((-1-2) - (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(4)+T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))))$	$9516 := ((-9+(8 \times T((T(7)+T(6)))) - (5 \times T(4+3+2+1)))$
$9517 := (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - (T((T(4)+T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))))$	$9517 := (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(T(6+5)) + T(4+3+2+1))))$
$9518 := T(-1+2+T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)$	$9518 := ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))$
$9519 := (-1 + (2 \times (T((T(3)+T(4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9))))$	$9519 := ((-9 \times (8 - (T(7) + T(T(6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
$9520 := ((-1+2+3) \times (T(T(4)) + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9520 := (((-9+8) \times 7) - T(T(6))) \times (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1)))$
$9521 := (-1 - (((2-3) - T(4+5)) \times (T(T(6)) - (7+8+9))))$	$9521 := ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
$9522 := ((-1 + ((T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \times (5+6))) - T(7+8+9))$	$9522 := ((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times (T(6) - (5+4+3+2+1)))$
$9523 := (T((-1+2+(3 \times T(4+5)))) + (T(T(6)) - (7+8+9)))$	$9523 := ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))$
$9524 := ((-1 + (T((2 - (T(T(3)) - T(T(4)))) \times T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9))$	$9524 := (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
$9525 := ((T(T((-1+(2+(3+4)))) \times T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9))$	$9525 := (((-9+T(T(8))) - (T(7) - 6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))$
$9526 := (T((-1+T(2 \times 3))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$	$9526 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7+6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))))))$
$9527 := (-1 - (2 \times (T(T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) - (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9527 := ((-9 + T((T(8+7)+6))) - (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
$9528 := (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9528 := ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))$
$9529 := ((-1 + T(T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (5 \times T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9529 := T(-9 \times T(8) + T(T(7))) + T(6) + T(T(T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))$
$9530 := ((T(-1+2+3)^4) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))$	$9530 := (((-9+8+(T(T(7))+T(T(6)))) \times T(5)) - (4+3+2+1))$
$9531 := (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))$	$9531 := (-9 + (T(8) \times (T(T(7)) - (T(6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
$9532 := (-1+2 + (T(T(T(3))) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))$	$9532 := (-9 + (T(((8+7)+T(T(6))) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
$9533 := (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9533 := (((-9+8) - 7) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
$9534 := (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9534 := (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((7 \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
$9535 := (((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/4) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))$	$9535 := (-9 - (8 \times (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+T(4+3+2+1))))))$
$9536 := (-1 - ((2 + (T(T(3)) + T(4))) \times ((5+6) - T(7+8+9))))$	$9536 := (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 \times T(6+5)))) - T(4+3+2+1))$
$9537 := (-1-2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6+7+8+9))))$	$9537 := (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times 6) + (5+4+3+2+1))$
$9538 := ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)}))$	$9538 := (-9-8 + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1)))$
$9539 := (-1 + ((T(T(T(2+3)))/4) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9539 := ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7+6)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1))))$
$9540 := (-1 + (T((T(2 \times T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$	$9540 := ((-9+8+(T(T(7))+T(T(6)))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))$
$9541 := (T((-1-2+T((T(3)+T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9))$	$9541 := (T((-9+(T(8)+T(7)))) + T((6+T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
$9542 := (-1 + ((T(T(2 \times T(3))) \times ((4+5) - 6)) + T(7+8+9)))$	$9542 := ((-9 + (T(8 \times 7) \times 6)) - (T(5) + 4+3+2+1))$
$9543 := (T((-1+2+T((T(3)+T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))$	$9543 := (-9 - ((T(8) - T(7)) \times (6 - (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))))$
$9544 := (-1-2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$	$9544 := ((-9+8+((T(T(7))+T(T(6))) \times T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))$
$9545 := ((-1 \times 2 - T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - (5 + T(6+7+8+9))))$	$9545 := (-9 + ((8 \times T(7)) + (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))))$
$9546 := (-1 + (T(T(2 \times 3)) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$	$9546 := ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1))))$
$9547 := (T(T(T((-1+2) \times 3))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))))$	$9547 := ((-9 \times (8 - T(7+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
9548 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(T(3))) + T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9549 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2 + 3)) + T(4))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9550 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) + (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9551 &:= ((T((-1 + 2) \times 3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + ((5 + 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9552 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9553 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9554 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T((4 \times T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9555 &:= ((-1 + T((2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))))) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9556 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) \times T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9557 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times 3 + T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9558 &:= (T(T(((T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9559 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9560 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9561 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + (T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9562 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - T(5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9563 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6)))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9564 &:= (((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6)))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9565 &:= ((T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times T((T(4) + T(5)))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9566 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3)^4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9567 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9568 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T((T(T(3)) - T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9569 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) + T(T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9570 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(3 + 4))))/5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9571 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9572 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times 4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9573 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9574 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9575 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9576 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9577 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9578 &:= (((-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) \times (4 + T(T(5)))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9579 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + T(T(4))) \times T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9580 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9581 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))) - (4 - (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9582 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T(T(3 + 4)) - (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9583 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9584 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 + 3 + T(4)))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9585 &:= (T(T(T((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))))) + (5 \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9586 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9587 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9548 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7 + 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9549 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times 7) + (6 \times (T(5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9550 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9551 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/6) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9552 &:= ((-9 + (T(8 \times 7) \times 6)) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9553 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (T(T(7)) - (6 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9554 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9555 &:= ((T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) + T(T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9556 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9557 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9558 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9559 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9560 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) - T(T(6))) \times (T(5) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9561 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - (7 + T(6))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9562 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9563 &:= ((-9 + 8) \times (T(7) - T((6 + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9564 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9565 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + T(T(6)))) \times (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9566 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(T(7)))) + ((6^5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9567 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) \times (T(6) - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9568 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + T(((7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9569 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9570 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + 7) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9571 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(T(6)) - (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9572 &:= ((-9 + (T(8 \times 7) \times 6)) - 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9573 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times 7) + (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9574 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9575 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) - 6) \times (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9576 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) + T((T(6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9577 &:= (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times (T(6) - T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9578 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(((7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9579 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + (T(T(5))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9580 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7 \times 6))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9581 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 \times T(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9582 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9583 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + T((6 + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9584 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + T((6 + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9585 &:= (-9 \times (T((T(8 + 7)/6)) - T((5 \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9586 &:= ((-9 \times (T(T(8)) - ((7 + 6) \times T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9587 &:= (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times 6) + (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9588 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9589 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (4 + (5 \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9590 &:= ((-1 + T(2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9591 &:= T(((-1 + 2 - 3) + (4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9592 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) + (T(5) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9593 &:= (-1 - (T((2 + T(T(3)))) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9594 &:= (-1 \times (T((2 + T(T(3)))) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9595 &:= ((T(T(-1+2+3)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9596 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T((5+6))) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
9597 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9598 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9599 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9600 &:= (T(-1+2 \times 3) \times (T(4) + T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9601 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9602 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))))) - ((5+6) - T(7+8+9))) \\
9603 &:= (T((-1+2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (5 \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9604 &:= (((-1+2 + T(3))^4) \times (T(T(5)) / (6+7+8+9))) \\
9605 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) - (T(T(4)) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9606 &:= (T(((-1 + T(2+3)) \times T(4))) - ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
9607 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T((5+6)) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
9608 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9609 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((5+6)))))) - (7+8+9)) \\
9610 &:= (((-1 + T((2+3 + T(T(4)))))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
9611 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(3) + (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9612 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9613 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9614 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times T((4 \times T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9615 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9616 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9617 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9618 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9619 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9620 &:= (((-1 + 2 + T((T(3) \times T(4)))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
9621 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + (T(3+4) \times 5))) + 6+7+8+9) \\
9622 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T((T(T(3)) - 4)) - T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9623 &:= (-1 + (((2 + T((3 \times T(4)))) - T((5+6))) \times (7+8+9))) \\
9624 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9625 &:= ((-1 + 2 \times 3) \times (T(T(4)) \times (5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9626 &:= (-1 + (T(T((2 \times 3 + T(4)))) + ((5+6) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
9627 &:= (T(T((-1+2+3) \times 4)) + ((5+6) + T(7+8+9))) \\
9588 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + T((6 + T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9589 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9590 &:= (-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9591 &:= (((-9 + T(8+7)) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9592 &:= (T(T(-9-8+T(7))) + T((T(6+5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9593 &:= (-9 - 8 + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9594 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9595 &:= (((-9 + 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(6)))) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9596 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6)))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
9597 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) + T((6 + (T(T(T(5))) / T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9598 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7+6)))) + T((T(T(T(5))) / T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9599 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7-6) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9600 &:= ((-9 - T((8 + (7+6)))) \times (T(5) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9601 &:= (T(((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 \times T(6+5)))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
9602 &:= (T(T(-9+8+7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9603 &:= (-9 + (T(8) \times ((7 \times T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9604 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9605 &:= ((((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 - 6) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9606 &:= (T(((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9607 &:= (T(-9-8+T(7)) + (T((6 + T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9608 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((7 \times (T(T(6)) \times 5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9609 &:= (-9 + 8 + (((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9610 &:= ((T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6)))) - T(T(5))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9611 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + ((T(T(6)) + 5) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9612 &:= (T(-9+8+7) + T((6 + (T(T(T(5))) / T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9613 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times ((7 \times T(6)) + T(T(5)))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9614 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9615 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) - (6 \times (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9616 &:= (-9 - ((T(8) - T(7+6)) \times (T(T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9617 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + 5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9618 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7) + ((6+5) \times (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9619 &:= (T((-9 \times T(8)) + T(T(7))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9620 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7+6)) \times (T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9621 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T((T(7) + T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9622 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) + (T(T(6)) - (T(5) \times T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9623 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(((7+6) + T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9624 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9625 &:= ((T((-9 \times 8 + T(7+6))) - T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9626 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9627 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9628 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) - (T(T(T(5)))) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9629 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 + T(T(3)))) + T(4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9630 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 + 3)) - (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9631 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3 + T(4))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9632 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times ((4 \times (5 + 6)) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9633 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(5))) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9634 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) - (T((5 + 6)) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9635 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 + T(3)))) \times 4) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9636 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(T(3))) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9637 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9638 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9639 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9640 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(T(3))) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9641 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (T(T(3)) + (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9642 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((3 \times T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9643 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((3 \times T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9644 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 + 3)) \times (4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9645 &:= (T((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9646 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((3 \times T(4 + 5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9647 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5)))) / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9648 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((T(T(3)) \times 4) - ((5 + 6) \times T(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9649 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T((4 + T((5 + 6)))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9650 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9651 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 + 3 + T(4)))) + (T(T((5 + 6))) + T(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9652 &:= (T(T((((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4))) + (T(5) + (T(6) + T(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9653 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(4) + (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9654 &:= (((T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (4 + T(5))) \times 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9655 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) + (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9656 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9657 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(3 + 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9658 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3 + 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9659 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 \times T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9660 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (4 \times T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9661 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(3 + 4) \times (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9662 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(T(5)) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9663 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2 \times 3)) - (T((T(T(T(4)))) / (5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9664 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2 + 3)))) + (4 + T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9665 &:= (((-1 + T(T(2 \times 3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9666 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (T((3 \times 4)) - ((5 + 6) \times T(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9667 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(T(4))) + ((5 + 6) \times T(7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9628 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((T(6 + 5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9629 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9630 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times T(6 + 5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9631 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9632 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + (T(T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9633 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - T(7 \times 6))) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9634 &:= (-9 \times 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9635 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9636 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (T(6 + 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9637 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7 \times 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9638 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + T((6 + (T(T(T(5))) / T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9639 &:= (-9 - ((T(T(8)) + T(T(7))) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9640 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9641 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) - (7 - (6 \times (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9642 &:= (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9643 &:= (-9 + (T(8 \times 7) + (T((6 + T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9644 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9645 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + (7 - T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9646 &:= (T((((-9 \times T(8)) + (7 \times T(6 + 5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9647 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9648 &:= (-9 \times 8 \times (7 - (T(6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9649 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9650 &:= ((-9 + (T(T(8)) + (T(7) \times (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9651 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9652 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7) + 6) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9653 &:= (T((((-9 + T(T(8))) - T(T(7) + 6))) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9654 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + T(7 + 6)))) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9655 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 + (6 \times (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9656 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times T(T(6)))) \times 5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9657 &:= (-9 \times (8 - T((T((7 + 6 - 5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9658 &:= (-9 \times 8 + T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9659 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 - 7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9660 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 - 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9661 &:= (T((((-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9662 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9663 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) + T((T(7) + (6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9664 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7 + 6))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9665 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9666 &:= (-9 + (T(((8 + T(T(7))) / 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9667 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) - (T(6) - T(T(5)))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9668 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + T(T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9669 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) + ((5+6) \times (7+8+9))) \\
9670 &:= (T(T((-1 + T(2+3)))) + (T(4) + T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9671 &:= T(T(-1 + 2 + T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
9672 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9673 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9674 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9675 &:= (T((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + T(5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9676 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9677 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times T(T((T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9678 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + (T(3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9679 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (T(4) \times (T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9680 &:= (T(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times (T(T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9681 &:= (T((-1 + (T(T(T(2+3)))/T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9682 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + (T((5+6) + T(7+8+9))) \\
9683 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T((5+6) + T(7+8+9)))) \\
9684 &:= (((-1 + 2 + 3) \times T(T(4+5))) + (T(T(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
9685 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))))) \times (4 \times 5)) + T(6+7+8+9) \\
9686 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) - (T(T(4)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9687 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9688 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9689 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(T(3))) \times (T(4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9690 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T(T(3))) \times (T(4+5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9691 &:= ((-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9692 &:= (T((-1 + T(2+3))) - (4 - T((T(T(5)) - (6 - (7+8+9)))))) \\
9693 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times T(T(T(3)))))) \times (4+5)) + (T(T(6)) \times (7+8+9))) \\
9694 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 \times T(T(T(4)))) - 5)) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9695 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2+3))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9696 &:= (T((-1 + (2 \times T(T(3)))) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9697 &:= ((-1 - 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9698 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9699 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2+3)) + (4 + T(5)))) - (6+7+8+9)) \\
9700 &:= (T(((T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)))/T(4)) - T(5))) - (6+7+8+9) \\
9701 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9702 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) \times ((4+5) - (6+7+8+9))) \\
9703 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(5))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9704 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) - T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9705 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9706 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + T(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9707 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9668 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times (T(7) - (6+5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9669 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9670 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 - 6) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1 \\
9671 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T((T(7) + T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9672 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (7 \times 6))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9673 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T(T(7)) + ((T(6) - T(5)) \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9674 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7+6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9675 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + (7 \times 6)))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9676 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (T(7) - (T(6) + T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9677 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1))))))) \\
9678 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T((T(7+6) - T((5+4)))))) + T((3+2+1))) \\
9679 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9680 &:= (((T((-9 + T(8+7)))/T(6)) - T(T(5))) \times T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9681 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + (T(T(6)) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9682 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (T(T(6)) - (T(5) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
9683 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + 7)) + (T(T(6)) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
9684 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9685 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9686 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7 \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9687 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9688 &:= -9 + T(8 + T(7)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9689 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
9690 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9691 &:= (T((-9 + T(8+7))) + ((T(T(6)) \times T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9692 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9693 &:= (-9 \times ((T(8) \times (7+6)) - (5 + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9694 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T((7 - (6 - (5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9695 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9696 &:= (((T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9697 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (T(T(6)) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9698 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (T((T(7) + T(6))) - (5+4)))) - T((3+2+1))) \\
9699 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9700 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9701 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (7 + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9702 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9703 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) + T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9704 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9705 &:= (((-9 + 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9706 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9707 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9708 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9709 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9710 &:= ((T((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9711 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (5 + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9712 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{3+4}))) + (T((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9713 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9714 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2 + 3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9715 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T(T(4))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9716 &:= ((T((-1 - 2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(T(4))) + ((5 + 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9717 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 \times T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9718 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (3 \times T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9719 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + T(3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9720 &:= ((-1 + T(((2 + T(3 + 4)) - 5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9721 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 \times T((T(T(4)) - (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9722 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9723 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times T(T(T(3)))) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9724 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) \times ((T(4)/5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9725 &:= (((-1 + T((2 + T(T(3)))) \times T(4)) + (T(5) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9726 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9727 &:= (-1 - 2 + T((3 + T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9728 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9729 &:= (-1 + T(((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9730 &:= T((-1 + (T((2 \times (3 + 4)) + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9731 &:= (-1 + 2 + T((3 + T(((4 \times T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) \\
9732 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9733 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9734 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2 + 3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9735 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9736 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T(3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9737 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + ((4 + T(5)) \times T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9738 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9739 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times T(((4 + 5) + T(6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9740 &:= (-1 + (T((2 + T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9741 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((4 - 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9742 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((4 - 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9743 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) \times ((4 - 5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9744 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9745 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9746 &:= (T((-1 + (2^{T(3)}))) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times 5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9747 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3) + (4 + T(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9708 &:= (T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) + (6 \times (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9709 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9710 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6 \times 5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9711 &:= (-9 + (T(8 + 7) \times (T(6) + (5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9712 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + (T(T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9713 &:= (-9 - 8 + T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9714 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9715 &:= ((((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 - 6) \times T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9716 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 + 7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9717 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9718 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9719 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5))))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9720 &:= (-9 \times (T(8 + 7) \times (6 - (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9721 &:= (-9 + T((T(8) - (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9722 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + (T(7) + T(T((T(6) + (5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9723 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9724 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9725 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9726 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + ((T(T(6)) + T(T(5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9727 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9728 &:= (T(-9 + T(8)) + ((T(7) + 6) \times (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9729 &:= (-9 + 8 + T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9730 &:= T((-9 \times 8 + (T(7 + 6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9731 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) + (T(7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9732 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9733 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9734 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9735 &:= (-9 + (((8 + T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9736 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + (T(7) + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9737 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8)) + ((T(7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9738 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(((7 \times 6) + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9739 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9740 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + (T(7 + 6) + T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9741 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) \times (7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9742 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8 + 7)) + (6 + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9743 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(((7 + T(6)) \times 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9744 &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + T(7) \times T(6) + T(T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9745 &:= (T(T((T(-9 + 8 + 7) - 6))) + T((T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9746 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9747 &:= ((-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9748 &:= ((-1+2-3) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9749 &:= (-1 - (T(T(2+3)) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9750 &:= (-1 \times (T(T(2+3)) - T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9751 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) + (4+T(5)))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9752 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T((T(3+4) - (T(T(5)) - T(T(6)))) + 7+8+9)) \\
9753 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9754 &:= ((-1+2+3) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9755 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2+3))) + (T((4+T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9756 &:= (T(((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9757 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9758 &:= ((T(-1+2+3)^4) - (T(T(T(5)))/(6+7+8+9))) \\
9759 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(2+3)) + (4+T(5)))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9760 &:= (((-1+2+3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9761 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((4 \times 5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9762 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9763 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(T(4)) + (5 - (6+7+8+9)))))) \\
9764 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) - (4+5)) \times T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9765 &:= ((-1 + (T((2+T(T(3)))) + 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) \\
9766 &:= (T(T(((-1+2+3) \times 4))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9767 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9768 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) \\
9769 &:= ((-1 \times T(T(2 \times 3))) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\
9770 &:= ((-1+2 - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) \\
9771 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3)) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9772 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3)) \times (4 - (T(T(5)) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9773 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9774 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) + T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) \\
9775 &:= (T(((-1+2+T(3)) \times T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9)) \\
9776 &:= (T(T(((-1+2+3) \times 4))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9777 &:= ((-1+2 + T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (5 - T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9778 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3)) + (T((T(4) + T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9))) \\
9779 &:= (-1 + (T(T(T(2+3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9)))) \\
9780 &:= (T(T(T(-1+2 \times 3))) + (4 \times T(5+6+7+8+9))) \\
9781 &:= (T((-1+2 + (3 \times T(4+5)))) + T(6+7+8+9)) \\
9782 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3) + (T(4) + T(T(5)))) + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9783 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 - 5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9784 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 - 5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9785 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) \times ((4 - 5) - T(6+7+8+9)))) \\
9786 &:= (T(T(((-1+2+3) \times 4))) + (5 + T(6+7+8+9))) \\
9787 &:= (-1+2 - (T(T(3)) \times ((4 - 5) - T(6+7+8+9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9748 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (7 \times (T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9749 &:= (T(-9+8+T(7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9750 &:= (T((T(-9+T(8)) - (7+T(T(6)))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9751 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (T((T(7) + T(6)))) + (5 - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9752 &:= (-9 + (T((T(T(8)) - T(T(7)+6))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9753 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + ((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9754 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7+6) \times 5) + T(T((T(4) + 3+2+1)))) \\
9755 &:= ((T(-9+8+7) \times T(6 \times 5)) - (4+3+2+1)) \\
9756 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9757 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9758 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(T(7)) - ((T(6) \times T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9759 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) - T(7)) \times (T(6) + (T(T(5)) \times (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9760 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(T(7)) + (T(T((T(6) - 5))) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9761 &:= (-9 + ((T(8+7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1)))) \\
9762 &:= ((((-9+8) - T(T(7))) \times (T(6) - T(5+4))) - (3+2+1)) \\
9763 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T(7) + T(T(6)))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9764 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + 7) \times (T(T(6)) - 5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9765 &:= (((-9 + T((8+T(7)))) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9766 &:= (-9 + ((T(((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times 5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9767 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + (T((T(7) + T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
9768 &:= ((-9 - 8 + T(7+6)) \times (T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9769 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9770 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - T(T(6)))) + (5 \times T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9771 &:= (-9 + ((T(8+7) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9772 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9773 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(6) + 5)) - T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9774 &:= ((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) + (6+5 - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9775 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) + (7+6)) \times (T(5) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9776 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times T((T(7) + T(6)))) - (5+4+3+2+1)) \\
9777 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8+7) - T(T(6)))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9778 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) \times T(7))) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9779 &:= (-9 + (T((T(8) + T(7+6))) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9780 &:= ((-9+8+7) \times ((6 \times T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9781 &:= (-9 + ((T(8+7) \times T(6)) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4+3+2+1)) \\
9782 &:= -9 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(7)) \times T(6) + T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1) \\
9783 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9784 &:= (-9+8 + (T((T(7) + (T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9785 &:= (T((-9 \times 8 + (T(7+6) + T(T(5)))) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9786 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9787 &:= (-9 + (T((8 + T(T(((7 - 6) \times 5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9788 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) - (T(4) - (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9788 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + T(((7 + T(6)) \times 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9789 &:= -1 + (2 + T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9789 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7 + 6) + T(T((5 + 4)))))) - T((3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9790 &:= (T(T(T(-1 + 2 + 3))) + (T(T(4)) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9790 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9791 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9791 &:= (-9 + (8 \times T((T(7) + (6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9792 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9792 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9793 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9793 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (T(6) + (T(T(5)) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9794 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9794 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times T(T(6)))) - (T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9795 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{3+4})) + T(T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))))) & 9795 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times (T(T(6)) - ((5 + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9796 &:= (T(T((-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4)) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9796 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9797 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T((T(3) + T(4)))) + (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9797 &:= (((-9 + T(8 \times 7)) \times 6) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9798 &:= (T((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3))/T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9798 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(T(7)))) + T((T(T(6)) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9799 &:= (-1 + ((T((2 + T(T(3)))) + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9799 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8 + 7) - T(T(6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9800 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(3))) \times (T(4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9800 &:= (((-9 + T(((8 + 7) + T(6)))) \times T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9801 &:= (T(T(T((-1 + 2) \times 3))) + (T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6))) - T(7 + 8 + 9))) & 9801 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9802 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 \times T(3)))) + ((4 + T(T(T(5)))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9802 &:= (((-9 \times T(T(8))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9803 &:= (-1 + ((T(2 + T(3)) \times (4 \times T((5 + 6)))) + T(7 + 8 + 9))) & 9803 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9804 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((T(4)/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9804 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times T(T(6)))) - T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9805 &:= (-1 - (2^{T(3)} - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9805 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + 7))) - (6 \times (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9806 &:= (-1 \times (2^{T(3)} - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9806 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times T((T(7) + T(6)))) + (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9807 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(T(3))) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9807 &:= (-9 + (T((T(T(8)) - T(T(7) + 6))) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9808 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(T(3)) \times ((T(4)/5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9808 &:= ((-9 \times 8 \times (7 - T(6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9809 &:= (-1 + ((2 + T((T(3) + (4 + T(5)))) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9809 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (T(7) - ((6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9810 &:= (T((-1 + T((2 \times 3 + T(4)))) + T(5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9810 &:= (-9 \times (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (6 \times T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9811 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times T(T(3 + 4))) + ((5 \times 6) \times T(7 + 8 + 9))) & 9811 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9812 &:= (-1 + (T((T(T(T(2 + 3))/T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9812 &:= (((-9 \times T(8)) + (T(T(7)) \times 6)) + (5 \times T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9813 &:= (T((T(T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3))/T(T(4)))) + T((T(5) + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9813 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9814 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(2 + 3)))) - (T(T(T(4))) - T((T(T(5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9814 &:= ((T((-9 + T(8 + 7)))/6) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9815 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) - T(T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9815 &:= (T((T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))/(6 + 5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9816 &:= (T((-1 + T(T(2 + 3)))) + (T(T((T(T(4))/5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9816 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8) - 7)) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9817 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9817 &:= ((-9 + 8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9818 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(5)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9818 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (T(6) + 5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9819 &:= (-1 - ((2 - T(3)) \times (T((T(T(4)) + T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9819 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 + 7) + 6) \times T((T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9820 &:= ((T(T(-1 + 2 + 3)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9820 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6 \times 5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9821 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3)^4)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9821 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9822 &:= (-1 - 2 + ((T((3 \times 4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9822 &:= (T(T(-9 + 8 + 7)) + T((6 + (T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9823 &:= (-1 \times 2 + ((T((3 \times 4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9823 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - (6 + 5)) - T((T(T(4)) - (3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9824 &:= (-1 + (T(2 + 3) \times (T((4 + T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9824 &:= (T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))) - (T(T(6)) - T((T(T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9825 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times T(5)) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) & 9825 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - T(((7 + 6) \times T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9826 &:= (-1 + 2 + ((T((3 \times 4)) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9826 &:= (-9 + (T(T(((8 + 7) - 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9827 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(T(3))) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9827 &:= (-9 + 8 + (T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9828 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(T(3))) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9829 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(4)) + (T(T((5 + 6))) - T(7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9830 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - (T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9831 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - (T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9832 &:= -1 - (2 \times (T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9833 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9834 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9835 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) - (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9836 &:= (((-1 + T((2 \times T(T(3)))) - T(4)) \times (5 + 6)) + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9837 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T((T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9838 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + T((T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9839 &:= ((-1 + T((T(T(2 + 3)) + (4 \times 5)))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9840 &:= (T((T((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4))) \times 5)) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9841 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T((T(3 + 4) \times 5))) - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9842 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(T(3)))) + (4 \times (T(T((5 + 6))) + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9843 &:= ((-1 - 2 + T(((T(3) \times T(T(T(4))))/T((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9844 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3) \times (T((4 + T((5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9845 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) + (5 - (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9846 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9847 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9848 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9849 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 \times 3) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9850 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9851 &:= (((-1 + 2 \times 3) + T((T(T(T(4)))/(5 + 6)))) - (7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9852 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times T(3)) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9853 &:= T(-1 + T(2 \times T(3))) + T(T(4)) + T(T(T(5))) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
9854 &:= (-1 - (T(2 + 3) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9855 &:= (-1 \times (T(2 + 3) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9856 &:= (((-1 + T((2^{T(3)}))) \times 4) + T(T(T(T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9857 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times T(3)) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9858 &:= ((-1 \times 2 \times T(3)) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9859 &:= (-1 + (T((2^{T(3)})) + (T(T(4)) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9860 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) - T((T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
9861 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9862 &:= (-1 \times 2 - (T(3) - T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9863 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9864 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9865 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) \\
9866 &:= (T((-1 + T(2 + 3)) \times T(4)) - (T(T(5)))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9867 &:= (T((-1 + 2 + T(T(3)))) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
9828 &:= (-9 \times (T((8 \times (7 + 6)))/(5 - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9829 &:= (((-9 - 8 + T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9830 &:= ((((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 + 6) \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9831 &:= (T((-9 + 8 + 7) \times T(6)) + T(5 + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9832 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) - (T(5) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9833 &:= (T((T(-9 - 8 + T(7)) + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9834 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9835 &:= (T((-9 \times (8 - 7 - 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9836 &:= (-9 + ((8 + T(7 + 6 + 5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9837 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9838 &:= ((T(-9 + 8 + T(7)) \times (T(6) + 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9839 &:= ((-9 + T(T(8))) - (T(7) + (6 \times (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9840 &:= (((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 + 6) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9841 &:= (-9 + (((T(T(8)) - 7 - 6) \times T(5)) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9842 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + (5 \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9843 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times T(6)) - (T(T(T(5)))/(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9844 &:= T(-9 \times T(8) + T(T(7))) + 6 \times T(T(5 + 4)) + T(T(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9845 &:= (((-9 + T(((8 + 7) + T(6)))) \times T(5)) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9846 &:= (T((-9 + T(8 + 7))) + (T(6 + 5) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9847 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (T(7) \times (6 + 5 - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9848 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times 6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9849 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) \times (7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9850 &:= ((((-9 + T(T(8))) - 7 + 6) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9851 &:= ((-9 + T(((T(8 + 7)/6) + T(T(5)))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9852 &:= (-9 + (((8 + T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + (5 + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9853 &:= (-9 - 8 + T(((7 + 6) \times T(5)) - T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9854 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8) + 7) \times T(T(6)))) - (T(5) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9855 &:= ((-9 + T(((8 + 7) + T(6)))) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9856 &:= (((-9 + T(8)) \times (T(7) \times (6 + 5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9857 &:= -9 + T(T(8)) + T(T(7)) - (6 - T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9858 &:= (((-9 + (T(8) + T(T(7)))) \times 6) + T(T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9859 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7 + 6)))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9860 &:= (T((T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7)))/(6 + 5))) - (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9861 &:= (-9 + T(((T(8 + 7)/6) + T(5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9862 &:= (-9 + (((8 + T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + (T(5) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))) \\
9863 &:= (-9 - 8 + (T(((7 + T(6)) \times 5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9864 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (T(T(5)) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9865 &:= (((-9 + T(((8 + 7) + T(6)))) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9866 &:= (-9 - 8 + ((T(7) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(5)))) + T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9867 &:= (-9 + ((T(8) \times T(7 + 6)) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9868 &:= ((-1+2-3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9868 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((T(7) - T(6)) \times (T(T(5)) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9869 &:= (-1 + T((T((2 \times (3+4))) + 5+6+7+8+9))) & 9869 &:= (-9+8 + T((((7+6) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9870 &:= T((-1 - (2 - (3+4))) \times (5+6+7+8+9)) & 9870 &:= T((T(-9+T(8)) - (7+T((6+5+4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9871 &:= (((-1+2)^{T(T(3))}) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9871 &:= (T((-9+T(8+7))) + T(((6 \times 5) + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9872 &:= (-1 - (T(2 \times 3) - (T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6))) + 7+8+9))) & 9872 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) + (T(6) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9873 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9873 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (T((T(7)+T(6))) - T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9874 &:= ((-1+2+3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9874 &:= ((-9 + ((T(8)+7) \times T(T(6)))) - (5 \times (4+3+2+1))) \\
9875 &:= ((-1+2 \times 3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9875 &:= (T((T(-9+T(8)) - (7+T(T(6)))))) - 5+4+3+2+1 \\
9876 &:= (T((-1+2) \times 3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9876 &:= (-9 + ((T(T(8)) - (T(7) - T(6))) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9877 &:= (-1+2 + (T(3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9877 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((T(T(7)) - T((T(T(6)) - T(T(5)))))/(4+3+2+1))) \\
9878 &:= (-1 - (T(2+3) - (T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6))) + 7+8+9))) & 9878 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7))+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - (4+3+2+1))) \\
9879 &:= ((-1 - T(T(2+3))) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) & 9879 &:= (-9 + (T(T(8+7)) + T(((6 \times T(T(5)))/(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9880 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9880 &:= (T((T((-9 + (T(8) + T(7))))/(6+5))) + 4+3+2+1) \\
9881 &:= (-1 + (2 \times T(3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9881 &:= (T((-9 - (T(8) - T(7+6)))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9882 &:= ((-1-2) \times (T(3) + ((T(4) - T(T(5))) \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 9882 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9883 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)) \times T(4)) - ((5+6) - (7+8+9))) & 9883 &:= ((T(-9+8+T(7)) \times (T(6)+5)) + T(4+3+2+1)) \\
9884 &:= (-1 + (T(2+3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9884 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times T(6)) + (5 - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9885 &:= (T(-1+2 \times 3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9885 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times 7) - (T(6) - T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9886 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(6+7+8+9)))))) & 9886 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (T((T(7)+T(6))) + 5)) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9887 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (T(3) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 9887 &:= (-9 - (T(8) + (T(7) - (6 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))))) \\
9888 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9888 &:= (T((T(-9-8+T(7))+6)) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9889 &:= (-1 \times 2 + (T(T(3)) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9889 &:= (-9-8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9890 &:= (-1 + (T(2 \times 3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9890 &:= ((-9+8 + T((T(7) + (T(6) - 5)))) \times (4+3+2+1)) \\
9891 &:= (T(T((-1+2) \times 3) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9891 &:= (-9 + ((T((8+T(7))) - 6) \times (5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9892 &:= (-1+2 + (T(T(3)) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))))) & 9892 &:= (-9 + ((T(8 \times 7) \times 6) + T((T(5) + 4+3+2+1)))) \\
9893 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 9893 &:= (T(-9+T(8)) + (((T(7) \times 6) + 5) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9894 &:= (-1 \times 2 \times (3 - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) - (6+7+8+9)))))) & 9894 &:= ((-9 + (T(8) + 7)) \times (T(T(6)) + (5 + T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9895 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)) \times T(4)) - (5 - (6+7+8+9))) & 9895 &:= (((-9+T(T(8))) - 7+6) \times T(5)) + T(4+3+2+1) \\
9896 &:= (-1 + (T((2 \times T(3+4))) + (T((T(T(5)) + 6)) + T(7+8+9)))) & 9896 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(7+6)) \times T(T(5))) + T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9897 &:= (-1 - 2 + (T((T(3+4) \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 9897 &:= (-9 + (T(8) + T((((7+6) \times T(5)) - T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9898 &:= (T((-1+2+T(3))) + T((4 \times (5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9898 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times ((6+T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))) \\
9899 &:= (-1 + (T((T(2+3) - 4)) \times (5 \times (6+7+8+9)))) & 9899 &:= (-9+8 + ((T(T(7)) - (T(T(6)) - 5)) \times T(4+3+2+1))) \\
9900 &:= (T(-1+2+3) \times T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6+7+8+9)))) & 9900 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - T(7)) \times (T(6) - T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9901 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(3+4) \times 5)) + 6+7+8+9)) & 9901 &:= (((-9+8+7) \times T(T(6))) + T((T(T(5)) + 4+3+2+1))) \\
9902 &:= (-1+2 + (T((T(T(3)) + T(T(4)))) + (T(5) \times T(6+7+8+9)))) & 9902 &:= (-9 - (T(8) - (T(T(7)) + (T((6+T(T(5)))) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9903 &:= (T((-1+2+T((T(3) + T(4)))) - (T(5) - T(6+7+8+9))) & 9903 &:= (-9 + (((T(8) + T(T(7))) \times 6) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1)))) \\
9904 &:= (T(-1+2+3) + (T((T(T(T(4)))/(5+6))) + 7+8+9)) & 9904 &:= (-9 - (((8 - T(T(7))) \times T(6)) - (T(5) + T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9905 &:= (T((-1+T(2+3)) \times T(4)) + 5+6+7+8+9) & 9905 &:= (-9+8 + (T(T(7+6)) + (T(T(T(5))) - T(T(4+3+2+1)))))) \\
9906 &:= (T((-1+(2 \times T(T(3)))) + T(((T(4) \times (5+6)) + 7+8+9))) & 9906 &:= ((T(-9+T(8)) \times (T(7) - T(6))) + T(T(5+4+3+2+1))) \\
9907 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(T(T(5))) + 6+7+8+9))) & 9907 &:= (T((-9 + (8 \times 7))) - (T(6) - (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4+3+2+1))))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9988 &:= ((-1 + 2 + T(T(3))) \times (4 - (T(5) - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9988 &:= ((-9 \times (T(8) - (T(7) \times 6))) + (T(T(T(5))) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9989 &:= (-1 + (T(T(2 + 3)) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9989 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (T(T(7)) \times T(6)) - (5 - T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9990 &:= (T(T(-1 + 2 \times 3)) + T((4 \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9990 &:= (T(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6)) \times (5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9991 &:= (-1 + 2 + (T(3) \times ((T(4) \times T(T(5))) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))) & 9991 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times T(T(6) + T(5))) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)) \\
9992 &:= ((-1 \times 2 - T(3)) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) & 9992 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - T(7 + 6))) + (5 + (T(T(T(4))) \times (3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9993 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (T(T(3)) \times (4 - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9993 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (T(T(7)) - T(6)))) + (T(T(5)) \times T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
9994 &:= ((-1 - 2 - 3) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) & 9994 &:= ((-9 + T((T(8) + (7 + 6)))) + T((T(T(T(5)))/T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9995 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) & 9995 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) + (T(6 + 5) + 4)) \times T((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9996 &:= ((T(-1 + 2 + 3)^4) - (T(T(5))/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) & 9996 &:= ((-9 + 8 + 7) \times (6 + (T(T(5)) + T(T(4 + 3 + 2 + 1)))))) \\
9997 &:= (-1 + 2 - (T(T(3)) \times (4 - (T(5) + T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9997 &:= (T(T(-9 - 8 + T(7))) + 6^5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
9998 &:= ((-1 + 2 - 3) + (T(4)^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)})) & 9998 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times T(T(6) + T(5)))) - (4 - T((3 + 2 + 1)))) \\
9999 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (T(T(T(4))) - (5 - T(6 + 7 + 8 + 9))))) & 9999 &:= (-9 + 8 + ((T(T(7)) - 6) \times (T(5) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1))) \\
10000 &:= (T((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))))^{T(T(5))/(6+7+8+9)}) & 10000 &:= ((T(((-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6)) \times T(5)) + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)
\end{aligned}$$

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